

**THE EDUCATIONAL PROVISION FOR
LEARNERS WITH AUTISM IN PRIMARY
MAINSTREAM STATE SCHOOLS IN
MALTA: REVEALING THE EDUCATORS'
PERSPECTIVES ON THE SWOTS**

CLAIRE SCIBERRAS

**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of
the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of Doctor
of Philosophy**

May 2023

Abstract

During the past years, an upsurge in the incidence rate of autism has been noted (e.g. Baio *et al.*, 2018; Farrugia, 2013; Lyall *et al.*, 2017; Russell *et al.*, 2022; Tanti Burlo', 2016). Although this rise has led the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (2014) to call for increased support within educational settings in Malta, little is known about how schools in Malta support learners with autism.

The Ecological Systems Framework (Bronfenbrenner, 1979) and its reconceptualisation by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) served as a lens to identify the areas worth exploring to shed light on the provision for learners with autism in Malta. This framework prompted this research to locate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOTs) of the process of: i) teaching and learning; ii) training for educators; iii) home-school collaboration. A sequential explanatory research design was applied to collect data from primary school educators on the three areas from a pragmatic philosophical perspective. Following the data analysis of the first data collection phase based on questionnaires ($n = 53$), semi-structured interviews ($n = 5$) were conducted.

Educators identified adaptations of classroom instruction as one of the strengths of the teaching and learning process, whilst developing more quiet spaces has been located as one of the opportunities. However, lack of funds to purchase resources and Learning Support Educators (LSEs) developing most adaptations have been acknowledged as weaknesses, whilst lack of knowledge on policy content and implementation has been identified as a threat.

Sharing good practices among colleagues has been identified as one of the strengths of the training process. The opportunities are represented by prospects for more training during school hours and by having educators bring forward their training needs. In contrast, training on how to support learners with autism after being appointed to work in schools is viewed as a weakness, whilst having teachers and school administrators being less trained on autism than Learning Support Educators (LSEs) threatens the training process.

Schools being more sensitive to the parents' needs and providing parents with more opportunities to meet with the school have been identified as opportunities. Having parents share information about their children with the school has been located as a strength of the home-school collaboration process. However, from the educators' perspective, having some parents under-involved has been identified as a weakness that hinders home-school collaboration. One of the threats to the home-school collaboration process, as perceived by educators, is potentially having parents who may not prioritise their children's education.

Based on these findings, recommendations to policymakers and practitioners are put forward, as are suggestions for areas that may inspire future research studies.

Keywords: Autism, Ecological Systems Framework, Inclusive Education, Malta, SWOT Analysis, Primary Schools.

Acknowledgements

I began this research study building upon my interest in inclusive education and autism. Working in schools in Malta has inspired me to explore how the provision for learners with autism could be improved. Many thanks go to all the educators who shared their experiences, as without their participation, none of the outcomes published in this study could have been possible. The participants in this study were willing to share their views with me even though Malta, like the rest of the world, was going through a global crisis due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This undoubtedly made data collection an even more complex task. My participants' experiences have served as an inspiration and an eye-opener, and I am particularly grateful for this.

Special thanks also go to my supervisory team. Dr Lisa McAuliffe, my director of studies, believed in me and supported me before I embarked upon this Doctoral experience. She and Dr Carole Bignell, my research supervisor, always gave me critical advice and were invaluable guidance during this journey. I am ever so indebted to them as their advice and guidance enabled me never to lose faith in what I was aiming to achieve. These two academics' positive approaches and unwavering support motivated me to continue and complete my research when thoughts of giving up cropped up. I am also thankful to Professor Henry Maitles, who has also been an insightful guide throughout this journey. His constructive feedback has been beneficial for me in completing this work.

I sincerely thank Dr Conny Gollek, who acted as chairperson during my Viva. Special thanks also go to Dr Xiao Qu, Senior Lecturer, School of Education and

Social Sciences at UWS and Dr Duncan Mercieca, Senior Lecturer, Education and Society, School of Humanities, Social Sciences and Law at the University of Dundee, for accepting to examine this work. Further, thanks go to Dr Yonah Matemba, Senior Lecturer, School of Education and Social Sciences at UWS, who always answered my technical queries when these were put forth.

Undertaking a doctoral degree whilst juggling full-time work and a family is undoubtedly no mean feat. Due to this, I am ever so grateful to my husband Josef, my son Kyle, my parents, sister, and in-laws, who have supported me every step of the way. Their patience, encouragement and love always made me appreciate how blessed I am to have such a great support system.

I would also want to thank God for guiding me throughout this journey. I have felt His presence and guidance during this journey's most challenging times.

Finally, special thanks go to the ENDEAVOUR Scholarship Scheme (Malta) within the Ministry for Education, Sport, Youths and Research and Innovation (MEYR), who believed in my research following my proposal and fully funded this Doctoral programme. The financial support from the scholarship funds facilitated this research endeavour, and I am forever thankful for this.

Student Declaration

All elements of this research, including the design and development of original data collection material, data analysis and write-up are my own work.

Dedication

This work is dedicated to my husband Josef and my son Kyle.

You are the centre of my life.

List of Abbreviations

ADHD: Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder

ADOS: Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule

APA: American Psychiatric Association

ASST: Autism Spectrum Support Team

CARS: Childhood Autism Rating Scales

CC: Central Coherence

CDAU: Child Development Assessment Unit

CDC: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

CEFT: Children's Embedded Figures Test

CoPE: Community of Professional Educators

DSM: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders

EU: European Union

HoS: Head of School

HoD: Head of Department

ICD: International Classification of Diseases

IEN: Individual Educational Needs

INCO: Inclusion Coordinator

EBP: Evidence-Based Practice

LSE: Learning Support Educator

M-CHAT: Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers

MEYR: Ministry for Education, Sport, Youth, Research and Innovation

NMC: National Minimum Curriculum

PECS: Picture Exchange Communication System

PDD: Pervasive Developmental Disorder

PPP: Peer Preparation Programme

SENCO: Special Educational Needs Co-ordinator

SLT: Senior Leadership Team

SWOTs: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

ToM: Theory of Mind

U.K.: United Kingdom

UN: United Nations

UNCRPD: United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities

U.S.: United States

WCC: Weak Central Coherence

WHO: World Health Organization

Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction	1
1.1 The Background of the Study.....	1
1.2 The Purpose of this Research	29
1.3 The Aims, Objectives, and Research Questions	40
1.4 The Methodology of this Research	41
1.5 The Researcher’s Positionality	46
1.6 The Personal Motivational Drive of this Study	49
1.7 The Outline of this Research.....	49
Chapter 2: Literature Review	51
2.1 The Theoretical Framework Underpinning this Research.....	54
2.1.1. The Microsystem	62
2.1.2 The Mesosystem.....	65
2.1.3 The Exosystem	66
2.1.4 The Macrosystem	68
2.1.5 The Chronosystem	69
2.2 Local Policy and Practice: The Maltese Context	72
2.3 Educators' Perspective on the Educational Provision for Learners with Autism	80
2.4 A SWOT Analysis of the Provision for Learners with Autism	82
2.5 The Teaching and Learning Process	83
2.5.1 Strengths of the teaching and learning process	86
2.5.2 Weaknesses of the teaching and learning process	98
2.5.3 Opportunities to the teaching and learning process	106
2.5.4 Threats to the teaching and learning process	114
2.5.5 Conclusion	118
2.6 Training on Autism.....	120
2.6.1 Strengths of training for educators.....	122
2.6.2 Weaknesses of training for educators	124
2.6.3 Opportunities to training for educators.....	129
2.6.4 Threats to training for educators.....	133
2.6.5 Conclusion	143
2.7 Home-School Collaboration Process.....	145
2.7.1 Strengths of the home-school collaboration process	148
2.7.2 Weaknesses of the home-school collaboration process.....	153
2.7.3 Opportunities to the home-school collaboration process.....	158

2.7.4 Threats to the home-school collaboration process	162
2.7.5 Conclusion	166
Chapter 3: The Methodology	168
3.1 Research Paradigms.....	168
3.2 A Pragmatic Approach	170
3.2.1 The use of the pragmatic approach in the current research	173
3.2.2 The ontology of pragmatism.....	176
3.2.3 The ontological approach in the current research: Accepting that multiple viewpoints can coexist	178
3.2.4 The epistemology of pragmatism	181
3.2.5 The epistemological stance of this research study: A practical and real-world benefit inquiry into autism.....	184
3.2.6 The axiology of pragmatism.....	186
3.2.7 The axiological stance of this research study: Improving future practice.....	187
3.2.8 The methodological assumptions of this research study.....	189
3.2.9 A balanced approach to educational research: Mixed-Methods.....	189
3.4 The Research Design.....	196
3.5 The Sample of this Research Study.....	198
3.5.1 The sample of the questionnaire participants	200
3.5.2 The sample of the interview participants	201
3.6 The Quantitative Data Collection Stage.....	201
3.7 The Qualitative Data Collection Stage	203
3.8 Data analysis	205
3.8.1 Quantitative data analysis	205
3.8.2 Qualitative data analysis.....	207
3.8.3 Limitations to using a web-based questionnaire in research	208
3.8.4 Limitations of using interviews as a research tool.....	209
3.9 Ethical Considerations	211
Chapter 4: Findings	216
4.1 The Teaching and Learning Process	216
4.1.1 Strengths of the teaching and learning process	218
4.1.2 Weaknesses of the teaching and learning process	230
4.1.3 Opportunities to the teaching and learning process	236
4.1.4 Threats to the teaching and learning process	242
4.2 Training for Educators.....	246
4.2.1 Strengths of the training process.....	247

4.2.2 Weaknesses of the training process	250
4.2.3 Opportunities to the training process.....	254
4.2.4 Threats to the training process.....	259
4.3 The Home-School Collaboration Process.....	266
4.3.1 Strengths of the home-school collaboration process.....	268
4.3.2 Weaknesses of the home-school collaboration process.....	276
4.3.3 Opportunities to the home-school collaboration process.....	279
4.3.4. Threats to the home-school collaboration process	284
Chapter 5: Discussion	289
5.1 The Interpretation of Findings	289
5.2 The Teaching and Learning Process	290
5.2.1 Strengths of the teaching and learning process	291
5.2.2 Weaknesses of the teaching and learning process	307
5.2.3 Opportunities to the teaching and learning process	313
5.2.4 Threats to the teaching and learning process	318
5.3 Training for Educators.....	322
5.3.1 Strengths of training.....	323
5.3.2 Weaknesses of training.....	326
5.3.3 Opportunities in training	332
5.3.4 Threats in training.....	338
5.4 The Home-School Collaboration Process.....	344
5.4.1. Strengths of the home-school collaboration process.....	345
5.4.2 Weaknesses of the home-school collaboration process.....	352
5.4.3 Opportunities to the home-school collaboration process.....	355
5.4.4 Threats to the home-school collaboration process	358
5.5 The Relationship of the Located SWOTs, the Ecological Systems.....	362
Framework and the Provision for Learners with Autism	362
Chapter 6: Conclusions and Recommendations	373
6.1 The SWOTs and the Provision for Learners with Autism	373
6.2 The Limitations of the Current Study.....	382
6.2.1 Lack of locally published research	383
6.2.2 Limitations related to sample size	384
6.3 The Strengths of this Research Study	388
6.4 Recommendations for Further Research Work	390
6.5 Implications and Recommendations for Practice	391
6.6 Implications and Recommendations for Policymakers.....	392

6.7 Final Thoughts	395
<i>References</i>	397

List of Tables

TABLE 1: THE FUNDAMENTAL BELIEFS DELINEATING RESEARCH PARADIGMS (GUBA AND LINCOLN, 1994, P.108).....	169
TABLE 2: THE PHASES OF THE SEQUENTIAL EXPLANATORY RESEARCH DESIGN	204
TABLE 3: INTERVIEW PARTICIPANTS	216
TABLE 4: THE SWOTS OF THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS.....	217
TABLE 5: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: ADAPTATIONS AS STRENGTHS.....	219
TABLE 6: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: SUPPORT FROM SLT	226
TABLE 7: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: SUPPORT FROM PEERS.....	227
TABLE 8: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: ADAPTATIONS DEVELOPED BY LSES	231
TABLE 9: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: LACK OF RESOURCES	232
TABLE 10: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: INADEQUATE CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT.....	235
TABLE 11: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: INADEQUATE CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT	238
TABLE 12: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: SUPPORT FROM EXTERNAL SERVICE PROVIDERS	241
TABLE 13: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: UNCLEAR PERSPECTIVES ON INCLUSION.....	243
TABLE 14: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: LACK OF KNOWLEDGE OF POLICY	245
TABLE 15: THE SWOTS OF THE TRAINING PROCESS	247
TABLE 16: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: SHARING OF STRATEGIES	248
TABLE 17: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: USER-FRIENDLY STRATEGIES	249
TABLE 18: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: THEORETICAL TRAINING.....	251
TABLE 19: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: TRAINING AFTER APPOINTMENT	253
TABLE 20: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: RECOGNISING EDUCATORS' TRAINING NEEDS	255
TABLE 21: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: TRAINING BY SPECIALISED TRAINERS.....	258
TABLE 22: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: TEACHER COURSES DO NOT PRIORITISE TRAINING ON AUTISM.....	261
TABLE 23: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: EXCLUSIONARY PRACTICES	263
TABLE 24: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: VOLUNTARY TRAINING.....	266
TABLE 25: THE SWOTS OF THE HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION PROCESS.....	268
TABLE 26: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: OPEN AND FREQUENT COMMUNICATION	269
TABLE 27: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: SHARING STRATEGIES WITH PARENTS	273
TABLE 28: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: PARENTS SHARING INFORMATION.....	275
TABLE 29: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: UNDER-INVOLVED PARENTS	276

TABLE 30: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: PARENTS IN DENIAL.....	278
TABLE 31: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: OPPORTUNITIES FOR FREQUENT MEETINGS.....	281
TABLE 32: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: BEING SENSITIVE TOWARDS PARENTS.....	282
TABLE 33: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: PARENT EDUCATION SESSIONS.....	283
TABLE 34: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: EDUCATION NOT A PRIORITY FOR SOME PARENTS.....	285
TABLE 35: RESPONSES INDICATED BY QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS: PARENTS' PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING.....	286
TABLE 36: SUMMARY OF DATA: ADAPTATIONS OF INSTRUCTIONS.....	300
TABLE 37: SUMMARY OF DATA: SUPPORT FROM THE SLT.....	301
TABLE 38: SUMMARY OF DATA: SUPPORT FROM PEERS.....	306
TABLE 39: SUMMARY OF DATA: ADAPTATIONS BY LSES.....	308
TABLE 40: SUMMARY OF DATA: LACK OF RESOURCES.....	310
TABLE 41: SUMMARY OF DATA: INADEQUATE CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT.....	312
TABLE 42: SUMMARY OF DATA: QUIET SPACES.....	315
TABLE 43: SUMMARY OF DATA: SUPPORT FROM EXTERNAL SERVICE PROVIDERS.....	317
TABLE 44: SUMMARY OF DATA: UNCLEAR PERSPECTIVES ABOUT INCLUSIVE EDUCATION.....	320
TABLE 45: SUMMARY OF DATA: LACK OF KNOWLEDGE ON POLICY CONTENT AND IMPLEMENTATION.....	322
TABLE 46: SUMMARY OF THE DATA: SHARING OF GOOD PRACTICE.....	324
TABLE 47: SUMMARY OF DATA: USER-FRIENDLY STRATEGIES.....	325
TABLE 48: SUMMARY OF DATA: THEORETICAL TRAINING.....	328
TABLE 49: SUMMARY OF DATA: TRAINING FOLLOWING APPOINTMENT.....	331
TABLE 50: SUMMARY OF DATA: TRAINING NEEDS.....	334
TABLE 51: SUMMARY OF DATA: TRAINING DURING SCHOOL HOURS.....	335
TABLE 52: SUMMARY OF DATA: TRAINING BY AUTISM SPECIALISTS.....	337
TABLE 53: SUMMARY OF DATA: TEACHER PREPARATORY COURSES.....	340
TABLE 54: SUMMARY OF DATA RELATED: EXCLUSIONARY PRACTICE.....	342
TABLE 55: SUMMARY OF DATA: NON-MANDATORY TRAINING.....	343
TABLE 56: SUMMARY OF DATA: OPEN AND FREQUENT COMMUNICATION.....	347
TABLE 57: SUMMARY OF DATA: SHARING STRATEGIES WITH PARENTS.....	349
TABLE 58: SUMMARY OF DATA: PARENTS SHARING INFORMATION WITH EDUCATORS.....	351
TABLE 59: SUMMARY OF DATA: UNDER INVOLVED PARENTS.....	353
TABLE 60: SUMMARY OF DATA: DENIAL.....	355
TABLE 61: SUMMARY OF DATA: EDUCATION FOR PARENTS.....	356
TABLE 62: SUMMARY OF DATA: FREQUENCY OF MEETINGS.....	357
TABLE 63: SUMMARY OF DATA: EMPATHY TOWARDS PARENTS.....	358
TABLE 64: SUMMARY OF DATA: PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF PARENTS.....	359
TABLE 65: SUMMARY OF DATA: EDUCATION NOT A PRIORITY.....	361

List of Figures

FIGURE 1: THE BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY.....	6
FIGURE 2: AN EXAMPLE OF THE CHILDREN'S EMBEDDED FIGURES TEST (CEFT) (WITKIN ET AL., 1971).....	17
FIGURE 3: SALLY ANNE TEST (BARON-COHEN, LESLIE AND FRITH, 1985, P. 41).....	20
FIGURE 4: AUTISM INCIDENCE TRENDS IN MALTA, THE U.K. AND THE U.S.....	26
FIGURE 5: THE ELEMENTS WITHIN THE ECOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION – TEACHING AND LEARNING.....	32

<i>FIGURE 6: THE ELEMENTS WITHIN THE ECOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION- TRAINING FOR EDUCATORS</i>	34
<i>FIGURE 7: THE ELEMENTS WITHIN THE ECOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION- HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION</i>	35
<i>FIGURE 8: THE PROCESS JUSTIFYING THE PURPOSE OF THIS RESEARCH</i>	37
<i>FIGURE 9: AN ILLUSTRATION OF BRONFENBRENNER’S ECOLOGICAL SYSTEM (GONZALES, 2020)</i>	55
<i>FIGURE 10: THE ECOLOGY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION (ANDERSON, BOYLE AND DEPPELER, 2014, P. 6)</i>	57
<i>FIGURE 11: STRENGTHS OF THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	87
<i>FIGURE 12: WEAKNESSES OF THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	99
<i>FIGURE 13: OPPORTUNITIES TO THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	106
<i>FIGURE 14: THREATS TO THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	117
<i>FIGURE 15: STRENGTHS OF TRAINING AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	122
<i>FIGURE 16: WEAKNESSES OF TRAINING AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	125
<i>FIGURE 17: OPPORTUNITIES TO TRAINING AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	129
<i>FIGURE 18: THREATS TO TRAINING AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	134
<i>FIGURE 19: STRENGTHS OF HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	148
<i>FIGURE 20: WEAKNESSES OF HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	154
<i>FIGURE 21: OPPORTUNITIES TO HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	159
<i>FIGURE 22: THREATS OF HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION AS IDENTIFIED IN CURRENT LITERATURE</i>	163
<i>FIGURE 23: THE PRAGMATIC PHILOSOPHICAL ASSUMPTIONS OF THE RESEARCHER OF THIS STUDY</i>	176
<i>FIGURE 24: THE RESEARCH UNION</i>	194
<i>FIGURE 25: THE ROLES HELD BY RESPONDENTS OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE</i>	200
<i>FIGURE 26: ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF ONLINE QUESTIONNAIRES (EVANS AND MATHUR, 2005, P. 197)</i>	202
<i>FIGURE 27: THE CODES AND NODES CREATED TO REFERENCE THE SWOTS OUTLINED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE USING NVIVO12</i>	206
<i>FIGURE 28: STRENGTHS OF TEACHING AND LEARNING</i>	218
<i>FIGURE 29: STRATEGIES APPLIED DURING THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS</i>	220
<i>FIGURE 30: WEAKNESSES OF THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS</i>	230
<i>FIGURE 31: OPPORTUNITIES TO THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS</i>	237
<i>FIGURE 32: THREATS TO THE TEACHING AND LEARNING PROCESS</i>	243
<i>FIGURE 33: STRENGTHS OF THE TRAINING PROCESS</i>	247
<i>FIGURE 34: WEAKNESSES OF THE TRAINING PROCESS</i>	251
<i>FIGURE 35: OPPORTUNITIES TO THE TRAINING PROCESS</i>	254
<i>FIGURE 36: TRAINING INTEREST</i>	256
<i>FIGURE 37: THREATS TO TRAINING FOR EDUCATORS</i>	260
<i>FIGURE 38: RESPONDENTS WHO ATTENDED TRAINING IN THE AREA OF AUTISM</i>	260
<i>FIGURE 39: STRENGTHS OF THE HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION PROCESS</i>	268
<i>FIGURE 40: THE MEANS USED TO COMMUNICATE WITH PARENTS</i>	270
<i>FIGURE 41: WEAKNESSES OF THE HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION PROCESS</i>	277
<i>FIGURE 42: OPPORTUNITIES TO THE HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION PROCESS</i>	280
<i>FIGURE 43: THREATS TO THE HOME-SCHOOL COLLABORATION PROCESS</i>	284
<i>FIGURE 44: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE LOCATED SWOTS, THE ECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS FRAMEWORK AND THE PROVISION FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM</i>	363

List of Appendices

APPENDIX 1: PERMISSION FROM THE MINISTRY FOR EDUCATION, SPORT, YOUTH, RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (MEYR).....	451
APPENDIX 2: ETHICAL APPROVAL FROM THE UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND	452
APPENDIX 3: CORRESPONDENCE TO THE HEADS OF COLLEGE NETWORKS.....	453
APPENDIX 4: CORRESPONDENCE TO HEADS OF SCHOOLS OF THE PRIMARY SCHOOLS	455
APPENDIX 5: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET	457
APPENDIX 6: THE QUESTIONNAIRE OF THIS RESEARCH.....	464
APPENDIX 7: THE INTERVIEW SCHEDULE	467
APPENDIX 8: CONSENT FORM FOR QUESTIONNAIRE PARTICIPANTS	470
APPENDIX 9: CONSENT FORM FOR INTERVIEWEES	471
APPENDIX 10: COMMUNICATION BY THE MALTA UNION OF TEACHERS (MUT)	472

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 The Background of the Study

Autism is a neurodevelopmental condition characterised by diversities in communication, social interactions, sensory processing and cognitive functioning (Ducarre, 2023; Jones *et al.*, 2022; Runswick-Cole *et al.*, 2016). Children with autism may find social relationships particularly challenging as they may have difficulty interpreting social cues and understanding social reciprocity (Jones *et al.*, 2022; Morrison *et al.*, 2019). Autism is four times more prevalent among boys than girls (Mamas *et al.*, 2021). Following a diagnosis of autism, scholars have consistently found that this is stable (Benedetto *et al.*, 2021; Ozonoff *et al.*, 2015; Pierce *et al.*, 2019), thus indicating that autism is lifelong (Sonido *et al.*, 2020; Torres, Caballero and Mistry, 2020).

Autism is regarded as being at the core of the neurodiversity theory (Lollini, 2018), with such a theory accepting and acknowledging neuro-cognitive variances among humans (Chapman, 2020). Given this, the neurodiverse approach views autism as a difference in neurological functioning (Jaarsma and Welin, 2012; Singer, 2017). The view of autism being perceived as a neurodevelopmental difference has not only impacted how this is perceived (i.e. as a neurological difference rather than a medical or a psychiatric condition) but has also triggered numerous debates on the terminology surrounding it.

A study by Kenny *et al.* (2016) which sought the views of the members of the autism community in the United Kingdom concerning the terms used to describe autism, provides an idea of how autism might be termed in the 21st century. These findings demonstrate that the general public uses several terms to describe autism. The most common terms applied are 'autism', 'autism spectrum disorder', 'persons on the autism spectrum' and 'persons with autism' (e.g. Kenny *et al.*, 2016; Shah *et al.*, 2022; Silverman, 2008). However, an online survey by Kapp *et al.* (2013) which assessed the conceptions of autism and neurodiversity among individuals with different relations to autism, demonstrated that adults with autism prefer the term 'autistic person' rather than the term 'person with autism'. This preference seems to transpire since many of these adults feel that: i) autism should be viewed as a fundamental aspect of their identity (Kapp *et al.*, 2013; Kenny *et al.*, 2016; Shah *et al.*, 2022); ii) the term 'autistic' moves away from the idea that autism is a disorder since it focuses on the notion of 'identity-first language' (Kapp *et al.*, 2013; Shah *et al.*, 2022). 'Identity-first language' derives from a strength-based approach (Saggers *et al.*, 2019), focusing on what individuals can do rather than what they cannot do (Lewin and Akhtar, 2020; Urbanowicz *et al.*, 2019).

On the other hand, further findings from the study of Kapp *et al.* (2013) on the conceptions of autism among individuals with different relations to autism, such as parents, siblings, friends, and educators of individuals with autism did not have any preference for either the term 'autistic person' or the term 'person with autism'. As this debate is currently unresolved, I use the term 'learners with autism' in this work, recognising the fact that this terminology is what is currently being used in the

Maltese educational context (e.g. Camilleri, 2022; Sciberras, 2018; Sciberras, 2019; Tanti Burlo', 2016).

The DSM-V outlines two fundamental patterns of behaviour that need to be in place for an individual to be considered as being on the autism spectrum (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (Fifth Edition) (DSM-V) states that the diagnosis of autism requires the manifestation of at least three characteristics of challenges in social communication and at least two characteristics in the category of repetitive behaviours (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; Di Tore, De Giuseppe and Corona, 2017). This Manual continued to support the concepts of impairments in social communication and insistence on sameness/resistance to change (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; Vivanti, 2020; World Health Organization, 2019) as outlined in Kanner (1943) and Asperger (1944).

Following the revision regarding the diagnosis of autism in the DSM-V, scholars argued that the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) should provide a definition more aligned with the DSM-V (Ousley and Cermak, 2014). Following this suggestion, the World Health Organisation (WHO) adopted the same two categories for diagnosing autism as the DSM-V in the 11th revision of the ICD (World Health Organization, 2019). Thus currently, both Manuals agree on the characteristics of autism. This mutual agreement sheds a better light on the profiles of individuals with autism, thus providing a clearer picture of what is classified as a characteristic of autism and what is not. The reciprocal alignment in diagnostic manuals is critical because if children are misdiagnosed, this will result in unnecessary therapies or

lead professionals towards the implementation of incorrect strategies when attempting to address the child's needs (Yong and Block, 2020).

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the extent of the challenges encountered by students with autism may differ as individuals with autism are predisposed to manifest difficulties according to where they lie on the spectrum (Chen *et al.*, 2019). Clark *et al.* (2020) argue that “autism, by definition, is highly heterogeneous, and the uneven cognitive profiles, academic fluctuation, and islets of ability mean there is no ‘one size fits all’ approach to ensuring inclusion in an education setting” (p.38). Indeed, request for increased support within schools has become allied to autism as persons with this condition tend to demonstrate extensive clinical variability vis-à-vis how they express their challenges regarding their type and severity (Jones and Klin, 2009). Such diversity has been attributed to the neurological differences which exist regarding autism. Indeed, the heterogeneity of individuals with autism spans several challenges related to the social communication and interaction domain and areas linked to restricted, repetitive behavioural patterns (Waterhouse, 2013). As a result, learners with autism may display a restricted range of interests, lack relationships with their educators and peers, exhibit self-stimulatory behaviours and have impaired language and communication skills (Goodman and Williams, 2007). However, this does not imply that students diagnosed with autism will encounter challenges in all the areas mentioned earlier to an extensive degree. Often, such occurrences lead to a situation where whilst there will be features which will unite students with autism as individuals, there will also be several ways in which their distinct differences would be apparent (Tutt, Powell and Thornton, 2006). Indeed, Lord (2011) states that people who have encountered more than one

individual with autism tend to be struck by the several distinctions among them. Furthermore, the manifestation and impact of the aforementioned characteristics on the individual with autism depend on the social and environmental context (Prizant and Fields-Meyer, 2015). Given the above, devising and implementing appropriate and equitable modifications for individuals without a coherent understanding of these attributes presents a substantial challenge (Holcombe and Plunkett, 2023), consequently, negatively impacting educational support for learners with autism.

However, despite that, heterogeneity regarding challenges needs to be acknowledged for appropriate support to be put in place. This is because intervention should not solely be based on a deficit-based approach whereby the focus is on the diagnosis and the challenges of the individual with autism (Burnham Risa *et al.*, 2017). Indeed, while studies have reported that a deficit-based intervention approach has, to a certain extent, demonstrated some effectiveness in helping students with autism improve their executive functioning (EF) and communication skills (e.g. Bambara *et al.*, 2018; Christ *et al.*, 2017), this approach might nevertheless have negative impacts on the mental wellbeing, educational experiences and outcomes of learners (White *et al.*, 2023). This results from the fact that the focus might be exclusively on the weaknesses and challenges of learners with autism, consequently ignoring the positive qualities and strengths (Burnham Riosa *et al.*, 2017; White *et al.*, 2023). For instance, a literature review conducted by White and colleagues (2023), who selected 18 articles published between 2009 and 2022 which identified at least one specific strength or interest of learners with autism found that, the strengths relating to students' learning and school experiences included knowledge in specific subjects linked to the learners'

particular interests, visual and sensory processing abilities, music, art, sports and motor skills. The common interests outlined in these 18 articles following the narrative synthesis approach applied by White *et al.* (2023) included computer and video games, vehicle and transportation, sports, cooking, comics and cartoons. These findings suggest that when schools unpack and explore the strengths and interests of learners with autism, 'a paradigm shift from a deficit-focused approach to a strengths-based approach takes place' (White *et al.*, 2023, p. 3) hence allowing schools to indeed provide an inclusive learning experience to learners with autism.

Figure 1 outlines the background of this study. The evolution of autism, its incidence, how it is represented in policies, and the identification of the profile of learners' strengths, needs, and challenges define this context. In order to understand the four developments surrounding the background, the following sections will analyse how autism has evolved. Indeed, these evolutions in research and policy have helped towards cultural and political shifts. As will be discussed in the following sections, these shifts may have contributed to a better understanding of autism from a neurological standpoint, awareness of the profile of strengths, needs, and challenges of individuals with autism, and consideration of the range of interventions that lead to a more inclusive educational and social approach.

Figure 1: The Background of the Study

How the Understanding of Autism and Policy Evolved

Although the preceding section highlights some promising developments of the DSM-V (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) and ICD-11's (World Health Organization, 2019) efforts to provide a set of characteristics that would aid in the confirmation or rejection of an autism diagnosis, autism had been conceptualised differently for over 80 years. Indeed, until the 1970s, autism research and perspectives were habitually embedded into diagnostic criteria like schizophrenia (Volkmar and McPartland, 2014). However, discoveries by Leo Kanner (1943, 1944) and Hans Asperger (1944) identified several characteristics that distinguish autism from other conditions, including schizophrenia (Adler, Minshawi and Erickson, 2014). Kanner and Asperger's discoveries inspired many scholars to hypothesise about autism diagnosis criteria. In hindsight, this shift may have given children more mainstream schooling opportunities in the 1960s and the 1970s since students with autism had few schooling options during that era due to a misdiagnosis of childhood schizophrenia or mental retardation (Grinker, 2020). Indeed, people with developmental differences have historically been institutionalised across cultures and contexts (Jackman and Zwaigenbaum, 2023), with such placement being a dominant practice in the first half of the twentieth century in North America, Australia, and parts of Europe for children with behavioural, cognitive, and psychiatric challenges (Lemay, 2009).

An audit conducted in 2014 by European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education reported that some 2,507 learners with IEN were receiving their education in mainstream schools whilst 54 students were placed in resources

centres (formerly known as special schools). This audit has reported that these figures give a segregated placement rate of just over 0.1%, one of the lowest across countries part of the European Union (EU) (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2014, p. 29). This low rate could have resulted from Malta being a signatory state of the Salamanca Statement which placed a responsibility on the country to transform educational settings into "regular schools with this inclusive orientation as being the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes, creating welcoming communities, building an inclusive society and achieving education for all" (UNESCO, 1994). This Statement obliged signatory countries to adopt policies that promote an inclusive approach focusing on human rights rather than an integrated one (UNESCO, 1994).

The shift in policy development and the way that Malta started to view mainstream school settings following the commitment made in 1994 (UNESCO, 1994) led policymakers to include inclusive education as one of the key principles of the National Minimum Curriculum (NMC) (Ministry of Education, 1999). Inclusive education is a concept based upon the idea that all individuals, regardless of unique characteristics, are entitled to be included in regular classroom environments while being provided with the necessary support to access information and the physical environment (Byrne, 2019; Scanlon *et al.*, 2022). However, the ultimate vision of the NMC was to extend inclusive education beyond the educational area and more towards a societal prospect where the fundamental rights of children, including those with a disability, are protected (Ministry of Education, 1999). Policymakers pursued this idea in Malta as the literature argues that society has a moral responsibility to acknowledge and sustain diversity and ensure it actively contributes

to establishing an egalitarian vision (Rose and Shevlin, 2019). This vision is based on the principle that individuals are all equal and merit equal rights and opportunities (Rose and Shevlin, 2019), including those related to education systems that guarantee equitable access to the curriculum for all learners, including ones with autism. This leads to an understanding that inclusive education is not defined merely as a placement but rather as a process and practice where schools are designed to support all learners (Artiles and Kozleski, 2016). Research has reported that children with IEN, including those with autism, experience positive academic, social and behavioural outcomes when educated in inclusive classrooms (Leonard and Smyth, 2020; O'Rourke, 2015). Thus, inclusive schools must 'recognise and respond to the diverse needs of their students' (UNESCO, 1994, p.11) and hence should provide suitable instructions, pedagogies, and resources (Boyle, Anderson and Allen, 2020).

In view of autism, Malta has devised national legislation (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). The aim of the 'Persons Within the Autism Spectrum (Empowerment) Act' was for the concerned authorities to establish an Autism Advisory Council (Sciberras, 2019), whereby its purpose is to promote initiatives that increase awareness to achieve further autism acceptance within the Maltese society (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). The Autism Advisory Council also aims to focus on improving how to identify and support undiagnosed adults. It also considers providing advice on self-determination to persons with autism as this would possibly enhance access to appropriate support services and equal opportunities for inclusion and participation in society (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). The intention of establishing

this Council was to develop and submit an Autism Support State Plan to the Minister responsible for persons with disability (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). The Autism Support State Plan intends to address family involvement, educational provision and support services, training, and professional and personal development (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). Nevertheless, the implementation of this plan is still in its initial stages. Therefore, the Act's impact will still need to be appraised in the coming years.

Paradoxically, the enactment of laws on specific disabilities also gives rise to concerns about its value since this might create disparities between individuals with different types of disabilities (Azzopardi, Azzopardi Lane and Bezzina, 2019). Azzopardi, Azzopardi Lane and Bezzina (2019) argue that it might be more sensible to increase the protection of persons with disabilities under umbrella provisions such as the amendment of the Maltese Constitution (Laws of Malta: Chapter 1. 1964) so that prejudice on the grounds of disability is outlawed. In line with the recommendations of Azzopardi, Azzopardi Lane and Bezzina (2019), it may be argued that the 'Policy on Inclusive Education in Schools: Route to Quality Inclusion' (MEYR, 2022a) is a policy which is more targeted at the inclusion of learners with disabilities, learners with high abilities, learners of all sexual orientations and learners from ethnic minorities and different religious backgrounds, attendance of learners, and a whole school approach to healthy living. Similar to what Scotland's National Framework for Inclusion 3rd Edition has enacted in terms of guidance for educators on inclusion and inclusive practice (Alves *et al.*, 2022), the Policy on Inclusive Education endeavours not to discriminate between specific conditions or

situations (MEYR, 2022a). Instead, it focuses on ensuring that learners, irrespective of their diverse needs, including those with autism, can achieve the essential understanding of values and acquire the required abilities for employability with the intention that such individuals become active participants within the community (MEYR, 2022a). This policy also explains how the principles of inclusion and diversity underpinned within the National Curriculum Framework for All (Ministry of Education and Employment, 2012) may be implemented within educational settings in Malta. This policy endorses the belief that all learners, irrespective of their needs, challenges, and abilities, should experience achievement through equitable access to learning (MEYR, 2022a).

However, alike the Autism State Plan, the Policy on Inclusive Education in Schools: Route to Quality Inclusion (MEYR, 2022a), is still in its early stages of implementation. Hence, how far policies are implemented in Malta within inclusive education and autism remains a question that needs to be addressed and appraised. Therefore, educational settings in Malta must continually document and report on what they are delivering concerning the educational provision for learners with autism (Sciberras, 2019). Documenting the provision is necessary as adequate approaches can increase the possibilities for students with autism to overcome the challenges they might encounter in the areas of social communication, social interaction, social imagination and flexible thinking (Danker, Strnadová and Cumming, 2019; McDougal, Riby and Hanley, 2020).

The Profile of Learners with Autism

The profile of children with autism is an intriguing pattern of strengths and challenges worth exploring as it provides a relevant background to this research study. These accounts are imperative to consider as they have attempted to explain the underlying causes of specific behaviour which may affect the learning of individuals with autism (Fletcher and Happé, 2019; Pastor-Cerezuela *et al.*, 2020). While some children with autism have difficulties with working memory, organisation, sequencing, flexible thinking, and verbal ability (Dijkhuis *et al.*, 2020; Pastor-Cerezuela *et al.*, 2020), other tests have revealed that these same children consistently outperform typically developing children on embedded figures (Baron-Cohen and Lombardo, 2017) and block design tests (Takayanagi *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, Norris (2022) has documented that some children with autism have excellent rote memory and demonstrate outstanding musical and drawing abilities (Meilleur, Jelenic and Mottron, 2015). Norris (2022) also outlines that tests involving knowledge based on facts and focused attention to detail may lead to peak performances by individuals with autism.

However, aside from the strengths above, Norris (2022) also observed that when presented with assessments related to conceptual knowledge required for generalisability, the presentation of these tasks may see individuals with autism underperforming. Empirical evidence indicates that repetitive and restrictive behaviour patterns within the educational setting influence the performance of students with autism in the classroom as these typically impact planning, organisation and cognitive flexibility (Demetriou, DeMayo and Guastella, 2019; Gentil-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2022). Carruthers *et al.* (2020) further argue that generalisation is necessary for an intervention to benefit everyday life beyond the

original learning environment. Counting, telling time, making payments, measuring and weighing, recognising fundamental designs and schemes, and executing numerical operations are essential abilities worth generalising as these are linked to independent living (Baglama, Yikmis, and Demirok, 2017). Further examples deriving from Duncan *et al.*'s (2022) study and which have been linked to learners with autism see them struggling with maintaining attention, focusing during class instruction, completing classwork, and initiating and persevering through tasks independently.

Further to the challenges above, due to a lack of flexible thinking abilities, students may struggle to adapt to changes (e.g. modified schedule or modified classroom procedures) and experience emotional dysregulation (Smith and Mercieca, 2021). In light of this, the DSM-V (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) and the ICD-11 (World Health Organization, 2019) outline the importance of exploring sensory sensitivities as this tends to be relatively common among individuals with autism. Pastor-Cerezuela *et al.* (2020) posit that "sensory processing refers to how the central and peripheral nervous systems manage incoming sensory information from the sensory organs, namely, visual, auditory, tactile, taste, smell, proprioception, and vestibular information" (p.2). Recent literature has progressively identified that most individuals with a diagnosis of autism may have difficulty processing sensory information (Butera *et al.*, 2020; Mirzakhani and Shahriyarpour, 2021; Proff *et al.*, 2022) with Pastor-Cerezuela *et al.* (2020) outlining that atypical sensory processing encompasses hyper and hypo-responsiveness to the stimuli encountered within the setting that individuals are in, including the school environment. Thus, when designing support and instructions for students with autism in schools, educators

must know their children's profiles in order to be able to empower and guide them (Nah and Tan, 2021), as this would potentially ensure equitable access to education and the acquisition of appropriate life-skills.

When considering the profile of learners with autism, several theories have attempted to define the behaviours related to this condition. A widely accepted cognitive explanation for at least some of the social and non-social challenges experienced by individuals with autism is the theory of executive dysfunction (ED) (Happé, 1999). EF is an umbrella term for functions related to planning, working memory and impulse control (Hill and Frith, 2003; Hill, 2004), whereby such skills support conscious, top-down control of thought, action, and emotion (Zelazo, 2020) and allow flexible shifting in thoughts and actions (Alsaedi, Carrington and Watters, 2020; Benallie *et al.*, 2021; Demetriou, DeMayo and Guastella, 2019; Fatima, 2019). It also refers to functions such as mental flexibility, the initiation and self-monitoring of actions, and even the inhibition of responses by an individual (Anokhin, Golosheykin and Heath, 2010; Hill and Frith, 2003; Hill, 2004; Kaland *et al.*, 2008). The latter functions are all thought to be determined by systems that involve activity in the prefrontal part of the brain in typically developing individuals (Hill and Frith, 2003; Gousse *et al.*, 2002; Hill, 2004; Kaland *et al.*, 2008). In view of this, the ED theory attempts to explain the behavioural impairments in individuals with autism linked to rigidity, perseveration and difficulty initiating new actions and the tendency to remain fixed on a given set of tasks (Alsaedi, Carrington and Watters, 2020; Benallie *et al.*, 2021; Demetriou, DeMayo and Guastella, 2019; Fatima, 2019; Hill and Frith, 2003). The latter leads to restrictive and repetitive behaviours whereby, without appropriate support, learners with autism may feel adrift in unpredictable

and chaotic classrooms (Ravet, 2018). Therefore, educators need knowledge and understanding of autism to better understand and be able to respond to the behaviour of students with autism (Ravet, 2018).

Nonetheless, although the ED theory sheds light and provides an understanding of the challenges encountered by learners with autism concerning restrictive and repetitive behaviour patterns, Frith (1998), Frith and Happé (1994) and Happé (1997) theorised that a Weak Central Coherence (WCC) might also explain the challenges related to restricted and repetitive behaviour. Central coherence (CC) is the term coined to explain the specific need to pursue higher-level meaning by extracting the gist of the incoming information in daily situations (Happé, 1999; Hatfield *et al.*, 2017; Hill and Frith, 2003). More than two decades ago, Frith (1998) suggested that humans possessed this common feature to process information, which was atypical in individuals with autism. Due to a WCC, individuals with autism focus, Frith (1998) and Happé and Frith (2006) documented that individuals focus on detail and cannot extract the gist of a situation or see the 'bigger picture' in everyday life.

Summarising a series of tests on memorising images and stories in an earlier research study, Bartlett (1932) concluded that neurotypical individuals do not typically take a situation detail by detail. Instead, on everyday occasions, a neurotypical human would tend to merely get a general impression of the whole picture (Bartlett, 1932). On such a basis, the individual would then construct probable details, processing daily general information and thus cognitively applying the central coherence (Bartlett, 1932). However, more than 50 years later, Frith

(1989) theorised that this common feature that humans use to process information was atypical in individuals with autism and that a WCC could explain why individuals with autism would be relatively good at tasks where attention to detail is required but would find tasks which require the recognition of the global meaning challenging.

The initial work on central coherence focused on perceptual processes. Shah and Frith (1983) found that children with autism scored above average on the Children's Embedded Figures Test (CEFT) (Figure 2) than typically developing children. In the CEFT, participants in this study were required to find a small shape in a larger drawing (Shah and Frith, 1983). Furthermore, a later study found that in a Block Design task, participants with autism were faster at replicating 40 different block designs than the control group, which included typically developing individuals and participants with a learning disability (Shah and Frith, 1993). The key feature of both the Block Design Test and the CEFT is that a figure can be segmented or include smaller constituent components; due to the drive for central coherence in the neurotypical population, the salience of these smaller components is not as great as the global figure. Indeed, Frith (1989) explained that if individuals are unable to extract the 'gist' from a dialogue stream, this will prevent them from understanding the 'deeper intentional aspects of communication' (Frith, 1989, p.124). Frith (1989) also applied the theory to the occurrence of repetitive behaviours. Such behaviours are spontaneously occurring behaviours generally inhibited by the central control processes responsible for creating coherence (Plaisted, 2001). In view of this, the WCC theory served to explain why learners with autism find it difficult to generalise across different contexts information which they have learned in one context (de Marchena, Eigsti, and Yerys, 2015). Gunning *et al.* (2019) define generalisation as

appropriate behaviour in different contexts. Thus, when a task requires an individual to extract the global meaning from a situation with many details, a learner with autism may struggle to "see the big picture" because they tend to focus on the details at the expense of gaining a global perspective of the presented context (De Jager and Condy, 2020). Due to a hyper-focus on details, learners with autism may become confused if the content lacks meaning (Ravet, 2018) and thus may prefer to engage in restricted and repetitive behaviour (Frith, 1998; Frith and Happé, 1994; Happé, 1997).

*Figure 2: An example of the Children's Embedded Figures Test (CEFT) (Witkin *et al.*, 1971)*

Nevertheless, since Frith's (1989) documentation, the theory of the WCC has been refined by scholars, even by Frith herself. Indeed, based on studies conducted by Happé (1991) and Happé (1994), Frith has abandoned the idea that a WCC only leads to underlying challenges linked to restrictive and repetitive behaviour patterns manifested by individuals with autism (Frith and Happé, 1994). Supporting Frith's idea were the conclusions of a more recent study investigating the application of the

Theory of Mind (ToM), ED and the WCC theory in children with autism (Syriopoulou Delli, Varveris and Geronta, 2017). In the object assembly task where the sample was assessed upon global precedence, neurotypical developing children scored better than those with autism (Syriopoulou Delli, Varveris and Geronta, 2017). Nevertheless, the scores were not statistically significant and hence, such results, did not permit the researchers of this study to support the WCC theory (Syriopoulou Delli, Varveris and Geronta, 2017). Indeed, the WCC hypothesis has also been put forward as an explanation for the distinct abilities observed in individuals with autism rather than the theory that explains the challenges encountered by individuals with autism. Hence, a WCC is regarded as a higher order in terms of local processing (Rajendran and Mitchell, 2007). Given this, it may be argued that the WCC is not a deficit but another cognitive style (Happé, 1999; Happé and Frith, 2006).

Further to the above viewpoints, whilst the WCC and the ED may explain the emergence of restrictive and repetitive behaviour patterns of individuals with autism, Finnegan and Accardo (2018) have argued that challenges related to social communication skills could transpire because learners with autism may find it challenging to understand other humans' thoughts, intentions and beliefs. Understanding what other people know, want, feel, or believe is critical to the development of appropriate social, imaginative, and communicative skills (Baron Cohen, 2001; Baron-Cohen, Leslie, and Frith, 1985; Frith and Happé, 1994; Happé, 1999), with such ability being referred to as the ToM by Premack and Woodruff (1978).

Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith (1985) have proposed that individuals with autism lack ToM. This theory attempts to explain why children with autism encounter challenges in performing behaviours related to joint attention and pretend play (Happé, 1999). The ToM also refers to the everyday ability to infer what others are thinking in a manner and to be able to explain and predict their behaviour (Happé, 1999). In a study that tested the hypothesis of whether children with autism have a ToM, the participating sample, which included children with a diagnosis of autism and with Down syndrome, was asked a critical question on the 'belief' (it/he/she thinks) of the doll in the experiment (Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith, 1985). In the task, the participants watched a sequence of events (Figure 3). The story evolves with the aim for the participants in the study to make conclusions about the location of where the doll will look for the marble (Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith, 1985). This was done for the participant to infer the mental state of the doll. If the children pointed to the previous location of the marble, they were considered as passing the *Belief Question* by appreciating the doll's 'false belief'. If, however, the participants pointed at the current location of the marble, they were considered as failing the question by not considering the doll's belief (Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith, 1985). Whilst all the children with Down syndrome who were part of the control group could account for the doll's belief, 80% of the children with autism who participated in this experiment failed the *Belief Question* (Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith, 1985). Hence, this study concluded that children with autism 'fail to employ a ToM' (Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith, 1985, p. 43). Thus according to the researchers of this study, this explains why individuals with autism encounter challenges in social, imaginative and communicative skills (Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith, 1985).

Figure 3: Sally Anne Test (Baron-Cohen, Leslie and Frith, 1985, p. 41)

Ghanouni *et al.* (2019) and Silveira-Zaldivar and Curtis (2019) have posited that such a lack of social skills development impacts the students' quality of life in and after compulsory schooling. For instance, literature has reported that learners with autism often feel lonely and isolated due to poor peer relations and social skills (e.g. Baczewski and Kasari, 2021; Hebron, 2018; Huxter, 2021; Rosello *et al.*, 2022) whilst classroom activities involving joint attention and pretend play may limit the participation of learners with autism (Carruthers *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, literature has consistently demonstrated that children with autism who encounter challenges linked to having fewer friendships are more isolated and are less socially involved and accepted into the social structure of their class when compared to their

neurotypically developing peers (Bauminger and Kasari, 2000; Chamberlain, Kasari and Rotheram-Fuller, 2007; Kasari *et al.*, 2011). More recent literature has outlined that if misunderstood due to not being able to share feelings, exchange thoughts and ideas, and predict the behaviour of others (Zhou, Zhan and Ma, 2019), students with autism may experience incidents of bullying and social isolation (Huxter, 2021; Milton and Sims, 2016; Stephenson and Adams, 2016). In hindsight, social communication difficulties are some of the most common issues that affect the social and academic lives of learners with autism, and which can isolate them from their environment, including the educational one, if appropriate support structures are not in place (Alkinj, Pereira and Santos, 2022).

Nevertheless, despite social communication challenges, literature shows that most students with autism understand friendship and want friends (Cresswell, Hinch and Cage, 2019). Thus, schools must create support systems to help students make friends, interact, recognise their social self-perception, and be accepted by peers (Mamas *et al.*, 2021). Building social relationships benefits children's well-being, self-esteem, and school participation, so support structures are needed (Crompton *et al.*, 2022). According to Smogorzewska, Szumski, and Grygiel (2020), some neurotypical students voluntarily interact with peers with disabilities, which improves their social development, responsiveness, and understanding of others. This interaction could improve neurotypical learners' social communication and autism students' social participation (Mamas *et al.*, 2021). Stephenson and Adams (2016) have also indicated that social communication interactions may be increased in schools by using the particular interest of the child with autism. This interest, often associated with children with autism who develop extensive knowledge about a

subject, tends to be an asset for positive social interactions and may serve as a familiar script for children with social communication difficulties (Stephenson and Adams, 2016). Thus, using these specific interests to help learners with autism engage with peers in like-minded pursuits may improve connections and social communication skills (Milton and Sims, 2016). In hindsight, it may be postulated that placement alone is insufficient to socially include learners with autism in the social setups of their classrooms (Chamberlain, Kasari and Rotheram-Fuller, 2007; Ferraioli and Harris, 2011; Ochs *et al.*, 2001) and thus appropriate social support structures should be in place. This insufficiency was also confirmed by Russell, Scriney and Smyth (2022), who posit that placement alone does not necessarily provide education systems which pledge fair access to all learners, including those with autism.

Even though parents and school staff may agree on what should be included in Individual Educational Plans (IEPs) regarding students' educational performance levels, goals, services, aids and criteria for curriculum and assessment modifications (Al-Shammari and Hornby, 2020; Tran, Patton and Brohammer, 2018), schools seem unable to do much more than provide what is barely sufficient (Merry, 2020). Attitudes towards inclusion (Merry, 2020), school staff's unwillingness to provide resources for inclusive education (Goodall, 2018), and educators' lack of knowledge and skills seem to contribute to the provision of the bare minimum (Hu, 2019). Due to such barriers, students with autism "receive little more than a warehousing experience, where schools become places of confinement and seclusion" (Merry, 2020, p.14) rather than inclusion "where the educational setting can facilitate a sense of belonging and is conducive to well-

being" (Merry, 2020, p.17). The latter could jeopardise the inclusive provision rights of learners with autism. Thus, educators must be optimistic about inclusion for them to be able to implement inclusion policies and practice appropriately (van Kessel *et al.*, 2021). Article 24 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCRPD) outlines that:

Inclusion involves a process of systemic reform embodying changes and modifications in content, teaching methods, approaches, structures and strategies in education to overcome barriers with a vision serving to provide all students of the relevant age range with an equitable and participatory learning experience and environment that best corresponds to their requirements and preferences (United Nations, 2016, para. 11).

The contents of Article 24 (United Nations, 2016, para. 11) are particularly currently important as educators, including those working in schools in Malta, are now more aware than ever before that it is highly likely for them to have one or more students with autism in their classes each year, particularly since an increase in its incidence has been noted (Clark *et al.*, 2020). Aligned with what literature and policy have depicted in terms of incidence rates in countries such as Australia and the U.K. (Ravet, 2018; Stokes *et al.*, 2017) and further discussed hereunder, most students with autism in Malta are receiving their education within mainstream educational settings. Indeed, according to data from the European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (2012), Malta has one of the highest proportions of learners with IEN including those with autism attending mainstream education among the EU Member States. Data from the school year 2011-2012 shows that, from a population of 2,572 learners having a statement of needs including ones with autism, 2,507 received their education in mainstream schools and 65 learners were in a resource centre (European Agency for Development in Special Needs

Education, 2012). This gives a segregated placement rate of just over 0.1%, which, according to the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (2014), is one of the lowest across EU countries.

Since autism is complex and heterogeneous, this section has attempted to illuminate its cognitive, social, and behavioural traits (Chen *et al.*, 2019). Thus, finding a mechanistic explanation for the wide range of social communication and restrictive and repetitive behaviour patterns is difficult (Beckerson, May and Kana, 2022). It is presumed that when pondered upon in isolation, the ToM, WCC and EF models may not be sufficient to explain autism. However, in hindsight, these theories still attempt to outline the numerous etiological hypotheses dominating autism and shed light on an understanding of its complexity and heterogeneity.

The Incidence of Autism

Recent literature has debated whether the criteria outlined in the DSM-V (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) and the ICD-11 (World Health Organization, 2019) could have led to the ever-increasing incidence rate of autism (Depastas and Kalaitzaki, 2022; Watkins and Angus-Leppan, 2022). The literature argues that diagnostic substitutions and increased awareness may have led to an increased diagnosis of autism (Russell *et al.*, 2022). This increase was explicitly noted in 1943 when Kanner initially documented his descriptions of the children he observed, and autism started to be regarded as a rare condition (Fletcher-Watson and Happé, 2019). Nevertheless, as diagnostic manuals have been revised, autism has increased. A Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) study conducted in the

U.K. appraised time trends from 2008 to 2018 to explore whether the incidence of autism increased over time and hypothesised that the identified increase could be due to increased demand for assessment. This increase in demand has been viewed as transpiring from greater public awareness of autism and also due to the de-stigmatisation of the label due to work by the neurodiversity movement and parent-led lobby groups (Russell *et al.*, 2022). Increased awareness and the de-stigmatisation of autism may have made parents more willing to seek professional advice when they observe any behaviours that may concern them.

The exploration of the previous question on the increase in the incidence rate is prompted by the presentation of the findings of two of the earliest studies which sought to appraise the incidence of autism. The findings of these studies derive from the fact that the diagnostic criteria for which children had to be included in the studies of Lotter (1966) and Brask (1972) were narrow as they included learners who lacked affective interaction until age five and had elaborate repetitive routines (Gillberg and Wing, 1999). Lotter (1966) and Brask (1972) discovered 4.4 and 4.9 children with autism for every 10,000. Following similar research criteria as the U.K. incidence rate, Wing and Gould (1979) found a slight increase in the incidence of 4.9 per 10,000 compared to Lotter's (1966) and Brask's (1972) conclusions. However, it should be noted that these studies were conducted when awareness of autism and clarity on its characteristics were limited, which may have contributed to the low incidence rate.

However, the 21st century has seen a considerable increase in the incidence rate of autism (Figure 4). As discussed earlier, this increase could have transpired following

the single category of autism created in the DSM-V (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) and the ICD-11 (World Health Organization, 2019; Lyall *et al.*, 2017). Furthermore, this increase in the incidence rate of autism has also been indicated as transpiring following the development and the implementation of autism assessment tools such as the second edition of the Childhood Autism Rating Scale (CARS-2) (Schopler *et al.*, 2010), the M-CHAT (Robins *et al.*, 2001) and the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule, Second Edition (ADOS-2) (Lord *et al.*, 2012). It has been reported that developed countries such as the U.K. and the U.S. had an estimated incidence of 1.5% in 2017 to a rate of 1.8% by 2022 (e.g. Lyall *et al.*, 2017; Russell *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 4: Autism Incidence Trends in Malta, the U.K. and the U.S.

Similar to what has been reported in international contexts, Malta also saw an increase in the incidence rate. The rate of autism recorded in Malta in 2013 was 1 in 100 (Farrugia, 2013). However, an estimated increase in its incidence rate was reported three years later. Tanti Burle' (2016) documented that professionals working with children with autism in Malta estimate a rate of 1 in 56 (1.8%), indicating a similar scenario to what is experienced in other countries. For instance, rates of autism in the United Kingdom and the U.S. are consistent with the estimated

rate by Tanti Burlo' (2016) (Baio *et al.*, 2018; Dillenburger, McKerr and Jordan, 2014; Pasco, 2018). In fact, in a study of autism among children aged eight years in 11 states in the U.S. (Arizona, Arkansas, Colorado, Georgia, Maryland, Minnesota, Missouri, New Jersey, North Carolina, Tennessee, and Wisconsin), Baio *et al.* (2018) estimated an incidence rate of 1 in 59 (1.7%). Likewise, further increased prevalence has also been reported in France (van Bakel *et al.*, 2015), South Korea (Hong *et al.*, 2020), and Australia (May, Brignell, and Williams, 2020). Therefore, this data continues to confirm a rise in incidence, which calls for quality provision for learners with autism, particularly when considering that whilst "a good quality education is paramount, a good quality inclusive education is optimal" (Russell, Scriney and Smyth, 2022, p. 2). Indeed, whilst Mitchell (2014) argues that learners with IEN would benefit from 'good teaching' even if this is not implemented in a dedicated environment, Ainscow (2005) posits that an inclusive school environment increases the presence, participation and achievement of all children irrespective of their diverse needs. As such, a quality inclusive education is based on the 'belief that education is a basic human right and the foundation for a more just society whereby the emphasis is on equity and fairness' (Ainscow, 2020, p.9).

When viewing how quality inclusive education is a necessity and a right for all learners, including those with autism, it is critical to understand how the Maltese educational systems have exercised such rights throughout the past decades. Indeed, following the implementation of compulsory primary education for all children in 1946, Malta has made progress, especially within the area of individual educational needs (IEN) (Ministry of Education, Youth and Employment, 2005). As a result of the island's British colonisation until 1964 and thus perhaps inspired by

the Warnock Report (1978), in the 80s, 0.2% (121 children) of learners identified as having IEN attended special classes in mainstream settings (Bartolo, 2010). However, this type of placement, suggesting integration rather than inclusion given that learners were segregated in classes away from typical developing peers, was eventually minimised in schools in Malta. Given this, it may be argued that this time, Malta moved away from the recommendations of Baroness Warnock when she rethought what she suggested in 1978. Indeed, in 2005, Warnock recommended that for children with moderate disabilities, such as those with Asperger's and Down Syndrome, 'inclusion is a nightmare ... and if they are to flourish and benefit from education, they need the relatively protected environment of a small or smallish special school' (p.15). As mentioned in the earlier sections of this work, Malta is one of the EU member states with the highest placement rate concerning students with IEN, including those with autism, attending regular classrooms in mainstream schools (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2014). Thus, when considering the incidence rates and the trends of the increase of learners, including those with autism who are receiving their education in mainstream regular classrooms, educators would expect to have at least one learner with autism in their classroom (Draper, 2021).

As discussed in the previous sections, justification for looking into the provision for learners with autism transpires from the following. Primarily, the de-stigmatisation of autism may have directly resulted from its recognition as a neurodevelopmental condition rather than one linked to mental health. Such de-stigmatisation may have led to an increase in the incidence rate, consequently leading policymakers to update policies on inclusion. Thus, looking into the provision of learners with autism

in Malta would shed light on the SWOTs (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) to possibly ameliorate policy and practice that ensures a quality educational experience for learners with autism. After all, inclusion has increasingly been recognised as not simply placing a child in a mainstream setting but as a concept that aims to ensure that each learner is an active member of school life (Alexaki, Foulidi, and Papakitsos, 2022; Karadağ, Yılmaz, and Yeganehi, 2021).

1.2 The Purpose of this Research

The background of autism (as discussed in Section 1.1) justifies the need for research regarding how provision for learners with autism transpires. A SWOT analysis is an evaluation tool that may enable a better understanding of the provision for learners with autism because it examines external and internal developments that are compatible or incompatible with the proposed intervention, intending to maximise success by utilising the advantages and anticipating and resolving barriers (Idris *et al.*, 2022). This analysis is necessary, particularly since inappropriate or insufficient support addressing challenges related to socialisation, communication, and restrictive and repetitive behaviour, may jeopardise the educational experience of learners with autism, which in turn may lead to exclusion (Hebron, 2018; Maciver *et al.*, 2021; Paget *et al.*, 2018). Even though inclusion has been linked to high levels of attainment for many learners, including those with autism (e.g., Cappe *et al.*, 2021; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Ravet, 2018), the implementation of inclusive practices in mainstream classrooms is possibly lagging (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022). The latter further justifies the need for research to explore how support takes place for learners with autism in mainstream schools.

This study's research questions emerged specifically from previous studies' findings which also explored the provision for learners with autism in mainstream schools. Following a comprehensive literature review, it was concluded that the findings of previous studies could be organised under three areas. Sections 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6 discuss in detail the salient points of why these three areas are worth a SWOT analysis. For instance, a study conducted in Sweden by Anderson (2020) on schooling for learners with autism concluded that a lack of teacher competence regarding autism and inadequate adaptation of teaching primarily caused the absenteeism of learners with autism. Considering these conclusions in light of the Ecological Systems Framework, it may be posited that training for educators impacts the quality of teaching and learning of learners with autism, particularly since educators are positioned at the child's most immediate systems, seeing them as catalysts in terms of them impacting child and learner development.

Further to the aforementioned, parents have also been positioned at the child's and the learners' most immediate ecological system, perceiving them as crucial agents in child development. This leads to an understanding that educator and parent collaboration is necessary, with the findings of an American study on the experiences of teachers regarding collaboration with parents concluding that open lines of communication circumvent situations where learners may potentially fall "through the cracks" (LaBarbera, 2017, p.45). Thus, home-school collaboration could allow for prompt intervention that is more targeted and relevant for learners with autism (Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022). These conclusions thus justify how the extent of home-school collaboration would impact the teaching and learning of learners with autism.

The aforementioned three areas emerged as a helpful framework for analysing the data collected. Bronfenbrenner's (1979) Ecological Systems Theory (Figure 8) and its reconceptualisation by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) to the field of inclusive education (Figure 8) were a helpful additional tool as these served as an additional positioning lens to locate the areas that emerged from previous research onto the systems. Both ecological systems frameworks (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979) position the child at the core of five interconnected systems proposed as the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem. Bronfenbrenner (2005) posited that by analysing the interaction of groups or entities within the five systems, it is possible to outline and distinguish the ecological properties of these significant social contexts as “environments for human development” (p. 54). As will be comprehensively explored in Chapter 2, within the reconceptualisation of Bronfenbrenner (1979), Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) have more specifically delineated how these social contexts impact learners' educational experiences by conceptualising them to inclusive education. Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) posit that these social contexts determine the extent of inclusive education regarding learner participation, achievement, and value. Participation requires the learner to be actively engaged in all schooling opportunities, including academic and social ones, with Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) arguing that participation would allow learners to achieve their full potential. The latter implies that the goals set for learners should meet their IEN as this would ensure that learners can access the curriculum and grow and develop to reach their full learning potential (Ferguson *et al.*, 2021). For instance, as illustrated in Figure 5, within the interconnected systems proposed by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), resource allocation, curriculum and

pedagogy are elements which have a ripple effect on the participation, achievement, and value of the learner. Therefore, this further justifies the need for research to explore how teaching and learning processes for learners with autism take place and the SWOTs within such processes.

Figure 5: The Elements Within the Ecological System of Inclusive Education - Teaching and Learning

Nonetheless, exploring teaching and learning processes in isolation is not sufficient since, as already discussed earlier, the literature suggests that the effectiveness of inclusion may be influenced by the extent of training received by educators on inclusive education and autism (e.g. Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Cook and Ogden, 2021; Rajotte *et al.*, 2022). Gulberg, Bradlet and Wittemeyer (2019) claim that guidance on good practice would ensure that educators' teaching strategies, awareness, and responses can effectively meet the needs of learners with autism. As illustrated in Figure 6, within the framework proposed by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), professional learning, professional standards, and accountability have been indicated as elements that, if (or not) in place, will influence the participation, value and achievement of learners including those with autism. For instance, research shows that accountability in education may be ensured through training educators since professional development establishes quality assurance systems that ensure

high-quality support programmes for learners (Darling-Hammond, 2020). Such high-quality support programmes resulting from training could potentially lead educators to reframe their support to adequately address any barriers to participation since value and achievement are at the core of inclusive education (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

All the evidence in this section makes the area related to ‘training for educators’ worth exploring since analysing its SWOTs would shed light on what is currently making training effective for educators and what areas need improvement. However, despite the positive impact on learners’ achievement, participation and value, the delay in terms of the implementation of inclusive support mentioned earlier (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022) has been identified as partly transpiring from a lack of professional development focusing on inclusive education practices for educators (van Mieghem *et al.*, 2020). Literature has consistently indicated that such limitation impacts educators’ confidence and readiness regarding their capacity to support learners, including those with autism, in the classroom (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Cook and Ogden, 2021; Rajotte *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, all this evidence suggests that such a lack of confidence deriving from limited knowledge and training on autism may potentially translate into limitations in providing adequate teaching and learning structures (Leifler *et al.*, 2021), which would impact the learners’ level of value, achievement, and participation (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

Training for Educators

Professional Learning

Professional Standards

Accountability

Figure 6: The Elements Within the Ecological System of Inclusive Education- Training for Educators

As noted earlier, further to teaching and learning and training for educators, literature has constantly documented that impacting the provision is the communication and connection between educators and parents (e.g. Roberts and Simpson, 2016; Stephenson *et al.*, 2021). Such impact is evident as this communication allows for children's learning (e.g. Roberts and Simpson, 2016; Stephenson *et al.*, 2021) and increases positive learning outcomes (McNeal, 2014). Collaboration is critical to successful inclusion (Reupert, Deppeler and Sharma, 2015; Roberts and Simpson, 2016; Stephenson *et al.*, 2021), with Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) also outlining this as impacting the participation, value and achievement of learners.

The early reports of Harper and Pelletier (2010) and, more recently, those of Josilowksi and Morris (2019) and Yan, Hou and Deng (2022) corroborate Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler's (2014) views on the importance of collaboration between the school and parents as part of their ecological system (Figure 7). These scholars have delineated that positive learning outcomes transpire as a result of frequent collaboration between the home and school, allowing parents to share their experiences and expertise with educators (Harper and Pelletier, 2010; Josilowksi and Morris, 2019; Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022). Such an optimistic impact ensues as

parents can share information about their child's condition, strengths, and weaknesses, which will potentially enhance the educators' awareness of the child's needs and abilities and thus enable them to tailor instruction accordingly (Saggers *et al.*, 2019; Schultz *et al.*, 2016; Walker *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, investigating home-school collaboration processes within the context of learners with autism who attend primary schools in Malta would shed light on how the provision for these learners occurs in terms of such collaboration, in particular since home-school collaborative patterns impact the development of the learners as proposed in Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014).

Figure 7: The Elements Within the Ecological System of Inclusive Education- Home-School Collaboration

Educators' views are pertinent to evaluating the teaching and learning process, training for educators and home-school collaboration. This evaluation is essential since it aligns with the samples in previous research (e.g. Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Cook and Ogden, 2021; Josilowksi and Morris (2019); Rajotte *et al.*, 2022), according to Bronfenbrenner's (1979) Ecological Systems Theory and its reconceptualisation in view of inclusive education by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), educators are at the core of the child's immediate supportive system mainly because they are in contact with them for several hours during the day. For instance,

in the framework proposed by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), educators are located within the micro, meso, exo, and chrono systems (Figure 10). Having educators placed in each interconnected system of this framework indicates that educators' perspectives and experiences are central to determining how teaching and learning occur, how home-school collaboration transpires, and how their professional development evolves (Majoko, 2018). Acquiring data from educators is thus needed to successfully and effectively include learners with autism in mainstream primary school classrooms since children learn in contexts, within spaces and places, and with the individuals they come into contact with (Hayes, O'Toole and Halpenny, 2023).

The inclusion of learners with autism within the mainstream school setting in Malta has been prioritised in national legislation. Although this is a step in the right direction, limitations regarding knowledge of the provision for these students still exist. Notwithstanding that, prominence has been given to the areas illustrated in Figures 5, 6 and 7 within the Ecological Systems Framework and also within current studies focusing on the provision for learners with autism (e.g. Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Clark *et al.*, 2020; Cook and Ogden, 2021; Roberts and Simpson, 2016; Stephenson *et al.*, 2021), no data outlines an analysis of these three areas impacting the inclusion of learners with autism in schools Malta. An electronic search concerning published research and literature on how support is provided to learners with autism in Malta yields minimal findings, with current published scholarly literature failing to outline what actions educational institutions in Malta have pursued regarding the daily implementation of the philosophies underpinning inclusive education in the educational provision for learners, particularly those with a diagnosis of autism. As

a result, there appears to be a disparity between what is recommended regarding autism policies, legislation, evidence-based research and what is being implemented.

Figure 8: The Process Justifying the Purpose of this Research

Due to this identified gap in research, particularly within the context of the Maltese educational system, the need to explore the provision for learners with autism who attend primary schools in Malta is regarded as critical. Such criticality may be observed as a SWOT analysis may facilitate the reportage of an in-depth analysis of the provision for learners with autism who attend schools in Malta. A SWOT analysis as a tool is relevant to appraise the provision for learners with autism because the 21st century has inspired many organisations, including educational ones, to engage in strategic planning since this method enables them to be more

productive and acquire appropriate guidance on allocating resources (Gürel and Tat, 2017; Sciberras, 2019). Sciberras (2019) has argued that although this framework is commonly used within companies and firms to investigate their competitive impact within the marketplace to develop future concepts, this analysis structure could also be usefully applied in educational settings to inform practice. Applying the SWOT analysis tool to evaluate provision within educational settings is strongly recommended since strengths and opportunities within a SWOT analysis enable the setting to achieve its objective; hence, these are perceived as constructive conditions impacting the system (Gürel and Tat, 2017). Conversely, weaknesses and threats cause obstacles to the setting or system, hindering the organisation from fulfilling its aims (Gürel and Tat, 2017).

This section has explored how educators play a critical role in the educational experience of learners with autism. Therefore, for this study, the data on the SWOTs in provision was gathered from educator participants, including Heads of Schools (HoS), Assistant Heads of Schools, Heads of Department who support the school in the area of inclusion, teachers, Kindergarten Educators (KGEs) and LSEs. For clarity and consistency in an area of considerable nomenclatures, the term Learning Support Educator (LSE) shall be used to refer to the role of Learning Support Assistants (LSAs) (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021), teacher assistants (Giangreco, Doyle, and Suter 2014), paraprofessionals (Carter *et al.*, 2009) or teaching assistants (Webster *et al.*, 2010). Since the term LSE is used in the Maltese educational context, this term will be used throughout this dissertation. Furthermore, the term Head of Department who supports schools in inclusion will

be used to refer to what international settings refer to as Special Educational Needs Co-ordinator (SENCO) and Inclusion Co-ordinator (INCO).

Figure 8 illustrates the current underlying matters and gaps that add relevance and purpose to researching the topic of this study. As noted, Figure 4 outlines that the increase in incidence and the increase in the number of learners with autism attending mainstream primary schools in Malta raises questions on the current situation of the provision for learners with autism, particularly in terms of exploring what is successful and what may be hindering their inclusion. Research has shown that three prominent areas which are enablers of inclusion leading to positive child development are: i) the teaching and learning process (e.g. Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Clark *et al.*, 2020; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Reupert, Deppeler and Sharma, 2015); ii) training for educators (e.g. Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Cook and Ogden, 2021). iii) the home-school collaboration process (e.g. Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Roberts and Simpson, 2016; Stephenson *et al.*, 2021).

Analysing the three areas regarding SWOTs would raise awareness of how the provision for learners with autism in Malta is put into force. Furthermore, following this study's findings and recommendations, this inquiry would potentially guide policymakers to shape and enhance the support provided to learners with autism. Delineating the SWOTs is, therefore, crucial as a lack of appropriate opportunities to overcome threats and weaknesses could jeopardise the educational and social experience that persons with autism have (Saggers *et al.*, 2016) hence, inhibiting them from acquiring a fruitful inclusive educational experience (Roberts and

Webster, 2022). Shedding light on the current situation regarding the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism would likely lead to incentives to implement changes, allowing learners to experience positive and practical educational experiences.

1.3 The Aims, Objectives, and Research Questions

This research study investigates the SWOTs present within the support provision for learners with autism since more learners are receiving their education in mainstream school settings in Malta (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2014). Such a placement denotes educators' responsibilities regarding the support provided to learners with autism (Rajotte *et al.*, 2022). Shedding light on the role of educators in schools is critical since educators are considered vital workers in the educational journey of all students, including those with autism (Bolourian *et al.*, 2021; Güleç-Aslan, 2020). As a result, this study aims to add to the limited research on educators' perspectives on the SWOTs in the provision for learners with autism in Malta.

Given what has been discussed in sections 1.1 and 1.2, the overall aim of the study is:

To explore the SWOTs in the provision for students with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta

Given the above, the main aims of this study are:

- a. To identify the SWOTs within: i) teaching and learning; ii) training for educators; iii) home-school collaboration.

- b. To develop recommendations for educational bodies, including school settings, to effectively support students with autism who attend mainstream schools in Malta.

The research questions guiding this study are the following:

Research Question 1: Which are the SWOTs within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Research Question 2: Which are the SWOTs within the training process of educators who support learners with autism in mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Research Question 3: Which are the SWOTs within the home-school collaboration process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

1.4 The Methodology of this Research

As the researcher of the current study, I took a pragmatic philosophical view to answer the research questions and realise this study's aim and objectives.

Pragmatists believe that the world may be changed through action, whereby action is the way to change existence (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). In pragmatism, actions are intermediaries in a situation or a context (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). Reflecting on my position as a pragmatic researcher, such an approach has been deemed fruitful for this research as pragmatism does not focus on whether an ideology fits a specific ontology but on whether it suits a purpose and can create action (Rorty, 1998). Indeed, pragmatism as a worldview inspired this research study to delve into the experiences of educators who have learners with autism in their classrooms by identifying the existing SWOTs thus, intentionally 'creating action' (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019; Rorty, 1998).

In view of the above, I, as the researcher, embarked on a journey in an attempt to change the 'world through action' (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019), whereby 'world' in the context of this study refers to the provision for learners with autism, and 'action' refers to the SWOT analysis being conducted. The findings of this study contribute to developing several recommendations that may inspire policymakers and practitioners to improve the quality of inclusive education for learners with autism by further promoting related strengths and opportunities whilst using the latter to overcome threats and weaknesses. Throughout researching currently available literature, it was noted that no published studies have looked into the educational provision for learners with autism through a SWOT analysis, and neither of the encountered publications included the Maltese educational context. Hence, following the recommendations put forth in this study, practitioners and policymakers could act as mediators for action to take place by possibly

ameliorating policy and practice related to the field of autism and possibly motivating educational institutions to embrace such a change (Benzaghta *et al.*, 2021).

Pragmatist scholars reject the idea that social science inquiry can access the truth exclusively using a single scientific method (Maxcy, 2003). Further to the idea that pragmatism assumes that change may be created by action, pragmatism also embraces a plurality of research methods and is, in effect, mainly associated with mixed methods (Biesta 2010; Creswell and Plano Clark 2011; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie 2004; Morgan 2014; Teddlie and Tashakkori 2011). Inspired by this, this research gathered educators' perspectives regarding the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism by employing a mixed-methods approach, as it was deemed that this enabled the integration and synergy of multiple data sources (Poth and Munce, 2020).

The combination and interaction of multiple data sources within this study arose from applying the Sequential Explanatory Research Design. This type of research design comprises two phases: the quantitative phase, which is subsequently followed by the qualitative phase (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). The rationale for this approach is based on the fact that the qualitative data and the following analysis deepen and enrich the understanding provided by analysing the data gathered through the questionnaire (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). The first data collection phase of the study gathered the quantitative data through questionnaires. Data related to the SWOTs was depicted in a descriptive statistical format using bar graphs (Taguchi, 2018). During the second data collection phase, the qualitative technique based on semi-structured interviews enabled this research

to elicit in-depth views and experiences of the educators, thus providing insights not captured in the quantitative phase (Almeida, 2018). Quantitative and qualitative research methods in this study have also enabled me, as the researcher, to employ triangulation, intending to utilise multiple methods to compare and validate findings (Maarouf, 2019; Molina-Azorin, 2016). Hence, this research used mixed methods intending to "provide rich insights into the research phenomena that cannot be fully understood" (Dawadi, Shrestha and Giri, 2021, p. 27) and was followed by abduction as a method which helped triangulate the findings of this research.

Data related to the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism was gathered from educators working in the primary school educational cycle. In Malta, primary school settings provide schooling for students aged 3 to 11. Such a setting is divided into two cycles; the Early Years, which caters for learners from Kindergarten 1 to Year 2 and the Junior Years, which caters for a cohort of students from Year 3 to Year 6. Identifying the SWOTs within these two cycles is crucial for an academic contribution towards the field of autism. Whilst earlier literature has indicated that the school environment becomes the key service provider for learners with autism (Brookman-Frazer *et al.*, 2009), more recent literature supports the idea that schools serve as an essential function for individuals with autism (Stenhoff, Pennington and Tapp, 2020) in particular for the implementation of effective strategies and their sustained use (Melgarejo *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, the school is viewed as "a fundamental part of society's fabric" (Brown *et al.*, 2021, p.2).

As indicated in Section 1.2, studies searching for educators' perspectives have been viewed as a springboard for synchronising daily practices and views regarding the

development and implementation of inclusive education (Majoko, 2018), mainly because they are critical to the development of the child as a learner (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). In view of this, it is undeniable that educators are thus perceived as instrumental in the lives of learners with autism, with Hummerstone and Parsons (2020) indicating that educators' support has been something brought forward by students with autism themselves. Lindsay *et al.* (2013) have also indicated that involving educators in research studies on the provision for learners with autism is "the first step in building a more inclusive environment where children are all considered an equally valued member of the class" (p.348). Lindsay *et al.* (2014) outline that for inclusive education to happen, "it is critical to understand the challenges educators may encounter when creating inclusive classroom environments, particularly for children with ASD" (p. 348). Nevertheless, even though literature outlines the criticality of involving educators in research on the educational provision for learners with autism, Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020) posit that there is a lack of empirical studies which focus on an analysis of issues concerning the evaluation of the needs of learners with autism and the effectiveness of the implemented practice of education. In order to support educators of learners with autism who attend mainstream settings (e.g. tailoring teacher training programs), their perspectives on their general experience of what impacts provision must be understood (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022).

Adding to the arguments above, it should be noted that the role of parents in research and practice is also imperative. Indeed, parents' involvement as active contributors in research and decision-making processes, particularly those related to their children's IEPs, and home-school collaboration is an imperative indicator of

academic success (Kurth *et al.*, 2020). However, despite these benefits, this research could not involve parents due to unexpected time constraints and the unforeseen climate that hit the world. During the intended data collection phase, an unprecedented school lockdown following a substantial rise in the cases of COVID-19 was enforced. COVID-19 lockdown made it difficult for me, as the researcher, to approach parents of students with autism, particularly when attempting to gain access through schools and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs).

Notwithstanding this significant unforeseen limitation related to involving parents as part of the research sample, this study still gathered some insightful perspectives from the voices of educators who work with students with autism, thus ensuring its validity and reliability. For instance, this study aimed to look into the provision for learners with autism through a SWOT analysis. Using the SWOT tool as a means of analysis was deemed essential as no research study had yet used a SWOT analysis tool to appraise the provision for learners with autism. This SWOT analysis tool was selected as opposed to other methods within this study because it could outline the current strengths and weaknesses within schools and define the external opportunities and threats beyond the school's control when inquiring about the provision for learners with autism. Therefore, a SWOT analysis within this research has allowed this researcher to gather rich data and information specifically focused on the aim intended to be reached, i.e. to explore the SWOTs in the provision for students with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta.

1.5 The Researcher's Positionality

Consideration of one's positionality is an integral part of research. The term positionality describes an individual's worldview and position in relation to a research task and its social and political context (Darwin Holmes, 2020). Thus, it reflects the researcher's chosen position within a specific research study (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013). Rowe (2014) argues that research positionality influences: i) how research is conducted; ii) its outcomes; iii) its results.

A reflexive approach is a prerequisite and ongoing process for the researcher to identify, construct, critique, and articulate their positionality (Darwin Holmes, 2020). Simply put, reflexivity is the idea that researchers should acknowledge and disclose themselves in their research to better understand their role or influence on it (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). During the initial planning stage of this research study, even whilst planning my research proposal, I brought to light my values, views, feelings and beliefs vis-à-vis inclusion, learners with autism and education. This was done because examining positionality intentionally allows for profound personal reflections, the discovery of oneself (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016) and the interrogation of biases that unconsciously drive decision-making (Berger, 2015).

My upbringing, educational journey, and professional as the researcher of this study formed my views and beliefs on fairness, opportunity, and being an active agent towards change. Throughout my career, I have passionately supported and promoted inclusive ideals in education, especially in the field of autism. Working within the Autism Spectrum Support Team (ASST) within the MEYR in Malta and as a current Head of Department supporting state schools in the area of inclusion has made me more aware of the need for a thorough understanding of the provision

for learners with autism. I reject the idea that learners, regardless of their diverse needs, should be provided support which is founded on a 'one fit all solution'. I am an educator who embraces an egalitarian vision whereby all learners receive equitable access to education regardless of their diverse needs.

Being conscientious towards a pro-inclusion viewpoint and considering the topic of my research study in regards to looking into the provision for learners with autism who attend mainstream schools in Malta made me more aware to avoid 'bias'. Bias is any tendency to prevent unprejudiced consideration of a question (Pannucci and Wilkins, 2010). To present an accurate picture of the SWOTs currently located in the provision of learners with autism in mainstream primary schools in Malta, I needed to be detached from my personal biases. This was particularly necessary as, due to the nature of my profession, I position myself as an insider researcher. My insider position in this research study emerges since; i) I am native to the setting of the research; ii) this research involves populations of which I am also a member of (Chammas, 2020).

To mitigate bias, particularly due to my insider position, all primary schools in Malta were invited to participate in this research study. This was an important step for me as an insider researcher, as educator participation was voluntary and open to all educators working in primary state schools and who support learners with autism. Furthermore, due to the nature of the topic vis-à-vis my values and beliefs on inclusive education and autism, I followed the guidelines of Sarantakos (2012) when analysing data. Thus as an insider researcher, I ensured that no information passed

on to me by the participants was withheld, and no parts of the data collected were forged or reworded with the scope of changing interpretation.

1.6 The Personal Motivational Drive of this Study

My interest in autism developed almost 20 years ago when I started working in the educational sector in Malta. Such an interest prompted me to pursue a Master's Degree in inclusive education to broaden my understanding of the field. However, whilst writing my Master's Dissertation, I observed several gaps in local literature on autism, which triggered the desire to partially bridge this gap with relevant research. After publishing the findings of my Master's research study (see Sciberras, 2018), the motivation to continue to explore the provision for learners with autism in Malta increased. In fact, through this research at a Doctoral studies level, the intention is to make a valid contribution to research and literature and potentially shed more light on the current provision at a local policy and practice level.

1.7 The Outline of this Research

This thesis is divided into six chapters. Chapter One 'sets the scene' for this research study. It provides a background to the study, justifies its need by identifying the gaps, and outlines its purpose. It presents the research questions and explains the methods employed to answer them and fulfil this study's aims and objectives.

The literature review in Chapter Two provides insight into the theoretical framework of this study. It also analyses how provision occurs in international contexts and what educators' perspectives of this provision are. This chapter further outlines the

gaps in relation to the SWOTs located within the provision for learners with autism, mainly since this is a limited area within research and literature. The intention is to understand the impact of school educational programmes on learners with autism. In Chapter Three, an overview of the methodology of this study is analysed and discussed. It explains the research design and provides details of the theoretical and applied structure of the research model. A mixed-methods approach was applied, followed by a Sequential Explanatory Research Design. The information provided by participants throughout the quantitative phase provided insights that required this study to identify which data required further explanation. Such in-depth information was captured when the qualitative data collection phase was conducted.

Chapter Four provides the analysis of the data collected. The quantitative analyses explored variables related to the provision and the SWOTs concerning the teaching and learning process, home-school collaboration, and training. The quantitative study findings highlighted several issues later explored during the qualitative phase.

Chapter Five provides a discussion of the data gathered in this research. This discussion revolves around the previously reviewed literature and the Ecological Systems theories with the intention that the necessary comparisons to international contexts are made.

Chapter Six provides conclusions and answers to the research questions. It outlines how this study contributes to new knowledge and fills the gaps in research and literature. This chapter also addresses the study's limitations and provides recommendations for policy and practice.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The provision for children with autism has long been a prominent area of attention and controversy within existing policies (e.g. Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government; The Scottish Government, 2018). It has also been a turning point in the scientific literature (e.g. Clark *et al.*, 2020; Daly *et al.*, 2016; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Majoko, 2018; Tynan and Davy, 2021) with scholars looking into the facilitators and barriers in relation to the inclusion of learners with autism in mainstream schools. Nevertheless, although preliminary analyses conducted on the provision for learners with autism have been carried out during the last decade in countries such as Turkey, the U.K., the U.S., Ireland and China, none of these studies has used a SWOT analysis as a tool for evaluation. Indeed, an earlier analysis conducted in Ireland on the evaluation of the education provision for students with autism did not make use of a SWOT analysis tool to pursue this (Daly *et al.*, 2016), and neither did the analysis on the provision for learners with autism in China as this was conducted through a literature review analysis (Sun *et al.*, 2013).

The same situation in regards to the lack of use of a SWOT analysis was found to persist in various recent studies that have explored the views of educators on the provision for learners with autism in schools (e.g., Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Clark *et al.*, 2020; Guldborg *et al.*, 2020; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Hamrick *et al.*, 2021; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Josilowski, 2019; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Majoko, 2018; Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021; Sobeck and Robertson, 2019; Tynan and Davy, 2021). These

limitations raise a salient question on whether the available research on the provision for learners with autism sufficiently guides schools to delve into appropriate long-term and short-term strategic planning as expected following the application of a SWOT analysis tool (Thamrin and Pamungkas, 2017).

Although these studies do not specifically use the SWOT analysis framework to gather and analyse data, they nevertheless still attempt to present descriptions of diverse themes related to how provision for learners with autism occurs. For instance, the research conducted by Hodges *et al.* (2020) focused on the interventions used to promote the participation of students with autism in schools, whilst the ones conducted by Hersh and Elley (2019) and Sobeck and Robertson (2019) provided a general view on the barriers and enablers to inclusion, and how training was sought. Further studies have also generated knowledge on what affects educator preparedness to support learners with autism (e.g. Hamrick *et al.*, 2021) and the ideal interaction between the home and school when supporting learners with autism (e.g. Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019). However, all of the above have used qualitative or quantitative collection methods to gather their data instead of mixed methods, whereby the latter tends to provide a richer view of the studied phenomenon. Furthermore, the studies above have not sought the views from a Maltese educational context. The gaps in local research on the field of autism are worth research appraisal mainly because the rise in the incidence rate of students diagnosed with autism has led to an increase in learners attending mainstream schooling. In this regard, mainstream schooling should be perceived as a setting which goes beyond the simple placement of students with IEN, including those with autism (Russell, Scriney and Smyth, 2022).

This literature review will first begin by presenting this study's theoretical framework. The Ecological Systems Theory of Bronfenbrenner (1979) and its reconceptualisation by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) were helpful additional theoretical frameworks which served as an additional positioning lens to locate the areas that emerged from previous research onto the systems and to appreciate the critical role that educators have in the development of children with autism. Presenting this at the beginning of this literature review is necessary as it will give the reader a clearer picture of the salient justifications as to why it is necessary to conduct a literature review in view of the current provision for learners with autism.

In order to look into the three areas above, this study shall seek educators' perspectives. Educators are at the core of the child's immediate environment, as proposed by Anderson Boyle and Deppeler (2014) and Bronfenbrenner (1979), thus considered as front liners in learners' educational experiences. Therefore, seeking the perspective of educators is critical as they are regarded as the agents who directly implement the curriculum and educational policies, organise learning experiences and, more notably, address the several needs of the learners within the classrooms (Aihie and Uwaoluetan, 2022). Since autism research is scarce within the Maltese educational context, this literature review will focus on studies conducted internationally to appraise the educators' perspectives on the provision. Furthermore, this Chapter will also look into the available published studies that indicate findings from educators' perspectives relating to the three areas discussed in Section 1.2.

Seeking educators' perspectives is necessary as, even though schools are generally viewed as crucial contributors towards the success of all learners, including those with autism, research consistently indicates that learners with autism do not always obtain the necessary support from these institutions. This idea is corroborated by Maciver *et al.* (2021), Roberts and Webster (2022), and Wilson and Landa (2019), who posit that lack of support may often lead to student failure in terms of participation and achievement throughout the educational experience. Lack of support may also lead to a situation where learners with autism are more likely to experience school avoidance and school refusal (Anderson, 2020; Filippello *et al.*, 2019; Totsika *et al.*, 2020), underperform (Anderson, 2020; Maciver *et al.*, 2021), or withdraw from the educational system altogether (McKinlay *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, this calls for an analysis of international educators' perceptions of how provision transpires in their contexts, as this will enable a direct comparison to the local context following the findings presented in Chapter 4.

2.1 The Theoretical Framework Underpinning this Research

In 1979, Bronfenbrenner adapted the Ecological Systems Theory to the field of education. Bronfenbrenner recognised two elements of child development: the first being the characteristics of the child and the environments in which he or she exists, and the second factor is the relationships and the interconnections between them (Gonzales, 2020). Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979) positions the child at the core of five interconnected systems, with the interactions that happen within and between these systems believed to influence the outcomes of the individual.

Figure 9: An Illustration of Bronfenbrenner's Ecological System (Gonzales, 2020)

The growing developing person's environment includes interconnections between different settings and external impacts from the wider environment (Calleja *et al.*, 2017). Bronfenbrenner (1979) hypothesised that the ecological system is “conceived as a set of nested structures, each inside the next like the set of the Russian Dolls” (p. 3). As illustrated in Figure 9, the structures vary from direct settings, such as family and educators, to more remote contexts in which the child is indirectly involved, such as society’s cultural beliefs and the policy system (Msangi, 2012). Given that the interconnection between the direct and indirect

systems impacts child development, it is critical to appraise each nested system co-dependently, as this would allow the understanding of the various environmental forces which impact the child (Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

According to the Ecological Systems Framework (Bronfenbrenner, 1979), these environmental contexts are found in different multifaceted levels proposed as the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem (Msangi, 2012). The interconnectedness between these systems is viewed as a “manifestation of overarching patterns of ideology and organisation of the social institutions common to a particular culture or subculture” (Bronfenbrenner, 2005, p. 54). As already outlined in Section 1.2, Bronfenbrenner (2005) argues that by analysing and comparing the characteristics of groups or entities sitting within the micro, meso, exo, macro and chrono systems, it is possible to systematically outline and distinguish the ecological properties of these large social contexts as “environments for human development” (p. 54). Such a description of the several inter-reliant social structures within each system will potentially allow for a better understanding of how these affect the connections with these systems, which in turn, shape the experiences and opportunities of the child (Kurth *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 10: The Ecology of Inclusive Education (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014, p. 6)

Building further on the abovementioned theory, Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) have reconceptualised Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory to inclusive education. As illustrated in Figure 10, this reconceptualisation was deemed necessary to build knowledge and increase the understanding of the learners' environment within this field, mainly since Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) support that inclusive education is a social construct. Like Bronfenbrenner (1979) proposed, Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) believe that inclusive education relies on the relationships between individuals and the systems within the

micro, meso, exo, macro and macro and chrono systems. They posit that, the relationship between the five interconnected systems must be explored in any learning environment that considers the needs of all learners (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). Such evaluation is critical as education systems are responsible for promoting social justice through the equitable distribution of quality education to all children hence, promoting a system based on fairness and inclusive education (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014)

In reaction to events and interactions mentioned in the previous sections, the brain never stops developing and changing (Hammond and Harvey, 2018). Hence, child development may be shaped (Hammond and Harvey, 2018). The school is one impactful setting that influences such child development. According to Deb (2018), a school is where information is imparted, skills are developed, and appropriate behaviour is instilled, resulting in responsible, possibly productive individuals to create a healthy society. Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems framework allows schools to contextualise child development and consider the different system levels' overlapping and interacting nature (Hayes, O'Toole and Halpenny, 2023).

Children are regarded as 'learners' when they enter the school system. However, their 'entry' comes with baggage whereby different developments such as family dynamics, socio-economic status, and disabilities would impact performance. According to Gonzales (2020), student well-being should be given as much attention in schools as academic achievement because it affects child development in terms of well-being. Although educators cannot change a child's history, they can

still attempt to understand each child's situation (Gonzales, 2020). Indeed, knowledgeable and compassionate educators may foster a caring, safe, and supportive atmosphere in which all learners may attain their full potential and become participating members of the school community and, eventually, of society.

When considered from an ecological systems perspective, educators may identify hidden barriers to learning and enable learners to succeed to the best of their capacity (Gonzales, 2020). In order to recognise a child's needs, schools should acknowledge the interactions with the child's significant others and across ecological systems levels as, according to Bronfenbrenner (1979), this is how child development occurs. An example provided by Darling-Hammond *et al.* (2020) highlights how emotions can trigger or block learning. According to Darling-Hammond *et al.* (2020), the child's social contexts activate emotions, and they can shape neural connections that contribute to attention, concentration, and memory, to knowledge transfer and application. Considering that in school, the child is a learner, but this identity (learner) is only one of the identities the child has in other microsystems such as the family, neighbourhood and wider community, the emotions experienced by the learners would either inhibit or facilitate their learning process. Nevertheless, although schools might not be able to control developments beyond their educational remit, they may still support the learner. Indeed, Darling-Hammond *et al.* (2020) have argued that schools should: i) have a deeply integrated approach to practice that supports the whole child; ii) build strong relationships and learning communities; iii) support social, emotional, and cognitive development; iv) provide a system of supports as needed for healthy development, productive

relationships, and academic progress (p. 99). This suggests that the school should see the child holistically, not simply as a learner.

When taking the recommendations of Darling-Hammond *et al.* (2020), in light of the reconceptualisation in the Ecology of Inclusive Education Framework whereby the child is referred to as the 'learner', Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, (2014) argue that the school setting, the learning process, and the relationships that learners with IEN build with their typically developing classmates and educators all contribute to their social, cognitive, and academic development (Anderson, Boyle, and Deppeler, 2014; Hayes, O'Toole and Halpenny, 2023). According to Anderson, Boyle, and Deppeler (2014), the school's social and physical elements contribute to every student's development. Physical elements include the school building, classrooms, courtyard, curriculum, and teaching methods, whereas social elements include students, parents, educators and their relationships (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). Both the physical and the social elements are reliant on one another. Thus, any decisions or situations taken throughout the learners' educational journey will likely impact their development.

Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) posit that all that transpires within and between each of the five systems involves pre-planned decisions followed by actions (e.g. early intervention, policy development and implementation) which impact child development and the inclusion of the learner in schools. Nevertheless, although the abovementioned impacts would benefit learners, this does not occur spontaneously. It may be hypothesised that if the decisions and actions taken within each interconnected system are based on

appropriate intervention and support, this allows for increased participation and thus “reduces exclusion within and from education” (UNESCO, 2005, p. 13). However, Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) note that the amount of influence a factor has on the experience of inclusive education for the learner will depend on: i) where the systems are positioned within which a factor sits, ii) the importance attached to a factor by those responsible for the system (Anderson, Boyle, and Deppeler, 2014). Taken together, what is proposed by Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) leads to an understanding that if the elements which are located within the five interconnected systems are measured, planned for, and implemented equitably by the persons responsible for doing so accordingly, this will enable learners to be active participants and achieve fruitful outcomes leading to an inclusive learning process.

According to Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), the inclusive process for the learners at the core of their Ecological Framework of Inclusive Education is underpinned by participation, achievement, and value. Rodden *et al.* (2019) argue that these three core principles allow individuals to be valued as “a whole person and not simply viewed exclusively through the disability lens of deficits” (p. 237). McLinden *et al.* (2018, p. 165) attest that the three principles outlined in the Ecology of Inclusive Education model ensure that all children can:

- i) **participate** through being actively engaged in schooling;
- ii) **achieve** through access to appropriate learning goals that meet individual needs supported with meaningful and attainable assessment;

- iii) be **valued** for who they are as an individual and what they have to offer to others.

Whilst the description of McLinden *et al.* (2018) provides an understanding of how participation, achievement and value within the context of a learner in a school setting should be promoted, Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) posit that these do not transpire in an educational vacuum. Indeed, they indicate that “there are many factors that sit within various systems of the Ecology of Inclusive Education that influence and, at times, put pressure on the three determinants of inclusive education” (p. 7). The elements of participation, achievement and value will be discussed and contextualised in the following sections regarding what impacts their existence within the five interconnected systems proposed by Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014). This analysis shall allow for a better understanding of how each system impacts the educational experience of learners, particularly those with autism.

2.1.1. The Microsystem

The prime system an individual is surrounded by in their most immediate environment is identified as the *microsystem*. The microsystem includes individuals or systems the child frequently interrelates with, such as the family, educators, and peers (Predescu, Al-Ghazi and Darjan, 2018). Similar to Bronfenbrenner (1979), Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) have placed the learner directly at the centre of the microsystem. The microsystem encompasses all the situations during which the learner directly experiences formal and informal learning in schooling, such as those related to “teachers, non-teaching staff, peers, physical learning spaces,

classroom cultures and routines, resources and the playground” (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014, p. 29). Positive impacts within Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler’s Ecological Systems Framework of Inclusive Education at a microsystem level were explored in a recent study based on focus groups conducted by Bolourian *et al.* (2022) on teachers’ perceptions of autism, inclusive practices, and relationship building strategies. The teachers’ perspectives in this study indicated that when learners with autism are provided with predictable classroom routines, these give them structure (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022). This study concluded that within such a structure, the classroom tends to run smoother as students with autism are more likely to be engaged in learning and are less likely to demonstrate behaviour perceived as challenging (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022).

The evidence retrieved from the study of Bolourian *et al.* (2022) provides an understanding that the participation, learning and achievement of learners with autism are impacted by the microsystem, indicating the criticality of adequate planning and implementation at this ecological level. The participating educators in this same study also considered the criticality of having adequate physical classroom environments, such as space for movement, purposeful seating arrangements, and proximity to the teacher, suggesting that such restructuring of the classroom layout would facilitate learning by including various instructional activities and more group work (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022). Conclusions following the outcomes of a structured classroom physical setting included that these minimise disruptions to students and increase the possible use of antecedent-based strategies, which promote skill learning and prosocial behaviours for learners with autism (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022).

When considering the determinants which sit at a microsystem level within the context of a learner with autism, it may be argued that if the physical classroom spaces and classroom routines are not adequately planned for and appropriately put in place, learners with autism would potentially be excluded from being active participants, from being valued, and from eventual achievement. Thus, the three principles Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) postulated determine that in such cases, inclusive education will be negatively impacted (Figure 9). Bolourian *et al.* (2022) have concluded that even though the teachers in their study demonstrated a strong understanding of several strategies which may enable the inclusion of learners with autism, the importance given to home-school collaboration as an element lying at a microsystem level (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979) was viewed as less salient for promoting inclusion. Following such findings, Bolourian *et al.* (2022) suggested that educators' training programmes should emphasise the relevance of parent-educator relationships for promoting the successful inclusion of students with autism more broadly. Such training focusing on parent-educator relationships would allow educators to seek parents' help in identifying students' unique talents, strengths, and interests, facilitating learners' academic engagement (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022).

All the evidence presented in this section further justifies the salience of evaluating the three areas that this study focuses on in terms of the process of: i) teaching and learning; ii) training for educators; iii) home-school collaboration. This section has substantiated that the microsystem, as proposed in Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) and Bronfenbrenner (1979), impacts learners' development to the extent that

appropriate input from persons who are closest to the learner would facilitate their participation, achievement and value within schools.

The following sections shall subsequently outline the remaining four systems in the Ecological Systems Theory of Bronfenbrenner (1979) and the Ecological Systems Theory of Inclusive Education proposed by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014). As already outlined in Section 1.2, this will further justify the significance of conducting a SWOT analysis of the three areas to provide a clear picture of the provision for learners with autism.

2.1.2 The Mesosystem

The *mesosystem* is another system outlined in Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014). This system differs from the other system levels since it suggests that influencing developments within the microsystem does not have an impact in isolation (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). In fact, the mesosystem locates the relationship between two or more microsystems which constantly interact with the other systems (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). For example, contributing to this interconnectedness, which at all systems-level might affect the inclusion process, is home-school collaboration. The latter takes the form of interaction and communication between the student's family and the school. Azad, Marcus, and Mandell (2021) posit that effective communication between the home and school is essential for optimising the provision for learners with IEN and particularly specify that this is critical in facilitating the generalisation of skills. The studies of Azad *et al.* (2016) and Azad *et al.* (2018) found that through collaboration, parents and teachers suggest that

home-school collaboration can facilitate the generalisation of skills for learners with autism, as parents can provide educators with information about their child's needs and strengths. After acquiring this information, educators may provide parents with information about teaching and learning strategies to help them support their children at home, thus promoting generalisation across settings (Azad *et al.*, 2016; Azad *et al.*, 2018). It may be hypothesised that such interaction between the home and the school at a mesosystem level would potentially support learners in acquiring resources and skills, promoting their participation, achievement, and value (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). Therefore, this suggests that educators and parents are considered key stakeholders and collaborative partners within the interconnected elements at a mesosystem level (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

Galkiene and Puskorienė (2020) corroborate this by affirming that a well-functioning mesosystem between the home and school mutually supports the microsystems. The connection of the microsystem and the mesosystem is located within a mechanism where adaptations of instruction and support to the teaching and learning processes for learners with autism become active (Galkiene and Puskorienė, 2020). Such dynamism in terms of adequate support would potentially see learners, including those with autism, participate, be valued and experience achievement (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

2.1.3 The Exosystem

The *exosystem* incorporates the formal and informal structures that “impinge upon or encompass the immediate settings containing the learner” (Bronfenbrenner 1979,

p. 6). Thus, what sits at an exosystem level does not exist directly within the immediate environment of the learners (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). However, such “events occur to affect the setting containing the developing person” (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, p.25), indicating that what happens within the provision for learners depends on what happens outside of the school. Because of this, it may be posited that external influences indirectly influence the learner (Dobson and Douglas, 2018) and thus, the changes occurring in one part of a system impact other areas of the system (Colville *et al.*, 2021). Within a SWOT analysis, these external influences are related to the opportunities and threats focusing upon favourable and unfavourable forces in and outside the school's environment. These elements still impact the learners’ schooling experience, although they occur externally at an exosystem level (Onwuegbuzie, Collins and Frels, 2013).

Within their Framework, Anderson, Boyle, and Deppeler (2014) report that the exosystem includes school structures, culture, values and ideology, resource allocation, and policies and procedures. In her review on teachers and school administrators as leaders impacting the child’s exosystem, Gonzales (2020) has highlighted educators’ ability to show awareness of their development needs, their aptitudes to be flexible and adaptable, and the ability to work and build relationships with others collaboratively as skills which the learners’ exosystem may impact. The capability of educators to flexibly collaborate with stakeholders involved in the education of a child with autism justifies what Gonzales (2020) postulated as impacting the process of: i) teaching and learning; ii) training for educators; iii) home-school collaboration. Thus, the exosystem level, as proposed by Gonzales (2020), would, within the context of the learner with autism, enable educators to

become front-line leaders in school systems and recognise their strengths and weaknesses concerning the complex and challenging demands that learners with autism may have when joining their classroom.

2.1.4 The Macrosystem

Anderson, Boyle, and Deppeler (2014, p.30) note that within the Ecology of Inclusive Education, the:

macrosystem encompasses the varying contexts in which the school exists – social, political, historical and global – as well as other factors such as the education system or systems, current agendas (standardisation of student achievement and professional performance; increased accountability), and, if applicable, a mandated curriculum.

In line with Bronfenbrenner's (1994) argument about the *macrosystem* being considered to be the "societal blueprint for a particular culture" (p. 6), Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler's (2014) view suggests that laws, policies, customs, and societal values are perceived as part of the macrosystem that permeates the child's educational environment. Therefore, any political and social frameworks, government policies, and legislation mutually affect individuals' structures and behaviour at an internal and an external level of the educational institution (Onwuegbuzie, Collins and Frels, 2013). For instance, in the 90s, the culture of inclusive education, perceived as a right for all children, irrespective of their abilities, culture, socio-economic background, race and gender, was significantly influenced by the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994). Furthermore, the culture of inclusive education has also been influenced by movements such as the Disability Rights Movement and national law and policy (Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local

Government, 1988; Education Scotland Act, 2016; Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government, 2016).

Gonzalez (2020), however, holds a critical stance on the promising context in terms of legislation and policy on inclusive education and questions whether the endorsement of inclusive education policies in several countries may be portrayed as simply a rhetorical “window-dressing for policymakers and education ministries” (p. 114) rather than “an ongoing process involving of change and improvement to address the education needs of all children without discrimination” (p.114). According to UNESCO (2015), one of the challenges leading to the aforementioned transpires from educators’ lack of attention to and awareness of inclusive education policy, which, according to Gonzales (2020), derives from school and educator readiness. Gonzales (2020) argues that a lack of readiness findings in failure to implement policy. The lack of readiness to implement policy will impact learners’ achievement, participation, and value levels, thus affecting the child’s direct systems (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

2.1.5 The Chronosystem

The *chronosystem* represents the movement of time and its impact on the learner, providing prospects for reflection, transformation, restructuring, and evolution of the elements within each system (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). Within the Ecology of Inclusive Education, “the timeframe for this system is that of the learner’s enrolment within formal school education – the years of primary and secondary schooling” (p. 30). In the case of students with autism in Malta, the chronosystem

moves along the primary and secondary schooling years. Children transition from one school to another several times between 3 and 16 years of age.

Children attending schools in Malta undergo two major transitions in primary school. The first significant transition occurs for children in Year 1. This transition is considered a major one as the setting of the Year 1 class in Malta sees children learning formal literacy and numeracy skills, including writing. For these children, this is the first time they also experience homework. The other major transition occurs when children are in Year 4. Year 4 holds a significant transition as this is when children start sitting for formal examinations. The chronosystem is particularly relevant to this research, given that the value of educational stakeholders throughout each transition period places significant responsibilities upon educators for learners to be provided with essential support amid their compulsory educational journey (McLinden and McCracken, 2016).

Nevertheless, changes over time in terms of inclusive education and autism have also led to prospects of transformation, restructuring, and evolution (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). For instance, as mentioned in Section 1.1, the placement of learners with conditions such as autism from resource centres to mainstream schools gradually progressed following several countries' signing of the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994) and also through further knowledge of autism, meaning that it is no longer considered a rare condition (Bond and Hebron, 2015). Furthermore, following empirical research (e.g. Asperger, 1944; Kanner, 1943) and the restructuring of diagnostic manuals from the late 60s to the 21st century, the understanding of autism evolved from a condition linked to

schizophrenia to a neurodevelopmental condition (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; World Health Organization, 2019). The above leads to an understanding that the chronosystem would impact the learner's participation, achievement, and value if individuals and systems are willing to embark on a transformational journey in terms of training, policy and practice to improve the provision for learners, including those with autism.

The Ecology of Inclusive Education is used as a lens throughout this research study as Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) deem it necessary to understand what is required in terms of reform that provides quality education for all. They argue that the several causes of marginalisation and exclusion “sit beyond the boundaries of the school fence” (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014, p. 23). As discussed in Section 2.1, these causes could be located in the nested five systems. Hence it is critical to analyse the SWOTs within the three areas. This analysis is necessary as the interconnected systems “attempt to capture the dynamic complexity of education systems, where individuals, communities, policies, and practices are imbricated in enabling or constraining access and success” (Walton *et al.*, 2020). Even though the Ecology of Inclusive Education has been used as a lens in studies focusing on the role of school leaders (e.g. Óskarsdóttir *et al.*, 2020) and in understanding educational access for refugees with a disability (Walton *et al.*, 2020), it has not yet been used to appraise the provision for learners with autism. Notwithstanding this limitation, the different system levels will still allow an understanding of the experiences shaped by the interplay of developments located in each system. The understanding of what sits at these system levels would potentially raise awareness of the SWOTs, which in effect might either exclude

learners with autism or contrastingly create opportunities for their inclusion and success.

2.2 Local Policy and Practice: The Maltese Context

As mentioned in Chapter 1, the shift concerning policy development led policymakers to include the area of inclusive education as one of the key principles of the National Minimum Curriculum (NMC), where the basic rights of children including those with a disability, are protected (Ministry of Education, 1999). This has led policymakers to become interested in broader issues related to social inclusion and how education can play a role in encouraging social unity within societies that are progressively more socially and culturally diverse (Armstrong, Armstrong and Spandagou, 2011).

The NMC (Ministry of Education, 1999) was followed by a policy for students with disabilities where obligations on schools to effectively provide quality education and an Individualised Education Plan (IEP) for learners with a statement of needs, including those with autism were placed (Ministerial Committee on Inclusive Education (MCIE), 2000). The aforementioned policy for students with disabilities also emphasised the functions of the Statementing Moderating Panel¹ whereby where necessary, this Board puts forward recommendations for learners to be supported by learning support educators (LSEs). The role of the LSE is to facilitate the inclusion process of all learners, with or without a statement of needs within

¹ The body which establishes a statement of needs to the student and the level of educational support needed to ensure the entitlement of quality education in Malta.

mainstream educational settings. Support in the classroom includes the adaptation of the curriculum. This type of support is similar to what is implemented in other international educational scenarios. Indeed, similar to the Maltese educational scenario, LSEs are employed in the majority of schools in countries such as England, Scotland, the United States and Italy (Ashbaker and Morgan, 2012; Blatchford, Russell and Webster, 2012; Devecchi *et al.*, 2012; Symes and Humphrey, 2011; Warhurst *et al.*, 2014).

In 2009, the Human Resources Department of the Directorate of Educational Services issued a circular (HRD/46/2009) (Ministry of Education, Culture, Youth and Sport, 2009), which explained the support allocation recommendations of the Statementing Moderating Panel:

- **Full-Time Support on a one-to-one basis:** The learner who requires this type of support is allocated an LSE who dedicates all the time on school premises to support the learner on a full-time, one-to-one basis.
- **Full-Time Support but not on a one-to-one basis:** The student requiring the full support of the LSE is provided full-time support throughout the whole day but not on a 1:1 basis. Hence, the LSE may support other students in the same classroom.
- **Shared support in the same class:** The LSE who provides this type of support to learners is to be present in the classroom throughout the

whole day. This support is shared amongst learners in the same class who are entitled to this type of support

- **Shared Support across classes:** When this type of support is recommended, the child does not necessitate support by the LSE throughout the day while on school premises. Indeed, the LSE might be required to support other students in other classes in addition to the class where the student receives instructions.

- **Benefits from shared support if available:** The needs of the student requiring this type of support are to be addressed and met by the class teachers. If an LSE is available in the class, he/she needs to collaborate with the teacher to facilitate the learning and the inclusion of the learner who would benefit from further individualised support.

Building on the NMC (Ministry of Education, 1999), further educational policies placed inclusion on their agenda and embedded various values required for social unity. The National Curriculum Framework for All (Ministry of Education and Employment, 2012) and the 'Respect for All Framework' (Ministry for Education and Employment, 2014) placed a responsibility on each member of the school community to adopt progressive human values such as 'respect', 'inclusivity', 'equity' and 'diversity', to act as role models for the benefit of the school community. Both the aforementioned policies promote the belief that all students, irrespective of their diverse abilities, should experience success through justifiable access to learning (MEYR, 2022a).

In light of the aforementioned, Malta felt the necessity to develop a policy that considers all of the aforementioned aspects but focuses solely on the concept of inclusion. The policy 'A Policy on Inclusive Education in Schools Route to Quality Inclusion' (MEYR, 2022a) is developed upon the four central pillars which are key for 21st-century education vis-à-vis to teaching and learning and for the design of curricular programmes. These four pillars: Learning to know, Learning to do, Learning to live together and Learning to be (UNESCO, 1996) ensure that learners, irrespective of their diverse needs, including those with autism, will be able to achieve the essential understanding of values and acquire the required abilities for employability with the intention that such individuals become active participants within the community (MEYR, 2022a). This policy also outlines how the principles of inclusion and diversity underpinned within the National Curriculum Framework for All (Ministry of Education and Employment, 2012) may be implemented within educational settings in Malta. Indeed, this policy endorses the belief that all learners, irrespective of their needs, challenges and abilities, should experience achievement through equitable access to learning (MEYR, 2022b).

Through a letter circular issued by the Director General in charge of Educational Services, schools have been directed to develop action plans in their School Development Plan (SDP), which address the ten themes applied within this policy and will gradually be implemented within the school throughout the coming years (MEYR, 2022b). The ten central themes Inclusive and Strategic Leadership; Whole School Development Planning; Whole School Inclusive Environment; Collaboration with parents and community engagement; Individual Education Planning; Teaching and Learning; Learner and Staff well-being; Continuous Professional Development; Positive Behaviour Management; Support Structure and services which are

comprehensively outlined in the document 'National Inclusive Education Framework' (MEYR, 2022b). The central aim of this framework is to direct schools towards committing themselves to inclusive policies and practices with the intention that provision for learners is of high quality. Indeed, each pillar within the framework has a set of best practice indicators which all stakeholders responsible for the education and well-being of students, irrespective of their IEN, should consider.

Although the aforementioned policies are well intended and aim to provide support to all learners, including those with autism, it is unsure whether such educational policies deliver educational justice for students with autism (McLaren, 2013; Merry, 2020). For instance, a mixed-methods study conducted with parents of children with autism who attend mainstream schools in Malta concluded that the lack of educator knowledge seems to lead to parental concerns about whether their child's needs are being met (Attard and Booth, 2023). Furthermore, this study concluded that some parents felt that schools lack the necessary resources to support learners with autism (Attard and Booth, 2023). Another study that sought to explore the extent of implementing evidence-based practices (EBPs) in Maltese primary schools when supporting learners with autism also shed light on whether practice is aligned with policy on inclusive education (Sciberras, 2018). Indeed, this study involving educators who support learners with autism found that, only 10% of the practices used in the classroom to support learners with autism are classified as evidence-based (Sciberras, 2018). This questions whether current practice serves justice particularly since in an ethical analysis on whether educational policies deliver educational justice for learners with autism, Merry (2020) argues that educational justice for learners with autism revolves around rights whereby children on the

spectrum should have equal access to the necessary educational resources and adaptations as those students without autism. Similar to the views of Merry (2020), several scholars, including Roleska *et al.* (2018) and van Kessel *et al.* (2019), have argued that concerns prevail regarding whether current policy serves educational justice and fulfils the rights of learners with autism. Indeed, literature shows that although inclusion policies are in place and seek to improve learning outcomes for all students, many students with autism continue to experience high levels of exclusion and academic underachievement (Ashburner, Ziviani, and Rodger, 2010; Keen, Webster and Ridley, 2016; McLaren, 2013).

In view of the aforementioned, although several local policies include the aspects of well-being and sense of belonging as per the key features required in policy so as to fulfil the rights of learners with autism (e.g. Merry, 2020; Roleska *et al.*, 2018; van Kessel *et al.*, 2019), information on the latter in light of the educational instruction for learners on the spectrum is lacking (e.g. Ministry of Education and Employment, 2012; MEYR, 2022a; MEYR, 2022b). This transpires even though studies on the provision for learners with autism (e.g. Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Symes and Humphrey, 2011) have consistently concluded that students' sense of belonging is integral to their school participation to prevent intolerance to difference and maximise school participation, perhaps minimising the levels of exclusion and underachievement likely to be experienced by learners with autism (Ashburner, Ziviani, and Rodger, 2010; Keen, Webster and Ridley, 2016; McLaren, 2013). Minimising the latter and the former would need to see policy reflecting the opportunity for meaningful access, both in terms of the conditions which allow one to join the setting and the aspects of the physical environment (Merry, 2020). However, for this to transpire, policy

needs to translate itself into seeing educators embedding individualised intervention across routines, activities, and environments and ensuring adequate classroom adaptations by embedding organisational, communication, sensory or behavioural supports to make the content and environment more accessible (Siller *et al.*, 2021). The latter is necessary as lighting design, air quality, and temperature within the physical environment must be thoroughly evaluated, as such aspects tend to affect the behaviour of learners on the spectrum (e.g. Cunningham, 2020; Tola *et al.*, 2021).

Given that the end of the twentieth century led to an era of transition in relation to educational systems and policy across international scenarios, similarly, the Maltese educational authorities began planning a route to promote an inclusive education system to guarantee equitable access to the curriculum to all learners including those on the autism spectrum. Following the aforementioned transition period, the rate of students with autism attending mainstream educational settings in Malta increased significantly. Indeed, in 2007, Posada *et al.* (2007) reported that 80% of students with autism in Malta were attending mainstream schools. This rate continued to increase more than a decade later since, as already mentioned in Chapter 1, an audit carried out in the field of special and inclusive education in Malta identified that the rate of learners attending special school settings was just over 0.1%, placing Malta as one of the European Union (EU) member states with the highest placement rate concerning students with IEN including those with autism attending mainstream school settings (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2014).

As stated in Section 1.1, due to the aforementioned increase of autism in the Maltese Islands, Malta devised a national legislation, "Persons within the Autism Spectrum (Empowerment) Act", for the concerned authorities to establish an Autism Advisory Council (Sciberras, 2019). The purpose of the Council is to promote initiatives that increase awareness to further achieve autism acceptance within the Maltese society (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). The Autism Advisory Council also aims to focus on improving ways of identification concerning those undiagnosed adults. It also aims to provide advice on self-determination to persons on the spectrum as this would possibly enhance access to appropriate support services and equal opportunities for inclusion and participation in society (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government).

The formulation of the 'Persons within the Autism Spectrum (Empowerment) Act' placed Malta as one of thirteen European Union Member States having a policy that specifically addresses the needs of individuals with autism (Kessel et al., 2019). The intention of establishing this Council was to develop and submit an Autism Support State Plan to the Minister responsible for persons with disability (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). The Autism Support State Plan intends to address issues related to family involvement, early recognition of the condition and intervention services, educational provision and support services, access to sports and leisure, adult support services, training and professional and personal development (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). In terms of this State Plan, the Government of Malta has launched a National Autism Strategy that is intended to be implemented between 2021 and 2030. In terms of the context of the education of individuals with autism, this Strategy will ensure that

an updated, modernised, all-inclusive framework is established and reviewed to meet the educational needs of students on the autism spectrum (Ministry for Inclusion and Social Wellbeing, 2021). Furthermore, the National Autism Strategy, as part of the Autism State Support Plan shall extend IEPs also to students in tertiary education (Ministry for Inclusion and Social Wellbeing, 2021). The establishment of the principle of Universal Design as a design that works for everyone is also part of this Strategy (Ministry for Inclusion and Social Wellbeing, 2021).

2.3 Educators' Perspective on the Educational Provision for Learners with Autism

Following the discussion on the theoretical framework guiding this research, it may be noted that educators are seen as critical agents at an Ecological Systems Level. Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) view educators as active participants in child and learner development, with educators being present directly or indirectly, hence impacting the child's development in all five interconnected systems (Figure 9 and Figure 10). Aihie and Uwaoluetan (2022) argue that educators are regarded as the most meaningful agents in the educational system as they are the bodies who directly implement the curriculum and educational policies, organise learning experiences and, more notably, address the several needs of the learners within the classrooms. Thus, their knowledge, skills and attitude within the educational context are salient variables in the success of all teaching (Jordan, Roberts, and Hume, 2019). Within the context of learners with autism, Jordan, Roberts, and Hume (2019) argue that when developing inclusive practices for learners with autism, 'solutions' cannot exist solely in adjusting the curriculum but must also incorporate changes in those involved in planning and

teaching that curriculum. The changes required from those involved in the curriculum further confirm the role of educators in ensuring successful teaching and learning for learners with autism and their salient participation in research studies. The importance of considering the voices of educators who support learners with autism in research was confirmed by recent studies on inclusive education. For instance, Bolourian *et al.* (2022) argued that given that teachers' perceptions can considerably impact the effective inclusion of learners with disabilities, including those with autism, it is critical to understand these viewpoints to determine how to best support teachers in the development of valuable learning environments for their students. Similar views regarding including educators' perspectives in research on autism were brought forward by Güleç-Aslan (2020), who argued that the needs, experiences and recommendations of kindergarten teachers in the support provided to learners with autism are critical, mainly because these would allow participants to transfer their thoughts in depth and can also provide critical guiding insights for ensuring successful inclusion practices.

The points above and the primary goals of the present research contributed to the salient need to explore educators' experiences in recognising and identifying the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism. The driving factor behind this analysis is the awareness that proposed recommendations on how educators could address the barriers experienced by learners and their educational settings are informed upon these strengths and opportunities. Therefore, the following sections shall examine educators' perspectives in view of the educational provision for learners with autism in primary schools.

2.4 A SWOT Analysis of the Provision for Learners with Autism

The following sections will discuss the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism in the process of teaching and learning, training for educators and home-school collaboration. *Strengths* will be discussed and reviewed in view of the capacities currently allowing schools to achieve their goals. Ustabulut (2021) explains that when applying a SWOT analysis, *strengths* refer to the current assets and capabilities that have an advantage for an organisation to reach its goals. Ustabulut (2021) observes that these advantages must be protected and should be at the forefront of the organisation.

In contrast to the *strengths*, the *weaknesses* in this current study will be presented in view of the limitations that impede or slow down schools from achieving their desired goals when supporting learners with autism. Negeri, Kristiawan and Puspita (2020) identify *weaknesses* as conditions where the operational activities of work units or organisations cannot run smoothly due to several obstacles. Some of the points put forward by Negeri, Kristiawan and Puspita (2020), which according to them, may be considered *weaknesses* within an organisation, are the limited resources, staff abilities or competencies that are not optimal (Negeri, Kristiawan and Puspita, 2020) and which may slow down the setting from performing effectively.

Furthermore, considering this literature review, *opportunities* and *threats* will be perceived as favourable and unfavourable forces in and outside the school's environment. The *opportunities* in this research will reference the ideas that could support change and produce more quality provisions for learners with autism. This

perspective will be followed as *opportunities* in a SWOT analysis refers to any possibilities that could provide alternative solutions to organisations to determine and strengthen the status of their strategies and plans (Ustabulut, 2021). According to Ustabulut (2021), *opportunities* also reference the circumstances that could develop or change the setting to enhance positive environmental situations. Conversely to the *opportunities*, the *threats* referred to in this study will be discussed in view of the characteristics that may place potential risks that could eventually negatively impact the provision for learners with autism in the teaching and learning process, home-school collaboration and training for educators. Gürel and Tat (2017) represent *threats* within a SWOT analysis as situations or conditions that could jeopardise the realisation of an activity or a task and thus make it difficult or impossible for an organisation to fulfil its goals.

Given the above, seeking the educators' perspectives on the SWOTs is critical. Exploring the SWOTs from educators' perspectives is necessary as the research on using a SWOT matrix to identify SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism is limited. Therefore, it is understood that not only would a SWOT analysis allow schools to appraise the current support and any potential advantages and risks, but carrying it out from educators' perspectives would add relevance to it.

2.5 The Teaching and Learning Process

It is every learner's right to have access to a quality school situation that meets their social and academic needs (Anderson, 2020). Access to an appropriate educational context is necessary as the achievement of foundational skills such as social, communicative, emotional, and literacy have practical implications for future

independent living and autonomy of individuals, including those with autism (Chen *et al.*, 2019, Howlin and Magiati, 2017).

Nonetheless, research indicates that even though several good practices have been reported in terms of empowering learners with autism and promoting independence throughout the teaching and learning process, barriers hindering this process tend to still be observed (e.g. Hersh and Elley, 2019; McDougal, Riby and Hanley, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivar and Curtis, 2019). Several studies have revealed internal and external barriers within the provision, leading to low expectations for learners' success (e.g. Anderson, 2020; Norris, 2022; Roberts and Simpson, 2016).

To increase the expectations of the progress of learners with autism, schools must provide quality teaching and learning. Nonetheless, to acquire this, schools are required to embark upon an evaluation of a strategic process, not only to be able to identify the existing strengths and opportunities within the provision but also to be able to recognise any weaknesses and threats that may hinder learning and participation of all students (Roberts and Simpson, 2016; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Suhrheinrich *et al.*, 2021). This evaluation is salient as the earlier work of Smith *et al.* (1967) defined teaching as a system of actions involving an agent, an end in view, and a situation including two sets of factors. The agent in Smith *et al.*'s (1967) definition of teaching refers to the individual providing instruction within a school context which, in this case, refers to the educator. According to Smith *et al.* (1967), one of the factors leading to a lack of control in educators pertains to class size, characteristics of learners, and physical facilities. When encountering such issues beyond their control, educators of learners with

autism frequently find themselves at an impasse in terms of their capacity to increase the expectations of success for learners with autism.

Materechera (2018) substantiates this deterrent in moving forward to provide quality teaching and learning for learners with autism through evidence from a study which explored inclusive education from the perspectives of teachers in schools in South Africa. The findings of this study indicate that despite the positive perception towards inclusion, the lack of ability of not being able to control large class sizes, together with the lack of physical classroom space, sees teachers being “caught up in a dilemma between human rights and complex realities at the school level” (Materechera, 2018, p. 783). Therefore, despite the 50-year gap between the assertions of Smith *et al.* (1967) and the conclusions of Materechera (2018), class sizes and physical space are beyond the class teachers’ control and are, in effect, perceived as threats that could hinder the effectiveness of the provision for learners including those with autism.

Despite the scenario in terms of variables beyond the control of educators (Materechera, 2018; Smith *et al.*, 1967), there are several situations that educators may change (Smith *et al.*, 1967) to ameliorate the provision for learners. For instance, conclusions of recent studies have identified that educators may control their attitude towards learners with autism (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; D’Agostino and Douglas, 2021; Garrad, Rayner and Pedersen, 2019; Gómez-Marí; Russell, Scriney and Smyth, 2022; Sanz-Cervera and Tárraga-Mínguez, 2022). Such a change in attitude, which is entirely controlled by educators of learners with autism, would potentially see them becoming more focused on viewing the student as being able

to participate, achieve and be valued (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014) rather than viewing the student through a 'disability lens' (Rodden *et al.*, 2019).

To identify and address the variables that could influence current teaching practices that stimulate or inhibit students with autism from participating, achieving, and being valued within an inclusive environment, internal and external developments that affect such provision must be reviewed (Roberts and Simpson, 2016). Such implications could allow school settings to provide a more inclusive and barrier-free educational provision where children would succeed. Given this, the following section will look into the current SWOTs identified within empirical literature which are present within the teaching and learning process.

2.5.1 Strengths of the teaching and learning process

As already indicated in Section 1.1., the increase in the incidence of autism led to a shift for most learners with autism in terms of them attending mainstream primary schools worldwide, including Malta (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2014; van Kessel *et al.*, 2021). Hence, most educators can rationally expect to have one or more students with autism in their class each year (Clark *et al.*, 2020). Researchers have documented that students with IEN who attend mainstream settings, including those with autism, and who have teaching and learning strategies designed according to their abilities tend to exhibit higher levels of engagement and social interaction (Carter *et al.*, 2017) and have developmentally more innovative IEP goals than peers in resource centres (Kurth, Morningstar and Kozleski, 2014). This association highlights the need for learners' educational programmes to be prioritised and targeted through individualised

learning programmes designed to overcome barriers to learning, allowing learners with autism to build resilience (Lloyd, 2019). It may be assumed that such resilience would enable the ever-growing population of learners with autism in mainstream schools to become more engaged in learning, enhance their social communication skills, and potentially be able to steer across a predominantly neurotypical environment.

Figure 11: Strengths of the Teaching and Learning Process as Identified in Current Literature

Recent studies which have looked into the provision for learners with autism have indicated several current school strengths which allow learners to participate actively throughout the teaching and learning process (e.g. Clark *et al.*, 2020; Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021; Van Der Steen *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019). For instance, findings of a study that looked into the needs of 43 educational professionals who work with learners with autism in four Dutch schools have demonstrated that the current school's strength within the teaching and learning process of these schools is that of designing instruction tailored according to the unique needs of learners (Van Der Steen *et al.*, 2020). From the Ecological Systems perspective (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979), adapting instruction according to the child's individual educational needs happens within the microsystem, potentially increasing the children's participation

and engagement throughout learning. This association between the maximisation of participation and engagement and the development of adapted instruction justify the criticality of such a strategy when designing support for learners with autism.

Evidence gathered from a six-year longitudinal study which focused on exploring the classroom practices of teachers who educate students with autism in Australia enables the understanding of how adaptations of instructions whilst supporting learning with autism tend to occur (Clark *et al.*, 2020). This analysis deriving from data gathered from 87 teachers, concluded that the adaptations of instructions in the schools they work in are generally based mainly on the provision of modified or alternative tests (74.7%), slower-paced instructions (67.8%), and the simplification of teacher language when providing classroom instruction (58.6%) (Clark *et al.*, 2020). An emphasis on the latter was also made by a Turkish mixed-methods study by Yazici and McKenzie (2019) involving 27 teachers, whereby these indicated that step-by-step instruction is a feature supporting the adaptations of learners with autism. Acknowledging that step-by-step instructions are not the fastest way to teach skills to learners with autism, it is still considered a critical factor that allows for learners' gradual progress and leads them to comprehend what is expected of them (Yazici and McKenzie, 2019). In consolidation, the findings in this section suggest that despite being a slower and more protracted process of how adapted instructions are designed, step-by-step instructions are imperatively critical to the provision for learners with autism (Clark *et al.*, 2020; Van Der Steen *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019).

Although step-by-step instruction has been perceived as beneficial for learners with autism by Yazici and McKenzie (2019), educators should always consider each

child's learning preferences when designing such instruction (Rissanen *et al.*, 2019; Sasson, Yehuda and Miedijensky, 2021). For instance, research has demonstrated that learners with autism have generally been considered to possess strong visual processing skills (Curtin and Long, 2021; Grandin, 1995; Santos, Breda, and Almeida, 2017). Studies have established that when information is made visually accessible to learners with autism, they tend to demonstrate enhanced comprehension (Ayuningtyas *et al.*, 2021; Cooper *et al.*, 2022; Dyer, 2022; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019). Yazici and McKenzie (2019) concluded that benefits arising from the use of visual support within the provision for learners with autism lead to: (i) converting intangible phenomena into tangible ones to be better apprehended by the student, (ii) improving the student's communication skills since teaching words through visuals eases the learning process, (iii) increasing the capacity of students' vocabulary. Considering all the evidence presented in this section, it may be postulated that the benefits arising from visual support as part of the adaptations of instructions confirm that visual support is a relevant intervention strategy for addressing the diverse needs of learners with autism (Curtin and Long, 2021; Rutherford *et al.*, 2020).

Whilst exploring teachers' strategies for including children with autism in mainstream classrooms, a study by Lindsay *et al.* (2014) reported that 13 Canadian teacher participants highlighted the importance of having visual schedules as a strategy that supports adaptations for learners with autism. This study concluded that visual schedules provide a consistent and structured routine to learners with autism in the classroom. More recent research by Clark *et al.* (2020) yielded similar findings. This research concluded that visual support schedules were critical to

adapting learners' teaching and learning since they help enhance students' academic skills by addressing difficulties related to attention, EF, processing speed, and memory (Clark *et al.*, 2020).

The benefits of visual schedules as a supporting strategy were confirmed by two other recent studies conducted in America and Ireland, respectively (Curtin and Long, 2021; Tynan and Davy, 2021). Participants in the Irish study of Tynan and Davy (2021) that sought the views of educators on how the classroom environment can support pupils with autism during the teaching and learning process view visual schedules as a resource where children with autism "know what's happening next" and whereby "the subjects are laid out clearly for students" (p.10). The study of Curtin and Long (2021) involving eight primary school teachers also concluded that schedules help highlight the lessons or activities in order of sequence for the day. Collectively, the evidence in this section leads to an understanding that schedules enable predictability, forewarning and consistency for learners with autism, hence serving as a source that reduces worry, tension, frustration and anger. These benefits transpire as learners understand why a change in activity occurs (Curtin and Long, 2021). Indeed, visual schedules help learners to better cope with the difficulties they may encounter when initiating new actions, mainly due to their predisposition to remain fixed on a given set of tasks (Alsaedi, Carrington and Watters, 2020; Benallie *et al.*, 2021; Curtin and Long, 2021; Demetriou, DeMayo and Guastella, 2019; Fatima, 2019; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Majoko, 2018).

Tangibles are physical objects that can be held, manipulated, and used to teach specific concepts (Bassette *et al.*, 2019). Ongoing research has shown that using

tangibles is also part of the adapted instructions for learners with autism (Carbonneau, Marley, and Selig, 2013; Goñi-Cervera, Cañadas and Polo-Blanco, 2022; Marley and Carbonneau, 2014; Spooner *et al.*, 2019). These resources improve understanding of any underlying problem-solving processes, mainly when intangible concepts are presented to learners with autism (Goñi-Cervera, Cañadas and Polo-Blanco, 2022; Marley and Carbonneau, 2014). Learners with autism encounter such challenges due to difficulties related to EF skills, which tend to affect their academic abilities (Dijkhuis *et al.*, 2020).

Substantiating the benefits of using objects to teach learners with autism were findings of a survey conducted with 86 teachers across 10 states in the U.S. who support learners with complex needs, including those with autism (Jimenez and Stanger, 2017). Teachers in this study reported that they frequently used tangibles such as toy cars to make sets, toy frogs on a line for counting, or using a ruler and objects found in the classroom to teach concepts such as measuring skills (Jimenez and Stanger, 2017). This study concluded that using objects as a complementary source to the adaptations made to the learners' curriculum was critical to support students' learning, engagement, and generalisation during the teaching and learning process (Jimenez and Stranger, 2017). It may be posited that applying tangibles as part of the adapted instructions for learners with autism leads to enhanced generalisation skills, improving this area as part of their challenges in EF skills. For instance, a Spanish exploratory study conducted on the strategies which may be used to promote generalisation skills in students with autism found that building blocks and cubes were tangibles used to model counting (Goñi-Cervera, Cañadas and Polo-Blanco, 2022). The conclusions from this research study

indicated that these tangibles are required as these help students move towards more abstract terms and generalisation of concepts and skills (Goñi-Cervera, Cañadas and Polo-Blanco, 2022).

In addition to the use of tangibles, the use of digitalised tools has also been identified as enhancing the adaptations of instructions for learners. A study by Jimenez and Besaw (2020) has demonstrated that digital tools based on internet-based resources, such as educational software and games, are necessary to adapt instructions for learners with autism. Such means have been identified as a necessity as “the concept of inclusive education puts an obligation on educators to have a good knowledge of and ability to combine education technologies which meet the needs of all the learners participating in the education process” (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020, p.210).

Concerning adopting technological resources throughout learners' learning programmes, including those with autism, access to technology and electronic resources has significantly increased these past decades (Camilleri and Camilleri, 2017). This increase may have resulted from shifting educational stakeholders' mindsets in incorporating technology to promote innovative pedagogical practices in their classrooms (Sabayleh and Alramamneh, 2020). Research has shown that most educational practitioners, including teachers and LSEs, use smart boards, tablets and personal computers when teaching children with autism (Licona and Loke, 2017; Rising, 2017; Rutherford *et al.*, 2020). A study that involved 17 teachers and LSEs who work in a school in the U.S. which analysed how children with autism are currently using applications on tablets concluded that, students spent 51% of

their time in the classroom using a digital application that was intended to support academic areas such as reading, writing, and maths (King, Brady and Voreis, 2017).

The popularity in terms of the use of technology in the classroom may be increasing as research has shown positive associations between the inclusion of digital tools in classrooms and the ability of teachers to effectively meet the academic, social and behavioural needs of students with IEN, including those with autism (Judge, 2013; Kariippanon *et al.*, 2018; Knight, McKissick, and Saunders, 2013; Licona and Loke, 2017; Neely *et al.*, 2013; Rising, 2017; Soysa and Al Mahmud, 2019). For instance, one benefit of using educational games was strengthening fine motor and early literacy skills for students with autism (Soysa and Al Mahmud, 2019). However, while the analysis and conclusions of research findings indicate that technology is influential in education, one identified research in the field has shed some doubts on its constant use. Indeed, the study by Yazici and McKenzie (2019) conducted in a school in Turkey has seen educators outlining that using the computer in the classroom could damage the education process, particularly when the child becomes obsessed with the games presented in the class. One teacher in this study expressed how such fixations have led her to give up on using computer games to support classroom content altogether (Yazici and McKenzie, 2019).

Further to the current strengths linked to teaching and learning on support within the classroom for learners with autism is the implementation of peer support. Peer support strategies have been demonstrated as being a current strength in the provision of learners with autism, particularly in being effective in the teaching and learning of social behaviour and promoting social skills for learners with autism

(Crompton *et al.*, 2022; Watkins *et al.*, 2015). For instance, in one study that gathered data from 120 education professionals in Poland, introducing a buddy system in classes was seen as a current advantage by questionnaire participants (Hersh and Elley, 2019). Participants in this Polish study felt that this system was beneficial for learners with autism to acquire the necessary social, behaviour, and academic skills (Hersh and Elley, 2019). These participants highlighted that this system was deemed as currently successful as even neurotypical learners understood the “sense and the needs of such system” (Hersh and Elley, 2019, p.124) to promote further the inclusion of learners with autism (Hersh and Elley, 2019). Inclusion is necessary as whilst a good quality education is paramount to learners, including those with autism, a good quality inclusive education is optimal (Russell, Scrinet and Smyth, 2022).

A similar point to Hersh and Elley's (2019) findings on using the buddy system in classes was derived from a Canadian qualitative study that sought primary school teachers' perspectives on strategies for including students with autism in the mainstream classroom (Lindsay *et al.*, 2014). The findings of this study concluded that the buddy system gave “other children in the class the opportunity to get to know the students with autism and develop a tolerance for differences while recognising similarities” (Lindsay *et al.*, 2014, p. 118). The latter indicates that implementing the buddy system leads to shared social activities promoting equality and building on children's natural talents. Hence, the buddy system may be perceived as a promising strategy for promoting academic, behavioural, and social learning within inclusive environments (Dahary *et al.*, 2022).

Similar to the buddy system, an approach that promotes peer support to benefit learners in terms of social, behaviour, and academic skills is the Peer Preparation Programme (PPP). Throughout a four-week programme delivered to peers of a learner with autism in Australia, the PPP focused on autism awareness and acceptance and the reinforcement of acknowledging similarities and differences amongst individuals in the class (Xuereb and Lawson, 2019). This programme enabled neurotypical learners to work on and endorse empathy skills and be exposed to the meaning of stigma and its repercussions (Xuereb and Lawson, 2019). Following this four-week programme, observations and interviews with peers indicated that neurotypical students could put themselves in the shoes of their peers with autism and practised empathy through play during recess time (Xuereb and Lawson, 2019). As evidenced, most pupils were particularly interested in identifying common grounds of similarities rather than differences (Xuereb and Lawson, 2019). Corroborating this point is data from focus groups involving 11 educators, including teachers, assistant heads of schools and learning support coordinators, who reported having experience working with primary school students with autism in a mainstream school (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). In this Australian study, participants indicated that by implementing programmes such as the PPP, neurotypical learners could recognise their differences and take on the perspective of others, hence, being in a better position to be more accepting of diversity (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). Participants explained how this enabled neurotypical peers to proactively support students with autism in the classroom and on the playground (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). Similar to Hodges *et al.* (2020), a Spanish study involving the views of 10 teachers on how to address challenging behaviour manifested by students with autism in mainstream schools found that neurotypical developing

peers should be able to understand their classmates with autism to manage and understand behaviours perceived as challenging as they occur (Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021).

Nevertheless, evidence from the findings of a Lithuanian study conducted by Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020) involving 16 teachers saw participants lamenting the fact that they do not know how to present information about children with autism to typically developing children whilst also facing a dilemma regarding what to tell other children, and whether their parents [of typically developing children] should also be informed. To the authors' knowledge, this dilemma has not yet been addressed and answered within published research studies. The current evidence presented in this section offers essential insights regarding peer support as a current strength associated with the teaching and learning of students with autism and illustrates the beneficial effects of these practices. Nonetheless, dilemmas related to how educators present sessions such as PPPs frequently arise during the implementation process.

However, peers are not the only body currently enabling schools to provide a better inclusive environment for learners with autism in teaching and learning. Literature indicates that school administrators play a crucial role in the formation of inclusive school policy (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020), thus in motivating changes to instructional practices for learners with autism (Stadnick *et al.*, 2019). An indicative explanation of the aforesaid derives from the recent work of Lüddeckens, Anderson and Östlund (2022) on the principals' perspectives of inclusive education involving students with autism in Sweden. These scholars have argued that school

leaders must ensure that the schools' vision, values, and outcomes are non-discriminatory to ensure that all learners' requirements are supported in ways that facilitate inclusive education policy and practice. Preceding findings have also highlighted the points above. A qualitative study that looked into what facilitates or hinders the ability of LSEs to support pupils with autism in the North-West of England found that several LSE participants perceived that a strength in the school is having the support of members of the Senior Leadership Team (SLT) (Symes and Humphrey, 2011). LSEs in this study explained how the head of school is one of the critical bodies within their school who ensures that all learners with autism are included and that "the Head is obviously behind it, which makes a difference" (Symes and Humphrey, 2011, p. 157).

All the evidence above indicates that support at an SLT level is a strength that potentially enables schools to support learners with autism, thus highlighting the idea that the SLT is crucial in promoting a child-centred school ethos (Lloyd, 2019). The fact that the SLT is a critical body in supporting the teaching and learning process of learners with autism was also documented in ensuing research to that of Symes and Humphrey (2011). This research which looked into educators' perspectives concerning the provision for learners with autism in the U.S., concluded that one of the current school's capacities is that Heads of Schools were instrumental in developing an accepting, inclusive environment (Iadarola *et al.*, 2015). Along the same lines, a more recent qualitative study that sought Australian educators' perspectives on what impacts their decisions when selecting strategies for learners with autism also saw educators highlighting support from the SLT (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). This study saw participants in focus groups reporting that for

educators to be able to support the participation of learners with autism, they need to have access to adequate support, including resources. This research concluded that “without support from the top, it is often challenging to implement strategies and support the participation of students with autism on the ground” (p.7). Therefore, despite being situated at an exosystem level (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014), the support of the school’s administrators impacts the value of the potential of learners and is seen as impacting the extent of students’ participation, achievement, and value.

This section has outlined the strengths observed in the current empirical literature in the field. Figure 11 outlines the strengths identified in this literature review. As noted, the three strengths emerging from the current studies in view of teaching and learning for learners with autism are the adaptations of instructions for learners to support learning, educators having the support of members of the SLT, and students with autism having support from their peers. These contributions to the child's development are evident in the Ecological Systems of Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014). Indeed, whilst Bronfenbrenner (1979) places the educator and peers at the child’s microsystem, implementing appropriate support strategies would permeate the child’s development. Hence, the three identified strengths within this literature review, as illustrated in Figure 11, would impact the levels of participation, values, and achievement of the learner with autism.

2.5.2 Weaknesses of the teaching and learning process

Following a literature review of the weaknesses of the teaching and learning process, this analysis has outlined three key areas. As shown in Figure 12,

educators of students with autism perceive the weaknesses of the teaching and learning process as emerging from a lack of resources, students receiving instruction from LSEs rather than the class teacher, and teachers' lack of acceptance of students with autism. The following sections shall put forward the evidence gathered from recent research regarding the weaknesses of the teaching and learning process.

Figure 12: Weaknesses of the Teaching and Learning Process as Identified in Current Literature

Despite the critical need for adaptations to the instructions and the learning environment as outlined in Section 2.4.1, a study which sought to understand better facilitators and barriers to success at school for students with autism saw educators reporting that they often feel ill-equipped when they do not have the necessary resources as they attempt to meet the needs of learners with autism in their classrooms (Roberts and Simpson, 2016). Findings from more recent studies conducted in Ireland, Australia, France, Lithuania, Vietnam and Turkey have also consistently reported such an impediment within the provision for learners with autism (e.g. Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Cappe *et*

al., 2021; Leonard and Smyth, 2022; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Tran *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019).

Hersh and Elley's (2019) study collated data from questionnaires distributed to 120 teachers and other professionals, including educational therapists. Whilst sharing their views on the barriers and enablers of inclusion for learners with autism in Poland, the participants outlined that weaknesses arising in their schools from lack of resources included difficulties related to the employment of additional specialists due to the absence of funding (Hersh and Elley, 2019). Research has found that such limited input from experts in the field leaves educators feeling anxious, stressed and burnt out from wondering whether they are doing the right thing in terms of the accuracy of methods when supporting learners with autism (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Cappe *et al.*, 2021; Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Vincent and Ralston, 2020). Additionally, a situation whereby without external knowledge, educators can be involved in a "mechanism for recycling existing patterns of thinking and thus reinforcing the status quo" (Walton *et al.*, 2022, p.142) tends to be inflicted. All this evidence leads to an understanding of a focal point related to associations made between the lack of resources, and the quality of provision for learners with autism, further reinforcing the fact that these issues may hinder schools from helping learners with autism achieve their individual educational goals (Cappe *et al.*, 2021; Leonard and Smyth, 2022; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Roberts and Simpson, 2016).

Further to the points mentioned earlier, a previous Canadian study by Lindsay *et al.* (2013) on the challenges teachers face when supporting learners with autism

reported that resources and equipment, such as fidgets, saw teachers commenting that these tend to lack in their schools. When faced with the issue of a lack of resources, the teachers in the study of Lindsay *et al.* (2013) reported finding themselves advocating on the child's behalf on their own time to access these resources, which they deemed necessary to adapt instructions. Similarly, the findings of a more recent mixed-methods study followed these preliminary conclusions. This research which was conducted in the U.S. and examined the barriers to evidence-based social skills interventions for primary students with autism from the voices of educators, saw participants lamenting that in their schools, they lacked access to the materials required to develop resources to support the teaching and learning of learners with autism (Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019). Several staff members in this study indicated spending their money on essential student resources such as pens, paper, stickers, laminator sheets, and objects for the students they support (Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019). Collectively, this evidence further implies that deficits linked to a lack of resources increase the challenges for educators to adequately adapt instruction for learners with autism (Hersh and Elley, 2019) hence, further impeding the teaching and learning process of learners with autism in terms of participation, achievement, and value.

Another weakness hindering schools from performing at their optimum level in teaching and learning of learners with autism enunciated by educators is located within the learning environment. The learning environment refers to the space allocated within classrooms, labs, open areas, and offices (Che Ahmad and Amirul, 2017; binti Ghazali *et al.*, 2021). Within the context of the Ecology of Inclusive Education, the physical space in the classroom is an element situated at the

microsystem level hence directly impacting the learner's participation, achievement, and value (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). Shaari and Ahmad (2016) concluded that learners are influenced by their physical and social settings, particularly since these tend to impact their behaviour, academic performance, and development. However, even though the circumstances in the physical settings tend to impact the development of learners, including those with autism, Polish educators in the study of Hersh and Elley (2019) voiced frustration that despite seeing the potential of learners, “the conditions surrounding them are unfavourable” (Hersh and Elley, 2019, p.9). Such ‘unfavourable conditions’ have been reported as being located within the schools' inability to create and ensure comfortable, quiet and calm learning spaces for learners to reduce sensory stimulation (Hersh and Elley, 2019).

According to the findings of Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020), the persistent non-adaptive school environment due to the increased sensory sensitivity of children with autism is witnessing teachers observing unprecedented levels of stress, fear, and feelings of insecurity for children with autism. Similar concerns were also outlined in a British quantitative study that explored the impact of sensory processing differences on learning and school life for learners with autism (Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020). Data collected from the 70 teachers who participated in this study led this research to conclude that the classrooms whereby these teachers worked in had high levels of stimulation for students with autism, such as highly coloured displays, multiple objects hanging down from the ceiling, and busy environments, resulted in children feeling overwhelmed, thus impacting their active classroom participation towards more effective teaching and learning (Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020).

Similar to the conclusions of Jones, Hanley and Riby (2022) were the findings of a study carried out in Turkey with kindergarten teachers on including learners with autism (Güleç-Aslan, 2020). The following statements from interviews showed participants implying that overcrowded classrooms are a weakness of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism: “Classes are too crowded for inclusion. For example, my class size is 24, and I'm on my own. How can I succeed? It is very difficult” (Teacher Participant); “Work cannot be attained in crowded classes; The class sizes must be reduced. I have 20 students and no assisting staff” (Teacher Participant) (Güleç-Aslan, 2020, p. 45). Teachers brought forward similar views in a study which investigated the extent of the inclusion of learners with autism in three schools in Johannesburg (Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022). It outlined that overcrowded classrooms present a challenge because it makes it difficult for educators to assist learners individually according to their needs (Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022). Participants in a study conducted in Turkey also indicated that overcrowded classrooms impeded them from teaching play skills to learners with autism (Gulveren *et al.*, 2022). This situation transpires even though teaching social skills to learners with autism is critical, particularly since they encounter challenges in social communication (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; World Health Organisation, 2019). All this evidence gathered from the voices of educators points towards an understanding that crowded classroom environments are associated with weaknesses which are hindering schools from effectively performing well in the provision, particularly since such an issue impacts the behaviour, academic performance, and development of learners with autism (Shaari and Ahmad, 2016).

A characteristic perceived as currently damaging the school's long-term performance and considered a weakness was evidenced by findings of an earlier large quantitative American study involving 1800 LSEs (Fisher and Pleasants, 2011). LSEs in this survey raised concerns that, in most cases, they tend to become the primary instructors of students with a statement of needs as teachers "do not teach or do lessons for a student with one-to-one assistance" (Fisher and Pleasants, 2011, p. 292). The misconception that the responsibility of learners with a statement of needs, including those with autism, is that of the LSE was also confirmed in the findings of a recent quantitative study examining the views of 361 LSEs working in state schools in Australia (Carter, Stephenson and Webster, 2019). This research concluded that whilst 16.1% of LSE participants reported that the provision for adaptations for learners tends to take place without direction from teachers more than once a day, a further 39.9% of participants reported that the provision for adaptations for learners without guidance from teachers takes place at least once daily. The conclusions of Fisher and Pleasants' (2011) and Carter, Stephenson and Webster's (2019) studies collectively indicate that the pedagogical instructions provided to learners with autism are sometimes shifted upon the LSE – a role they are not responsible or qualified for (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021). Such a situation contradicts the argument posited by Giangreco (2013) in earlier work on inclusive education that any potential instruction, including adaptations of instructions for learners provided by LSEs, should be supplemental to that of the class teacher and not primary or exclusive.

The shift above may be transpiring from possible ambiguity related to the roles of the LSE and the responsibilities of teachers regarding the education of learners with

autism. For instance, this hypothesis may be validated from recounts of LSEs who participated in a study conducted in the U.S. on their experiences whilst supporting learners with autism. These LSE participants recounted how class teachers would address them as follows: “Come get *your* kid out of my class” or “I need help with *your* kid” (Holmes and Butcher, 2020, p. 9). According to LSE participants, this led to a situation whereby instead of teachers seeing learners with autism as equal members of their classroom, this did not happen simply because these students had an IEP, with some educators stating that this resulted in a lack of opportunities for the learner with autism (Holmes and Butcher, 2020). The hypothesis that the responsibilities may be constantly shifted to LSEs due to a lack of clarity in terms of roles and responsibilities has also been confirmed by the findings of a study on transition approaches for learners with autism conducted at 16 universities across the U.S. (Jellinek *et al.*, 2022). This study concluded that the participants who were pre-service teachers were unsure about who was responsible for facilitating transition practices for students with autism and further concluded that this is the responsibility of LSEs and not classroom teachers. Taken together, the growing body of evidence conducted in research in the past decade (Carter, Stephenson and Webster, 2019; Holmes and Butcher, 2020; Jellinek *et al.*, 2022) raises concerns about whether inclusionary practices in terms of the teaching and learning process are fully taking place for learners with autism. Thus, as concluded in the study of Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera (2021), an analysis of the LSEs’ and the teachers’ roles and responsibilities on support, including that of learners with autism, would avoid different expectations of parents and teachers from LSEs, whilst also preventing teachers from shifting all the responsibility for supporting students’ academic and social progress on to LSEs.

Figure 12 outlines the identified weaknesses within the currently available international literature. The identified weaknesses seem to be located within the lack of resources, the fact that students with autism are not being provided instructions by teachers and teachers' lack of acceptance of the condition. The following section shall present the opportunities related to teaching and learning as identified in the current empirical literature.

2.5.3 Opportunities to the teaching and learning process

Following a literature review of the opportunities for the teaching and learning process, this evidence has outlined three key areas. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 13, the opportunities for the teaching and learning process are located within quiet spaces for withdrawal time, smaller class sizes and support from external service providers. The following sections shall put forward the evidence gathered from recent research studies regarding the opportunities for the teaching and learning process.

Figure 13: Opportunities to the Teaching and Learning Process as Identified in Current Literature

Modifications to the school's physical environment have been considered as elements that could impact the quality of teaching and learning and support change within a context of involvement and engagement of students with autism (Dargue, Adams and Simpson, 2021; Howe and Stagg, 2016). Indeed, as outlined in the Ecology of Inclusive Education, the physical space where the child spends time is located within the child's immediate environment, hence in the microsystem. This being located in the microsystem leads to an understanding that the physical space that the child is in would potentially impact the levels of participation, achievement and value. However, it may be argued that in order to adapt physical spaces in terms of making them more inclusive for the learner with autism, developments located in the exosystem, such as resource allocation and school rituals, are also elements impacting the physical space. For instance, if the school administration would allocate funds to make classrooms more autism friendly (exosystem), the child's physical space (microsystem) would benefit the learner. Therefore, classroom designs may facilitate or inhibit learning for learners with autism (Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020). Thus, the school's physical environment reflects the school's inclusive mindset, which consequently impacts the teaching and learning experience of learners with autism.

Environmental supports that could lead to a change in enhancing the provision for learners with autism and which were identified by educators included having "sanctuary" spaces in schools (Roberts and Simpson, 2016, p.1093), mainly because sensory stimulation causes difficulty to the oversensitive student (Hersh and Elley, 2019). A subsequent study which gathered data from Polish educators on the inclusion of children with autism in schools (Hersh and Elley, 2019) made a

broadly similar point to that of Roberts and Simpson (2016). This study concluded that educators perceive that including learners is likely to depend “at least in part on the ability to create suitable, quiet environments” (Hersh and Elley, 2019, p.9). Teachers in a study conducted in the U.S. that sought teachers’ perceptions of autism, inclusive practices, and relationship-building strategies saw participants endorsing that such quiet spaces may be set up in the corner of the classroom (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022). Participants in the study of Bolourian *et al.* (2022) concluded that this idea for the creation of quiet spaces could provide a sense of security and predictability for learners with autism due to this area being regarded as a “safe place” (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022, p. 7). Such “safe places” have been viewed as an idea that could have an impact on the learning experience of children with autism, as challenges related to sensory processing could lead to situations where these learners may be unable to concentrate on the task at hand (McDougal, Riby and Hanley, 2020). Some behaviours which have been identified by participants in the study of McDougal, Riby and Hanley (2020) and which lead to learners lacking focus were represented as follows: “a child with autism may flap a lot, get out of his seat, make noises, trace things” (McDougal, Riby and Hanley, 2020, p.4).

However, in a subsequent study, kindergarten teachers' working in schools in Turkey identified these quiet environments as 'resource rooms' (Güleç-Aslan, 2020), thus indicating that these spaces may be created outside the classroom environment. Interviewees in this phenomenological study recommended such spaces as an opportunity that could potentially improve the provision for learners with autism (Güleç-Aslan, 2020). Indeed, educators said, “If there were resource rooms at schools, we would work with children with ASD in those rooms at certain

times” (Güleç-Aslan, 2020, p.45). Similar views were put forward by teachers in a study which was conducted in schools in Ireland who outlined that an opportunity that would potentially facilitate inclusion would be for them to have a “lights room”, “quiet room” or “multisensory room” (Leonard and Smyth, 2022, p. 744). Although the findings of the studies in this section (Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Leonard and Smyth, 2022) provide converging evidence that having rooms outside the classroom settings for learners with autism could give the school an advantage that could enhance the teaching and learning experience of learners with autism, mixed views regarding this seem to exist. A recent study which looked at the strategies used by educators in Bhutan who support learners with autism concluded that when observations were conducted in four schools, it was noted that students with autism were mostly taught in self-contained classrooms (resource rooms) during most of the school day (Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021). This teaching approach in self-contained classrooms could lead to micro-exclusion, whereby students become segregated from their neurotypical peers leading to a situation inconsistent with the inclusive pedagogy approach (Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021).

Nevertheless, one should keep in mind that resource rooms should be solely used according to the learners’ needs as due to autism being a spectrum, whilst some would hinder the participation and achievement of learners with autism, this may be beneficial to other learners on the spectrum. Indeed, the latter was confirmed from the views of learners with autism themselves, who had outlined that due to the noise and clutter significantly affecting them, quiet rooms are preferred, with one student participant responding with ‘yes, a thousand times yes!’ when he was asked if he

liked going to the resource room to escape the noise (Eguiguren Istuany and Wood, 2020, p. 212). This view of learners with autism provides an understanding that adjusting the physical classroom environment seems necessary, particularly since learners with autism may become overwhelmed by how they respond to the learning environment (Eguiguren, Istuany and Wood, 2020; Ghazali *et al.*, 2021). Modification to the environment is critical as several scholars have posited that children with hyper-sensitive and hypo-sensitive responsiveness could become overwhelmed by the existing distresses within the environment (Ghazali *et al.*, 2021; Pastor-Cerezuela *et al.*, 2020). Thus, as Ghazali *et al.* (2021) have outlined, the seven components related to sensory sensitivity: sight, sound, smell, taste, touch, proprioception, and vestibular must be considered when planning environments for learners with autism.

A further element regarded as an opportunity leading to change in the school environment was confirmed through a review of literature that included studies involving educators and which were conducted in the U.S. (9), the UK (7), Australia (3), Canada (2), Turkey (1) and India (1) (Roberts and Simpson, 2016). These findings collectively reported that an idea that could support change in terms of the provision for learners with autism and which, in turn, could benefit these learners includes reduced class sizes (Roberts and Simpson, 2016). The issue of class sizes needs to be considered as overcrowded classrooms previously identified as a weakness (Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022) can make the classroom environments less conducive to learning (Ghazali *et al.*, 2021).

Research conducted in Portugal focusing on the net costs of reduced class sizes in state schools reported that implementing class-size reduction may result in a significant increase in costs, mainly since this requires larger investments in facilities and equipment, as well as in educators, administrators, and technical staff (Mucharreira, Cabrito and Capucha, 2019). However, the authors of this study also argue that the reduction in the number of students per class should be seen as “a highly profitable investment in the medium and long term, as it guarantees the development of a country and its people, as a result of the immediate pedagogical impact that it can have on student success” (Mucharreira, Cabrito and Capucha, 2019, p. 179). In consolidation, this evidence leads to an understanding that positive associations exist between the reduction of classroom sizes and the level of achievement that students, including those with autism, may have, particularly since educators feel that ‘space’ could allow them to improve the inclusion of learners with autism (Leonard and Smyth, 2022).

In a literature review of studies focusing on interprofessional collaboration using a multidisciplinary approach when supporting learners with autism, Strunk, Leisen and Schubert (2017) it was concluded that an external factor that could give the school an advantage in view of support to learners with autism is that of having better-quality interdisciplinary collaboration. A similar conclusion was derived from the study of McDougal, Riby and Hanley (2020), which, following data gathered from teacher participants, concluded that relationships with external agencies such as educational psychologists were also considered to be vital, as this would potentially enable educators to provide the necessary support to learners with autism.

Educator collaboration is widely accepted as a key to inclusive practice (Ainscow, 2014) as it extends to the relationship of educators with parents and support professionals (Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022). The earlier research by Syriopoulou-Delli *et al.* (2012) substantiated this view, concluding that collaborative relationships with external service providers impact the quality of education provided to students with autism, hence, serving as an increased possibility to ameliorate provision. The latter was also corroborated by more recent research on autism. The findings of an Australian study by Sulek *et al.* (2019), which looked into the perspective of teachers who support learners with autism, substantiated the findings of the literature review conducted by Strunk, Leisen and Schubert (2017) and the findings of the research of Syriopoulou-Delli *et al.* (2012). This qualitative study concluded that if educators had to establish connections with professionals outside their school, this would provide them with an opportunity that would allow them to increase their knowledge and awareness of strategies to further support their learners (Sulek *et al.*, 2019). Subsequent findings from a Spanish study that explored how teachers address the challenging behaviour of students with autism also saw interviewees reporting that the support of external service providers would allow them to be positively supported by professionals (Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021). Indeed, these teachers argued that such support is necessary as external service professionals would provide them with advice and share their knowledge and experiences to address behaviour perceived as challenging (Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021).

Verifying the need for educators to be supported by external service professionals as an advantage that could enhance the teaching and learning process of learners

with autism were findings of a phenomenological study that sought the views of 24 educators on the inclusion of children with autism in mainstream primary school classrooms in Zimbabwe (Majoko, 2018). This research saw participants reporting that the services of educational psychologists could provide opportunities to the provision for learners with autism as they instil in them [educators] “positive attitudes, skills, competencies, understandings and provision for responsive services and programmes” (Majoko, 2018, p. 646). Similar views to those of Majoko (2018) were brought forward in a study that reported on the education provision for students with autism in Ireland (Daly *et al.*, 2016). Aligned with what has been postulated by Mercieca and Mercieca (2022), this research concluded that through the recommendations of psychologists, educators could increase the possibilities for addressing the needs and challenges of students, mainly since the role of the psychologist should ensure that barriers to children’s learning and development are removed (Daly *et al.*, 2016). Indeed, the psychologist's role is critical since it would ensure equitable education by identifying the children’s needs and recommending how these may be met (Mercieca and Mercieca, 2022).

However, psychologists are not the only external service providers that educators have reported that they would like to collaborate with. The findings of a mixed-method study which sought the views of educators to explore the impact of professional development related to the IEP on teachers’ understanding and practices in the Republic of Ireland saw educators voicing desires to increase collaborative relationships with speech therapists who are supporting learners with IEN including those with autism (Cloninger, 2017). Participants in this study outlined that this is salient as they felt more at ease when seeking the views of speech

therapists prior to or whilst implementing strategies for learners with autism. For instance, Cloninger (2017) explained that when a speech therapist who used a specific self-regulation framework to support a child shared relevant details with the student's teacher, this equipped the educator with the appropriate knowledge to implement this particular strategy within the classroom and school setting. Furthermore, the aforesaid shared vision ensures that the approaches implemented to support learners are consistent across environments, thus further associating this with the promotion of increased possibilities for enhancing provision (Cloninger, 2017).

From the evidence gathered thus far, several opportunities seem to transpire in the current literature related to teaching and learning. Figure 13 illustrates that these are located within the opportunity of having quiet/withdrawal rooms, smaller class sizes and support from external service providers. The following section shall outline the threats identified within current studies seeking educators' perspectives.

2.5.4 Threats to the teaching and learning process

Within the mainstream classroom, inclusion seeks to include all students' participation, acceptance, and achievement at all levels (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Chung *et al.*, 2015; Odom, 2019; Russell, Scriney and Smyth, 2022). As mentioned in Section 1.1., policy and legislation are imperative for shaping an inclusive context where students with autism are given the necessary opportunities to become active participants, reach their full learning potential, and be valued as learners within the class community.

Even though policy and legislation are critical for shaping the context whereby discussions and research on inclusion take place, translating these ideas into concrete educational reforms and practices rarely occurs (e.g., Abed, Jameel, and Ahmad, 2021; Forlin, 2006; Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Xu, 2012). Confirming this were findings from the Lithuanian qualitative study involving 16 primary school teachers conducted by Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020). The participants of this study argued that there appears to be an attitude and a disposition where collective efforts from all parties involved in the implementation policy of the child's educational journey seem to be lacking. Participants in this study suggested that such an inclination may place the teaching and learning process of learners with autism at risk (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Therefore, it is understood that the lack of efforts to transform policy into practice may lead to minimal progress in providing inclusive teaching and learning for learners with autism.

When researching the root of the limited collective efforts in terms of translating policy into practice, both the studies of Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020) and that of Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis (2019), which were conducted in the U.S. concluded that educators feel that they have unclear views of inclusion related policy. On a parallel point to the aforementioned, teachers in a study which sought their views on the inclusion of learners with autism in Vietnam reported that such blurred understanding of policy derived from the fact that there were no opportunities for them to learn about the content of policy documents (Tran *et al.*, 2020). Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis (2019) have concluded that a lack of clarity in terms of policy could consequently lead teaching teams to become more inclined in

terms of maintaining the “status quo” (p.59). Fox *et al.* (2021) posit that if educators’ beliefs and experiences are incongruous with the reform approach, those beliefs and experiences may act as a barrier to implementing reform. Having educators with unclear views about the concept, which impedes them from translating policy into practice, may lead to a situation where the teaching and learning process of learners with autism is put at risk.

Further findings from the study of Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis (2019) have also outlined that a factor which may be a threat to the teaching and learning process may emerge from the differing perspectives that staff have on the notion of inclusive education. Corroborating this view were findings of a quantitative study conducted in Luxembourg which concluded that the understanding of inclusion for the sample of 43 teachers varied according to the educators’ experience in the education system (Krischler, Powell and Pit-Ten Cate, 2019). Indeed, while 67% of teachers characterised inclusion as a concept that meets all students’ social and academic needs, 24% of participants defined inclusion as meeting the social and academic needs of students with disabilities or needing special support (Krischler, Powell and Pit-Ten Cate, 2019). The remaining 9% of teachers in this study characterised inclusion as placing students with disabilities or needing special support in general education classrooms (Krischler, Powell and Pit-Ten Cate, 2019).

Figure 14: Threats to the Teaching and Learning Process as Identified in Current Literature

When reflecting upon the findings of Krischler, Powell and Pit-Ten Cate (2019), it may be noted that the differing conceptions of inclusion may have varying implications and consequences for action (Felder, 2018). According to Felder (2018), if inclusion is seen as an effective form leading to the participation of every learner in a mainstream learning setting and diverse classrooms, the scope would rather be to facilitate interpersonal relationships and equality of provision. This perspective sees inclusion as successful as it emphasises valuing diversity and encouraging differentiation rather than homogeneity and curriculum commonality (Ainscow *et al.*, 2006). However, if inclusion is merely regarded as having learners, including those with autism, attend the same school building, this does not do justice in having every student provided adequate opportunities to actively participate in the school community (Krischler, Powell and Pit-Ten Cate, 2019). Such conceptualisation of inclusion being regarded as merely placing learners with IEN, including those with autism in mainstream schools, would not be deemed as an effort to promote participation but rather as a meagre placement with no reference to support and practice (Russell, Scriney and Smyth, 2022). Hence, the latter suggests that the differing perspectives held by educators on the notion of inclusive

education may impact the frequency of the implementation of inclusive practice, including EBPs, and the supportive mechanisms enhancing its implementation (Abed, Jameel and Ahmad, 2021; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019).

In order to solve the issue related to a better understanding of the notion of inclusive education, its policies and practice, Engelbrecht *et al.* (2016) suggest that prompt action is necessary to introduce the changes pledged in legislation and policy. Given this, it is critical that educational authorities further organise programmes and workshops to enlighten all stakeholders on implementing inclusive policy for learners with IEN, including those with autism (Adewumi and Mosito, 2019). It may be postulated that due to the threats illustrated in Figure 14, more awareness would potentially decrease the gap between policy and practice, thus removing any risks within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism.

2.5.5 Conclusion

What has been mentioned so far in terms of SWOTs indicates that the identified literature focusing on the voices of educators points towards the support of the SLT (e.g. Hodges *et al.*, 2020) and of neurotypical peers (e.g. Hersh and Elley, 2019) as strengths to the teaching and learning of students with autism (Figure 9). The literature reviewed has also recognised that adaptations of instructions for learners (e.g. Clark *et al.*, 2020) which are mainly based on visual (e.g. Ayuningtyas *et al.*, 2021; Cooper *et al.*, 2022; Dyer, 2022) and manipulative supports (e.g. Jimenez and Besaw, 2020), are also current approaches within the current schools' capacities that enhance such teaching and learning.

The production of more quality provisions in teaching and learning has also been indicated within the possibilities of reducing class sizes. According to the literature review, these may vary depending on national policies. In contrast, a lack of resources (e.g. Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019) seems to be associated with hindering schools from performing at optimum levels, with possibilities to ameliorate the teaching and learning process through the development of quiet areas and resource rooms outside the classroom (e.g. Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Leonard and Smyth, 2022) as ideas that could further support learners with autism in schools. However, this is only deemed necessary because classrooms seem overcrowded (Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022) and are hence overloaded with sensory stimulation. Such stimulation acts as a barrier associated with teaching and learning, in particular since learners with autism may encounter sensory processing challenges (American Psychiatric Association, 2013), which could, in turn, impact their educational experience altogether (Hersh and Elley, 2019; Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020).

Although several international studies have outlined what works and what does not within the teaching and learning process, there appears to be a gap in local empirical Maltese literature. Nevertheless, this research gap appears to be not only a local but also an international one. Despite the extensive literature review, none of the international studies identified has utilised a SWOT analysis to represent the provision for learners with autism regarding teaching and learning. Therefore, given this, research and literature are faced with the question of which SWOTs are located

within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism who attend primary mainstream state schools in Malta.

The following section shall look into the SWOTs within the training provided to educators regarding autism. This analysis is critical to report since educators' knowledge of autism is imperative in successfully including learners in state schools (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022). Hence, it becomes essential to understand what impacts teachers' knowledge of autism (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022), with the following section thus attempting to identify the current SWOTs within training for educators.

2.6 Training on Autism

Having well-trained educators is critical to safeguarding good quality educational services, especially since individuals with autism generally tend to have more complex needs than other populations in daily life skills and psychological and physical health (Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Kossewska *et al.*, 2020; Russell *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, a growing body of evidence suggests that having educators who are not adequately trained could have a detrimental effect on the provision for students and the morale of educators, leading to burn-out and increased anxiety and stress (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Cappe *et al.*, 2021; Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Vincent and Ralston, 2020). Therefore, training is necessary as more significant knowledge of autism in terms of its characteristics, cause, and management, is related to increased awareness and understanding of classroom practices (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Segall and Campbell, 2014). Often, such cognisance is critical as teaching students with autism highlights concerns in areas of development, including social interaction, verbal and

non-verbal communication, sensory processing, and restricted and repetitive behaviour (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; World Health Organization, 2019), thus making the mainstream classroom setting a challenge (Kisbu-Sakarya and Doenyas, 2021). Given this, the following section shall provide a detailed outline of the SWOTs currently presented in empirical literature by educators working in primary schools.

Given the challenges mentioned above, educators must implement successful strategies for including learners with autism within mainstream classrooms (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Ravet, 2018; Saggars *et al.*, 2019). Implementing adequate support is critical since, as Merry (2020) argues, through an environment with adequate services that allows for a sense of belonging, which contributes to a child's well-being, educational justice for learners, including those with autism, would take place. However, a growing body of literature documents that for equity to occur, educators need to be sufficiently trained (Baghdadli *et al.*, 2014; Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021; Hernández-González *et al.*, 2022; Kisbu-Sakarya and Doenyas, 2021; Leonard and Smyth, 2022; Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013). Training is perceived as an indirect factor located at the macrosystem level and, thus an element penetrating the exo, meso and microsystems (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Hence, training is necessary as it would enable educators to demonstrate a more positive view for applying inclusive strategies within their practice (Baghdadli *et al.*, 2014; Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Hernández-González *et al.*, 2022; Kisbu-Sakarya and Doenyas, 2021; Leonard and

Smyth, 2022; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013), thus ensuring that educational justice for learners with autism takes place.

2.6.1 Strengths of training for educators

The following sections shall put forward the evidence gathered from recent research regarding the strength of the training process for educators on autism. As illustrated in Figure 15, this strength is located within the sharing of good practices amongst educators. Following a literature review into the strengths of the training process, this evidence has outlined one key area.

Figure 15: Strengths of Training as Identified in Current Literature

A recently proposed reform in educational settings termed the ‘Professional Learning Community’ encourages educators to practice “collective enquiry through dialogue, sharing experiences and information” (Hung, 2022, p.31). Through such an opportunity, educators can “further model to expand professional learning and share personal perspectives in an environment where teachers become resources of professional development for each other, thus fostering the peers helping peers” (Hung, 2022, p.31).

Literature suggests that having training based on sharing good practices, as proposed by Hung (2022), is perceived as one of the current strengths of the schools' capacity in terms of training for educators on autism (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Ho, 2022). Validating this are findings from a study that sought the perspectives of primary teachers in Ireland on their self-efficacy in supporting the inclusion of children with autism. Data gathered qualitatively saw teachers outlining that whenever they were allowed to share their practice with their colleagues, they felt more confident in meeting the needs of learners with autism in the classroom (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017).

Another Irish qualitative study conducted with teachers of children with autism confirmed the findings of Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella (2017). In fact, the conclusions drawn from the study of Brennan and King (2021) indicate that following the opportunity for educators to share their experiences with other educators during training sessions, they felt more confident to ask colleagues for support, seek their advice, and ask for their ideas when planning lessons. It is understood that such an opportunity to share experiences leads to a situation whereby teachers feel that their ideas are valued while feeling confident about having the necessary knowledge and skills to include all learners (Brennan and King, 2021). Ho (2022) outlines that when educators are given a platform where they can share their perspectives and exchange ideas, resources, and expertise, this allows them to bring forward what is happening in the classroom and, thus, be in a better position to explain the strengths and challenges they may encounter. Indeed, such collaboration has been regarded as one of the most effective approaches for including all learners (Ní Bhroin and King, 2020), allowing educators to share challenges and find solutions together

(Ainscow, 2020). In sum, as outlined in Figure 15, all this evidence points towards an understanding that “wider use of collaborative and reflective practice may allow greater opportunities for teachers to share examples of good practice and build confidence in their ability to differentiate the curriculum to meet the needs of all pupils with autism” (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017, p. 14).

Further to the aforementioned, an earlier study which explored on the experience, attitudes and knowledge of school staff in relation to inclusive education for pupils with autism attending mainstream schools in England, around four in every five respondents reported that they would attend further training on autism if this were made available – indicating a strong willingness to develop their **knowledge** and expertise (Humphrey and Symes, 2013). Given that this study data emerged from 53 participants including members of the SLT, Heads of Department supporting inclusion in schools, English, Maths and Science teachers, training for whole school teams may be considered as valuable in developing a positive ethos and ensuring consistency of practice (Humphrey and Symes, 2013). This sheds light on the critical role that schools can play in raising awareness and implementing quality provision for learners (Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020).

2.6.2 Weaknesses of training for educators

Following a literature review into the weaknesses of the training process, this evidence has outlined two key areas. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 16, these weaknesses have been identified in view of training lacking practical strategies which may be used in the classroom and within the view that training is provided after issues arise and not prior. The following sections shall put forward the evidence

gathered from recent research regarding these weaknesses of the training process for educators on autism.

Figure 16: Weaknesses of Training as Identified in Current Literature

Earlier research has reported that a training continuum should stress the importance of hands-on rather than theoretical training, allowing educators to apply the skills taught in the classroom (Morrier, Hess and Heflin, 2011). However, the growing body of research on training based on practical rather than theoretical content has demonstrated several shortcomings leading to a significant weakness within training for educators. Earlier evidence of this originates from the voices of teacher participants in a study conducted by Sukbunpant, Arthur-Kelly and Dempsey (2013) on Thai preschool teachers' views on inclusive education for young children with disabilities, including those with autism. This research concluded that the training content received by educators on autism was dominated by theoretical content rather than practical one. Similarly, a subsequent mixed-methods study conducted in schools in Canada saw teachers and LSEs also concluding that training concerning strategies tends not to include hands-on learning opportunities for educators (Corkum *et al.*, 2014).

Paradoxically, although the findings and recommendations above date back a decade, policies were updated, and awareness of the needs of learners with autism has consistently increased in research (e.g. Hebron, 2018; Maciver *et al.*, 2021; Paget *et al.*, 2018; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019), this apparent weakness in current autism educator training is still persistently recurrent in recent studies. Indeed, qualitative and quantitative research on teachers' experiences in Australia, Turkey, Croatia, Poland, and North Macedonia (Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Lisak Šegota *et al.*, 2022) all concluded that teachers' training was based on theoretical rather than practical content, confirming this as a characteristic that limits schools' provision for learners with autism. Conclusions following the views of educators in the Australian study of Devi and Ganguly (2022) indicated that it is only through practical experience that awareness tends to grow, as knowledge on how to support learners with autism is “not something you can learn from a textbook; it takes practice” (p.7). Similar conclusions emerged from a study on teachers' perspectives on the impact of visual schedules. Similar to the findings of Devi and Ganguly (2022), Curtin and Long's (2021) research outlined that knowledge on how to support learners with autism in the classroom cannot be “learnt from a book” (p.69). These findings confirm the views of the participants of Devi and Ganguly (2022) that knowledge of how to support learners with autism requires practice. In consolidation, these conclusions establish that theoretical training is ineffective for educators to gain the necessary skills to support learners with autism. This type of training consequently hinders schools from performing at optimum levels to support learners. Given this, it may be determined that practical training methods are preferred to those solely based on the theoretical viewpoint of autism due to their effectiveness in supporting these learners.

The currently available published literature on the subject identifies another weakness in the training, explicitly referencing situations where educators obtain information on how to support learners with autism only once they start having students in the classroom rather than before. Confirming this was the latest research on the training needs of teachers and LSEs in early childhood settings in the U.S. and Scotland. Conclusions drawn from these studies indicate that teachers and LSEs learn about the traits and difficulties of learners with autism whilst on the job (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Frantz *et al.*, 2022), thus suggesting that this takes place after educators are appointed to carry out duties in schools. This critical data emerged even though an increase in the attendance of learners with IEN, including those with autism, has been noted worldwide following the signing of the Salamanca Statement (e.g. Byrne, 2019; MEYR, 2022a; Ministero dell'Istruzione, 2020; UNESCO, 1994).

Following the indicated data from this section, it may be concluded that training following appointment leads to educators facing a steep learning curve before acquiring adequate knowledge to support learners with autism (Devi and Ganguly, 2022), thus consequently impacting the learners' participation, value and achievement (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). The situation above was confirmed by LSE participants in the study of Frantz *et al.* (2022). One participating LSE recounted that when she was appointed, she faced a situation where a child with autism banged his head as he entered the classroom and the LSE did not know how to address this problem (Frantz *et al.*, 2022). This predicament was also faced by other LSEs who participated in this study, leading to a situation where LSEs had to physically struggle to mitigate the issue. A teacher participant who also

contributed to the study of Frantz *et al.* (2022) analogised the situation encountered to “putting the fire out when it’s already started” (p.26).

Further data collated from the educators' voices in the study of Frantz *et al.* (2022) has established that training on addressing challenges and situations that educators may encounter when supporting learners with autism is only given when problems arise. Data from this study further confirms the earlier findings on research on training on autism which Ravet (2018) asserted was being given to educators “too late” (p.717). As noted in current studies, this weakness in terms of training for educators being provided following their appointment in schools imposes a situation where educators tend to take up decisions regarding provision upon trial-and-error approaches rather than from knowledge gained through training (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Sulek *et al.*, 2019). The latter seems to add to the feelings of uncertainty which already exist in teachers when addressing the needs of learners with autism, with educators in an Irish study voicing that the current training on autism provides “no answers” (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017, p.80). These findings point to a situation in which such constraints may have an impact on the success of inclusion and provision for learners with autism (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Dillenberger *et al.*, 2016; Sharma *et al.*, 2019; Silveira-Zaldivar and Curtis, 2019; Vlcek, Somerton, and Rayner, 2020). These constraints mainly transpire since teachers’ sense of efficacy in addressing the needs of these learners tends to be related to the amount and type of support they perceive to have received at that time (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017).

Following the identification of the weaknesses which exist within training on autism for educators, as illustrated in Figure 16, the following section shall delve into exploring the opportunities which have been identified within empirical literature on training on autism for educators.

2.6.3 Opportunities to training for educators

Following a literature review of the opportunities of the training process, this evidence has outlined three key areas. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 17, these opportunities have been identified in view of enquiring about the training needs of educators, organising training during school hours and having autism specialists provide training to educators. The following sections shall put forward the evidence gathered from recent research regarding these opportunities for the training process for educators on autism.

Figure 17: Opportunities to Training as Identified in Current Literature

Support from the school's administration regarding providing training opportunities has been identified as one of the most prominent embedding mechanisms for educators to approach training on autism (Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Williams *et al.*, 2021). A study exploring how school leaders shape school culture and climate found that

educators appreciate Heads of Schools who provide them with time to undergo training during school hours throughout the scholastic year (Williams *et al.*, 2021). Such gratitude in terms of having the approval of school administrators for release time to attend training during school hours could be an element that has the potential to improve provision in terms of the effective implementation of strategies while support is being provided to learners with autism (Suhreinrich *et al.*, 2021). In fact, one-off training opportunities do not result in the shifts required for sustained, inclusive practice (Walton *et al.*, 2022). Hence, it is understood that there should be a training continuum if the provision for learners with autism is to be enhanced.

The opportunity to be provided with training during school hours was not only a call made by teachers and LSEs. Indeed, this point has also been put forth by school administrators in a study that sought educators' perspectives on the current practices and barriers to training for LSEs of students with autism in mainstream settings (Sobeck and Robertson, 2019). In the administered survey, school administrators working in schools in Tennessee and Pennsylvania indicated that the opportunity of increasing time for training, particularly during school hours, would improve the training needs of teachers and LSEs, thus, indicating this as an element which may produce more provision for quality to learners with autism. Therefore, the evidence in this section concludes that there is a common consensus deriving from the voices of teachers, LSEs and school administrators that an opportunity which could provide schools with an advantage in terms of the provision for learners with autism is the provision for more training during school hours.

Following the agreement in terms of views of educators and school administrators regarding having training provided during school hours, the literature recognises

that enabling educators to choose between training topics may also contribute to faster strategy adoption and higher implementation quality (Johnson *et al.*, 2014). Earlier conclusions deriving from the study of Iadarola *et al.* (2015) led to an understanding that educators strongly desire to participate in autism-specific training and implement it if its content applies to them. Further to this, following data from a study conducted in 11 schools in the north-west of England that explored teachers' attitudes, experience, and knowledge on the inclusion of students with autism concluded that the majority of participants (80%) were willing to attend autism training if this was offered, hence, confirming that they recognised the need for this (Humphrey and Symes, 2013).

Further interest in those above was shown in a survey study of 456 teachers and school administrators working in schools in Tennessee on the professional development needs related to educating students with autism by Brock *et al.* (2014). The researchers reported that most participants indicated they were interested in training that addresses EBPs, such as computer-aided instruction, functional communication training, and self-management. To a lesser extent, participants in this study showed interest in pursuing training on speech-generating devices, Picture Exchange Communication Systems (PECS), and visual support (Brock *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, evidence from a recent study on the training needs of Polish teachers on autism identified that participants would like to be given training on visual support systems. Further to the abovementioned requirements, teachers in this study also highlighted the need to learn how to adapt lessons and review students' achievements (Kossewska *et al.*, 2020). Evidence gathered from a group of teachers in Lithuania also outlined that they would like to pursue training on how

to select and apply appropriate strategies for them to be able to reduce challenging behaviour and promote more positive conduct when supporting learners with autism. This study concluded that the lack of knowledge on how to manage challenging behaviour led educators to spend most of their time in class attempting to find solutions to mitigate these concerns (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Collectively, this evidence establishes that gauging educators' training requirements would possibly motivate them to attend such sessions, thus exploring this as a future trend that could benefit learners with autism. Such a shift also leads to an understanding that an idea that would support change and improvement is for training on autism not to be uniform in all schools (Brock *et al.* 2014). Brock *et al.* (2014) argue that this should be an element for schools to consider since every educational setting has its instructional capacities and, therefore, has different professional development needs and priorities. A study supporting this argument sought to analyse the effect of autism-focused in-service professional development training in Pennsylvania. The teachers and LSE participants in this study reported appreciation for training content, including information on the characteristics of autism, and identified the challenges encountered by children with autism in social interaction, communication, and restricted and repetitive behaviour (Bertuccio *et al.*, 2019). According to the participants, this might enable them to increase their awareness of the subject, thus considering this an opportunity to promote change in the training content (Bertuccio *et al.*, 2019).

An idea that would increase the prospects of training for educators on autism is the opportunity to receive training from autism specialists (Hamrick *et al.*, 2021). Evidence of this was gathered from a study examining educators' knowledge and

preparedness for educating students with autism in public schools in the State of Texas (Hamrick *et al.*, 2021). Almost 60% of the LSE participants from a sample of 255 respondents argued that one major factor that could impact their decision-making when determining what interventions to use whilst supporting learners with autism is providing advice and training by autism specialists (Hamrick *et al.*, 2021). This point was also brought forward through the conclusion of recent studies conducted in Scotland and Australia, respectively, which saw staff showing high levels of enthusiasm related to learning from professionals who were explicitly trained in autism, from more experienced staff, and Autism Specific Service Providers (ASSPs) (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Walton *et al.*, 2022). The participants in Walton *et al.*'s (2022) study posit that such experts hold a wealth of professional-specific knowledge about autism, which would subsequently be beneficial to them, particularly in terms of accessing timely information, therefore suggesting that increased opportunities to effectively support learners with autism would consequently transpire. Ballantyne *et al.* (2022) argue that access to appropriate training on autism for schools and educators should be a priority for local authorities and the Government, particularly since this leads to staff feeling more prepared to support learners with autism in mainstream schools.

Following the identification of the opportunities within training on autism for educators, as illustrated in Figure 17, the following section shall explore the threats identified within empirical literature regarding training on autism for educators.

2.6.4 Threats to training for educators

Following a literature review of the threats to the training process, this evidence has outlined four key areas. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 18, these threats are located within educators seeking training voluntarily, training on autism is not included in preservice training, teachers are less likely to be trained than LSEs, and when training is unavailable, educators need to self-fund such training. The following sections shall put forward the evidence gathered from recent research regarding these threats to the training process for educators on autism.

Figure 18: Threats to Training as Identified in Current Literature

Literature indicates that one of the threats within the training provided to educators on autism seems to be linked to training being non-mandatory for educators (Boujut *et al.*, 2017; Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Roberts and Simpson, 2016). This threat transpires even though training in the Ecology of Inclusive Education context has been identified as the most influential regarding the extent to which learners are included in the mainstream classroom (Hoskin, Boyle and Anderson, 2015). Confirming this were findings of a recent study which explored the need for training for teachers and LSEs in two schools in the U.S. (Frantz *et al.*, 2022). One participant reported that LSEs do not want to participate in training after school hours because they are not paid, suggesting that training is voluntary (Frantz *et al.*,

2022). Similar evidence arose from a study which sought to explore the role of the LSE in Austria, Bulgaria, the UK, Portugal, and Slovakia (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021). This study was also able to conclude that whilst it is mainly the responsibility of educational institutions to provide training to LSEs, participation is voluntary, and LSEs mostly have to attend such training in their private time (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021).

The inaccessibility to training, as mentioned above, makes it more difficult for educators to voluntarily attend sessions which may provide them with adequate knowledge on how to support learners with autism. Such unavailability of training arises even though school leadership teams and educators have highly prioritised education and training on autism, suggesting that this professional development should be given utmost importance within school systems (Roberts and Simpson, 2016). The research of Roberts and Simpson (2016) reviewed studies that sought the voices of educators on their perspective of inclusive education for learners with autism and which were conducted in the U.S.(9), the U.K. (7), Australia (3), Canada (2), Turkey (1) and India (1), saw educators pleading for training on autism to become compulsory (Roberts and Simpson, 2016).

Further corroborating the point above were various professionals' views on staff training in the area of autism (Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016). Findings of this mixed-methods study conducted in North Ireland which collected data from surveys and interviews, saw these participants reporting that training on autism is lacking and that this should be mandatory for all staff working with individuals with autism. Distinctly, most participants in this study reported that training is not incorporated

into professional (pre-qualifying) courses, nor does it form part of staff induction when recruited to support learners with autism (Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016). Similar findings were yielded from a study which sought the views of teachers in Greece and Romania and which revealed that even though participants already had more than three years of experience in the classroom, training on how to address the needs of learners with autism was limited (Folostina *et al.*, 2022). This study saw participants claiming that courses they underwent on autism 'were mainly private', thus understanding that educators sought training on autism in their own time and on their own initiative. Parallel evidence was yielded from a study conducted with educators carrying out duties in primary schools in Poland, Croatia and North Macedonia, which also saw 47% of participants not undertaking any training on autism whatsoever, whilst almost a third of the participants seeking such training via a self-study method (Lisak Šegota *et al.*, 2022). Collectively, these studies (Boujut *et al.*, 2017; Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Folostina *et al.*, 2022; Roberts and Simpson, 2016) have concluded that a threat to training on autism is relatively linked to it not being mandatory for educators, which consequently may inflict a situation where educators underperform in terms of providing the necessary support for learners with autism due to inaccessibility to training. Echoing these findings are the findings of a mixed-methods study that gathered data from stakeholders involved in the education of learners with autism, including school administrators and teachers in Australia (Saggers *et al.*, 2019). This study concluded that teacher training, mainly undergone voluntarily, tends to lead to a lack of understanding of what students may require. Hence, educators may not be able to cater well for students with autism by providing them with an education targeting different learning styles as necessary (Saggers *et al.*, 2019). Given this, it may be established that the lack of mandatory

training sessions for educators is a shortcoming and a current limitation hindering schools from performing at an optimum level in terms of the provision for learners with autism.

Research has identified another threat to the provision for learners with autism whereby this seems to be located within the view that adults without knowledge of autism often perceive these children as defiant, socially isolated, disruptive, and exhibiting behaviour deemed not to be age-appropriate (Ferroni-Bast *et al.*, 2020; Huws and Jones, 2010). This threat was also substantiated by a study carried out in mainstream school settings, which found that students with autism were often perceived as challenging to teach by their teachers due to the many misconceptions these educators have about autism (Ferroni-Bast *et al.*, 2020). Thus, specialised training and work experience are pertinent in shaping teachers' perceptions and the quality of provision for learners with autism (Hernández-González *et al.*, 2022).

This view was corroborated by a previous U.S. study that highlighted a situation where teachers with no previous knowledge of how to support learners with IEN, including those with autism, were likely to dislike and avoid autism (Chung *et al.*, 2015). A more recent study conducted in Ireland revealed similar conclusions, as only 10% of primary school teachers had positive attitudes towards including learners with autism (Leonard and Smyth, 2022). Further supporting the findings of Leonard and Smyth (2022) are also the recent findings of a study that examined the views of teachers carried out in Turkey on the inclusion of learners with autism (Güleç-Aslan, 2020). Teachers in this study felt that lack of knowledge leads to difficulties in carrying out inclusion processes due to shortcomings linked to their

understanding (Güleç-Aslan, 2020). One teacher participant stated they “are experiencing difficulties in accepting children with autism” (Güleç-Aslan, 2020, p.42). As indicated in a Mexican phenomenological study exploring teachers' experience supporting children with autism, the lack of acceptance leads to a lower success rate of inclusive education programs for learners with autism (De La Cruz, 2020). One implication related to negative attitudes and a lack of acceptance would be decreased training opportunities, fuelling “a culture of exclusion” (Iadarola *et al.*, 2015, p. 700). Without appropriate training, educators are confronted with children they know very little about. This results in lower frequency rates in terms of the adaptation of instruction according to the needs of the students, which in turn would contribute to their marginalisation (Boujut *et al.*, 2017).

Despite the need for more training to possibly decrease segregation and exclusion whilst supporting learners with autism, the literature indicates that when training is provided, its quality seems relatively minimal and does not commence before educators start teaching in the classroom (Güleç-Aslan, 2020). Evidence of this derives from a study conducted in Georgia that looked into the quality of teacher training related to the implementation of teaching strategies for students with autism. The findings of this study saw fewer than 15% of the participants of a total sample of 90 reporting to have received training through teacher preparatory courses provided by colleges or universities (Morrier, Hess and Heflin, 2011). A later qualitative study had similar concluding findings. This research which involved 13 primary school teachers conducted by Finch *et al.* (2013) in Missouri, found that a limited number of preservice courses included training for teachers to support learners with autism and that courses lack the number of credits in the curriculum

related to inclusive education. This posits that training might be somewhat deficient for educators, despite research suggesting that they are very likely to have students with autism in the class (Clark *et al.*, 2020).

Subsequent and more recent studies also made further conclusions related to the findings above, thus confirming that not including content on autism is an existing prevailing threat within the training (or lack thereof) provided to teachers. Indeed, according to a study of U.K. teachers' experiences during initial teacher education, training on how to support students with autism was limited (Ravet, 2018). This British perspective suggests that training on autism is not mandatory in teacher preparatory courses, which is unhelpful for educators. Parallel evidence was gathered from teachers in a study that sought their experiences of including students with autism in their Turkish classrooms. Distinctly, one participant said, "We don't know enough about what autism is. We did not have any courses on this in university" (Güleç-Aslan, 2020, p.43). Corroborating this point are findings of a mixed-methods study conducted by Dillenburger *et al.* (2016) in Northern Ireland, who saw teachers outlining that training on autism at the start of their careers was lacking, regardless of the increased probability of having children with autism in the classroom. Similar concerns were also brought forward in the recent study by Kossewska *et al.* (2020), which also indicated that in the course of academic university studies, fewer than 50% of teachers working in mainstream schools become familiar with issues related to autism, hence, further highlighting this issue as a threat to the provision for learners with autism.

Additionally, comparable concerns were voiced by educators in similar studies, who lamented that their teacher preparation programs did not emphasise practical strategies for individualisation in the classroom to the extent that they are unable to be individually responsive to students' needs (Able *et al.*, 2015; Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). In conclusion, these studies suggest that the provision for learners with autism may be threatened by the shortcomings of preservice training for prospective teachers on how to support learners with autism in the classroom, indicating that the training environment, in terms of frequency, needs to be monitored to address these threats. Such monitoring is necessary as following educational and national policies, educators are expected to fulfil the mission, and the purpose of the inclusive educational paradigm, particularly since educators have a social responsibility to educate learners with autism in a mainstream classroom (Hernández-González *et al.*, 2022).

The situation of untrained teachers tends to place a potential risk to the quality of provision for the learner with autism. Prior studies that reported upon the levels of confidence in the application of strategies for learners with autism found that, although Heads of Schools, Heads of Department who support schools in the area of inclusion, and LSEs, rated themselves as more aware of strategies, primary classroom teachers seem to lack such awareness (Humphrey and Symes, 2013; Segall and Campbell, 2014). Further confirming these outcomes were the findings of a subsequent study on teachers' knowledge of autism in Turkey (Rakap, Balıkcı and Kalkan, 2018). This quantitative study reported that even though the 478 participants possessed a degree at a Bachelor level, Kindergarten Educators indicated to have somewhat better knowledge of autism when compared to primary

classroom teachers (Rakap, Balıkcı and Kalkan, 2018), hence, further confirming this as one risk potentially threatening the school's ability to support learners. Recent research that looked into the training needs of teachers and LSEs working in early years settings concluded that a characteristic that adds risks to training has been outlined as 'second-hand training' (Frantz *et al.*, 2022, p.25). According to one teacher participant, this transpires when schools send only one person to training sessions and expect that this person shares the information gained during these sessions with colleagues (Frantz *et al.*, 2022).

Evidence related to the aforementioned threats derives from a recent study which sought educators' perspectives on including learners with autism in primary schools in Vietnam (Tran *et al.*, 2020). Participants in this study reported that one of the threats to the learning and teaching provision for learners with autism is the inadequacy of teacher preparation. Data from this research outlined that a significant 43.7% of participating teachers ($n=115$) indicated they had not participated in any training on autism. Furthermore, participants in this research outlined that the training content they received was focused on general information on disability (Tran *et al.*, 2020), placing inadequate training as a potential risk limiting the school's ability to support learners with autism. Along the same lines, findings of a study that involved 120 Polish teachers and educational therapists responding to a questionnaire that sought their perspectives on the barriers and enablers of inclusion for young learners with autism found that teachers recognised that the challenges encountered whilst supporting these learners transpire from their lack of knowledge and understanding of autism (Hersh and Elley, 2019). The significant persistent body of evidence (Hersh and Elley, 2019; Humphrey and Symes, 2013;

Rakap, Balıkcı and Kalkan, 2018; Segall and Campbell, 2014; Tran *et al.*, 2020) raises an issue requiring evaluation and immediate amendments on autism and inclusive education, as the lack of training provided to teachers could place the inclusion of learners with autism throughout the teaching and learning process at risk. In Hersh and Elley's (2019) study, educators stated that being insufficiently skilled in the area makes it challenging to understand the behaviour of students with autism, identify their requirements, and learn about their preferences. Thus, the latter may inflict a situation where teachers' lack of knowledge may substantially influence the context of students' performance and educational resources (Ozel *et al.*, 2022). Teachers with knowledge of IEN are more likely to be competent in teaching learners with autism (Au and Lau, 2021), thus possibly reflecting lesser extents of any potential risks to the school's ability to support learners.

An earlier study which gathered data from school administrators, teachers, LSEs, and psychologists, found that LSEs are more likely to be trained to support learners with autism than teachers (Segall and Campbell, 2012). Similar findings were outlined in a previous study that reported upon the professional development needs of educators working with children with autism in mainstream schools conducted in Nova Scotia, Canada (Corkum *et al.*, 2014). Teachers who responded to the survey in this mixed-methods study were reportedly less likely to have specific autism-relevant coursework than LSEs during their initial training, indicating this as a current limitation that may lead to underperformance related to support (Corkum *et al.*, 2014). Although 57.1% of teachers had taken a course on teaching children with IEN, including information on autism, only 7.1% had undergone training solely focused on educating learners with autism (Corkum *et al.*, 2014). In contrast, 85.4%

of LSEs received training on autism and had professional development opportunities to support learners with autism (Corkum *et al.*, 2014). Such data leads to an understanding that most of the current mindset on inclusive education seems to indicate that LSEs are expected to fulfil the role of primary school teachers (Butt, 2016). Indeed, a recent study analysing the role of the LSE in five European countries indicated that in some cases, teachers delegate all responsibilities regarding students with IEN, including those with autism, to LSEs (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021). However, when pondering upon the latter, it is interesting to note that a recent study has indicated that such training is given following the appointment of LSEs in the classroom hence, raising the question of how well-prepared and equipped they are to support learners in the classroom (Frantz *et al.*, 2022). Thus, such inconsistency in training for educators acts as an impediment, posing a threat to “producing, maintaining, and retaining well-trained educators in the industry” (Teo, Lau and Then, 2022, p.625).

2.6.5 Conclusion

This section has attempted to outline the existing SWOTs in training for learners with autism. The discussed findings indicate the need for greater attention to teacher training in this area. The evidence gathered in this section suggests that training based on sharing experiences amongst educators fosters confidence in supporting learners with autism (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Ho, 2022; Hung, 2022). An opportunity that may enhance the strengths and help overcome the weaknesses and threats has been linked to the idea that training should ideally be held during school hours (Suhrheinrich *et al.*, 2021; Williams *et al.*, 2021). Further to this, the fact that educators are empowered when choosing the topic of training

they feel that they mostly require (Bertuccio *et al.*, 2019; Kossewska *et al.*, 2020) and having specialised personnel provide such training on autism (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Hamrick *et al.*, 2021; Walton *et al.*, 2022) have also been located as opportunities.

The issues mentioned earlier have, in effect, placed several threats upon the training process, as illustrated in Figure 18, mainly because these may inflict a situation where due to lack of knowledge, a high exclusion level by educators towards children with autism may transpire (De La Cruz, 2020; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Saggars *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, the current weaknesses in the area of training on autism for educators are based on the fact that some of the training provided is theoretical rather than practical (Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Güleç-Aslan, 2020). Moreover, this training is provided when educators are already carrying out duties in the classroom hence, leaving them attempting to support students with autism mainly by using a trial-and-error approach (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Sulek *et al.*, 2019).

Furthermore, even though current legislation such as the 'Persons on the Autism Spectrum (Empowerment) Act' and the Autism State Plan have stated that they intend to address several issues, including training and professional and personal development on autism, there is a gap in published local research on the situation (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government). Despite this, the SWOTs of such professional development from the perspectives of educators in Malta have yet to be investigated. Distinctly, although several international studies have outlined what helps and what hinders the provision for learners with autism in

training provided to educators, research in Maltese schools is so far lacking in scientific literature. Thus, a related question to this identified gap that would need to be addressed includes inquiring about the current underlying SWOTs within the training on autism being made available to educators who support learners with autism in schools in Malta.

Further to the evidence above related to training for educators, questions also arise regarding what impacts home-school communication, mainly since the literature indicates that “quality cooperation and partnership between parents and teachers are a significant factor in the successful inclusion of students with disabilities, including those with autism in inclusive education” (Krampač-Grljušić, Ralić, and Akšamovic, 2021, p.227). Indeed, the collaboration between educators and parents is necessary and inevitable, affecting the students’ learning, personal development, and behaviour (Krampač-Grljušić, Ralić and Akšamovic, 2021). Therefore, the following section shall report on the current SWOTs regarding the home-school collaboration.

2.7 Home-School Collaboration Process

Collaborative practices are the purposeful endeavours of educators to build effective partnerships with families (LaBarbera, 2017). Home–school collaboration refers to parents and educators working together to promote children's academic, socio-emotional, and behavioural outcomes (Collier, Keefe, and Hirrel, 2015; Stroetinga, Leeman, and Veugelers, 2019). Practices that intentionally establish relationships based on trust demonstrate an attitude of involvement toward families, welcome their input, and invite parents to become active partners in the educational

decisions of their children who fall into this category (LaBarbera, 2017). In particular, for children with autism, parental collaboration with schools at every stage of education and intervention is considered critical and essential because it is beneficial for learners but also a legal requirement (Azad, Marcus and Mandell, 2021). The Maltese law states that “it is the right of every parent of a minor to give his decision about any matter concerning the education which the minor is to receive” (Education Act, Cap.327, p.5). Further to the aspect of legislation, Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) have delineated the role of parents and their connection with educators within their framework since, according to them, parents directly influence child and learner development. In hindsight, such a link between what is required by legislation and the involvement of parents is more pronounced for learners with autism, particularly for decision-making regarding IEPs, educational intervention at school and home, and communication with educators (Azeem, Imran and Khawaja, 2016; Kurth, Love and Pirtle, 2020).

When a collaborative environment is developed, this typically predicts educational engagement and achievement, thus favourably arguing that collaboration between the home and school is a vital contributor to providing learners with autism with appropriate opportunities for them to achieve their full academic and developmental potential (Vlcek, Somerton and Rayner, 2020). A growing body of research has recurrently shown the need for schools to embark on efforts to encourage parental involvement and to facilitate meaningful home-school partnerships, as this would benefit the student, especially in academic, behavioural, and social skills together with mental health (Damianidou and Phtiaka, 2013; Josilowski, 2019; Josilowski and

Morris, 2019; La Barbera, 2017; Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016; Minke *et al.*, 2014; Sheridan *et al.*, 2019; Syeda and Bruck, 2022; Todd, Beamer and Goodreau, 2014). In contrast, when home-school collaboration does not occur throughout the educational journey of learners with autism, it is unlikely that parents and educators will be able to work together to develop and implement strategies, including EBPs, across contexts (Azad *et al.*, 2018). Thus, it may be established that home-school collaboration positively impacts the provision for learners with autism as the proactive involvement by all parties would establish and develop communication methods to share information, ideas, and progress (Guldberg, 2019).

Based on the above, seeking the capacities of the school on which SWOTs are located within home-school collaboration could help stakeholders working in the field to ameliorate this critical facet, mainly since parental collaboration with schools is not only seen as benefitting students but also as a two-way process that mutually also benefits both parents and educators of learners with autism (Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022). This two-way process transpires as while through communication with educators, parents may gain critical information about their children's performance in school, in contrast, educators may acquire information regarding family values and the children's strengths and preferences, possibly permitting the implementation of more targeted and consistent educational and intervention programmes (Josilowksi and Morris, 2019; Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022). This literature review seeks to analyse published research that has looked into the perspective of educators. This review will be followed through as research has consistently demonstrated that educators can inform a debate on home-school

collaboration in terms of their perspectives and beliefs about their relationships with families of children with IEN, including those with autism (Garcia-Melgar, 2022; Mazon *et al.*, 2021; Lalvani, 2015). Therefore, researching how such collaboration transpires in terms of SWOTs from the voices of educators may better target potentially amenable characteristics that could facilitate the increased collaboration of parents and educators of learners with autism (Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022).

2.7.1 Strengths of the home-school collaboration process

This evidence has outlined three key areas following a literature review into the strengths of the home-school collaboration process. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 19, these strengths are located within having open and frequent communication between the home and school, having parents share information about their child with the school and having educators share strategies with parents. The following sections shall present the evidence gathered from recent research regarding these strengths of the home-school collaboration process.

Figure 19: Strengths of Home-School Collaboration as Identified in Current Literature

Given that an increasing number of learners with autism are receiving their education in mainstream schools, home-school collaboration is essential for student success (Josilowski and Morris, 2019). A growing body of research suggests that robust home-school collaborative processes, in which families and schools share information to improve how they can further support their children, are built upon open, frequent, and authentic two-way communication (e.g. Busiku and Matafwali, 2022; Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016; Yan, Hou and Deng, 2021). Data drawn by Daniel (2016) following a longitudinal study conducted in Australia on parents' experiences of teacher outreach in the early years of schooling has outlined the importance of teachers supporting parent collaboration with schools through regular teacher facilitation of parent involvement termed 'teacher outreach'. A study conducted during the same period by Murray, McFarland-Piazza and Harrison (2015) concluded that parental involvement might be achieved through regular communication about the child's learning, behaviour, play, and interactions with parents to keep them informed about their child's well-being. Related to this point is data from the study of LaBarbera (2017) on the experiences of teachers in collaboration with parents in the U.S., who outlined that open lines of communication and availability to caregivers were current school strengths and a necessity for collaboration between schools and parents to take place, since it allows for communication to occur. According to a participant in this study, open lines of communication avoid situations where students may potentially fall "through the cracks" (LaBarbera, 2017, p.45). Thus, open and frequent communication may be established as a current strength of home-school collaboration, as it allows for immediate intervention, promoting more targeted and relevant intervention programmes for learners with autism (Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022).

Despite there being limited research attempting to identify the favoured methods used by schools to communicate with parents of children with autism, three studies have endeavoured to provide an outline of such communicative means (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019; La Barbera, 2017). Josilowski (2019) conducted a qualitative study with 10 teachers on their perceptions of home-school collaboration to improve learning for children with autism, inquired about the methods used to communicate with parents of learners with autism. Teachers in this study indicated regular phone calls, text messages, and e-mails as means frequently used by educators to communicate with parents of children with autism (Josilowski, 2019). Research participants also reported that the communication above allows educators to provide “quick” updates on the child's progress to the parents (Josilowski, 2019, p.3013). Another study that made a comparison of teacher and caregiver perspectives of collaboration in the education of students with autism concluded that phone calls were means that strengthened their satisfaction with parents' involvement in the decision-making process, with the same study also outlining parents' notes as a current school strength of home-school collaboration (LaBarbera, 2017).

Further to the findings above, Josilowski's (2019) study participants also outlined that they use communication notebooks to inform the parents about their child's progress and suggest ways to extend the classroom content at home. Similarly, a study that looked into the views of 18 teachers in schools in the U.S. and which sought their perspective on the ideal interactions between parents and teachers of children with autism saw them reporting that the communication book was a tool that enabled them to frequently engage parents in the education of their children

(Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018). This study concluded that the intention was for the communication book to facilitate two-way communication when it was sent home and returned to school. Many participating educators in this study reported how they would write about the child's day and asked parents to return the communication book with inquiries or concerns. As collectively identified in this section, two-way communication transpiring from various means has been identified as a current advantage, classified as a strength within the collaborative process between educators and parents of learners with autism.

Other quantitative and qualitative studies have identified another pertinent variable that has been considered a strength impacting the level of collaboration between the home and the school. Indeed, the qualitative and quantitative studies of Busiku and Matafwali (2022) and Yan, Hou and Deng (2022) conducted in Zambia and China, respectively, concluded that sharing strategies with parents on how they may help their children with autism at home was a current example of home-school collaboration which contributed to learners having consistency both at school and at home. Educators in the study of Josilowski (2019) indicated that strategies shared by educators with parents of learners with autism included ways to reinforce positive behaviours and approaches for decreasing challenging behaviours and forwarding social narratives to parents for them to support their children's behaviour (Josilowski, 2019). Similar findings were observed in a study that sought the views of 102 educators on collaborating with caregivers of learners with autism in California and Ohio (LaBarbera, 2017). In a related manner to Josilowski's (2019) findings, the study of LaBarbera (2017) saw 99% of teacher participants outlining that they suggested helpful strategies to caregivers on how to support their children.

These suggestions seem critical as Azad, Marcus and Mandell (2021) argue that effective communication between parents and teachers in sharing strategies with parents is essential for optimising individualised educational service provision and the generalisation of skills. Data collated from the voices of educators in the study of Josilowski and Morris (2019) also concluded that parents should share strategies to reinforce skills that their children learn at school and home, thereby assisting their children in potentially generalising these skills. The findings of this qualitative study posit that when educators collaborated with parents, with the latter taking their suggestions on board, children with autism felt more confident with the new material presented in class, as parents reviewed and practised such skills at home (Josilowski and Morris, 2019).

A further unique strength indicated by research data on home-school collaboration demonstrates that parents can also provide educators with valuable information about the child through collaborating with schools. Indeed, this point was expressed by educators in a study that sought their perceptions of parent-professional collaboration (Schultz *et al.*, 2016). In their research, Schultz *et al.* (2016) saw focus group participants reported that the fact that parents share helpful hints, behaviours, and clues about the student with autism allowed them to avoid the three to four-week wait in terms of “going through a steep learning curve trying to figure out what works and doesn't work for students” (Schultz *et al.*, 2016, p.349). Similarly, interviews with Australian educators in an earlier but relevant study conducted by Soto-Chodiman, Pooley and Taylor (2012) indicated that a strength within the liaising process with parents is that parents have substantial first-hand experience in addressing their children's behaviour. Educators view such parental insights as

applicable (Soto-Chodiman, Pooley and Taylor, 2012). This type of communication was also corroborated by recent mixed methods research that sought educators' views on the support provided to learners with autism in schools in Australia (Saggers *et al.*, 2019). Participants in this study emphasised the importance of communication with parents. They concluded that parents know their children best (Saggers *et al.*, 2019), thus agreeing with Merry's (2020) argument that, while educators unquestionably play an essential role in the placement and education of learners with autism, parents are typically in a better position than educational professionals to know what is in their own child's best interest.

Taken together, the evidence gathered in this section, and which is illustrated in Figure 19, points towards an emphasis that the current characteristics that schools possess on the strengths within the home-school collaboration are located within having open and frequent communication, having parents sharing information with schools about the strengths and needs of the child, and having educators sharing resources and strategies with parents. Such information sharing enables the identification of strengths, interests, and growth areas across people and settings, facilitating the implementation of instructional strategies at home and school (Anthony and Campbell, 2020).

2.7.2 Weaknesses of the home-school collaboration process

Following a literature review into the weaknesses of home-school collaboration, this evidence has outlined three key areas deriving from educators' perspectives. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 20, research which considered educators' views outlined that these weaknesses are located within having some parents not willing to be active participants in fostering home-school collaboration, not following

through with the suggestions that the school provides in terms of supporting their child and in some of them being in denial of their child's condition. The following sections shall present the evidence gathered from recent research regarding these strengths of the home-school collaboration process.

The relationship between parents and educators of children with autism should be dynamic and interpersonal, as both are crucial in determining what is best for the child. This interpersonal relationship should occur since the partnership between the home and school provides opportunities for the two stakeholders to discuss the learner with autism's learning needs, support their learning style, and encourage consistency of support across all settings (Hodges *et al.*, 2020). This collaboration may, in turn, lead to a consistent, structured, and predictable home and school environment for student learning (Clark and Adams, 2020; Lei *et al.*, 2017). Such practical home-school collaboration flourishes if there is mutual respect, parents and educators view themselves at par, and parents actively participate in the decision-making process concerning their children's education (Murray and Mereoiu, 2015).

Figure 20: Weaknesses of Home-School Collaboration as Identified in Current Literature

For such consistency to transpire, the willingness of parents to collaborate with schools is a crucial determining factor. However, research conducted with educators shows that, at times, there might be low levels of willingness of parents of children with autism to collaborate with schools (Josilowski, 2019; Schultz *et al.*, 2016). Substantiating this point was a study examining educators' satisfaction with the school's collaborative efforts with parents of children with autism (LaBarbera, 2017). This research found that a current weakness perceived by participants concerning collaborative practices related to parents who are unwilling to become involved in their child's education due to several issues, including the inability to understand the educational system and educational needs and also the lack of effort made to understand professionals (LaBarbera, 2017). From the educators' perspectives, this study has concluded that under-involvement leads parents viewing such collaboration as unnecessary (LaBarbera, 2017).

The level of willingness of parents to collaborate with schools is explored further in a qualitative study that looked into teachers' perceptions of the home-school partnership and how this enhances learning for children with autism (Josilowski, 2019). The participants in this study perceived this lack of an active parental role in their child's education as a constant struggle due to difficulties in getting parents on board when attempting to involve them in any projects due to them [parents] being on tight schedules. Similar views were yielded from a Lithuanian study, which also saw teachers perceiving that not all parents of learners with autism show interest in involving themselves in the educational journey of their children (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Both the study by Josilowski (2019) and Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020) concluded that the current lack of involvement of some

parents who are not willingly open and ready to collaborate with the school is leading to a scenario that is hindering schools from implementing the suitable approaches as part of the support programmes for learners with autism. Schultz *et al.* (2016) argue that in a situation where the parents of children with autism are under-involved in schools, these are not following through with supports suggested by the school within the home environment, with Josilowski and Morris (2019) positing that this negatively impacts students' performance. The same views emerged from the participants in the study of Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020), who also perceived that failure by parents to follow through with work at home does not bring “good results” for learners with autism (p. 217). Conversely, Josilowski and Morris (2019) outlined that when parents were involved, learners with autism could complete their homework, perform well on exams, and do better during class activities.

According to educators, the under-involvement of parents of children with autism in collaborating with schools could transpire because of feelings experienced by parents about their children's diagnosis of autism (Josilowksi, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Schultz *et al.*, 2016). An earlier but relevant study that investigated the challenges educators face when supporting learners with autism saw teachers perceiving that one of the weaknesses that hinder home-school collaboration lies in having parents choosing not to identify their child's condition (Lindsay *et al.*, 2013). Similarly, recent studies that looked into educators' perception of home-school collaboration of children with autism have also concluded that ‘denial’ was one of the key feelings they observe in parents, and which acts as a barrier that hinders effective home-school collaboration (Josilowksi, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Schultz *et*

al., 2016). Distinctly, data collected from focus groups with 34 educators found that most participants perceived that a lack of parental collaboration with the school transpired because some parents struggled to accept that their child has autism (Schultz *et al.*, 2016). This lack of acceptance was also perceived by subsequent quantitative studies on the inclusion of students with autism in primary schools in Vietnam and Lithuania, from educators' views (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Tran *et al.*, 2020). Data from both studies led scholars to perceive that when some families of children with autism do not recognise their children's diagnosis, the school may be at a disadvantage regarding performing at an optimum level in terms of the provision for learners with autism (Raudelinait and Steponnien, 2020; Tran *et al.*, 2020).

Previous but relevant findings of Lindsay *et al.*'s (2013) Canadian study, which involved teachers sharing the challenges faced related to the inclusion of children with autism in their classrooms, indicated that a lack of formal identification of autism by parents led to students not being eligible to receive resources and support that could help to enhance their educational experience. Similar to the study of Lindsay *et al.* (2013), Schultz *et al.*'s (2016) research which included the voices of educators, reported that when parents chose not to identify their children's condition, this led to a situation where students were not eligible to receive the necessary support, including provision from schools. This lack of eligibility for support further suggests that denial is an element that may damage the school's performance in terms of long-term goals related to the provision, particularly since, according to educators, parents tend to delay to refer to a specialist for their children to get the necessary diagnosis and support (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). This points

towards an increased educator perception that parental denial impedes schools from providing more quality educational programmes for learners with autism. Further to the point mentioned earlier, the qualitative study of Josilowksi (2019) saw educators reporting that due to parents being in denial of their child's condition, such parents detach themselves from and display a lack of interest in partnering with the school. In fact, this study saw the majority of participants perceiving that denial was a major stumbling block currently impacting the process of forming collaborative relationships between the school and parents, resulting in lower success rates of children with autism (Josilowksi, 2019) and a lack of services which children are entitled to (Lindsay *et al.*, 2013).

Following the identification of the weaknesses within the home-school collaboration, as illustrated in Figure 20, the following section shall explore the opportunities identified within empirical literature.

2.7.3 Opportunities to the home-school collaboration process

Evidence from the voices of educators has outlined four key areas following a literature review into the opportunities to home-school collaboration. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 21, these opportunities are located within having parents with sufficient knowledge and skills of how to support their children, having parents acquiring such knowledge and skills through training, having schools being sensitive to the needs and challenges of parents and having more opportunities to meet with the school. The following sections shall present the evidence gathered from recent research regarding these opportunities to the home-school collaboration process.

Figure 21: Opportunities to Home-School Collaboration as Identified in Current Literature

Having parents who are knowledgeable about how to support their children has been viewed as an opportunity that enhances school and home collaboration, reducing the stress levels experienced by parents of students with autism and increasing their sense of competence (Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016; Schultz, Schmidt and Stichter, 2011). This sentiment has also been brought forward by educators who have reported on parental education on autism, which they deem increases the success experienced by children with autism (Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016; Schultz *et al.*, 2016). An earlier but relevant Australian study was conducted with parents and teachers on their perspectives of students with learning difficulties, including those with autism, focusing on the tensions in home-school partnerships (Ludicke and Kartman, 2012). The findings of this study indicated that having parents participate in parenting skills workshops would benefit schools when providing quality educational programmes to learners with autism. Further findings from this Australian study saw participants outlining that an element that could potentially improve provision and enhance home-school collaboration is to have a section on the school website where parents may access information, links to resources, and tips on how they "might engage with their young people" (Ludicke

and Kortman, 2012, p.166). A more recent study on teacher perceptions of what is required to support students with autism in an inclusive classroom regarding home-school collaboration also saw teachers outlining that a similar opportunity would be one step forward in enhancing parental involvement (Schultz *et al.*, 2016). The participants in this study stated that an idea that supports change in improving the provision for learners with autism is having parents become more aware and educated about the characteristics of autism. Schultz *et al.* (2016) concluded that if parents are more aware of the condition, they could potentially be in a better position to become involved with the school, thus improving the prospects for learners with autism to experience continuity in their care (Azad and Mandell, 2016; Azad *et al.*, 2020; Azad, Marcus and Mandell, 2021).

Further to the point above, another possibility emerging from literature in the field, which could increase the school's potential to reach long-term goals in terms of the provision for learners with autism, is to meet parents more frequently in a face-to-face manner, particularly since Azad, Marcus and Mandell (2018) posit that time allocated to such opportunities is limited. In an earlier longitudinal mixed-methods study involving parents and educators on the nature of parent involvement and parent-educator communication in early childhood settings and school, McFarland-Piazza and Harrison (2015) reported that home-school communication decreased as children moved from early childhood settings to elementary schools. Educators in a subsequent qualitative study to that of McFarland-Piazza and Harrison (2015), which looked into the ideal interactions between educators and parents of learners with autism, identified that more opportunities for frequent teacher-parent meetings are an action that schools may take to enhance such home-school collaborative

relationships (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018). In this study, one of the reasons outlined by teachers in wanting to have more 'face-to-face' time was for them [teachers] to be able to “show off the child and for them [parents] to see first-hand [in-person] how far their child had come” (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018, p.5). The recommendation of frequent face-to-face meetings aligns with the findings of Schultz *et al.* (2016), whereby teacher participants suggested that this trend could improve collaboration with schools as it allows parents to promote their child's skills and share specific information about the child's strengths and needs. This increased frequency of meetings could lead schools to enhance such collaborative relationships as parents would be provided with more opportunities to go to schools more often and “voice their thoughts on things” (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018, p.11). All the evidence in this section leads to an understanding that parental involvement is critical during the educational process of learners with autism, mainly since this keeps both the school and home updated regarding the child's progress. Indicated by educators as something which could produce more home-school collaboration of quality is criticality for schools to become more sensitive towards the parents' needs (Josilowski, 2019). Educators in Josilowski's (2019) study acknowledged that parents need their support to “pull through challenging times and stay focused on the collaboration” (p. 3014). Participants outlined that given that the parents of learners with autism need support to collaborate with the school due to challenges they could encounter, staff must initiate ways to reinforce such parent-educator contact. For instance, encouragement and constantly involving parents in the education of learners with autism were among the strategies mentioned by educators in this study as opportunities to enhance home-school collaboration (Josilowski, 2019). Furthermore, findings from the study of LaBarbera (2017) saw

educators stating that an opportunity to increase collaboration with parents of learners with autism is the consideration of the family's requirements, particularly when devising interventions for students. This study concluded that when schools are sympathetic to the challenges and frustrations that their students' families encounter, this encourages parents and families to be more involved in the home-school collaborative process (LaBarbera, 2017). In the same vein, findings from a study that sought the perspectives of parents and educators on the collaborative relationship between the home and school, also conducted in the U.S., observed participants in a focus group acknowledging the need to better understand the family experience in the education of children with IEN, including autism (Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016). Such understanding is critical during crucial moments, particularly when parents receive their child's diagnosis and transition processes throughout the educational journey (Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016). Taken together, the findings in this section suggest that family-centred practice, specifically in being sensitive to the parents' needs, tends to increase the level of collaboration between home and school (Josilowksi, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016) hence, benefitting learners with autism during the educational process.

Following the identification of the opportunities within home-school collaboration for educators, as illustrated in Figure 21, the following section shall explore the threats identified within empirical literature.

2.7.4 Threats to the home-school collaboration process

This evidence from research conducted with educators has outlined three key areas following a literature review into the threats to home-school collaboration. Indeed, as illustrated in Figure 22, these threats are located within having parents experiencing grief and loss following their child's diagnosis, having parents not prioritising their children's education and some others not consistently implementing strategies as suggested by the school within the home setting. The following sections shall put forward the evidence gathered from recent research regarding these threats to the home-school collaboration process.

Figure 22: Threats of Home-School Collaboration as Identified in Current Literature

There is considerable and numerous research indicating that families of children with autism may experience greater stress levels than those of children with any other developmental disability (e.g., Bonis, 2016; Cooke, Smith, and Brenner, 2020; Da Paz, Wallander and Tiemensma, 2018; Giovagnoli *et al.*, 2015; LeBlanc *et al.*, 2020; Shepherd *et al.*, 2018; Zaidman-Zait *et al.*, 2017). A qualitative study that looked into the perspectives of 30 teachers on disability and stigma saw participants articulating beliefs that feelings of grief and loss are likely to be manifested

throughout the lives of parents of children with autism (Lalvani, 2015). Whilst discussing what they perceived it might be like to bring up a child with a disability, including one with a diagnosis of autism, some educator participants used terms such as “a struggle”, “drains their emotions”, and “wears them out” (Lalvani, 2015, p.386). This study concluded that the perceived stressors above from the voices of teachers could threaten the school’s ability to support learners and impact partnerships between the home and school (Lalvani, 2015). Data from a more recent study that explored the perspectives of 18 educators on the ideal interactions between them and parents of children with autism (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018) also substantiated this view. Conclusions drawn by this research, whereby the sample was drawn from 13 state schools in the U.S., indicated that the numerous hardships experienced by parents of children with autism, including lack of employment and limited social and financial support, place potential risks on the collaboration between the school and home (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018).

Educators have perceived a further external issue recurrently indicated as potentially threatening the home-school collaboration process as linked to the fact that parents might place all the educational responsibility on schools rather than pursuing this as a collaborative process. In an early but relevant study conducted by Lindsay *et al.* (2013), teacher participants claimed that due to the lack of acceptance by parents, parents of children with autism might not be on board with the school, as their children's education is not given priority. The study of Lindsay *et al.* (2013) has seen educators perceiving that if parents are not on board and hence place the responsibility of their children's education on the school, the success experienced by learners is limited. Similar findings were yielded from the

Lithuanian study of Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020), who corroborate Lindsay *et al.*'s (2013) findings, arguing that one implication of this predicament is that the educational process of learners with autism becomes “more complicated” (p. 217).

In a mixed-methods study involving 102 educators, the majority of participants also perceived that provision might be affected if parents do not prioritise their children's education and are not “entirely willing to become involved in their child's education” (LaBarbera, 2017, p.46). From the evidence gathered thus far from educators' perspectives, several threats seem to be evidenced in the current literature on home-school collaboration. Findings from further qualitative data of a study which sought to reveal the ideal interactions between the home and school indicate the frustration educators experienced at having parents lacking to follow through with support at home. This threat could be identified as a risk that decreases the possibility of improving provision (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018). The same views were brought forward by the study of Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020), which also observed teachers lamenting that having parents showing a certain level of indifference and inconsistency in activity continuation at home places home-school collaboration at risk. Both studies, which gathered data from educators' perspectives, concluded that such parental indifference toward their child's education is a potential risk, not only to the home-school collaborative process but also to the quality of support for learners with autism, even though collaboration intends to create consistency across home and school (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Figure 22 illustrates that these are situations where parents may feel grief and loss when receiving their children's

diagnosis. Some parents not following up with strategies recommended by educators and not prioritising their children's education have also been identified by educators regarding home-school collaboration.

2.7.5 Conclusion

This section has sought to outline the existing SWOTs regarding the home-school collaboration of children with autism with schools. Amongst the evidence gathered in this section, open and frequent communication has been identified as being a current strength that facilitates the home-school collaborative process (e.g. Azad *et al.*, 2020; Busiku and Matafwali, 2022; Josilowski, 2019; Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016; Yan, Hou and Deng, 2021). This type of communication needs to be based on schools to identify the preferred communication means by parents (e.g. Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019; La Barbera, 2017). Amongst the identified weaknesses, this review has unfolded a lack of willingness to collaborate with schools by parents (e.g. Josilowski, 2019; Schultz *et al.*, 2016) and having parents not acknowledging the diagnosis of their children (e.g. Josilowski, 2019; La Barbera, 2017; Tran *et al.*, 2020). Further to this, also threatening the home-school collaboration process is the increased stress levels that parents of children with autism experience (e.g., Bonis, 2016; Cooke, Smith, and Brenner, 2020; Da Paz, Wallander, and Tiemensma, 2018; Giovagnoli *et al.*, 2015; LeBlanc *et al.*, 2020; Shepherd *et al.*, 2018; Zaidman-Zait *et al.*, 2017), and the fact that some parents may entirely place the responsibility of the education of their children on schools (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Identified opportunities that may help strengthen home-school collaboration have been located within the provision for training on autism to parents (e.g. Mereoiu,

Abercrombie and Murray, 2016), and more frequent face-to-face meeting opportunities (e.g. Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018).

Nevertheless, despite this relevant and noteworthy evidence of the SWOTs within the home-school collaborative process, it may be noted that this evidence focuses mainly on the international context, with no Maltese studies outlining the perspective of educators on the home-school collaboration of students with autism being found. This limitation transpires even though schools are obliged to fulfil the requirements of the prescribed National Inclusive Education Framework (MEYR, 2022b), which has the areas of 'Collaboration with Parents' as one of its pillars. In this regard, scientific literature addressing the SWOTs of home-school collaboration of children with autism attending primary schools in Malta is limited, hence perceiving this area as being underrepresented by past and current literature.

This chapter has outlined the conceptualisation of autism and a literature review of the SWOTs within teaching and learning, home-school collaboration, and training for educators. This section has also reviewed the theoretical framework underpinning this research study based on the Ecological Systems Models presented by Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014). Amid this review, this research has identified a gap related to the underrepresentation of published empirical research within the Maltese context. The following section will focus on the methodology of this study by delving into the justification of adopting a pragmatic research approach to this project.

Chapter 3: The Methodology

Two significant gaps have been identified from the literature reviewed in Chapter 2. This review has discovered that, to the author's knowledge, no studies have recently used a SWOT as a framework of analysis to report on the provision for learners with autism who attend mainstream primary school settings. Furthermore, following the literature review, it was noted that no studies have looked into the Maltese context beyond the use of a SWOT analysis framework. This limitation makes these identified gaps worth looking into through this study. Thus, these gaps add to the criticality of exploring the SWOTs in the provision for students with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta. The current chapter will present the research philosophy concerning how data on this phenomenon has been gathered, analysed, and used. It will also provide justifications for the methods applied regarding the research tools and how ethical procedures were addressed in this research study.

3.1 Research Paradigms

The universal set of beliefs and practices guiding a field or a topic within scientific research is typically called a *paradigm* (Lincoln, Lynham and Guba, 2011; Morgan, 2007). Such a *paradigm* or *worldview* informs the collection and interpretation of research data (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Each paradigm has a different outlook on ontology, epistemology, and research methodology (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019; Weaver, 2018). As outlined in Table 1, comparably, Guba and Lincoln (1994) state that the fundamental beliefs delineating a specific research paradigm may be abridged by the responses to four central questions relating to ontology,

epistemology, axiology, and methodology. Thus, a paradigm allows the researcher to understand the world and the phenomena which shape the world.

When the researcher identifies the paradigm regarding philosophical beliefs, this serves as a lens through which the researcher analyses the available research approaches and tools and decides how data should be collected and analysed (Khaldi, 2017). The literature argues that in practice, many researchers choose their methods because of the paradigms that directly or indirectly frame and answer their research question most appropriately (Creswell, 2009; Glogowska, 2011; Simons and Lathlean, 2010). The paradigm choice must be aligned with the research purpose, motivation, and prospects (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006).

Table 1: The Fundamental Beliefs Delineating Research Paradigms (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p.108)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

3.2 A Pragmatic Approach

Since pragmatism rejects the 'either-or' view of constructivism and positivism and relatively adopts both points of view (Subedi, 2016), pragmatic researchers may be objective and subjective in ontological and epistemological orientations over the course of studying the research question (Subedi, 2016). Creswell and Miller (1997) suggest that one study might start quantitatively by deductively testing a theory and then enhancing it through qualitative interviewing, while another might start qualitatively and inductively by using specific case studies to find relevant variables and theories and then deductively testing the emerging theory with a sample population.

It is important to note that pragmatism has been referred to as an *approach* rather than a *paradigm* (Morgan, 2007). This distinction is highlighted at the outset of this discussion because pragmatism is defined as an approach that offers specific ideas about what constitutes knowledge (Biesta, 2010). However, despite the aforementioned, pragmatism does not give that much importance to an exclusively encompassing worldview (Biesta, 2010).

Pragmatism draws on many individuals' philosophies, including historical figures such as Charles Peirce, John Dewey and William James, and contemporary philosophers such as Cherryholmes and Murphy (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2011). For pragmatism, an ideology is true only if it works (particularly in promoting equity, freedom, and justice) and produces practical consequences for society (Gray, 2017). Hence, pragmatists focus not on whether an ideology fits a specific ontology but on whether it suits a purpose and can create action (Rorty, 1998). Thus,

pragmatism draws on the principle concept of *what works*, and thus guides researchers to a mid-position between positivist and constructivist approaches founded on outcome-oriented actions (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Through aiming to reach outcome-oriented actions, pragmatism is viewed as an approach that aims to improve the condition of humans (Rorty, 1991). Thus, the pragmatist researcher's objective is not to explore the truth and existence but to facilitate human problem-solving (Powell, 2001; Sharma, Devi and Kumar, 2018).

Pragmatism emphasises the use of various methods and on valuing objective (positivist) and subjective (constructivist) knowledge in an equal manner (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2011; Weaver, 2018). Using mixed methods to embed the idea leads to human problem-solving, and to a "needs-based or contingency approach to research method and concept selection" (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p.17), which is crucial in pragmatism. Given the latter, pragmatism allows the researcher to apply multiple methods, diverse worldviews, different assumptions, and various data collection and analysis procedures in the mixed methods study (Creswell, 2003). In fact, rather than framing research around obligations to an inconcrete set of philosophical views, the three key principles of pragmatism that underpin the worldview of the philosophers are:

- that emphasis should be placed on actionable knowledge to ensure that research is of practical relevance;

- that there is recognition of the interconnectedness of experience, knowledge and action, as this enables the researchers to holistically address the phenomena and their context;
- that the inquiry should be perceived as an experiential process that allows researchers to be exposed to everyday situations and understand complex societal and /or organisational processes.

(Kelly and Cordeiro, 2020)

During the literature review process, several gaps were identified regarding the provision for learners with autism in Malta, and no published research in the field within the Maltese context was located. Furthermore, when reflecting upon the latter, to my knowledge as the researcher of this study, no research has used a SWOT analysis tool to report on the provision for learners with autism. Hence, considering the identified gaps, the pragmatic philosophical view has enabled this research to:

- generate relevant knowledge regarding the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism of teaching and learning strategies, home-school collaboration and training for educators;
- apply this data to develop an understanding of the provision for learners with autism;

- encourage the relevant authorities to adopt the necessary recommendations based on the data collected by educators who support students with autism.

3.2.1 The use of the pragmatic approach in the current research

Education is viewed as something which is constantly reorganising and reconstructing experiences. Pragmatism approaches the issues in education from a *progressivist* viewpoint, whereby progress indicates change (Sharma, Devi and Kumar, 2018). The change further suggests innovation; thus, education cannot be considered a traditional setting where change never or rarely occurs. In fact, given that problem-solving is at the core of all transformation in education, the educational process becomes empirical, investigational, and fragmented, thus, in other terms, pragmatic (Sharma, Devi and Kumar, 2018).

The above concepts outlined by Sharma, Devi and Kumar (2018, p.1551), and the three key principles of pragmatism (Dewey, 1931; Mead, 1938; James, 1907) were thoroughly considered when I as the researcher of this study was contemplating my research position. Given that I intended to somehow be an active contributor to possibly ameliorate the quality of the educational provision for learners with autism, a pragmatic approach was deemed the most sensible to pursue while carrying out this research study. Rather than pursuing single worldviews like positivism and constructivism, this research has focused on educators' experiences and perspectives of "what works" in the teaching and learning process, educator training, and home-school collaboration. This analysis has also enabled me as the researcher to locate the existing SWOTs within such provision from educators'

perspectives and make recommendations for policymakers, practitioners, and future research areas.

Given the above, I, as the researcher, have adopted the functional pragmatist role. In pragmatism, knowledge is seen as a means to improve the world (Goldkuhl, 2008). With reference to William James, Dewey (1931) writes that “reason has a creative function ... which helps to make the world other than it would have been without it” (Goldkuhl, 2008, p.4). This perspective is established on a view of the world as a state that is still becoming. Therefore, knowledge should be useful for action and change, and the term functional in the context of pragmatism means that knowledge should be valuable and applicable in action (Goldkuhl, 2008).

As illustrated in Figure 23, using both quantitative and qualitative methods, my intentions as the researcher intended to explore and better understand the provision for learners with autism who attend schools in Malta. As a pragmatist research, I applied a positivist and constructivist approach to this research. Therefore, the philosophy of functional pragmatism has enabled me to shed light on the underlying characteristics of the educational provision for learners with autism in primary mainstream schools in Malta, through the educators’ perspective on the SWOTs within such provision. Furthermore, according to the participants, this analysis has identified what works and which areas within the provision need ameliorating. Consequently, stakeholders involved in educating learners with autism in Malta may review such analysis and take action to improve the quality of provision for learners with autism and their parents.

The aforesaid has also allowed for possible local improvement by creating knowledge and explaining these practices as emphasised when adopting a pragmatic approach (Goldkuhl, 2012). Goldkuhl (2012) states that the key tenant of pragmatism is to 'be helpful to the world' (p.144). Indeed, pragmatism is an innovative approach that replaces a traditional way of evaluating the differences between methods and research by considering those differences as social contexts for inquiry as a form of social action rather than abstract philosophical systems (Morgan, 2014). The aforesaid derive from Dewey's (2008, p.14) views, who argues that:

intellectual progress usually occurs through sheer abandonment of questions together with both of the alternatives they assume—an abandonment that findings from their decreasing vitality and a change of urgent interest. We do not solve them: we get over them. Old questions are solved by disappearing, evaporating, while new questions corresponding to the changed attitude of endeavour and preference take their place.

Considering this research study, the aim was to ask new questions that have never been asked in the context of autism and educational provision in Malta, with the intention that readers of the study's findings would potentially change their practice where necessary. Forwarding new questions was essential as several gaps regarding the existing SWOTs within teaching and learning, training for educators, and home-school collaboration within international and Maltese contexts were noted following an extensive literature review. Thus, following Dewey's (1910/2008), Goldkuhl's (2012), and Morgan's (2014) views, the rationale behind this research study is to identify the strengths and any problems which are present within the provision for learners with autism in Malta concerning SWOTs. Pursuing this

approach in terms of pragmatism was necessary as one of the study's aims was to produce recommendations that can positively impact educators, parents, and students closely involved in the field of autism in Malta.

Figure 23: The Pragmatic Philosophical Assumptions of the Researcher of this Study

3.2.2 The ontology of pragmatism

Research has argued that scholars have somewhat overlooked the ontological issue in pragmatism (Maarouf, 2019). Pratt (2016) has criticised pragmatic scholars for focusing on pragmatism as epistemology and methodology while disregarding pragmatism as ontology. Furthermore, Lohse (2017) has referred to similar views in what he has termed *anti-ontological pragmatism*, where pragmatists argue that social scientists need to think less about social ontology and instead focus their efforts more exclusively on epistemological and methodological work. However,

when reflecting upon the arguments above, the prime issue is not that pragmatism does not have an ontological stance but that its ontological stance is misunderstood (Hathcoat and Meixner, 2017).

Unlike positivism, where the ontological position is one of realism (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2007), and unlike constructivism, where the viewpoint suggests that "reality is socially constructed" (Mertens, 2005, p.1), pragmatism is not committed to any single system of philosophy and reality (Weaver, 2018). Thus, pragmatic research accepts both the existence of one reality and that individuals may have multiple interpretations of such reality (Morgan, 2007). In view of this research study, I accept that there is a need for a better understanding of the educational provision for learners with autism in Malta. However, I believe multiple interpretations of the realities within the provision could exist. These diverse interpretations have been gathered from educators who carry out duties in primary schools in Malta, to gain a better understanding of such provisions.

Pragmatic researchers perceive reality regarding processes linking all sorts of entities in relational and recursive ways (Farjoun, Ansell and Boin, 2015). An example of this is the systems in Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory underpinning this research, where the reality of the child is connected to several entities interactively and recurrently. According to Dewey's framework, humans are living organisms capable of establishing and preserving dynamic coordination with their environment (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019) to the extent that a learning process based on trial and error creates a set of habits for action (Biesta 2010). For Dewey, "habits are abilities of conditions of intellectual efficiency developed through

repeated but varied practice” (Shusterman, 1994, pp.135). If our habits of observation and organisation primarily structure the situation, our explicit purposes tend to further shape it (Shusterman, 1994). Such shaping of specific situations leads to the ontological element of pragmatism (Shusterman, 1994). Pragmatists embrace a processual view of the world that values social life's progressive and emergent features (Hernes, 2014). Therefore, the world is in an enduring flux and in the process of becoming (Farjoun, Ansell and Boin, 2015). It is a “work in progress” rather than a final product (Langley and Tsoukas 2012, p.3). Pragmatists are predominantly interested in processes that relate back to themselves in a looping fashion (Ansell, 2011). Hence, the pragmatic approach focuses on a phenomenon that the researcher attempts to understand and ontologically considers that human beings live in a world where action needs to be taken (Putnam, 1994). Such understanding of the world enables knowledge to be produced as ‘knowing’ in such a context and can potentially change practice (Biesta, 2010).

3.2.3 The ontological approach in the current research: Accepting that multiple viewpoints can coexist

Given that the ontology of pragmatism embraces the idea that multiple theories and viewpoints can be true and coexistent (Christ, 2010), my ontological assumptions as the researcher of the current study are based on the belief that reality is based upon reflecting on behaviours, seeing what works and what does not, and seeking possible modifications to improve the impact of this behaviour. In view of this study, I, as the researcher aimed to understand the ‘behaviours’ of educators regarding the provision for learners with autism in Malta, see what works in relation to the

strengths and opportunities within the provision, explore what the weaknesses and threats are, and provide recommendations of how such provision may be improved. These recommendations support Dewey's model of inquiry (Morgan, 2014), where the abovementioned cycle must be repeated as necessary. This cycle should be repeated since pragmatism as a research paradigm accepts that individuals may have multiple constructs of reality, thus making this a 'fluid reality'. Hence, this approach views the world as fluid rather than fixed, allowing people to change their behaviour to improve themselves and others. This view has been adopted as unlike the positivist paradigm and constructivism, pragmatism is flexible in its nature, thus it has permitted me as the researcher of this topic to explore the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism: i) neutrally; ii) through espousing a combination of diverse methodological approaches in research; iii) considering that the results of this research study cannot be explained by one single reality, but rather through multiple realities (Campbell, 2002). As the pragmatic paradigm includes numerous methods, ideas and principles that may offer a solution to a given research problem (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019), it was deemed the most suitable paradigm for this study. In view of this, this research study aims to bring to light educators' perspectives about the provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta, what works and what impedes progress, and what can be done to improve such provision. This is necessary as the type of provision for learners with autism attending primary schools in Malta is unknown; thus, it is an area that needs to be explored. This analysis of the provision is required to potentially uphold the positive *habits* (referred to as strengths for the sake of this research study) and improve any negative *habits* (referred to as weaknesses for the sake of this research study) that impede learners from fully achieving their learning potential. Therefore, by

disseminating the findings of this research within primary schools in Malta and the MEYR, this research will embark upon a process whereby it will potentially inspire stakeholders to make the necessary changes according to the findings of this SWOT analysis. It may be assumed that the process will repeat in some years, enabling Dewey's model of inquiry to recur as necessary (Morgan, 2014).

Taking into consideration the direct relationship of the child with their educators, the ontological assumptions around “how things are” and “how things really work” (Lincoln and Denzin, 2003, p.224) within the pragmatic worldview enabled me as the researcher of this study to gather the perspectives of educators regarding what is being put in place vis-a-vis the provision for learners with autism and the SWOTs within such provision. The amount of influence a factor has on the learner with autism's experience of inclusion depends on its location within the system, and the importance given to the interconnected aspects by the system's administrators (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

In view of the latter, the pragmatic approach, which acknowledges *reality* as the practical effect of ideas and the multiple interpretations of this reality, influences the researcher. By nature, educators are problem-solvers, and the world of logic and practical application of knowledge tends to be instilled in their daily practice. Therefore, obtaining diverse educators' viewpoints would enable the examination of what is put in place for students with autism, what works and what does not, and how the ecological system's interrelated parts affect the type of provision being implemented. Furthermore, this study has allowed me as the researcher to bring to light educators' perspectives on the opportunities and threats of external entities,

organisations, and societal attitudes (exo and macro system) as realities that may help overcome the problems at an internal school level (microsystem). This continues to support the ontological position taken by me, whereby the pragmatist seeks to be helpful to the world.

3.2.4 The epistemology of pragmatism

Johnson and Christensen (2013) have stated that when conducting mixed methods research, it is critical to understand reality's objective and subjective viewpoints. Unlike positivist and constructivist views, pragmatism researchers believe that objective and subjective perspectives are not mutually exclusive (Wahyuni, 2012). Understanding objective and subjective realities fosters the appreciation of intersubjectivity, which enables researchers to highlight and contrast the personal experiences of individuals and interrelations as a concept, which allows the understanding of how two or more things are related.

Hall (2013) argues that pragmatism offers “an alternative epistemological paradigm” (p.19). In this research study, I, as the researcher, have understood that it is suitable to accept objectivity and subjectivity as viewpoints of reality that can be applied in one study. Therefore, gathering data from all education stakeholders in this research study enabled the latter. Thus, pragmatism provides researchers with a way out of idealised notions of science, such as those linked exclusively to positivism or constructivism. Instead, it provides a platform upon which “*inquiry*, in all its manifestations, can rest easy, merely because the several approaches applied all have equal validity contingent on the purpose(s) of said inquiry” (Hothersall, 2018, p. 864).

Dewey views *inquiry* as a process that begins with a question and which aims for “the controlled or directed transformation of an unknown situation into one that is determinate in its constituent distinctions and relations as to convert the elements of the original situation into a unified whole” (Dewey, 1938/1991, p. 108). As noted by Smith, whilst Peirce aimed at “fixing” beliefs, Dewey aimed at “fixing” the situation (1985, p. 549). For Peirce, the meaning of a concept is found in all possible experimental phenomena whereby indications to assert or reject a theory are brought forward (Das *et al.*, 2020). According to Peirce, if humans truly know anything, what they believe in must be real (Das *et al.*, 2020). In contrast, Dewey views beliefs as induced by conditions dominated by imbalance and conflicts (Das *et al.*, 2020). Hence, Dewey believes such thoughts should lead to resolution, as this produces the necessary truth, possibly leading to satisfactory solutions to the thought condition (Das *et al.*, 2020).

It is important to note that in the abovementioned context, the situation is *scientifically* unknown, as truth is not based only on the mere beliefs of humans but is understood and transformed by experience rather than logic. Similarly, Goldkuhl (2011) states that epistemically, one of the types of pragmatism is based on introducing new artefacts (products) as reactions to difficulties and needs in human practices. Indeed, new artefacts derive from the recreation of human experience (practice), whereby such experience is considered true (Das *et al.*, 2020). This true experience calls for an understanding and description of encountered situations that need to be solved or further comprehended (Goldkuhl, 2011).

This research study may motivate educators to improve current autism support practices based on the experiences of educators in Malta. Dewey recognises that when human beings are faced with a question, the first task which needs to be carried out is to understand such difficulty by describing its elements and recognising their relations (Zalta *et al.*, 2020). Identifying a concrete question that needs to be answered is a sign of progress (Zalta *et al.*, 2020). In the pragmatic worldview, knowledge comprises justified contentions that emerge from action-taking and experience of outcomes (Dewey, 2008; Morgan, 2014). Therefore, pragmatism's epistemological premise is based on the idea that research can steer clear of hypothetical deliberations about the nature of truth and reality and alternatively focus on "practical understandings" of concrete, real-world issues (Patton, 2005, p. 153).

The aforesaid is particularly helpful in organisational settings such as schools, as the practice being implemented in such organisations is closely connected to the behaviours in which knowledge (perspectives of individuals) is generated (Kelly and Cordeiro, 2020). It is critical to understand that pragmatism enables researchers to overcome the contrast between theory and action and give voice to those impacted by organisational processes (McKenna, Richardson and Manroop, 2011). As a result, pragmatic epistemology revolves around inquiry as a process of knowledge-seeking to use this knowledge to benefit the communities involved. Considering this research study, educators' practice within schools may be impacted by the surrounding structures, such as the availability of resources, which would influence the provision for learners with autism. Thus, in applying pragmatism, researchers who base their inquiry on organisational settings can move beyond objectivist

conceptualisations towards investigating and comprehending the links between knowledge and action in context (Kelly and Cordeiro, 2020). Knowledge in such a context potentially transforms practice (Biesta, 2010). The major underpinning of pragmatist epistemology is that knowledge is always based on experience, as “one’s perceptions of the world are influenced by our social experiences” (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019, p. 7). Pragmatist epistemology does not position knowledge as reality (Rorty, 1980), and instead, knowledge is built to better manage one's existence and take part in the world (Goldkuhl, 2012).

3.2.5 The epistemological stance of this research study: A practical and real-world benefit inquiry into autism

Following the assumptions made by Dewey on viewing pragmatism as a purpose to better explore issues within society epistemologically, this research has taken the path of such a process. My fundamental commitment as the researcher of this study is to engage in an inquiry that has the potential to be practical and provide real-world benefit to the population being researched in this study. This study views the world through the lens of educators concerning educational provision for learners with autism in Maltese primary schools. The goal is to inspire readers to make the necessary changes to improve the educational conditions of learners with autism and those of their educators. Thomson, Lingard and Wrigley (2012) argue that while change may in many ways seem like an impossible task, "just because schools cannot do everything does not mean they cannot achieve something" (p. 20). Hence, by disseminating the findings of this research within primary schools in Malta and the MEYR, this research will embark upon a process whereby it will encourage

stakeholders to make the necessary changes according to the findings of this SWOT analysis.

Even though this research study's recommendations may inspire readers to change their practices, change may be difficult. Such difficulty transpires as schools may operate in a rigid educational system with high levels of accountability and expectations for sustained progress (Anderson, Boyle, and Deppeler, 2014), which in turn may not provide an equitable learning environment (Wilkinson and Pickett, 2010). Thus, there should be an “epistemological shift in terms of knowledge from *what-is*” (the existing reality/issue/situation) to “*to-be*” (how such reality/issue/situation may be improved) (Goldkuhl, 2011, p.88).

Goldkuhl suggests that a diagnostic mode must be applied to the prevailing situation to reveal its characteristics. In view of this research study, the diagnostic mode to achieve the *what-is* is applied through the SWOT analysis tool. The diagnostic SWOT analysis tool has been used within the Ecology of Inclusive Education model as this theory allows researchers to take a snapshot of the existing provision within educational settings (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). The Ecology of the Inclusive Education framework allows the focus of the research to be on systemic, institutional, or ideological facets of inclusion for learners, including those with autism (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

Epistemologically, this research has sought to transform educators' knowledge of the existing SWOTs into tangible and practical recommendations for policymakers

and practitioners. From a pragmatic epistemological standpoint, I have prioritised the concept of the to-be by conceiving ideas leading to positive changes.

3.2.6 The axiology of pragmatism

Notwithstanding their preferred method of inquiry, most researchers would acknowledge that axiology plays a crucial role in selecting and developing research questions, which drives their attention to particular topics over others (Biddle and Schafft, 2015). Contingent on the norms of their specific research community and individual commitments, social science researchers demonstrate their engagement with axiological issues to varying degrees (Biddle and Schafft, 2015).

The term 'axiology' originates from two Greek roots, axios and logos—axios meaning 'worth' or 'value', and logos referred to as 'logic' or 'theory' (Biedenbach and Jacobsson, 2016, p.140). Combined, the conception of 'a theory of value' is founded (Biedenbach and Jacobsson, 2016, p.140). According to Hesse-Biber (2012, p.878):

Axiology means being cognizant of our values, attitudes, and biases and acknowledging how these might play out in research praxis in terms of (a) what questions are asked or not asked in our research, (b) what type of data are or are not collected, and (c) the type of methods, measurement, analysis, and interpretation that shape our understanding of the research process.

According to Kivunja and Kuyini (2017), axiology considers the value of the researcher in terms of the study, the research sample, the data, and the audience to whom the findings were reported. In simple terms, it addresses questions about what is valued and considered appropriate for humans and society. For instance, if

researchers believe that there is no objective reality and that reality cannot be studied objectively, they openly recognise their values and biases and how they influence their interpretations and interactions with participants that shape the findings (Nyein *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, research is still worthy of pursuing, despite the subjectivity involved, but this subjectivity should be acknowledged.

On an axiological philosophical ground, pragmatic researchers believe ethics play a crucial role in “conducting research and drawing conclusions from their studies” (Subedi, 2016, p.571). Pragmatists view value as a relative and situational notion, and as the culture changes, so do its values. Such concepts transpire as pragmatism accentuates social relations, which most fundamentally shape the realm of values, the processes of evaluation, setting norms, and generating discourses through which axiological issues can be articulated (Skowroński, 2019). The aforementioned leads pragmatism towards axiological pluralism by espousing several values, such as tolerance and freedom (Skowroński, 2019).

3.2.7 The axiological stance of this research study: Improving future practice

Through this study, I aimed to look into what is 'good' and what is not 'good' within such provision and provide recommendations that could improve future practice for the benefit of learners with autism. This analysis of the SWOTs has motivated me to take a pragmatic stance. Indeed, I take on the position that the primary focus of pragmatism is on the issue that needs to be researched (rather than on metaphysical ideologies), on using appropriate research methods to answer the research questions, and on the research's consequences (Feilzer, 2010).

Therefore, the abstract search for knowledge through inquiry, central to the metaphysical approach, is surpassed by an endeavour to acquire knowledge in pursuing sought-after ends (Morgan, 2007).

Given the above-mentioned, my axiological position, understanding of the world, and what I deem valuable are as follows. My beliefs lie within the fact that, if possible, all children, including those with autism, should be included in mainstream settings. I understand that while many educators share this view, the type of provision implemented in schools in Malta is still an area that needs to be explored and explained. Hence, rather than framing this study on an abstract set of philosophical beliefs, this research concentrates on beliefs more directly linked to actions (Morgan, 2014). Through the SWOT analysis tool, I believe this research has better understood the strategies for learners with autism on teaching and learning, training for educators and home-school collaboration. As the researcher, I shall put forth this knowledge to educators and policymakers for the current strengths in the provision to be emphasised and for any barriers to be resolved. Through this, students with autism, their educators, and their parents would benefit from any changes that would ameliorate the provision.

Furthermore, Simpson (2009) notes that “human beings are all active participants (practitioners) in their social worlds, and it is through their participation that they constantly construct and re-construct the social values that shape their beliefs and actions” (p. 1333). In the context of this study, educators were active participants in this research. Such a decision to involve educators was because, within Bronfenbrenner's (1979) ecological systems theory, the school is one of the most

immediate and influential contexts in children's lives. Bronfenbrenner (1979) argues that the interactions within microsystems (the immediate level) are typically very personal and crucial for nurturing and supporting the child's development. Therefore, since learners with autism need a sound support system regarding the educational provision to ensure their inclusion, I, as the researcher of this study, believed that gathering the perspectives of the key educational stakeholders would provide valuable insights into the current state of such provision. The methods and ethical considerations I pursued are discussed in the following sections.

3.2.8 The methodological assumptions of this research study

Pragmatism is widely associated with mixed-methods research (Onwuegbuzie and Johnson, 2006; Johnson, Onwuegbuzie and Turner, 2007; Teddlie and Tashakkori, 2011). Rather than framing the research around obligations to a conceptual set of philosophical beliefs, pragmatism focuses on the research questions and outcome (Morgan, 2014). Unlike positivists' and constructivists' assertions that research should rely exclusively on one method as a philosophical approach, pragmatism allows researchers to combine different approaches and methodologies. Thus, adopting a pluralist position uses a combination of methods that best fit the research study's goals.

3.2.9 A balanced approach to educational research: Mixed-Methods

The growing popularity of mixed methods research, particularly in the field of applied social science, is entirely plausible, as the overall rationale for mixing methods in social inquiry fosters a "better understanding of the intrinsic complexities and

contingencies of human phenomena” (Greene and Hall, 2015, p. 119). Although the specific explanation of a mixed-methods approach remains a disputed area (Cameron, 2011) due to researchers constantly debating its philosophical arguments concerning its validity (Morgan, 2014), it has progressed to an extent where it is viewed as a distinct methodological position with its own worldview, terminology, and methods (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003). This view has been identified as a feasible alternative for researchers involved in social research and who consider a pluralist paradigm for thinking about research problems (Jones and Kennedy, 2011). Such a pluralistic paradigm could overcome the false dualism that divides positivist and constructivist researchers into positivists believing in objective reality and constructivists arguing that reality is a social construction. Hence, building on Dewey's view, where his perspective is that experiences always involve a process of interpretation, the principle of anti-dualism emerged out of an endeavour to halt the conflict between the two competing theories - realism and constructivism (Morgan, 2007). This belief avoids emphasis on one specific category over another (Ansell, 2011; Farjoun, Ansell and Boin, 2015; Frega, 2011).

Many researchers believe that both quantitative approaches deriving from positivism, and qualitative approaches emerging from constructivism (as discussed in the previous sections), may be combined to attend to the process of social inquiry for two primary reasons (Maarouf, 2019). Firstly, the choice between quantitative and qualitative research approaches is mainly based on the researcher's position on the theory (Maarouf, 2019). For instance, whilst the scope of the quantitative researcher would be to apply a deductive approach to test a theory, the qualitative researcher would aim to develop a theory through inductive reasoning (Glogowska,

2011). Secondly, further to the role of each approach in developing knowledge, as previously discussed, the two approaches have complementary advantages and disadvantages. Indeed, in quantitative research, the data can be quantified, and samples are generally large and considered to be representative of the population being investigated (Martin and Bridgmon, 2012).

Nevertheless, these quantitative findings may miss some critical variables and hence might not necessarily mirror the local social understanding (Maarouf, 2019). The aforementioned transpires since quantitative research is limited in terms of it focusing on understanding the context of the research topic because the researcher is not close to the sample (Queirós, Faria and Almeida, 2017). On the other hand, qualitative research is valuable in exploring a limited number of cases in depth (Maarouf, 2019) and thus helps address multifaceted phenomena due to the provision for rich details (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). However, the knowledge generated by qualitative research cannot be generalised to other contexts.

Furthermore, qualitative research can be very time-consuming regarding data collection and analysis (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). A notion that claims to bridge the gap between the positivist (quantitative) and constructivist (qualitative) orientation is the pragmatic approach (Creswell and Miller, 1997). Pragmatism involves the relationship between knowledge and action (Morgan, 2007). This approach makes it suitable as a foundation for research approaches that intervene in the world and do not merely observe it (Morgan, 2007). When reflecting on this, given that I am professionally involved in the field of inclusive education and have a particular interest in autism, the scope of this research study was to provide a better

understanding of the provision for learners with autism in primary school settings regarding: i) the SWOTs within the teaching and learning process; ii) the SWOTs within the training made available to educators on autism; iii) the SWOTs within the home-school collaboration process. This analysis enabled me, as the researcher, to provide recommendations to policymakers and practitioners. Due to the three areas above, this research has decided to take Morgan's view as a valid motivation for using quantitative and qualitative approaches to this research in the educational field.

In line with the principles of pragmatism, the research problem I identified was that, although there has been an increase in the number of learners with autism attending mainstream primary schools in Malta, the provision regarding teaching and learning, training, and home-school collaboration is an understudied local phenomenon. In this situation where the SWOTs within the educational provision are unknown, room for improvement in eliminating barriers is limited due to the unidentified information. The aforementioned research problem led to the development of the research questions designed explicitly for this study to generate relevant knowledge (Goldkuhl, 2012). The development of such research questions was done to follow the pragmatic approach of potentially yielding findings for local improvement, which in the case of this study is focused upon the educational setting and possibly the recommendation of more effective practices (Goldkuhl, 2012; Hall, 2013; Morgan, 2007; Shannon-Baker, 2016).

Given the assumptions mentioned above, the research questions addressed in this research study were as follows:

Research Question 1: Which are the SWOTs within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Research Question 2: Which are the SWOTs within training for educators who support learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Research Question 3: Which are the SWOTs within the home-school collaboration process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Although qualitative and quantitative data are often viewed as incompatible from a positivist and a constructivist point of view, pragmatism allows the potential and possibility to work back and forth between both strands. Figure 24 illustrates the research onion whereby as explained by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009), the research process may be viewed as an onion with several essential layers. As shown in Figure 24, each layer leads to another, with the centre of the research onion illustrating the choice of data collection techniques and data analysis procedures.

The first layer represents the research philosophy related to the nature and development of knowledge, which, in the case of this research, focuses on pragmatism. After selecting the research philosophy, the researchers must select a research approach. In the case of this research, it focuses on abduction, whereby

its process commences with an observation or a set of observations. Abduction then pursues to find the simplest and most probable conclusions from the observations that have been carried out. According to Morgan (2007), pragmatism also relies "on a version of abductive reasoning that moves back and forth between induction and deduction" (p.71) to connect theory and data. This abductive process is typically employed by researchers who combine qualitative and quantitative methods sequentially, where the inductive goals of a qualitative approach are based on the deductive data resulting from a quantitative approach and vice versa (Morgan, 2007). Hence, such a stance enables the researcher to explore the worthy areas of connection between these two data types.

Figure 24: The Research Onion

Different research strategies need to be applied to answer the research questions in the third and fourth layers of the research onion (Figure 24). When reflecting upon my methodological position, I felt that mixed methods following a sequential

explanatory research design were the most suitable approach to achieve the research study's aims and provide answers to the research questions. Using qualitative and quantitative methods in the same research followed the pragmatic philosophical stance, as I intended to generate knowledge that informs effective practice (Sharp *et al.*, 2012). Mixing methods in pragmatic studies necessitate the researcher to decide how and at what stages the mixing has taken place (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2007). In the context of this research study, during the quantitative phase, I gathered data about what is in place for learners with autism in Malta and identified the SWOTs within the provision. However, an explanation of the generated quantitative findings was necessary. Gathering an explanation was a crucial step in the use of mixed methodology, as without understanding the *why* behind success or failure, the effect of context cannot be understood (Albright, Gechter and Kempe, 2013). Hence, the *why* in view of the existing SWOTs within the provision was revealed during the qualitative phase, which focused on identifying the rationale behind what works in one area and what needs improvement in another.

The aforementioned occurred cross-sectionally as per the fifth layer of the research onion, given that this research is part of an academic degree, I was time-constrained (Figure 24). It also occurred within the context of the sequential explanatory research design, as this was deemed the most appropriate, enabling me to address the research questions. It also allowed for triangulation to take place as it followed the three-step process of validation of meta-inferences of Ivankova (2014, p.25) whereby I:

- i) used a systematic process for selecting participants to include in the quantitative phase and a qualitative follow-up;
- ii) elaborated, followed up and probed on unexpected findings from the quantitative data and their analysis;
- iii) observed and reported on interactions between quantitative and qualitative strands of the study.

3.4 The Research Design

The type of research design that implicitly and explicitly fits into this research is the sequential explanatory research design. The mixed-method sequential explanatory design comprised of two phases where the quantitative phase was followed by the qualitative phase (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). The rationale for this approach was based upon the fact that the qualitative data and the following analysis deepened and enriched the understanding provided by the analysis of the data gathered through the questionnaire (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). Hence, the data collected in the qualitative phase provided insights not captured during the quantitative phase. Thus, during this phase, I, as the researcher, could identify which quantitative findings linked to the three areas require a further explanation. Subsequently, the qualitative data and its analysis illuminated, complemented, and extended the statistical findings (Creswell, 2014). Therefore, this study combined quantitative and qualitative research's strengths by connecting and comparing notions and perspectives.

When a SWOT analysis is used as a research tool, it enables the identification and examination of current situational strengths and weaknesses whilst also exploring

tendencies and patterns that may have either positive or negative effects on the organisations or situations under investigation (Namugenyi, Nimmagadda and Reiners, 2019). This SWOT analysis tool was selected as opposed to other methods within this study because it could outline the current strengths and weaknesses within schools and define the external opportunities and threats beyond the school's control when inquiring about the provision for learners with autism. Indeed, many establishments carry out a SWOT analysis as a strategic planning tool that allows for quality control and for formulating government policies and legislations (Namugenyi, Nimmagadda and Reiners, 2019).

Given that the provision for learners with autism has not been investigated within the Maltese educational context, the SWOT analysis tool was used to inspire thought about the provision. This research study also gave an idea of possible future consequences because “a SWOT analysis tool is based on a simple analysis method that can provide a realistic interpretation of an organisation's strengths and weaknesses” (Benzaghta *et al.*, 2021, p. 58). Thus, this tool was pursued over other methods, as it is a useful tool to “aid thinking” (Sarsby, 2016, p.4) and helps in “characterising the SWOTs of the process or structure under scrutiny” (Leiber, 2017, p. 290). A SWOT analysis can help develop the assessed entities for further rounds of improved goal achievement. It usually brings to the forefront SWOTs that have not been noticed by other means of analysis. The investigative force of a SWOT analysis derives from the necessity to recognise and explicitly distinguish the processes or structures' four different categorisation dimensions (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) (Leiber, 2017). For instance, in the case of the current study, both questionnaire and interview participants were probed to

outline and discuss the SWOTs, particularly since it helped identify external opportunities and threats, which in most research cases, tend to be missed. Therefore, a SWOT analysis within this research has allowed this researcher to gather rich data and information specifically focused on the aim intended to be reached, i.e. to explore the SWOTs in the provision for students with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta.

Primary schools were selected for this study due to their nature of providing an in-depth analysis of the provision for learners with autism. Seeking the latter through the lens of a SWOT analysis framework has enabled this research to fill several existing gaps to inform policymakers, professionals and parents about the current existing SWOTs, intending to motivate educational institutions to embrace change (Benzaghta *et al.*, 2021), hence, possibly leading to improvements within the provision.

3.5 The Sample of this Research Study

Purposive sampling was deemed fit to gather relevant and valid data for this research to answer its research questions. Through purposive sampling, the researcher stipulates the characteristics of the population of interest and locates individuals with those characteristics (Johnson and Christensen, 2013). When reflecting on this, I identified the participation criteria to minimise this limitation, given that purposive sampling has been deemed limited regarding the ability to generalise findings to the wider population (Johnson and Christensen, 2013). Following the

recommendations of Johnson and Christensen (2013), I, as the researcher of this study, set the following inclusion criteria for participants:

- i. educators working in a mainstream school setting;
- ii. educators working in state primary schools in Malta;
- iii. educators who have, in some way or another, supported learners with autism in mainstream primary school.

Through the predetermined criteria mentioned above, I obtained data from educators who have supported learners with autism in primary schools in Malta. The inability to gather research data from parents will be discussed in detail further on.

The link to the questionnaire was electronically disseminated to the heads of schools that manage the 59 state-funded primary schools in Malta to gather data from educators and gain access within schools. This procedure was followed as Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) outlined that clear official channels to formally request permission to conduct research should be used to negotiate access when data is intended to be collected. The Heads of Schools were requested to circulate this link amongst the educators working in their schools following a brief research project outline (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This dissemination to all primary schools was pursued as it provided an equal opportunity for all educators working in primary state-funded schools in Malta to participate in the research, with the understanding that participation in this research study was entirely voluntary. However, it is important to note that due to the inclusion criteria necessitating

participating educators to have supported learners with autism, not all educators conducting duties in state mainstream primary schools could participate in this research study.

3.5.1 The sample of the questionnaire participants

As illustrated in Figure 25, of the 53 participants who responded to the questionnaire, 5 (9%) were Heads of Schools, 4 (8%) were Kindergarten Educators, and 2 (4%) were Assistant Heads of Schools. 28 out of the 53 participants were LSEs (53%). Furthermore, eight respondents were primary school teachers (15%), and six were Head of Departments (11%) supporting schools in the area of inclusion. This sample was retrieved from disseminating the link to the questionnaire to 2,791 educators across Malta. However, it should be noted that not all of these educators fell within the criteria set for this research study. When responding to the questionnaire, the participants were required to list their years of teaching experience. The average years of experience of the sample was of 10 years.

Figure 25: The Roles Held by Respondents of the Questionnaire

3.5.2 The sample of the interview participants

Five educators took part in these interviews. Two of them held the roles of LSEs, one of a Head of School, one was a class teacher, and the other participant was a Head of Department supporting inclusion schools. The LSEs had an average of 15 years of teaching experience within the profession, as did the Head of School and the Head of Department. The class teacher had, on average, three years of teaching experience.

3.6 The Quantitative Data Collection Stage

As part of applying a sequential explanatory research design, this study's quantitative data collection phase provided a preliminary indication of how the provision for learners with autism within mainstream primary school settings in Malta takes form. This phase also allowed for the identification of SWOTs, which shape the provision of teaching and learning strategies, training for educators, and collaboration between the school and the parents of learners with autism.

As outlined in Table 2, a questionnaire was distributed to educators working in primary state schools across Malta to complete the first phase of the mixed-methods sequential explanatory research design. The questionnaire was developed as self-administered and web-based (Appendix 6). According to Spitz *et al.* (2006, p. 22), “web-based questionnaires are more accessible than paper-based ones as technology allows the respondent to use screen readers and magnify font and screen resolutions as necessary”. The questionnaire was based on a series of

closed and open-ended questions. This style of questioning was applied as whilst closed-ended questions gathered factual data such as the age of the children with autism and the educators' teaching grade, open-ended questions within the questionnaire provided an initial analysis of the current provision for learners with autism and the SWOTs related to the three areas. Other pros and cons of applying the questionnaire as a data collection tool were considered in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Advantages and Disadvantages of Online Questionnaires (Evans and Mathur, 2005, p.197)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Prior to the dissemination of the questionnaire, this was piloted. The piloting was crucial to this research study as literature shows that no matter how often a researcher edits the questionnaire, they would not know how questions have been interpreted until the pilot is executed (Bernhardt and Geise, 2016). Given the aforementioned, two of my colleagues voluntarily offered to test this questionnaire. The feedback from the individuals who piloted the questionnaire led me to make several amendments to the question structure and formatting. This feedback and editing thus enhanced the validity and reliability of the questionnaire (Bernhardt and Geise, 2016) whilst also ensuring dependability (Stahl and King, 2020).

3.7 The Qualitative Data Collection Stage

This study also collected qualitative data for the sequential explanatory research design. This phase enabled me as the researcher to explore issues identified from the questionnaire findings concerning the three areas and the SWOTs indicated within the provision. Applying a qualitative approach in the research was suitable as it allowed to elicit fuller responses about participants' views and experiences (Hancock, Ockleford and Windridge, 2009). Thus, when educators completed the questionnaire, they were allowed to provide their contact details so that I could contact them to participate in the qualitative phase of this research. Follow-up interviews enabled me to gather a more robust perspective regarding this research topic to explain the findings emerging from the questionnaires.

The qualitative phase of this research study was based upon individual semi-structured interviews, which lasted around 45 minutes and inquired further about

the provision for learners with autism and the SWOTs within the three areas with educators of children with autism (Appendix 7).

<p style="text-align: center;">Phase 1 Collection of Quantitative Data</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Dissemination of the web-based questionnaire to Heads of Schools of the primary schools in Malta. The link was circulated amongst all educators in their respective schools.</p> <p>Parents of students with autism were also approached through several attempts, including social media and associations for individuals with autism. However, no parent accessed the link to the questionnaire despite several reminders being sent. Given this situation, I resorted to focusing this research on only gathering the educators' perspectives.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Phase 2 Analysis of Quantitative Findings</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Analysis of the 53 questionnaires findings concerning the three areas and the SWOTs indicated by participants.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Phase 3 Determine which Issues Require Further Exploration</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Establishing which issues from the questionnaire findings needed to be further explored.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Phase 4 Collection of Qualitative Data</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Interviews with five educators who voluntarily showed interest in participating in the interviews.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Phase 5 Analysis of Qualitative Findings</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Analysis of the data emerging from the interviews.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Phase 6 Interpretation and synthesis of the findings</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">An interpretation of how the qualitative data explains the findings of the quantitative data and synthesis of the findings using triangulation.</p>

Table 2: The Phases of the Sequential Explanatory Research Design

3.8 Data analysis

When using two diverse modes of data collection, the primary challenge is to adopt modes of data analysis for each one that ultimately informs and complements one another. Mixed data analyses encompass quantitative and qualitative analytical methods within the same framework (Onwuegbuzie and Combs, 2010). Onwuegbuzie and Combs (2011) argue that analysis of both data types may occur concurrently, in no chronological or sequential order, where the qualitative analysis phase heads the quantitative analysis phase or vice versa.

3.8.1 Quantitative data analysis

Following the data collection of the quantitative questionnaires through Google Docs®, all responses were downloaded into an Excel® sheet and checked for consistency in data representation. All 53 questionnaires were deemed valid as all participants answered all the questions within the questionnaire.

Bengtsson (2016) suggests that 'content analysis can be used on all types of written texts no matter where the material comes from' (p. 10). Following this position, content analysis was applied to analyse the data emerging from the questionnaires of the current research study. This research also sought to numerically represent the data, as Berelson (1952) and later Neuendorf (2002) and Krippendorff (2004) had shown that content analysis allows researchers to gather facts from text and present them as frequency expressed as a percentage or actual numbers of key categories. To achieve this, following the process of content analysis, the data in

the questionnaires was summarised in a deductive manner (Krippendorff, 2004; Neuendorf, 2002). Indeed, following a deductive approach whereby from the beginning of the analysis of questionnaires, it was decided that I would look for the SWOTs within the three areas, the data pertaining to each SWOT was imported into the NVivo® software. This process enabled me as the researcher to create creating nodes and codes, as illustrated in Figure 27 in terms of the SWOTs in view of the three areas. The number of references generated by NVIVO® then enabled me to provide a numerical representation of how many participants referenced specific approaches, strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the three areas. Through this data, I could plot the information on graphs on Excel® sheets as it made it easier to interpret the data and, hence, develop the questions that needed to be asked during the qualitative stage of this research study. The findings generated from this phase will be discussed in detail in the following chapter.

Figure 27: The Codes and Nodes Created to Reference the SWOTs Outlined in the Questionnaire Using NVivo12

3.8.2 Qualitative data analysis

As opposed to how the data in the questionnaires was analysed, the data emerging from interviews was analysed inductively, enabling me to 'identify, analyse, and report patterns (themes) within data' (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p.6). Indeed, whilst content analysis, as applied in the analysis of questionnaires, allowed me to gather information from text with the intention that these are presented in the form of frequency expressed in actual numbers of key categories (Berelson, 1952; Krippendorff, 2004; Neuendorf, 2002), thematic analysis enabled me to report upon explanations which directly focused on the provision for learners with autism on teaching and learning, home-school collaboration and training for educators, hence, the SWOTs within the abovementioned three areas, and the reasons behind these SWOTs, as indicated through the perceptions of educators. Patterns were identified and allocated according to the data sets identified to provide a comprehensive view of the provision for learners with autism.

For the analysis of the qualitative data gathered through the semi-structured interviews, I also used Excel[®]. After transcribing the interviews verbatim, the interviewees' quotes related to the SWOTs were plotted into cells within the Excel[®] programme according to themes. Such plotting enabled me to make sense of the explanations provided by interviewees following the sequential explanatory research design. During this process, I constantly asked questions about distinct events or beliefs that were specified in the statements made by the participants during the interview. In fact, during the thematic analysis procedure, I asked myself the following:

- What is this?
- What is going on?
- What does it stand for?
- What else is like this?
- What is this distinct from?

(Adapted from O'Donoghue, 2007, p.60).

3.8.3 Limitations to using a web-based questionnaire in research

Research shows that self-administered questionnaire designs in web surveys may gather richer data than when applying other survey modes (Reja *et al.*, 2003). However, this tool still has its limitations. Reja *et al.* (2003) argue that selection bias, lack of motivation to complete the entire questionnaire, and lack of human interaction while carrying out a self-administered questionnaire may lead respondents to “abandon the questionnaire” (p. 161).

Another limitation in the application of a web-based questionnaire is located within the dissemination of online surveys, given that it is not always possible to ensure that respondents answer truthfully (Lefever, Dal and Matthíasdóttir, 2007). Indeed, Lefever, Dal and Matthíasdóttir (2007) argue that individuals can pose as different people in web-based self-administered questionnaires. In the case of this study, it is hard to tell whether the demographic information inputted by participants reflects the truth, for instance, on their role and teaching experience.

3.8.4 Limitations of using interviews as a research tool

Qualitative research is not concerned with statistical representations but with an in-depth understanding of a given situation. Hence, qualitative methodology is concerned with explaining the dynamics of social relations (Queirós, Faria and Almeida, 2017). In-depth semi-structured interviews are a qualitative data tool encouraging participants to speak freely. In turn, this provides (i) rich information, (ii) the opportunity for the researcher to ask follow-up questions, (iii) probes for further information, (iv) justifies previous responses, (v) establishes a link between several topics (Queirós, Faria and Almeida, 2017). However, there are some limitations and weaknesses when researchers adopt interviews as one of their data collection methods.

In this research, each interview took approximately forty-five to sixty minutes. Interviews were carried out through a video call. Such a decision was employed due to the data collection coinciding with the national lockdown following the COVID-19 pandemic. However, these were scheduled according to the participants' availability, as literature shows that interview appointments must be conveniently planned (Robson, 2011). During the five scheduled interviews, I strived to maintain neutrality in how questions were asked and the body language portrayed. Furthermore, 'interviewer bias', which focuses on how the interviewer acts and conducts an interview, was minimised. Indeed, I allowed and gave time to the respondents to respond freely according to their perspectives. Furthermore, bias was reduced in these interviews by avoiding effects like the 'Santa Claus' and 'Grandpa' effects, whereby the researcher expects too much from the respondent

in the former and too little in the latter (Sarantakos, 2012). Hence, I asked the scheduled questions, which were pre-planned and probed when necessary, without placing any pressure on the respondents to gather further in-depth data about the provision for learners with autism.

The transcription process also contributed to limitations related to time consumption. Every hour of audio and video interview recording took me six hours to transcribe verbatim. The literature argues that it takes the novice researcher as much as four to eight hours of transcription for each hour of recorded data (McGrath, Palmgren and Liljedahl, 2019; Dörnyei, 2007). Transcribing the interviews word for word has allowed me to ensure that all facts were analysed. Thus, all the information gathered in the interviews was transcribed in a manner that ensured that:

- no information passed on to the researcher by the interviewee was withheld;
- no non-responses were replaced with the responses of other participants;
- no parts of the data collected were forged or reworded with the scope of changing interpretation

(Sarantakos, 2012).

Following the aforesaid to make the data more credible, I forwarded the transcripts to the research participants. Having transcripts forwarded to participants enabled them to verify the statements outlined in the transcriptions, contributing to respondent validation (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). All five interviewees agreed with the way transcripts were transcribed, and none of the interviewees

requested any amendments to these. Thus, no conflicts regarding the interpretation of findings arose in this case.

Another limitation associated with interviews is the issue of anonymity. Sarantakos (2012) argues that interviews tend to offer less anonymity for participants than any other method, as the interviewer gets to know the identity of the participants. In the case of this research, anonymity with interview participants was lacking as through the video-recorded interviews, I could identify the participants. To overcome this, I assigned pseudonyms to each participant to protect their identities throughout the research process. All data was secured within password-protected devices and encrypted to ensure the interview participants' identities were never disclosed. These security measures ensured that anonymity would be guaranteed (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018) and confidentiality would be safeguarded. To avoid jeopardising the trustworthiness between myself as the researcher and the participants, I guaranteed that no discussions about the interviewees or what was discussed were conducted with other parties who did not participate in this research. Furthermore, the participants were ensured that no information written in this work would allow for their identification and traceability (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Autonomy, Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation

Information sheets with details of what the study entailed and what participation would involve were forwarded to prospective participants through the Heads of College Networks and the Heads of Schools of the 59 primary state schools in Malta

(Appendices 3, 4 and 5). These information sheets were critical as they led to: i) potential contributors being *informed of the intentions of this study*; ii) potential participants being *debriefed*; iii) *avoidance of deception*. Hence, I ensured that there was an understanding among participants of the study's goals, risks, and benefits (Perrault and Keating, 2018).

Furthermore, prior to gathering data from this research's participants, approval and consent from the relevant committees, authorities, and participants were sought (Appendices 1, 2, 8 and 9). This enabled participants to contribute to this research through *informed consent*, ensuring they were informed of their rights, responsibilities, and risks before participation (Perrault and Keating, 2018). The data in the information sheets provided participants with sufficient detail related to the research in a relevant and accurate manner (University of the West of Scotland, 2020). Therefore, all information was clearly and honestly outlined and included all the relevant details for participants to consent to (University of the West of Scotland, 2020). Potential participants were also given sufficient time to consider the information and decide on participation (University of the West of Scotland, 2020). Therefore, as the researcher of this study, I ensured that individuals made their own informed decision about whether or not to participate in the research; hence, their participation was entirely voluntary. No payment or use of incentives to encourage participation was adopted. Indeed, as the researcher of this study, I ensured that the principle of autonomy was followed (University of the West of Scotland, 2020).

Right to Withdraw

Participants were also allowed to withdraw from the study at any time if they felt it was necessary. Yet, once participants submitted their responses to the questionnaire, I as the researcher could not identify such withdrawals, as their contribution was anonymous. Therefore, as suggested by the British Educational Research Association (BERA, 2018), the data from the questionnaire was made available to the research during the year 2020.

Data Retention

Participants were notified from the start that their questionnaire and interview responses would only be utilised for this research. Hence, the information provided by the sample was utilised only for this research, kept in a secure place within password-protected devices during the research process, and disposed of when it was no longer required. Therefore, all the data collected from the participants was managed as per the Data Protection Act (2018).

Anonymity

In this research, *anonymity* was also ensured. Anonymity is assured when neither researchers nor readers of the findings of a study can identify or link a provided response with any of the research participants (Babbie, 2017). Anonymity is the responsibility of the researcher. Previous educational research studies carried out in small settings such as the Maldives and Macau (China) demonstrate that the issue of guaranteeing the anonymity of the participating sample is almost impossible (Crossley and Vulliamy, 1997; Goodson, Loveless and Stephens, 2013; Moosa, 2013; Morrison, 2006). Such an ethical concern transpires as the number of individuals within small territories eligible to participate in specific research studies

is part of a narrow network. One participant's identification may lead to others' exposure (Moosa, 2013). While some research participants choose to be named as they consider this action empowering, others do not want their identity revealed (Moosa, 2013). Hence, at no point in the questionnaire were participants required to disclose their name and/or personal and/or contact details. This research only required the email address of participants who voluntarily wanted to participate in the interview. The link where participants could include their email addresses was independent of the questionnaire for the latter to remain anonymous. This email address was solely used to contact participants to schedule a convenient date and time for them to conduct the interview. Email addresses were removed from my contact list following the completion of this research study.

Confidentiality

In this study, I ensured that no discussions about the interviewees or what they discussed would take place in any way. This guarantee was given to avoid jeopardising the researcher's and the participants' trustworthiness. Furthermore, the participants were ensured that no information written in this work would allow for their traceability (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Transparency

Transparency throughout this research was maintained in particular since this ensured that the appropriate data was collected and the welfare of the participants and the researcher was not jeopardised (British Educational Research Association-BERA, 2018). Hence, I ensured that transparency was maintained to ensure research integrity throughout the data reporting process and within the analysis and

interpretation of data (University of the West of Scotland, 2020). Fairness and equity for all research participants were maintained throughout this research process by following the ethical principle of transparency. Indeed, all educators who fit the sampling criteria were allowed to participate in this research study since requests for participation were forwarded to all the primary state mainstream schools in Malta.

In this chapter, I outlined my research paradigm and data collection methods and explained why they were deemed the most appropriate to address her research questions and the best suited to yield rigorous, thorough findings of value to others in academia and education. I argue that as an informed researcher, I can offer fresh perspectives and generate new knowledge on the provision for learners who attend primary mainstream schools in Malta. Ethical considerations were central to my role as a researcher as I believe that it is my explicit duty and responsibility to ensure ethical conduct towards the research participants and to produce work that is helpful to others. The following chapter shall present the findings of this study, whereby data was collected using a sequential explanatory research design. Thus, the data gathered from the questionnaires, together with extracts from the interviews, will be presented in the following section to be able to shed light on the current SWOTs as indicated by educators working in schools in Malta related to the teaching and learning process, training for educators, and the home-school collaboration process.

Chapter 4: Findings

This chapter outlines the data gathered from the online questionnaire and the semi-structured interviews with educators on the three areas related to teaching and learning, training, and home-school collaboration. This phase attempted to gather information about the existing SWOTs in the three areas above. The qualitative analysis supported the inferential analysis, thus justifying the data emerging from the questionnaire (Table 2). Representative quotations deriving from the voices of interview participants are provided as descriptive examples supporting the data from the questionnaire. To ensure anonymity, interview participants will be referred to as outlined in Table 3.

Participant 1	Learning Support Educator
Participant 2	Head of School
Participant 3	Learning Support Educator
Participant 4	Teacher
Participant 5	Head of Department (Inclusion)

Table 3: Interview Participants

4.1 The Teaching and Learning Process

The following section shall present the findings brought forward by participants in this study regarding teaching and learning. Through the phases of the sequential explanatory research design (Table 2), data attempted to answer the following research question aligned to teaching and learning:

Which are the SWOTs within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

As noted in Table 4, the participants identified several SWOTs within teaching and learning when responding to the questionnaire. During the interviews, the participants were asked questions about the SWOTs they identified in the questionnaire to gather an explanatory perspective.

<p><i>Strengths within the teaching and learning process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Adaptations of instructions ➤ Support from the SLT ➤ Support from peers 	<p><i>Weaknesses within the teaching and learning process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lack of funding to purchase resources ➤ Adaptations of instructions are developed mainly by LSEs ➤ Inadequate Classroom Environment
<p><i>Opportunities that could enhance the teaching and learning process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Support from external service providers ➤ Quiet spaces 	<p><i>Threats that could hinder the teaching and learning process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lack of knowledge of policy content and implementation ➤ Unclear perspectives on Inclusion

Table 4: The SWOTs of the Teaching and Learning Process

4.1.1 Strengths of the teaching and learning process

Adaptations of instructions for learners: As illustrated in Figure 28, a strength of the teaching and learning process of students with autism, which outlines one of the current capacities of schools in Malta brought forward by questionnaire participants, was having adaptations of instructions for learners. When questionnaires were analysed, this study saw 29 references retrieved from the respondents' replies to the questionnaires outlining this as a strength in teaching and learning. Table 5 provides a sample of some of the responses provided by questionnaire participants.

Figure 28: Strengths of Teaching and Learning

Participant Number	Response
3	Experienced LSEs who adapt the curriculum
19	Using adaptations as a learning approach
31	LSE doing adaptation in class makes instruction easier for children with autism to learn
34	LSEs adapt and cater for students with autism to reach the aims
36	Adapted hands-on strategies

Table 5: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Adaptations as Strengths

When participants were asked why adaptations of instructions were indicated as a current strength by questionnaire participants, the views of interviewees were as follows:

Adaptations of instructions are a must for students with autism, mainly if the curriculum is beyond the students' abilities. Adaptations make them understand what is going on in the classroom, and they may follow in steps what is being presented (Participant 3: LSE).

The Head of Department, who supports schools in the area of inclusion, outlined that adaptations of instructions are critical in particular since students with autism may find it difficult to understand abstract concepts rather than tangible ones.

When teaching them concepts like Religion, these are too abstract. You have to use a lot of pictures and visuals. You have to try to explain concepts to them in the simplest way possible and not necessarily in the way how the other children learn. However, I still think that teachers and LSEs need to see whether these subjects are relevant to teach learners skills, as I think they are not needed to perform daily activities (Participant 5: Head of Department).

As illustrated in Figure 29, when providing their opinion on which strategies are used to support teaching and learning for learners with autism, visual support was the strategy that questionnaire participants frequently mentioned.

Figure 29: Strategies Applied During the Teaching and Learning Process

When asked to provide their views concerning this, all five interview participants agreed that visual aids are frequently used since students with autism are perceived as visual thinkers. Participant 5 outlined that:

Children with autism find it harder to understand when they do not see a visual cue. Most of them have a good visual memory, so pictures and written text helps them retain more information. When you show them something is written or with more pictures or content on flashcards, they can relate to that situation and remember more (Participant 5: Head of Department).

Additionally, Participant 4 outlined that when carrying out tasks with students with autism, visuals help them see that tasks are completed and when it is time to get their reinforcing reward:

When the task is ready, the visual outlining the task is put in the 'finish' box. The child sees that the activity is now completed. For example, the child will tangibly see that he has three more activities to complete to go on the trampoline or complete an activity that serves as a reward (Participant 4: Teacher).

The five interview participants also stated that visual schedules are a "must" when supporting students with autism because "they [students with autism] respond to it very much," "it [visual schedule] provides structure," "it is fixed," "it is there," and "they can see it."

When interviewed, a Head of School outlined that the visual schedule allows learners with autism to be more prepared for any changes and transitions that may occur, hence, increasing predictability:

I can tell you from experience. When we had children with autism, we noticed that they needed routine and structure. So schedules give them a specific structure, preparing them for any changes and transitions. It helps them predict what will come next (Participant 2: Head of School).

Parallel to the perspective of Participant 2, two other Participants also discussed that enabling the child to see what will happen next through the visual schedule tends to 'avoid a lot of frustration' (Participant 1: LSE) and also 'reduces anxiety in students as with visual schedules they have a step-by-step guide of what to do' (Participant 5: Head of Department).

When providing an example of how the visual schedule is used in the classroom, Participant 3 outlined that:

You start, for example, with Maths. When the task is completed, I will indicate that Maths is over. I tell the child to look at the visual schedule and tell me what is next. The child removes the Maths card from the schedule as he can see that Maths is done. This method helps the child access the curriculum as they are better prepared for the next activity (Participant 3: LSE).

Further to the perspectives outlined above, when asked about the extent of the use of digital tools in the classroom, most participants indicated that digital tools are critical in supporting learners with autism. One interviewee mentioned using the YouTube application on the child's tablet as a visual resource supporting the class content. This participant believed that children with autism tend to better comprehend the presented concepts:

There is a lot of visual content on YouTube. From my experience, all the children I supported enjoyed watching videos on YouTube. I like songs and channels that provide further information on the topic...to motivate the child...it helps them remember the information. I have also noticed that children tend to be more independent when I use the school tablet and indicate methods on it. I also use it for reading. The student I support prefers reading an online book. Children enjoy it as this is part of their generation (Participant 3: LSE).

I make social stories on the computer using PowerPoint®. The student follows it and reads it on the laptop, computer...or sometimes his tablet. I let the students touch the screen to turn the page on the PowerPoint®, so, you know...make them involved. Some children find the transitions between each slide very intriguing (Participant 4: Teacher).

All participants disagreed when asked about the possibility of children with autism becoming 'obsessed' with such digital tools. Participant 3 argued against the idea as follows:

The teacher or the LSE needs to control the time spent on the computer or tablet. Such control does not only apply to digital tools but also to fidgets etc..

(Participant 3: LSE).

When participants were asked about why 26 references retrieved from the questionnaire indicated the use of manipulative resources as incorporation to adapting instruction, one teacher explained how she includes these as part of the support provided to learners with autism.

I use little balls with colours and put things in them. It depends on the level of the students. If they are learning letters, I put plastic letters in the balls. We take them out from the ball piece, and the child has to say what the letter is.

I have students who do not like letters. To increase understanding, I put plastic animals instead, and we try to say the sound that the animals make and name them. So, there is learning through these activities (Participant 4:

Teacher).

An LSE commented on how educators may use resources such as sand and playdough to improvise resources when unplanned content is presented in the class.

Children with autism must see the 'real thing'. If the teacher presents something that I have not planned for, I use resources such as blocks or flashcards. When using tangibles, children understand better as they learn through what they see (Participant 1: LSE).

Another participant voiced a similar view. Participant 5 outlined that when objects rather than a paper and pencil approach are presented, children with autism tend to be more engaged in learning.

I see children being more engaged when you have the right curriculum for them, and you have a lot of resources, such as lollipop sticks, for them to use for counting, adding, or subtracting as they see something concrete. That is how I see the children happy and involved. When you do not have these things, you see them in their own world, and they are lost (Participant 5: Head of Department).

Support from the SLT: As illustrated in the sample of responses in Table 6, 16 references from the questionnaire indicated that support of the school's administration is a current advantage within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism.

Participant Number	Response
4	Support from Hos

21	Support from SLT, such as the Head of School.
22	I get help from the Head of School
36	Teamwork between educators and SLT
51	The administration helps when issues with parents arise

Table 6: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Support from SLT

When asked about the above, interviewees held similar perspectives and reported the role of the SLT in the process as follows:

Let me tell you, the SLT always plays a vital role in a school. I think that schools in Malta have SLT members who support staff and students, which makes inclusion for children with autism work well. Being on board means that you must believe in the potential of these children ...not just the student with autism but everyone, because you will be able to help them better and be more informed about their needs (Participant 2: Head of School).

It is essential to have the support of the SLT. I have SLT members in my school who are knowledgeable about autism, understand, support, and help me when I need support... I feel less helpless (Participant 3: LSE).

Support from peers: Questionnaire respondents in this study outlined that a current strength enabling them to manage the provision for learners with autism is related to peer support. In fact, several questionnaire respondents outlined that peer preparation programmes (PPPs) and buddy systems are advantages that allow them to enhance the teaching and learning process (Table 7).

Participant Number	Response
1	I get support from peers. They cooperate
10	PPP;Buddy System
17	Support from other students
26	I try to involve other children in the classroom too to help students with autism
31	Involve other children through the buddy system and maybe a PPP

Table 7: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Support from Peers

When asked about this strength during the interview phase, Participant 2 argued the following:

I feel that PPPs are a key factor because, first of all, you must see what benefits all students have and not only the child with autism. PPPs allow typical developing peers to work with this child and to communicate with him
(Participant 2: Head of School).

Participant 3 outlined that PPPs are usually implemented at the beginning of the scholastic year, yet outlined a rather significant challenge to their implementation.

Peer preparation helps a lot when children start school at the beginning of the school year. You prepare their peers and tell them what autism is, so they will be informed of what might happen in class or at school. I see that they respond better to the need of the child with autism following the PPP. However, what I find rather challenging is that we need parents' consent to carry out this. Some parents approach the school themselves for a PPP. But speaking out from my experience, most parents refuse when the school requests consent to carry out a PPP since this involves explaining their child's condition to other peers (Participant 3: LSE).

Parallel to what Participant 3 outlined on informing neurotypical students regarding particular behaviours which learners with autism may manifest, Participant 1 argued the following:

You want to try to involve this child by telling the rest of the class what things might be annoying and the difference between a tantrum and a meltdown, which most people do not know. Peers will respond positively and not be

scared or make fun of the child. Yet you still need parents to approve whether the class team should give this information to classmates (Participant 1: LSE).

Interview participants also discussed several pros and cons of implementing a buddy system. While a participant argued that, from her experience, children with autism make progress when having a buddy, another participant argued that peer buddies should be changed regularly.

I like to use the buddy system a lot because certain children with autism make social progress. At least they are not alone or constantly accompanied by an adult. They carry out work with their buddy (Participant 3: LSE).

In my opinion, the buddy system has its pros and cons. If you implement it, you have to make it a point that the peer buddy changes and are not always the same because it is unfair. From my recent experience, I believe that when the buddy system is implemented, the peer buddy should be changed daily (Participant 1: LSE).

Further to the opinion of Participant 3, Participant 4 outlined that the buddy system not only supports learners with autism during the teaching and learning process but also benefits the assigned buddy.

We had a child with challenging behaviour in the class. He was not with autism. But when I told him to take care of the student with autism, his

behaviour changed. He was less impulsive and took care of the student. He helped him pack his bag and do classwork (Participant 4: Teacher).

4.1.2 Weaknesses of the teaching and learning process

Adaptations developed by LSEs: As illustrated in Figure 30, a weakness frequently referred to by questionnaire respondents concerning teaching and learning within the schools' current limitations was that the LSE makes most of the adaptations developed in the classroom. Table 8 illustrates a sample of the responses of questionnaire participants.

Figure 30: Weaknesses of the Teaching and Learning Process

Participant Number	Response
1	Some teachers just let the LSE get on with the student and do not take an active interest in him/her as the LSE does adaptations

14	LSEs have to take on all the responsibility of the child alone and teachers do not help out even in curriculum support
34	Training is given only to LSEs, creating a situation where even the child does not know his teacher because the LSE takes care of him throughout the day. LSEs are responsible for adapting the curriculum without the guidance of the class teacher
50	LSEs are expected to prepare content and worksheets
51	Teachers lack awareness of how to develop individual work

Table 8: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Adaptations developed by LSEs

Similar to what questionnaire participants indicated, Participant 1 argued that most adaptations are developed by the LSE rather than the class teacher. This participant outlined the following:

Unfortunately, the mentality is still that the teacher teaches and the LSE supports. This shift is evident in our school, and collaboration is limited. That is the main teaching method that is used. The teacher provides schemes of work and provides topics on what to work on. But it is up to the LSE to adapt. It is not the ideal situation (Participant 1: LSE).

Further to those mentioned above, another LSE participant argued that some teachers tend to see the student with a statement of needs, including one diagnosed with autism, as the LSE's responsibility and not 'her' [the teacher's] responsibility.

When asked to elaborate, this participant said the teacher encouraged the student to approach the LSE for help when the student posed a question.

Lack of resources: Questionnaire participants outlined that a weakness that is stopping the school from performing at its optimum level in terms of the provision for learners with autism in the area of teaching and learning is the lack of available resources. Table 9 illustrates a sample of the responses provided by questionnaire participants.

Participant Number	Response
5	Not enough resources for support
17	The lack of resources makes it difficult for educators to keep up with the adaptations needed
18	Specialised materials for students with autism students are lackin in schools
36	The budget is low
39	Lack of resources (such as sensory bottles, stress balls etc...)

Table 9: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Lack of Resources

When putting forward this viewpoint to interviewees in terms of this weakness, one participant reported that during one instance, the parents had to pay for the resources needed in the classroom.

Participant 1 (LSE): For example, we had a child at school who needed black-out curtains due to visual hypersensitivity. The parents of this student had to pay for these curtains. They bought these curtains, the material, and they sewed them. Since the child changes class every year... these curtains had to be taken by the parents to the dry cleaners. The parents had to bring them back to school and hang them in the new class. The windows are not all the same. So we had an issue, for example, that the curtains were shorter, so...you know it is something which ... if the parent has the means to keep their child comfortable – I am talking about State Schools here – yes the child would be very comfortable but if they do not have the money...it is an issue.

Researcher: Did the parents discuss this matter with the school before?

Participant 1 (LSE): Yes...but because these curtains and the modification were needed only for their child, they had to pay for it.

Furthermore, this participant argued that if the required resource would benefit only one child, authorities or the school administration would not always be willing to invest in it, despite the fact that such resource would be recommended for the student.

Due to budget and money, it will not happen only for one child. There is empathy...we understand...the school tries to understand. But then recommendations are not always executed because it depends on the budget...if money is involved (Participant 1: LSE).

Another participant outlined that sometimes, the lack of resources does not allow her to help children with autism in class and that despite having been provided with a resource allowance, this is not enough as '*specific resources such as spiky cushions, coloured printing, fidgets and lamination are expensive*' (Participant 3: LSE). When this participant was asked to explain further what the outcomes of this are, she responded as follows:

I have a limit to how much I can use the resource allowance. When it is maxed out, I stop providing such resources, particularly flashcards, as they require colour printing and lamination. When I ask the school for help, they tell me that LSEs have resource allowance...so they do not help (Participant 3: LSE).

Yet, when asked about this, the Head of School and the Head of Department who participated in this study had diverse views as they outlined that schools are equipped with resources, and if educators ask for them, they will be provided with what they require.

I always try and provide the necessary resources for my staff and students. I rarely say 'no' (Participant 2: Head of School).

Believe me.. .if educators ask for them {resources}, they will be given what they need. I can tell you from my own experience that there are rooms full of resources that are never used in schools (Participant 5: Head of Department).

Inadequate classroom environment: Several questionnaire respondents outlined that the physical environment of the classroom they work in is inadequate for learners with autism and considered it as a weakness impeding the school from providing adequate quality within the teaching and learning process. Table 10 illustrates a sample of the responses provided by questionnaire participants.

Participant Number	Response
	The classroom environment is not suitable
17	Crowded classrooms
18	Students with autism need an appropriate class environment (clear spaces), as what currently exists is inadequate
24	Some school buildings are old, and classes are overcrowded
29	There is not enough space in the classroom for specific techniques to be practised

Table 10: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Inadequate Classroom Environment

When participants were asked about this identified weakness, some interview participants argued that classes are overcrowded and that students with autism would benefit from environments not being overloaded with material and noise.

Classrooms are overcrowded and stuffed with children. We can barely breathe...it is hot. The environment is what it is.and there are too many children in the classroom. So, it is already very challenging for certain learners, let alone people with autism, to function in that environment. I could see the difference when the student worked on a one-to-one in a less cluttered space outside the classroom. The student was calm. Once she entered the classroom, which is different from the clinical environment, where you have all the distractions, many charts on the wall, the teacher explaining, and the students shouting...students talking over others...it was a different story (Participant 1: LSE).

Correspondingly, another participant argued that a clustered environment creates confusion and can be overwhelming for students to such an extent that this participant described this environment as being a 'hazard'. This participant also indicated that the class is:

An overstimulating environment where we LSEs do not even have the space to conduct work on a one-to-one basis with the student (Participant 3: LSE).

4.1.3 Opportunities to the teaching and learning process

Quiet spaces: As illustrated in Figure 31, An idea that could support change outlined by questionnaire respondents regarding teaching and learning was the creation of quiet areas. Table 11 illustrates a sample of their responses.

Figure 31: Opportunities to the Teaching and Learning Process

Participant Number	Response
4	An adequate room that is quiet for children
31	It would be ideal to have a withdrawal room where lessons can take place to enhance learning for students already diagnosed as being on the autism spectrum

46	Although available, we are not allowed access to the resource room
47	A quiet room for the students to use during the day
53	Quiet areas or rooms

Table 11: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Inadequate Classroom Environment

When interviewees were asked about the opportunity related to quiet spaces, one Participant argued that if she had room in the classroom, she would create a separate, quiet area.

One may easily implement a quiet area if there is space in the classroom. Some space ...not a huge area... just a small corner with cushions. This may help when children need to retreat for some quiet time due to the overwhelming environment that the class may create (Participant 3: LSE).

An external factor related to how the school's physical environment may be improved was for education authorities to invest in refurbishing schools to make them more autism-friendly.

If you have an autism-friendly school, it will help a lot. Educational authorities need to invest more in this. For example, lighting needs to be professionally designed to be more autism-friendly (Participant 5: Head of Department).

A Head of School argued that although schools are to a certain extent 'equipped', more work is needed for them to be considered 'autism-friendly'. This participant argued that for the school to be autism-friendly, the following need to be in place:

Children with autism need certain specialised rooms. We had these, but the MEYR told us to close them down. Students need the quiet room, the dark room, the multisensory room, or whatever, as the noise in the classroom may stress them. We are not providing these areas in schools. I have been in administration for six years but have been in the education sector for twenty years. A lot has been done, but still, schools do not provide the proper setup for kids with autism. I am not saying that they are entirely excluded because the severity of the condition also plays a role in this. But I do not think we are yet well equipped to consider our schools as autism friendly; hence, this would be a good opportunity to improve children's schooling experience (Participant 2: Head of School).

Participants' views regarding how quiet spaces may be designed were discussed during the interview.

The school may have a withdrawal room for students struggling to stay in class. If a classroom activity is too loud and disturbing, the child may be allowed to leave and carry out work in the withdrawal room (Participant 1: LSE).

According to Participant 4, quiet rooms should be designed as follows:

I would say that maybe there could be a little bit of a quiet place in the school library, with a sofa, maybe with a computer (Participant 4: Teacher).

Contrastingly, one Participant argued that quiet spaces should not necessarily be set up outside the classroom. This participant outlined the following:

You could make an area...a quiet area in the classroom where the child can retreat whenever he feels the need to do so. I disagree that the child leaves the classroom (Participant 3: LSE).

A related view was shared by Participant 5, who agreed that quiet spaces should be created in the classroom.

I prefer an area in the classroom. I disagree with the quiet room outside the class because students are often taken there, and it looks like a playroom rather than a pull-out or quiet room. Children look at it as a source of free time rather than doing one-to-one sessions with LSEs or trying to calm down (Participant 5: Head of Department).

Support from external service providers: With regard to external opportunities having the potential to improve provision, questionnaire respondents outlined support from service providers such as the Autism Spectrum Support Team (ASST), Speech and Language Therapists, and Psychologists as part of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism. Table 12 illustrates a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
	Services offered by NSSS, such as psychological services
	Support from other professional people like ASST
25	Working with different professionals is very important. I think that speech therapists may help us
27	Service by support staff can be an opportunity for development if used well. ASST helps us when we need support. But we also need psychologists to be available
49	Professional staff, such as persons who know about autism, may offer their expertise, help and support all staff members. E.g., Speech therapist, autism support.

Table 12: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Support from External Service Providers

Two interviewees mentioned that support from external service providers might be quite helpful in implementing better strategies. An LSE participant commented as follows:

Services like ASST, speech therapy, and the help of psychologists are fundamental. It is imperative that everyone pulls the same rope and works together. LSEs must take on board recommendations provided by autism specialists. They could help with strategies and suggestions about resources. I have never seen psychologists intervene in schools ... at least with students with autism. I think the service is understaffed, and since they

receive many referrals for assessments, they have no time to carry out interventions with children (Participant 3: LSE).

There are dedicated people whose expertise is how to include these learners and give us strategies to address their needs. I always try and follow what the child's speech therapist suggests. The child has regular sessions, and I continue to implement the recommendations of what was carried out in the clinic. This helps me overcome some of the challenges I may encounter during the support process. However, I wish that psychologists could also help us in intervention and not only in carrying out assessments and providing reports (Participant 1: LSE).

4.1.4 Threats to the teaching and learning process

Unclear perspectives on Inclusion: As illustrated in Figure 32, some participants indicated that differing perspectives about inclusive education could threaten the teaching and learning process for learners with autism. Table 13 illustrates a sample of their responses.

Figure 32: Threats to the Teaching and Learning Process

Participant Number	Response
8	There is not a clear picture of inclusion
12	Some educators think that inclusion is that all children are equal
17	Teachers lack knowledge on inclusion
33	The lack of awareness of inclusion
43	When you go higher up the chain (teachers or SLT) they might not be comfortable with the changes needed as they are not aware of what inclusion really is

Table 13: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Unclear Perspectives on Inclusion

Interview participants also had similar views when asked about their perspectives on this threat. One participant outlined that although progress has been noted

regarding schools having an inclusive attitude towards learners with autism, they feel that this is not always the case:

Although we are moving towards inclusion, I cannot say that all educators have instilled this attitude. Everyone needs to be on the same wavelength. For me, inclusion has all children in the same classroom. The LSE will provide support where needed (Participant 4: Teacher).

Lack of knowledge on policy content and implementation: A threat that questionnaire participants in this research brought forward as one which may be threatening the teaching and learning process is the issue of not having clear ideas of what policies entail. Table 14 illustrates a sample of their responses. Specifically, when asked about this threat, interview participants discussed that despite having heard about the development of an Inclusion Policy (MEYR, 2022a), they have no idea of what this entails or how this should be implemented. When asked to elaborate on the latter, interviewees had the following perspectives:

I know that there is an inclusion policy which will soon be in place. But it is unclear how this should be implemented at school, so educators may delay the change (for the better) when supporting children. I still need guidance on its content and how to guide my staff (Participant 2: Head of School).

I am unsure of my role as I have not yet been given information about it
 (Participant 3: LSE).

Participant Number	Response
1	I need a clear view of policies. I see this as a threat
19	Policies are not clear on how to support students with autism
34	Lack of practical strategies implemented in the classroom as policy is not explained to us
33	Lack of awareness of policy
52	Maybe lack of clear policies

Table 14: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Lack of Knowledge of Policy

The findings in this section suggest that the development of adaptations of instructions, the extent of support of external service providers, the availability of resources and the importance (or lack of) that autism is given during teacher preparatory courses all affect the provision for learners with autism. Together, these findings provide salient insights into the SWOTs that influence the teaching and learning of children with autism within primary schools in Malta. The following

section shall move on to discuss the SWOTs, which are located within the process of training for educators.

4.2 Training for Educators

The following section shall present the findings brought forward by participants in this study regarding training on autism. Through the data gathered from the questionnaire and the interviews, this study attempted to answer the following research question:

Which are the SWOTs within training for educators who support learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

As noted in Table 15, several SWOTs were indicated as prevailing throughout the training process on autism for educators. During the second data collection phase, interviewees were asked to suggest reasons behind the SWOTs identified by the questionnaire participants. This explanatory phase enabled this researcher to gather an in-depth perspective on each identified SWOT related to training.

<p><i>Strengths within the training process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Training involves opportunities to share good practices among colleagues	<p><i>Weaknesses within the training process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">➤ Training sessions are based on theory rather than practical strategies
---	--

▶ User-friendly strategies	▶ Training is provided after being appointed
<p>Opportunities within the training process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Asking educators what training should entail ▶ Providing more opportunities for training to all educational stakeholders during school hours ▶ Training provided by specialised trainers 	<p>Threats within the training process</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Teacher preparatory courses lack substantial content on autism ▶ Lack of training could lead to the implementation of non-inclusive practices ▶ Participation in training is voluntary, not mandatory

Table 15: The SWOTS of the Training Process

4.2.1 Strengths of the training process

Sharing of good practice with colleagues: Questionnaire respondents who participated in this study reported that, on occasions, training enabled them to share their good practice with colleagues (Figure 33). Table 16 illustrates a sample of their responses.

Figure 33: Strengths of the Training Process

Participant Number	Response
	I was able to listen to colleagues give their views on strategies they carried out in the class
15	I have acquired knowledge of new strategies as the SLT lets us discuss amongst us what works best with students in the class
21	Sharing of good practice
23	Opportunities to ask questions and discuss what works for us educators in the class
47	We could share our ideas and concerns

Table 16: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Sharing of Strategies

When asked to suggest reasons behind the involvement of educators during training sessions, an interviewee outlined that the time allowance to share good practices was one of the strengths of the training sessions she attended. Sharing good practices made her feel more confident in helping her staff when they sought her advice.

I received training from the NAS. It was very informative. During the three-day sessions, we had a lot of time to share good practices. I think this was one of the benefits of this training as I was more confident when

recommending strategies to other educators when they sought my help
 (Participant 5: Head of Department).

User-friendly strategies: Questionnaire participants stated that the sessions they attended included some less complicated and user-friendly strategies, which indicates another strength related to the training process. Table 17 illustrates a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
3	Ease of implementation
10	User-friendly techniques
14	I think that the strategies shared were easy to implement in the class
29	The experiences the trainer described on certain situations she dealt with whilst working with children on the Autism Spectrum were fruitful. The fact that she shared these strategies felt that these are not impossible to implement in the class
33	The strengths are that training sometimes builds on autism friendly practices and on the understanding that all children are different

Table 17: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: User-Friendly Strategies

When discussing this strength, Participants 1 and 3 reported the following:

I received training on autism linked to the characteristics of children with autism, such as them not responding well to change. I tried the visual schedule, suggested during training with the child I supported back then. It was easy to prepare and to present to the child. The student could transition from one task to another quite calmly (Participant 1: LSE).

I had training on autism, and most of what the trainer shared were strategies that I had already used and which I believe are basic and easy...for instance, all children with autism need to have a visual schedule...the trainer told us about it...it is easy to implement...or for example the buddy system...this was suggested in training I underwent. It is a straightforward strategy that helped the student I supported to enhance his social skills (Participant 3: LSE).

4.2.2 Weaknesses of the training process

Theoretical training: As illustrated in Figure 34, when participants were asked to outline the SWOTs located within the training process on autism, questionnaire respondents indicated that one that is limiting schools from performing at their optimum level is the fact that training for educators on autism is more focused on the theoretical, rather than the practical viewpoint of such strategies. Table 18 illustrates a sample of their responses.

Figure 34: Weaknesses of the Training Process

Participant Number	Response
	Too much talking about things that were not practical by the lecturer. Lost interest after some time
11	Theory dominated the session
28	Some training is repetitive and gives no strategies which I can use in the classroom
30	I am fed up with having training on the same things which are too theoretical
52	Repetitive information on the triad of impairments. No strategies

Table 18: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Theoretical Training

The interviewees also confirmed the abovementioned concerns. Participant 4 shared the following:

I think there are a lot of issues to deal with, which, unfortunately, educators do not know how to address or implement strategies in the class. We listen to many lectures and a lot of theory, but session providers do not show these strategies in practice. We do not have training before we are given the job (Participant 4: Teacher).

Participant 3 also echoed the views of questionnaire respondents, indicating that practical recommendations are lacking in the training sessions, which leaves this participant concerned about being unable to implement what is being presented:

Sessions are mainly based on providing theories of autism rather than on how to be practical in the classroom. At least the sessions I attended were more theoretical. I feel quite concerned as it is difficult to implement what is presented in practice, especially if this is not demonstrated (Participant 3: LSE).

Training after appointment: Another factor brought forward by questionnaire participants as an impediment for schools to perform at an optimum level in providing quality support was that most training sessions are based on a ‘touch-and-go’ method once they have joined the educator force. Indeed, some questionnaire respondents outlined that sessions are provided after becoming

educators, are short, and do not involve follow-up sessions. Table 19 illustrates a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
	I think that this should have been provided before I was sent to the classroom
	The fact that I got training after becoming an LSE was not the ideal situation for me
27	Two hours of training on autism after being recruited in the class is not enough. There is much more to discuss
42	I was trained after two years of becoming an LSE
50	I was not given PD before I had students with autism. I had to learn through experience. It is not fair to me or the student

Table 19: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Training After Appointment

When asked about the latter, one participant reported that lack of opportunities for ongoing training on autism often leads her to try strategies through 'trial and error', which tends to increase a sense of uncertainty throughout her practice:

I know that autism is a very complex condition and there is a lot that one should know, but we are always given, you know... that touch-and-go

method ...no follow-up sessions as there is no time. Most of the time, I learn from my classroom experience rather than from training...sort of a trial-and-error approach. I did not get any training before I was appointed as an LSE. It makes me feel uncomfortable and anxious when I do not know what to do or expect from students (Participant 1: LSE).

4.2.3 Opportunities to the training process

Asking educators what training should involve: As illustrated in Figure 35, questionnaire participants outlined that an advantage to the school, whilst supporting learners with autism, is for training organisers to ask educators what they would like training to involve. Table 20 provides a sample of their responses. Figure 36 further outlines the area of training that the educator participants are interested in pursuing.

Figure 35: Opportunities to the Training Process

Participant Number	Response
16	Ask educators directly what they would like to learn about
21	Provide what educators want to be trained on
44	More consideration on what LSEs need
49	Training that acknowledges what teachers and LSEs require to support learners with autism
52	SLT recognizes the importance of Professional Development on what staff needs and that this is highly promoted

Table 20: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Recognising Educators' Training Needs

When explaining the opportunity outlined by questionnaire participants in terms of asking educators what training should involve, one interviewee emphasised that this should be an opportunity implemented in every school, as it is an effective means to get participants more involved during sessions:

When administrators asked about their training needs, I think their involvement was more positive. For instance, when we asked LSEs directly what training they wanted in one of my schools, we felt that the training was more successful. I observed that they felt more involved in it. I think this could

increase the possibility of improving support (Participant 5: Head of Department).

A teacher participant outlined that if the SLT had to ask about what training she would like to pursue, it would be an opportunity for her to seek areas that may help her acquire the necessary skills to support learners with autism.

Figure 36: Training Interest

Another idea that could support change in training and eventually improve the provision for learners with autism, is having more training during school hours. Participant 2 argued that if she had to be given that chance to organise training on autism in the school she manages, the following would be perceived as an advantage which could potentially involve all educational stakeholders in the school.

I think an opportunity for training would be to use the Community of Professional Educators (CoPE) sessions we have allocated from the Department, take some hours from these and do training specifically on autism. These are done during school hours; hence, they would become mandatory for all. When I say everyone, i.e. the LSEs, the teachers, SLT. ... everyone (Participant 2: Head of School).

Training by specialised trainers: Another opportunity reported by respondents perceived as an idea supporting change was related to having more training by specialist trainers on creating awareness of autism. Table 21 provides a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
	Opportunities where all staff are provided with up-to-date knowledge about autism. Autism specialists may help with this
13	Bringing specialized persons to talk about students with autism.

- 23 To bring speakers who can relate their experiences on how to support children with autism
- 24 HoD in inclusion and ASST specialists can provide sessions
- 33 I think occasionally, SLT should invite a speaker who is a professional in autism studies

Table 21: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Training by Specialised Trainers

When discussing this opportunity, interview Participant 4 outlined that training sessions on creating more awareness of autism could benefit all educators, as this would allow them to better address the needs of learners with autism:

Some students with autism have many challenging behaviours because I think the appropriate strategies are not in place. Everyone needs to know why behaviour occurs, why children with autism need structure etc...So I think more sessions on creating awareness of the condition by specialists are necessary. Teach us about strategies and the difficulties children with autism have, and better strategies will be implemented (Participant 4: Teacher).

Questionnaire respondents also indicated that specialised trainers on autism could also support educators on how they are expected to address challenging behaviour.

More specialised trainers should show us how to deal with challenging behaviour. For example, I want trainers to show me how to tackle the instances where, for example, the child becomes aggressive towards peers or teachers ... I know this will improve how I support the student. I think that such trainers have the most updated techniques. So, I think these should be the ones to offer school sessions (Participant 1: LSE).

Participant 1 added that specialised trainers should provide such training and involve all stakeholders to promote collaboration.

I wish people specialising in the field would provide training on more autism awareness that includes parents, teachers, and LSEs in one session. Like this, we would all benefit from each other's experience and enhance collaboration (Participant 1: LSE).

4.2.4 Threats to the training process

Teacher courses do not prioritise training on autism: As illustrated in Figure 37, one of the threats mentioned by questionnaire respondents, which may potentially harm the school's ability to support learners, was that autism is not prioritised as a topic of importance in courses for teachers. Figure 38 also illustrates the training undertaken by the educators who participated in the questionnaire, while Table 22 provides a sample of their responses.

Figure 37: Threats to Training for Educators

Figure 38: Respondents who Attended Training in the Area of Autism

Participant Number	Response
4	Teaching courses do not focus on autism
11	Pre-service teaching courses do not focus on training on autism
14	B.Ed course does not address autism
43	Not all teachers are prepared, as training is not provided in teaching courses
48	Lack of training for teachers before being appointed

Table 22: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Teacher courses do not prioritise training on autism

When asked for their perspective on the matter, a common view was also put forward by interviewees. All participants agreed that the lack of training opportunities on autism for teachers is a threat that places potential risks on the quality of training on autism and the quality of the child's educational development. A teacher participant confirmed that such training is not included in teacher preparatory courses.

I think that training for teachers on inclusive education is very much about human rights and multiculturalism ... but I do not think there is training on autism ... or at least this is not enough for us to be prepared for what we may encounter in the class. Teachers do not have enough training. Teachers are

unaware that students with autism need structure, a routine, and visuals and that any change is difficult for them to handle. At least I did not get this training from University (Participant 4: Teacher).

Another participant agreed with the latter and put forward the following suggestion hence indicating the lack of training for teachers in teacher preparatory courses.

Training on addressing the needs of children with autism should start where they teach the teachers...it should start there (Participant 2: Head of School).

A parallel view was outlined by Participant 1, who noted that although training on autism is provided to LSEs in undergraduate courses, this does not seem to be provided to class teachers.

Teachers are not trained. They do not know what is best for a child with autism because they are not given the appropriate training. It is not because they do not want to, but the structure of their education at university is like that. They do not teach them, for instance, how to adapt the curriculum for students with autism So, they are not given training about specific things...it is more general training on the disabilities they might encounter, but not specifically on the strategies that work (Participant 1: LSE).

When the findings concerning the attendance on training on autism by members of the SLT depicted in Figure 38 were forwarded to the Head of School involved in

these interviews, she confirmed these findings. This Head of School reported that she was never involved in training sessions that addressed autism, further placing this as a threat slowing schools down from performing effectively.

Exclusionary practices: Whilst conceding the fact that teacher preparatory courses lack training on how to address the needs of learners with autism, questionnaire participants indicated that lack of training might lead to practices which may exclude rather than include learners with autism. Table 23 provides a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
	Lack of training leads to labelling these children and thus being less accepting to include these children in the classroom
	Certain staff members will not want to go that extra step to include students with autism
12	When educators do not feel competent enough, they may not provide suitable resources and strategies due to a lack of training
23	I think that teachers and administrators are not trained, and this causes a lot of friction between them and LSEs. This impacts the inclusion of learners with autism
25	The lack of information or misinformation about certain issues leads to a rigid attitude from certain staff members.

Table 23: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Exclusionary Practices

When discussing the aforementioned findings, interview Participant 1 argued that in the case of not having the appropriate training to address a certain issue that occurs in the class, teachers might ask LSEs to take the child out of the classroom:

Teachers might tell you to take the child out of class during a tantrum so that he will calm down, but that may not necessarily be the solution (Participant 1: LSE).

The perspective above was also corroborated by Participant 3, who argued that if a teacher cannot manage a tantrum or a meltdown appropriately, this will impact the child's reaction to her action:

I know because teachers ask us LSEs many things such as 'Why is the child behaving like this?' or 'Why are you using this resource?' Sometimes teachers do not understand you, especially when you are developing a strategy that requires their collaboration. For instance, the teacher needs to know how to act when a child throws a tantrum or has a meltdown. Of course, if not handled correctly, this will have negative consequences on the child (Participant 3: LSE).

This current threat was further corroborated by Participant 4, who argued that teachers are often not invited to attend training, leaving teachers uninformed about how to support learners with autism in the classroom:

There was training about autism, and only LSEs were invited to this training. Most teachers have no idea about the importance of structure, routine, about, you know ... the basics. Because then a child is in the class, and if the teacher does not have structure, it's very difficult for LSE and the child to cope (Participant 4: Teacher).

Training is voluntary: Another threat indicated by questionnaire respondents was that participation in training sessions on autism tends to be voluntary. Furthermore, several questionnaire respondents indicated that staffs lack of interest in applying for voluntary training sessions on autism leads to a low turnout. A further threat indicated by questionnaire participants that affects training attendance was that educators have minimal time to attend courses, particularly if these are held outside school hours. Table 24 provides a sample of their responses.

	Response
	Not enough time to attend training during school hours
	Certain staff members will not want to go that extra step to include students with autism
21	Lack of training as this is not given in an obligatory way
22	Why do educators have to choose if they attend training or not?

Table 24: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Voluntary Training

Commenting on time and lack of attendance, interview Participant 3 implied that some educators have other commitments after school hours.

Undergoing voluntary courses is done on the educators' own time. Due to other commitments, teachers and LSEs may not have time to pursue this after school hours. However, I do apply for voluntary sessions in my own free time. No one imposes my attendance. I attend these talks or sessions to do my best for the children I support. But I do not think most educators seek after-school training (Participant 3: LSE).

I have an issue with attending training after school hours. I need that time to prepare lesson content and resources ...we do not get remunerated for attending courses after school hours. I prefer if these are held during school hours...to be honest, our school never organised training on autism during school hours (Participant 4: Teacher).

4.3 The Home-School Collaboration Process

The intended data collection phase coincided with an unprecedented national lockdown following a substantial rise in the cases of COVID-19. This national lockdown made it difficult for me as the researcher to approach parents of students

with autism, particularly by gaining access from schools, social media, and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs). Notwithstanding this significant limitation in terms of involving parents as part of the research sample, the following section shall present the findings brought forward from participants' perspectives on Home-School Collaboration. Through the information put forward by questionnaire respondents and through the data gathered from interviews, this research addressed the following research question:

Which are the SWOTs within the home-school collaboration process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

During the interviews, the participants were asked questions related to the SWOTs that the participants in the questionnaire identified. This inquiry process allowed this research to gather an explanatory perspective of each identified SWOT. As noted in Table 25, when responding to the questionnaire, the participants identified several SWOTs located amid the collaboration process with parents.

<p><i>Strengths within the collaboration process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sharing of techniques and resources with parents ➤ Parents providing valuable information about their child to the school ➤ Open communication channels between the school and parents 	<p><i>Weaknesses within the collaboration process</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Under involved parents ➤ Some parents may be in denial of their child's condition
--	---

Opportunities within the collaboration process	Threats within the collaboration process
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Parent education on autism ▶ Schools being sensitive to the needs of parents ▶ Further opportunities to meet with parents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Education not being a priority for some parents ▶ Parents' psychological well being

Table 25: The SWOTS of the Home-School Collaboration Process

4.3.1 Strengths of the home-school collaboration process

Frequent and open communication: As illustrated in Figure 39, questionnaire participants outlined three main strengths of the home-school collaboration process. One strength currently present within the provision for learners with autism is that most schools have frequent and open communication channels with the parents. Table 26 provides a sample of their responses.

Figure 39: Strengths of the Home-School Collaboration Process

Participant Number	Response
1	Good communication with parents
2	Open, continuous and honest communication with parents
5	Parents are informed daily about their children's progress through the communication book
17	Communication and continuous feedback between LSE and parents
26	Regular meetings when needs arise - we do not wait for IEP meetings. If the need arises, we address it immediately

Table 26: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Open and Frequent Communication

As illustrated in Figure 40, when asked about the means used by educators to collaborate with parents of students with autism, the use of the communication diary ($n = 44$) and face-to-face meetings ($n = 39$) dominated the responses of the educators ($n = 53$) who completed the questionnaire. To a lesser extent, some participants also listed emails ($n = 9$) and telephone calls ($n = 7$) to communicate with parents. Very few educators also indicated using social media ($n = 6$) as a source of home-school collaboration.

Figure 40: The Means Used to Communicate with Parents

During the follow-up phase based on interviews, participants ($n = 5$) were asked why they think the aforementioned were means used by educators to collaborate with parents of students with autism. Most educators outlined the following as sources that enable frequent and open communication:

I use the communication diary and have always used it throughout my profession. It was always suggested as the way how we communicate with parents. I honestly do not mind using it as sometimes it is the only communication channel with parents (Participant 3: LSE).

LSEs use the communication diary. They write down the daily events...the child's behaviour...how the day went. You have children with autism who are non-verbal or struggle to express themselves. Therefore, informing the parents of what happened during the day decreases tension (Participant 2: Head of School).

Sometimes you have parents you meet almost daily during pick up and drop off. I enjoy meeting the parent personally rather than writing down how the day went in the communication book. Because when you write down certain things, they may be interpreted differently than when you provide a verbal explanation. I get immediate feedback from parents, and the parents get immediate feedback from me. They feel better when conversing, especially if something about the child worries them (Participant 3: LSE).

Not all parents know how to use email. So I use emails with those parents who communicate with me by email (Participant 2: Head of School).

Telephone calls were justified as a better source to communicate with parents who may be illiterate both in reading and writing abilities and digitally:

I believe the school needs to be open and flexible and use other means of communication convenient for the parents. I use phone calls with parents who are not computer literate or do not know how to read and write. Moreover, one may also see phone calls as a means of providing prompt feedback (Participant 2: Head of School).

When interviewees were asked about the use of social media, four out of five of them outlined that they do not use such means to collaborate with parents. However, one participant outlined using Messenger® as a source of home-school collaboration. This participant acknowledged that this was done despite the Education Department in Malta not recommending such means:

I know we should not use social media as it is not an official communication means of the Ministry, but I use it most of the time because certain parents find it more convenient.../ use it there and then. For example, I just finished the activity with the child, I took a photo of this and sent it to the parents. It is just a few seconds, but that would mean much to the parents. It is prompt.. .parents appreciate the promptness. So yes, I do use it. I think that this is beneficial for the kids. The children feel happy when I tell them I will send their parents photos (Participant 1: LSE).

Sharing strategies with parents: Another strength indicated by questionnaire participants was related to having the possibility to share techniques and resources with parents. Table 27 provides a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
11	Educators work with parents using shared resources and adapted work to help the children feel more comfortable

15	To share with parents the same procedures that the LSE does at school
31	We share strategies with parents so they can scaffold what is done at school also at home
38	Sharing ideas and resources with parents to promote the continuation of work at home
52	Good relationship and sharing of ideas with parents

Table 27: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Sharing Strategies with Parents

When discussing the strengths above, one interviewee outlined that parents of children with autism appreciate the school's feedback, which is a strength of the home-school collaboration process. Interviewees outlined that their school believes in promptly informing parents about the progress made by children, particularly since children with autism may find it difficult to provide such feedback to their parents themselves:

Especially for non-verbal children, a parent should know the child's progress regularly. I am uncomfortable discussing the child's progress only once during Parents' Day and Evening. If the child did well during the school day, I either write in the communication copybook or email them how I feel about the child's performance during that activity. The parents should immediately know and not wait for Parents' Day (Participant 1 LSE)

Similarly, Participant 2 outlined the following:

I might be wrong on this.... A child with autism might not go home and give feedback. But this could be the case because of their communication difficulties. Promptly informing the parents about their child's progress, especially when the child has reached certain milestones, is very important. It removes any uncertainties they may have (Participant 2: Head of School).

Comparably, Participant 5 argued as follows:

During the IEP meetings I have with parents in my schools, I always emphasise that it is important that if they come across any problem during the year, they should come forward, set up a meeting and discuss any issues (Participant 5: Head of Department).

I think continuing behavioural techniques is critical so everyone uses the same approach with the child. It helps the child consolidate behaviour skills (Participant 3: LSE). It also helps me collaborate with parents and share the techniques I use with them. In that way, you will be helping the student and the parents to continue using the strategies at home.

Parents sharing information with educators: Another strength indicated by questionnaire participants was related to having parents share information about the student them. Table 28 provides a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
1	<p>Parents feel comfortable discussing their children's concerns</p> <p>Parents give a clear picture of their child's abilities/limitations</p> <p>Parents suggest better alternatives for their son/daughter</p>
20	<p>Listen to parents as much as possible</p>
41	<p>Parents are an important asset as they know the child very well</p>

Table 28: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Parents Sharing Information

When commenting on the rationale behind the current schools' strength on having parents sharing information with educators, one questionnaire respondent outlined that in her practice, parents are always a critical source for her to get to know the child better:

You cannot get a resource better than this [referring to parents]. The parents inform me about their background, the child's knowledge, what may annoy them, and what he enjoys doing. These things are very important and have helped me better support the child (Participant 1: LSE).

4.3.2 Weaknesses of the home-school collaboration process

Under-involved parents: As illustrated in Figure 41, questionnaire participants in this research highlighted that one of the weaknesses perceived as a current limitation hindering the home-school collaboration of children with autism is the under-involvement of parents. Table 29 provides a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
1	Some parents feel that as long as there is the LSE, they do not need to worry about their children's education anymore
15	Some parents do not access the ilearn virtual classroom
29	Lack of interest in some parents
30	Not every parent responds when we call her to come for meetings
31	Parents do not communicate back most of the time

Table 29: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Under-Involved Parents

When discussing this weakness, an LSE participant outlined the following:

I have met parents who do not even bother to come to Parents' Day. They just missed the appointment, and when we called them, they said they did

not have time to attend these meetings. I fear little progress is seen when this happens, as parents will not know what is happening at school (Participant 3: LSE).

Figure 41: Weaknesses of the Home-School Collaboration Process

Another participant had similar views to the abovementioned, reporting that parental involvement impacted the progress of learners with autism:

I have parents who do not involve themselves. For instance, I send them messages in the communication book, and they do not even send a reply. You would tell they do not want to involve themselves and see collaboration as an 'extra' responsibility (Participant 1: LSE).

Denial: Some participants outlined that having several parents who may be in denial to the extent that they are at a loss of how to help their children is slowing the school down in performing effectively when providing support. Table 30 provides a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
	A few parents are in denia
	They still don't accept their child's learning difficulty
17	Sometimes parents are in denial and have unrealistic expectations
25	Some parents are still in denial, especially when it comes to the type of work assigned
47	Parents are sometimes in denial and do not cooperate with teachers and LSE. They still expect that homework is done just like other peers

Table 30: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Parents in Denial

Denial as a weakness to the home-school collaboration process was also elaborated upon by interview participants who argued on denial as follows:

Some parents are in denial and cannot continue and help their children
(Participant 4: Teacher).

Another participant argued that when parents deny their child's condition, progress takes longer to be observed:

We have cases of parents who are in denial, and to be honest, I see that their children take longer to reach certain milestones. I know it is not easy for parents to accept their child's diagnosis. I mean...I will not judge them because I am a mother, and it is difficult. However, things are seen more positively when you accept the situation. So denial is an issue (Participant 2: Head of School).

Further to this, Participant 2 also argued the following:

It is unfortunate when parents do not accept the situation because the children are the ones who suffer as the school will not be able to provide the services to the full (Participant 2: Head of School).

4.3.3 Opportunities to the home-school collaboration process

Opportunities for more frequent meetings: As illustrated in Figure 42, an external factor that could give the school an advantage whilst supporting learners, and was identified by questionnaire participants, was the creation of opportunities for more frequent meetings between parents and educators. Table 31 provides a sample of

their responses. When asked to justify such an external factor, one interview participant argued that such frequent meetings need to be an incentive created by the school, whilst another participant outlined that this would give further opportunities to parents to forward any queries, concerns or ideas they might have.

Figure 42: Opportunities to the Home-School Collaboration Process

Participant Number	Response
1	We could have more meetings with the parents to discuss difficulties as a whole school/individual cases

12	More meetings with parents so that educators and parents work hand in hand
19	Regular meetings of support and communication for parents
21	More time at our disposal for meetings because, unfortunately, meetings are timed due to the overloaded schedule that we have to juggle throughout the day at school
47	More regular meetings with parents when necessary

Table 31: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Opportunities for Frequent Meetings

Being sensitive towards parents: Questionnaire respondents outlined that as part of the opportunities for the home-school collaboration process, schools should ensure empathy towards parents of learners with autism. Table 32 provides a sample of their responses.

Participant Number	Response
10	Empathising further
13	To keep the existing collaboration strong between staff and parents means that staff needs to listen to parents and see how support may be provided
28	Sometimes educators are not always sensitive to the needs of parents. Maybe if they are more understanding, this will help in creating more collaboration

38	Have educators who listen to the needs of parents. It is not always easy to be a parent of a child with autism
49	Parents go through a lot. Therefore I think that we should empathise further

Table 32: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Being Sensitive Towards Parents

When asked to elaborate on this opportunity, Participant 2 argued that having staff, including members of the SLT, being sensitive about how to approach parents serves as an opportunity to increase the possibilities to improve provision.

Being careful of how my staff, especially the SLT, communicates with the parents could be an advantage in my school. As you know, these parents need someone sensitive to their situation. In this sense, you have to bring them on board and not let them reject you (Participant 2: Head of School).

Parent education sessions: Training opportunities for parents have also been identified as an external factor that could potentially increase opportunities for collaboration with parents whose children are diagnosed with autism. Table 33 provides a sample of the responses brought forward by questionnaire participants.

Participant Number	Response
9	Organise training sessions mostly for parents in need

14	Provide sessions where parents may learn on how to support their children at home
34	Local training for parents
41	The school may organise some training for parents
47	Development sessions for parents as well

Table 33: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Parent Education Sessions

When discussing the aforementioned opportunity, interview Participant 2 shared the following perspectives:

I think providing training to parents of children with autism would be a very good idea. I believe that training should not stop with us educators. Parents are critical stakeholders in the education of their children. And yes, I would find no problem encouraging parents or organising training. This training will help them be more aware of the condition, particularly if they have just discovered it (Participant 2: Head of School).

Another participant argued that parent sessions that could potentially improve collaboration is having parents being more informed about the condition. According to these participants, this would help them feel reassured about what they are doing 'right' and what they may improve when bringing up their child. This participant

further outlined that the feeling of reassurance through being more knowledgeable as a parent would reduce anxiety and tension and enhance collaboration with the school.

4.3.4. Threats to the home-school collaboration process

Education is not a priority for some parents: As illustrated in Figure 43, one threat that questionnaire respondents indicated as potentially placing home-school collaboration at risk was not having parents place their children's education first. Table 34 provides a sample of the responses brought forward by questionnaire participants.

Figure 43: Threats to the Home-School Collaboration Process

Participant Number	Response
3	Parents who show little interest in terms of schooling
6	Parents (few of them) who are reluctant to continue/consolidate work done at school at home
17	Parents' jobs and other commitments taking over the education of children
31	Parents feel that the school is a babysitting service and that learning for these students stops once the school day is over
40	Parents consider education not a priority

Table 34: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Education not a Priority for Some Parents

When interview participants were asked about the matter, interviewees had the following views:

I am noticing that some parents put the responsibility on the school ... mostly on the LSEs and teachers. I have seen this...not all [parents)...so not to generalise ...but some do. They do not give education a priority (Participant 4: Teacher).

I am frustrated when parents do not respond to my efforts to inform them of classroom activities and everyday events. What upsets me most is that they do not follow through with the work I inform them about...what does this

mean? As an LSE, I am expected to take all the responsibility for the child's education. I see this as unfair as it is their child at the end of the day. I am just his educator (Participant 1: LSE).

Parents' psychological wellbeing: Another external threat outlined by questionnaire respondents was related to having parents encountering psychological stress. Table 35 provides a sample of the responses brought forward by questionnaire participants.

Participant Number	Response
21	Whenever there are other underlying issues such as mental health issues, collaboration is more difficult to be established
23	Sometimes parents are depressed as they cannot cope with the needs of their children
42	Some parents may have need support in terms of their mental health
45	Psychologically parents may need support, especially if they have more than one child with autism
52	Some students come from difficult backgrounds, so parents do not always collaborate with the school. I think that psychologically, some parents need support

Table 35: Responses indicated by questionnaire participants: Parents' Psychological Wellbeing

One interview participant provided the following views on such a threat:

We have children with autism whose parents, for example, have issues with their mental health. In such cases, the parents also need help, as the last thing they have on their minds is coming to meetings with teachers and LSEs. Schools will not expect the extent of collaboration to be the same as those parents who do not have these challenges (Participant 5: Head of Department).

Another participant argued that a factor that could potentially harm the school's ability to support learners is having parents going through challenges related to their mental well-being. They tend to lack the energy to address the needs of their children, including collaborating with the school:

Some parents going through a psychological crisis do not always have the energy to collaborate with the school. I have had a parent who, despite me providing her suggestions of how to address tantrums to be on the same page with the school, was coming to me telling me stories of how depressed she is. She was then letting her son get what he wanted and giving in. I felt this affected collaboration as we were not on the same page (Participant 4: Teacher).

These findings suggest that the means educators use to collaborate with parents, the use of collaboration to regularly inform parents about the child's progress, and

the opportunity to involve parents to share their experiences with others on autism provide insights into the SWOTs on the collaborative process with parents.

This chapter has presented the views of educators working in schools in Malta on the SWOTs located in the teaching and learning process, within the training process for educators and within the home-school collaboration process. The following chapter shall provide a discussion of the current study's findings concerning the review of literature presented in Chapter 2. This discussion will allow for an interpretation of findings following the data collected in the current research compared to the international literature on the three areas.

Chapter 5: Discussion

Following the data collected from questionnaires and interviews with educators who all carry out duties in primary mainstream schools in Malta, this Chapter will interpret and explain the research findings as per the previous chapter's findings. It will also discuss how these findings relate to the literature reviewed in Chapter 2.

5.1 The Interpretation of Findings

Several social scientists and educationalists have examined and analysed data through the lens of the Ecological Systems Framework. Such a lens is “an effective conceptual guide for intervention to support individuals in need because it provides a broad and deep understanding of their environment and how environmental developments influence their growth and development” (Gonzales, 2020, p.35). Given that Ecological Systems have an impact on a child's development and level of inclusion in school, as discussed in Sections 1.2 and 2.1, the lines of interpretation of this research's findings have been centred on Urie Bronfenbrenner's (1979) Ecological Systems Theory, and its reconceptualisation focusing on inclusive education by Anderson, Boyle, and Deppeler (2014). Therefore, both theories have enabled this research to interpret the SWOTs in: i) teaching and learning, ii) training for educators; iii) home-school collaboration.

As outlined in Chapters 1, 2, and 3 of this research study, this analysis took place through a SWOT analysis tool. As mentioned in previous chapters, although a SWOT analysis is typically carried out in companies and firms to investigate their

competitive impact within the marketplace to develop future concepts, this analysis structure could also be usefully applied to inform practice within educational settings (Sciberras, 2019). Yet, despite its usefulness, this kind of analysis has never been implemented to identify the various school impacts which may influence the provision for learners with autism. This gap has been identified both in primary schools in Malta and also within international contexts. Indeed, scholarly material on the SWOTs located within the teaching and learning process, training for educators, and home-school collaboration concerning autism are limited. Therefore, to fill the existing gap, the current mixed-method study aimed to explore the existing SWOTs within the three areas.

5.2 The Teaching and Learning Process

Which are the SWOTs within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Although educators are increasingly likely to have one or more learners with autism in their classroom (Clark *et al.*, 2020; European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2014), there is a lack of research on how support within schools in Malta transpires. Thus, one of the study's objectives was to identify the SWOTs within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism who attend primary schools in Malta from the educators' perspectives. Several SWOTs have been identified, as outlined in Chapter 4, with the following sections attempting to interpret these findings.

5.2.1 Strengths of the teaching and learning process

Adaptations of instructions: As outlined in Sections 1.2 and 2.1, within the interconnected systems proposed by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), the quality of curriculum and pedagogy have a ripple effect on the participation, achievement, and value of the learner (Figure 4). As noted in Table 36, findings from the current study saw participants outlining that the availability of adaptations of instructions for learners with autism has been acknowledged as a strength of the teaching and learning process. Analogous to what a previous study has concluded (Van der Steen *et al.*, 2020), the current study concluded that adaptations provide learners with autism with the necessary support, mainly if the present content is challenging to understand. These findings further complement the conclusions already emerging from previous studies that also indicated the adaptation of instruction as a facilitator to the teaching and learning process of learners with autism (Clark *et al.*, 2020; Van Der Steen *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019). Such benefits provide a more nuanced understanding that the adaptations made to the content and instructions presented to learners possibly lessen the challenges they may encounter due to a WCC (De Jager and Condy, 2020; de Marchena, Eigsti and Yerys, 2015; Norris, 2020) and lack of EF skills (e.g. Happé, 1999).

Further echoing the conclusions of the Australian and Turkish studies conducted by Clark *et al.* (2020) and Yazici and McKenzie (2019), the findings of the current research indicate that although step-by-step instruction might not be the fastest way to teach skills to learners with autism, it is a strategy which supports adaptations, and which still facilitates comprehension skills. This finding suggests that step-by-

step instruction may be a strategy which could enhance the progress made by learners with autism and help them fulfil their learning potential.

Even though step-by-step instruction is viewed as a strategy facilitating comprehension, this may not be consistently effective. The current findings have particularly noted that such ineffectiveness may emerge from the fact that if the content presented to learners with autism is irrelevant to them, they might not necessarily understand it. Notably, this study saw one educator questioning whether teaching subjects such as 'Religion' (in Maltese state schools, this refers to the Catholic faith) to learners with autism is relevant, mainly since it minimally focuses on the 'skills needed to perform daily activities' (Participant 5). Although this data emerges from the voice of one participating educator, it is still a critical point to consider, mainly since Norris (2022) has observed that when learners with autism are presented with tasks related to abstract knowledge (such as in the case of Religion), these tasks may see learners underperform. Indeed, the more the information presented can be generalised within all contexts, the better the prospects for learners with autism to acquire knowledge and skills, particularly within areas where they manifest difficulties (Jimenez and Stranger, 2017).

Nevertheless, it is imperative to note that given that it is the students' right to follow Religion lessons at school since these are part of the curriculum, schools have a duty to provide adequate programmes for learners with autism. Considering learners' learning styles to teach abstract concepts such as Religion is critical as when taken from the perspective of the Ecology of the Inclusive Education Framework, the way that content is presented would either benefit or jeopardise the

learners' level and quality of participation, achievement, and value, as posited by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014). Thus the level of support must be linked to the student's learning style, allowing room for a better understanding of the presented concepts. On the other hand, it is also imperative to consider whether students with autism want to follow Religion lessons, particularly if they perceive that lesson content is unrelated to life beyond their original learning environment. Nevertheless, the views of students and parents with autism should be sought in regard to this finding since individuals with autism should have equal access to learning content related to religion/spirituality. Indeed, as outlined in Table 36, two salient questions arise following this finding, whereby the views on this matter from parents' and students' perspectives are critical.

The current research findings demonstrate that step-by-step instructions are not the only component incorporated within the adaptation of instruction as part of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism. Even though it is always critical to appraise every learner's learning style when designing classroom instruction (Rissanen *et al.*, 2019; Sasson, Yehuda and Miedijensky, 2021), the data presented in this study has seen visual support as an approach dominating the adaptation of instruction provided to learners with autism (Figure 28). Indeed, the data emerging from the current study, which is in line with existing evidence, suggests that learners with autism tend to have strong visual processing skills (Ayuningtyas *et al.*, 2021; Cooper *et al.*, 2022; Curtin and Long, 2021; Dyer, 2022; Santos, Breda and Almeida, 2017). Current research findings reveal that flashcards, pictures, and written text are some forms of visual support presented to learners

who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta, with educators explaining their benefits in the following section.

During the explanatory phase of this research, participants in this research argued that visual support predominantly emerged as the most frequently incorporated strategy within adaptations because it: i) facilitates the process that enables learners to relate better to the presented situation; ii) allows learners to possibly further retain the presented information; iii) enables learners with autism to be more engaged and have better learning outcomes. The three unfolded reasons behind the use of visual support brought forward by participants have further confirmed the conclusions of the studies of Dijkhuis *et al.* (2020), Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou (2021), Pastor-Cerezuela *et al.* (2020), and Yazici and McKenzie (2019) in terms of visual support being perceived as a strategy benefiting learners with autism. Thus, it may be concluded that visual support has the potential to improve students' performance (Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019) as it enhances comprehension of information when this is presented (Ayuningtyas *et al.*, 2021; Cooper *et al.*, 2022; Dyer, 2022). However, it should be noted that due to this study not including the voice of learners with autism, the perspectives of learners with autism who attend primary schools in Malta may be gathered to establish whether their learning preference aligns with what educators within this study have indicated. This inquiry would shed light on whether visual support is a preferred means of presenting instructional adaptations to learners with autism.

A further form through which educators provide visual support in schools in Malta, thus producing similar evidence to studies conducted in Scotland, Canada, Australia, the U.S., the U.K., and Zimbabwe (Clark *et al.*, 2020; Curtin and Long, 2021; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Tynan and Davy, 2021), is the provision of the visual schedule. When providing a rationale for its use, agreeing with Curtin and Long (2021), Lindsay *et al.* (2014), Majoko (2018) and Tynan and Davy (2021), participants delineated that visual schedules: i) provide structure for learners with autism; ii) help learners with autism identify what activities would follow; iii) enable learners to predict any changes that may happen; iv) reduce frustration and anxiety in learners with autism. All of the aforementioned make learners with autism more confident and prepared to shift from one task to another, lessening the instances where distress may be sensed. This evidence thus continues to confirm the use of visual schedules as a strategy which potentially addresses the challenges encountered by learners with autism in terms of facilitating cognitive flexibility and transitions (Alsaedi, Carrington and Watters, 2020), both linked as aspects impacted by lack of EF skills, ToM and WCC.

Parallel to the evidence above, in terms of visual support as an approach used when developing adaptations of instructions for learners, the findings of this study have demonstrated that tangibles are also frequently incorporated. Educators in the current study outlined that objects such as ball pieces, play dough, sand, blocks, plastic letters, and plastic animals tend to be incorporated as part of the adaptations of instructions to enhance learners' learning and understanding. Such resources were reported to be used in the current study to teach numeracy and literacy to learners with autism. The use of such resources by educators confirms what already

exists in literature in terms of objects being regarded as a complementary strategy which supports the individual needs of learners with autism (Carbonneau, Marley, and Selig, 2013; Goñi-Cervera, Cañadas and Polo-Blanco, 2022; Jimenez and Stranger, 2017; Marley and Carbonneau, 2014; Spooner *et al.*, 2019).

When placing the arguments above within the context of the Ecology of Inclusive Education (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014), the availability of various teaching and learning methods and resources can enhance learner participation, achievement, and value. This interpretation emerges as, at a micro and exo systems level, resources and school support structures have been viewed as critical in impacting learner development (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). A point worth a close observation emerges from the fact that whilst this study demonstrated how tangibles are used to support generalisation skills such as counting, as previously indicated by Jimenez and Stranger (2017) and Goñi-Cervera, Cañadas and Polo-Blanco (2022), none of the participants has indicated how these are used in other contexts such as when paying and telling the time (Baglama, Yikmis, and Demirok, 2017). However, this might be attributed to the fact that the participating educators are still working on more basic skills in the primary school setting, and hence these may be seen as skills more focused upon in the middle and secondary school setting. Educators in this study have acknowledged that when tangibles are used, learners tend to be more involved and less lost 'in their own world'. This finding agrees with the concluding evidence of the American study of Jimenez and Stranger (2017) and the Spanish one by Goñi-Cervera, Cañadas and Polo-Blanco (2022) that tangibles are critical in supporting students' learning and engagement. Therefore, this possibly hypothesises that incorporating tangibles within adaptations

would help learners with autism overcome some of the challenges related to EF skills (Dijkhuis *et al.*, 2020).

Adaptations of instructions have also been indicated to be developed through digitalised hardware and software (e.g. tablets, laptops, YouTube content, PowerPoint®) in primary mainstream schools in Malta. These findings mirror and add to the findings of previous studies that have demonstrated that high-tech visual support is part of the adaptations where provision is concerned (Camilleri and Camilleri, 2017; Jimenez and Besaw, 2020; Judge, 2013; Kariippanon *et al.*, 2018; Knight, McKissick, and Saunders, 2013; Licona and Loke, 2017; Neely *et al.*, 2013; Newbutt *et al.*, 2017; Rising, 2017; Rutherford *et al.*, 2020; Soysa and Al Mahmud, 2019). When discussing the use of digital means as part of the adaptations for learners with autism during the explanatory research phase, this research has found that technology is mainly used to present content related to literacy and numeracy skills. The current data echoes other scholars' findings regarding technology, which focus on allowing learners to acquire the necessary skills to function in the world beyond the classroom (Camilleri and Camilleri, 2017; Jimenez and Besaw, 2020; Rutherford *et al.*, 2020). This current study has also indicated that technology as part of the adaptations of learners with autism also increases learner involvement, acquisition of content, motivation, and independence throughout the execution of tasks in the classroom. This consensus on the benefits and use of technology leads to an understanding that stakeholders in education have shifted their mindsets on including technology to promote more innovative pedagogical practices in the classroom hence substantiating the views of Sabayleh and Alramamneh (2020).

Another intriguing finding worth noting that emerged from the present study but which contradicts previous research conducted by Yazici and McKenzie (2019) shows that educators who support learners with autism in primary schools in Malta do not perceive that the use of digital tools as part of the intervention of learners with autism leads to 'obsessions' or 'fixations'. The current research has indicated that this situation does not seem to transpire as the educator must control the time spent by learners with autism on devices such as tablets and computers. This leads to an understanding that classroom management skills play a crucial role in avoiding the 'fixations' that learners with autism have been indicated to develop when technology in the classroom is included. In this case, it may be concluded that the educator's role is critical in maximising the use of technology in the classroom to ensure that learners with autism access the curriculum, reach their learning potential and actively participate in the classroom.

A significant point that has also emerged from this study was the absence of educators' views on whether adaptations are made to assessments and tests for learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta. Thus, such lack of data could not be compared to the conclusions of the longitudinal study conducted by Clark *et al.* (2020) regarding teachers' implementation of adaptations to provide modified or alternative tests. A reason for this lack of data may emerge from the fact that until the last scholastic year (2021-2022), alternative examination papers were made available to learners according to which checklists students had achieved. These alternative examination papers were provided to learners in the core subjects, i.e. Maths, Maltese and English, by the MEYR. Hence, teachers and LSEs were not required to modify or adapt examinations.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that alternative papers will no longer be made available to learners as of this scholastic year (2022-2023). This situation may pose a situation whereby some learners with autism cannot sit for their annual examinations as their peers, potentially excluding them from the process altogether. This limitation transpires despite that, according to Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), the inclusive education of learners in mainstream schools is achieved through their participation in the curriculum by attaining teaching goals defined by informal and formal pedagogical assessment. Therefore, given that this situation is a novice procedure, its impacts are still to be evaluated. Hence, further research on whether this new procedure, in terms of the lack of availability of alternative examination papers, has led teachers and LSEs to adapt assessments and tests is needed.

Absent from the current study was also data showing whether adaptations made by educators in schools in Malta are used to teach communication skills as per the conclusions following the study of Yazici and McKenzie (2019). Participants' willingness to be trained to support learners in communication, self-management, and adapting examinations and assessments, as shown in Figure 36, suggests that a lack of training may explain the absence of references and descriptions of adaptations in assessments, tests, and communication skills. Therefore, this limitation in terms of data calls for future research to investigate these two strands to indicate how tests and the teaching of communication skills are adapted (or not) for learners with autism who attend schools in Malta. This inquiry would be pertinent since, according to Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), teaching methods that

encourage the active engagement of students in the learning process may impact the progress made by learners in all educational, cognitive and social domains.

Data confirming the findings of previous studies

- **Instructional adaptations based on visual support, step-by-step instruction, technology and tangibles, are a strength of the teaching and learning process in schools in Malta** (Ayuningtyas *et al.*, 2021; Camilleri and Camilleri, 2017; Carbonneau, Marley, and Selig, 2013; Clark *et al.*, 2020; Cooper *et al.*, 2022; Curtin and Long, 2021; Dijkhuis *et al.* 2020; Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021; Dyer, 2022; Gorii-Cervera, Cariadas and Polo-Blanco, 2022; Jimenez and Besaw, 2020; Jimenez and Stranger, 2017; Judge, 2013; Kariippanon *et al.*, 2018; Knight, McKissick, and Saunders, 2013; Licona and Loke, 2017; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Majoko, 2018; Marley and Carbonneau, 2014; Neely *et al.*, 2013; Newbutt *et al.*, 2017; Nguyen *et al.* 2015; Pastor-Cerezuela *et al.* 2020; Rising, 2017; Rutherford *et al.*, 2020; Santos, Breda and Almeida, 2017; Soysa and Al Mahmud, 2019; Spooner *et al.*, 2019; Tynan and Davy, 2021; Van Der Steen *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019).
- **The content presented should be relevant to learners with autism**, as already indicated in Norris (2022) and Carruthers *et al.* (2020).
- **Educators who support learners with autism in primary schools in Malta do not perceive that the use of digital tools as part of the intervention of learners with autism leads to 'obsessions' or 'fixations'** (Yazici and McKenzie, 2019).

Further emerging questions

- How are **assessments and tests for learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta adapted?**
- What are **the views of learners with autism** who attend schools in Malta **in terms of their preferred learning preference style?**
- Do **learners with autism want to learn Religion?**
- What are **the parents' views on having their children learning Religion?**

Table 36: Summary of Data: Adaptations of Instructions

Support of the SLT: Whole-school practices, as outlined in Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), fall within the remit of the SLT. Gonzales (2020) asserts that all school administrators must ensure that every learner has equitable access to quality education, feels secure, connected, and valued in the classroom, and receives the support and direction they need to grow and learn. As noted through the findings of the current research and what is posited by Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), any decisions at an SLT level tend to influence the child's microsystem hence aligning this with the findings with those of Lloyd (2019), RaudeliOnaite and Steponeniene (2020), Symes and Humphrey (2011) and Stadnick *et al.* (2019). As may also be noted in Table 37, this research has seen findings indicating that having the support of the school's administration is a strength of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- **Having the support of the school's administration is a strength within the support process of learners with autism** (Lloyd, 2019; RaudeliOnaite and Steponeniene, 2020; Stadnick *et al.*, 2019; Symes and Humphrey, 2011).
- **Support by the SLT is regarded as a strength as some members of the SLT prioritise the potential of learners with autism** (Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Iadarola *et al.*, 2015; LUddeckens, Anderson and Ostlund, 2022).

Further emerging questions

- **What measures are being taken by SLT members to see how collaboration regarding the development of adaptations is transpiring between teachers and LSEs?**
- **What actions are members of the SLT taking to help create a school environment which is accessible to learners?**

Table 37: Summary of Data: Support from the SLT

Furthermore, qualitative findings indicated that support is transformative, as some members of the SLT prioritise the potential of learners. When SLT members prioritise the potential of learners with autism, support is also permeated towards teachers and LSEs. Conclusions by Hodges *et al.* (2020), Iadarola *et al.* (2015) and Lüddeckens, Anderson and Östlund (2022) have indicated that when school leaders are helpful, they ensure that the vision of the school, its values, and ethos are supportive and non-discriminatory. This view leads to an understanding that the SLT is in a position whereby it may mobilise inclusive practices and attitudes, thus further confirming that, despite being situated at an exosystem level (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014), the support of the SLT in valuing the potential of learners is seen as impacting the extent of students' participation, achievement, and value.

As per the data presented in Figure 37, it is noted that not all Heads of Schools and Assistant Heads of Schools are trained to support learners with autism. Therefore, this raises a pertinent question regarding other supports, what measures are being taken by SLT members to see how collaboration regarding the development of adaptations is transpiring between teachers and LSEs, and how they may help create a school environment accessible to learners. Indeed, two weaknesses identified in this research, and which will be discussed in Section 5.2.2 have been linked to the fact that most of the adaptations are developed by LSEs rather than collaboratively with teachers and that classroom environments may be overwhelming to learners with autism.

Support by Peers: Parallel to previous findings (Crompton *et al.*, 2022; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Watkins *et al.*, 2015), the quantitative findings of this study indicate that a strength of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism is located within the support provided by peers of learners with autism. From the context of the Ecological Systems Framework (Bronfenbrenner, 1979) and its reconceptualisation (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014), peers have been seen as critical to learners' participation, achievement and value as they sit within the microsystem, directly impacting learner development (Anderson Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

Explanations from the qualitative findings of the current study regarding peer support were two-fold. The first explanation confirms the conclusions of preceding studies (Dahary *et al.*, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Russell, Scrinet and Smyth, 2022) in terms of the buddy system is regarded as a strategy which facilitates peer support. Aligned with the findings from previous studies, peer support tends to be beneficial for learners with autism and other learners in the class to develop empathy and tolerance (Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Xuereb and Lawson, 2019). The current study confirmed that buddy systems allow learners with autism to increase their academic, behavioural, and social achievements (Crompton *et al.*, 2022; Dahary *et al.*, 2022; Watkins *et al.*, 2015) and that these also allow neurotypical learners to become more accepting towards others. As indicated in this research and supported by previous studies, through strategies such as the buddy system, the special interests that learners with autism possess may serve as facilitators to engage with other peers who have the same interests (Milton and Sims, 2016). Consequently, this would, in turn, enable learners with autism to

enhance their social connections (Milton and Sims, 2016; Stephenson and Adams, 2016).

However, an interesting finding from the current research arises from the fact that one participant demarcated that students who are part of the buddy system should change regularly, as this would be 'unfair' if it is always the case that the same children had to support learners with autism. To the author's knowledge, however, no research studies have suggested that having the same students supporting learners with autism is perceived as an unjust situation that disadvantages typically developing students. Thus, this finding may have uncovered a novel contribution to the field. Nevertheless, reasonable considerations in terms of this new empirical contribution should take place in view that many learners with autism understand the concept of friendship and hence, want to have friends (Cresswell, Hinch and Cage, 2019), with such relationships benefitting their well-being, self-esteem and active school participation (Crompton *et al.*, 2022). Thus, eliminating or decreasing such peer buddy systems would negatively affect learners with autism. As may be noted in Table 38 in terms of the further questions emerging following these findings, it would be interesting, therefore, to involve peers of learners with autism in future research studies to determine how the buddy system impacts them and seek their views about it, particularly since, at a microsystem level, they are considered an essential element in their interaction with learners with autism (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

As noted in Table 38, findings emerging from the current research also validated the previous conclusion regarding PPPs' benefits when these are included as part

of the educational programmes of learners with autism (Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021). Indeed, this has been viewed as a source that allows learners with autism to be better understood by their neurotypical peers, as they can respond better to the needs of learners with autism when PPPs are implemented (Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021). This research has indicated that if parents do not consent, PPPs are not carried out in schools in Malta. The current findings have been somewhat challenging to compare with other international contexts since, to date, no research has looked into parental consent and PPPs. However, this finding should be considered salient and intriguing, particularly since educators in Malta feel that the extent of parental consent may hinder or prevent them from implementing PPPs as necessary. Then again, the views of parents regarding this would potentially shed light on the reasons underpinning their decisions to consent or dissent to the implementation of PPPs, particularly since considering their interaction and decisions on the matter may impact the learners' development at an Ecological Systems Level (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979).

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- **A strength of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism is support from peers as it is viewed as an aspect increasing their academic, behavioural and social achievements and which facilitates engagement with peers who have the same interest** (Crompton *et al.*, 2022; Dahary *et al.*, 2022; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Milton and Sims, 2016; Watkins *et al.*, 2015).
- **Peer support based on the buddy system is beneficial for learners with autism and for other learners in the class to develop empathy and tolerance** (Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Xuereb and Lawson, 2019).
- **PPPs are a source which allow learners with autism to be better understood by their peers** (Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Sim6-Pinatella, Gunther-Bel and Mumbard6-Adam, 2021).
- **Students who are part of the buddy system should change regularly, as this would be 'unfair' if the same children had to support learners with autism.** To the author's knowledge, however, no research studies have outlined the issue of having the same students supporting learners with autism as it being an unjust strategy that disadvantages typically developing students.
- **Educators in schools in Malta are concerned about the lack of consent that parents may provide to prepare peers about the needs and differences of a learner with autism.** To date, no research has looked into the associations of parental consent and PPPs.

Further emerging questions

- What are the **views of peers** of learners with autism **on peer buddy systems?**
- What are the **views of parents regarding the reasons underpinning their decisions to consent or dissent to the implementation of PPPs?**

Table 38: Summary of Data: Support from Peers

5.2.2 Weaknesses of the teaching and learning process

Adaptations developed by LSEs: The findings emerging from quantitative data delineate that a weakness of the teaching and learning process is located within teachers not being involved in the adaptations developed for students with autism. Such weakness seems to lie mainly within the issue that the LSE develops most of the adaptations presented to learners with autism in the classroom. As noted in Table 39, contradicting the importance that teachers have at a microsystems level, the current findings verify what previous findings have found in terms of teachers being under-involved in the education of learners with IEN (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021; Carter, Stephenson and Webster, 2019; Fisher and Pleasants, 2011; Holmes and Butcher, 2020; Jellinek *et al.*, 2020). LSE participants argued that the LSE, not the class teacher, provides most autism support.

Given that in Section 4.2.4, one of the threats of training has been identified as being located in the aspect that teacher preparatory courses lack training on autism, this finding is not surprising. Despite the fact that adaptations to instructions have been identified as a strength of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism, there seems to be a gap within such process in terms of teachers' support. Indeed, the current study has unfolded a situation where in some cases, when students directly ask the teacher for help, they are directed back to the LSE. The latter circumstance has also been disclosed by Holmes and Butcher (2020). This attitude persists, although literature argues that any instruction, including any adaptations made to the curriculum by LSEs, should be supplemental to that of the class teacher and not primary or exclusive (Giangreco, 2013). Hence, this research can determine that the current mindset regarding the development of adaptations lies within the

responsibility of LSEs thus considering this as a weakness in the teaching and learning process.

Current findings and their link to previous ones	Further emerging questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A weakness of the teaching and learning process is located within teachers not being involved in the adaptations developed for students with autism and are mostly developed by LSEs (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021; Carter, Stephenson and Webster, 2019; Fisher and Pleasants, 2011; Holmes and Butcher, 2020; Jellinek <i>et al.</i>, 2020). • When students with autism directly ask the teacher for help, these are directed back to the LSE (Holmes and Butcher, 2020). • Having adaptations developed by LSEs rather than the teacher have been linked to the issue that teachers lack the necessary training to support learners with autism (Boujout <i>et al.</i>, 2017; GOiec-Asian, 2020; Kossewska <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Ravet, 2018). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What type of training is provided to pre-service and in-service teachers in terms of skills acquisition on how to develop adaptations to learners with autism?

Table 39: Summary of Data: Adaptations by LSEs

Further discussed in section 5.2.4 and aligned with what has been significantly resurfacing in studies, a possible reason why LSEs rather than the teacher develop adaptations is that teachers lack the necessary training to support learners with autism (Boujout *et al.*, 2017; GOiec-Asian, 2020; Kossewska *et al.*, 2021; Ravet, 2018). Lack of training is seen as jeopardising the quality of support provided to learners with autism. Indeed, in the context of the Ecology of Inclusive Education, training has been identified as the most influential in terms of the extent to which

learners are included in the mainstream classroom (Hoskin, Boyle and Anderson, 2015). Hence, as will be discussed in further sections within this chapter, pre-service and in-service teacher training content needs to be appraised regarding how this may provide the necessary skills for teachers to provide adaptations for learners with autism.

Lack of resources: A certain level of consistency with what has been concluded by existing studies on the issue of lack of resources conducted in France, Poland, Turkey, Vietnam, Lithuania, Ireland, the U.S. and Canada (Cappe *et al.*, 2021; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Leonard and Smyth, 2022; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Tran *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019) was noted within the current research study. As noted in Table 40, findings indicate that limited resources are a weakness of the teaching and learning process. However, despite the current quantitative findings, the qualitative findings revealed some mixed perspectives. When asked about the lack of resources being perceived as a weakness in the teaching and learning process, the Head of School and the Head of Department who support schools in the area of inclusion disagreed with what was implied. They believe that teachers and LSEs mentioned such lack of resources either because staff might not know about the existence of specific resources in schools or because they lack knowledge on how to use them.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A weakness of the teaching and learning process is the **limited resources that teachers and LSEs** to support learners with autism (Cappe *et al.*, 2021; Hersh and Ellley, 2019; Leonard and Smyth, 2022; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Raudeliunaite and Steponeniene, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Tran *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019).
- One participant implied that **where specific resources would benefit only one child, schools tend to ask parents to purchase such resources.**
- **The Head of School and the Head of Department who support schools in the area of inclusion disagree that schools lack resources.** To the author's knowledge, there is no current available empirical data on this hence this study was unable to compare this with the findings of previous studies.

Further emerging questions

- Given that **parents' voices** were absent from this study, **their perspectives** regarding what has been implied within the findings of this research in terms **of the extent of the availability of resources** needs to be sought.

Table 40: Summary of Data: Lack of Resources

Contesting the views of the Head of School and the Head of Department were the views of one LSE who reported that she had encountered situations where due to specific resources benefiting only one student, schools asked parents to purchase such resources. If perceived from the context of the Ecology of Inclusive Education, it may be argued that the inability of schools to provide resources, even if these benefit few children, is a systemic barrier at a micro and exo level to the provision of inclusive education hence impeding the participation, achievement and value of learners with autism. Therefore, school leaders may be critical stakeholders in

mobilising school resources (Díaz-Gibson *et al.* 2021). Nonetheless, because parents' voices were absent from this study, their perspectives on what has been implied within this research's findings must be sought to validate the issue raised above and thus make these findings more credible. Furthermore, from an ecological perspective, parents are at the core of the child's microsystem. Thus, their views are pertinent to determine whether there is a lack of resources in schools and if and how this impact the development and progress of their children.

Inadequate classroom environment: Corroborating the conclusions of previous empirical studies which used both quantitative and qualitative data collection tools (Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020), the findings of this study indicate that the physical environment of the classroom is inadequate for learners with autism, and is considered as a weakness of the teaching and learning process. Verifying the views of teachers in the U.K. and South Africa (Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022), educators in Malta have delineated that the current classroom environment makes it challenging for learners with autism to 'function in that environment'. As noted in Table 41, the current study has found that this originates from the sensory over-stimuli that classrooms may have in terms of inadequate lighting and clutter and also from overcrowded classrooms. The latter is a factor which echoes that of educators in schools in Turkey and Poland (Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Gulveren *et al.*, 2022; Hersh and Elley, 2019), with this finding implying that overcrowded classrooms impact the behaviour and academic performance of learners with autism (Shaari and Ahmad, 2016).

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- **The physical environment of classrooms in Malta is inadequate for learners with autism** and is considered as a weakness in the teaching and learning process (GOiec-Asian, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022; Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene, 2020).
- Educators in Malta have outlined that the **current overwhelming and over-stimulated classroom environment makes it challenging for learners with autism to 'function in that environment** (Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022).
- **Classrooms in Malta are overcrowded** (GOiec-Asian, 2020; Gulveren *et al.*, 2022; Hersh and Elley, 2019).

Further emerging questions

- Which **other aspects** within the **school's physical environment may be modified** to address the needs of learners with autism?

Table 41: Summary of Data: Inadequate Classroom Environment

Given that within the context of the Ecology of Inclusive Education, the physical space in the classroom is an element situated at the microsystem level, directly impacting the learner's participation, achievement, and value (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). In addition, and of particular relevance to this research, teaching and learning contexts for learners, including those with autism, are nested within classrooms. This situation hence calls for the need to revise classroom populations and settings accordingly, with current participants indicating that having adequate quiet spaces in and outside the classroom would be an opportunity which may

mitigate this identified weakness. Further to this, current participants' insights have implied that the Maltese classroom environment for learners with autism is 'hazardous' due to the classroom being overcrowded, where one can 'hardly breathe', 'cannot conduct one-to-one time with the student' and where too 'many charts on the wall' tend to overwhelm learners with autism. These connotations from the participants' voices in the current study confirm the position of the 'unfavourable classroom conditions' identified by teachers in Hersh and Elley's (2019) and Jones, Hanley and Riby's (2020) studies. It is believed that despite the need to weigh and re-evaluate classroom populations, other issues within the whole school's physical environment (such as the yard where breaktime takes place) could have been missed.

5.2.3 Opportunities to the teaching and learning process

Quiet spaces: As noted in Table 42, one of the opportunities named by questionnaire respondents on teaching and learning was the creation of quiet areas. This perspective validates the conclusions drawn from other international research studies (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Roberts and Simpson, 2016), with the current findings also outlining the characteristics of how such quiet spaces may be designed. For instance, several questionnaire participants in the current study had the same views as educators in Turkey regarding having a resource room whereby learners could retreat and work with educators in a much calmer environment (Güleç-Aslan, 2020), mainly when the classroom environment is too overwhelming. Three out of five interviewees in the current study delineated that this area could have a sofa, a computer, and adequate lighting, indicating similar autism-friendly design ideas brought forward by Irish

teachers in the study of Leonard and Smyth (2022). If these quiet spaces had to be created, it might be argued that this may solve the identified weakness in the teaching and learning process related to inadequate classroom environments. Hence, the creation of quiet areas would potentially enable learners with autism to retreat to such spaces to be able to calm down and regulate their emotions.

Nevertheless, an intriguing finding from the current study saw two out of five interviewees outlining that such spaces should be ideally set up in the classroom as students with autism could interpret their time out of class as having free time rather than when tasks must be carried out. Current findings thus suggest that educators tend to have diverse interpretations and ideas of where quiet spaces should be put in place within schools to enhance the teaching and learning opportunities of learners with autism, with one Head of School outlining that MEYR closed down such rooms in schools. This finding may be interpreted in light of a situation whereby the school lacked guidelines on creating such spaces; thus, these rooms may have been inadequately set up to support learners with autism.

In view of the aforementioned situation regarding the previous 'quiet rooms' being closed down by MEYR, clearer guidelines of how these may be set up should be in place. This set-up is essential since whilst students with autism seem to deem these as essential to 'take a break' from the overwhelming classroom environment (Eguiguren, Istuany and Wood, 2020), conversely, such practice is also perceived as something which could lead to micro-exclusion (Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021). Given that the voices of parents of learners with autism and the voices of learners themselves were not part of this research, it would be

interesting to investigate whether they would like quiet spaces to be set up, why (if indicated so) these are required, and how should these be set up. This inquiry would enable a comparison between the views of educators, peers, and parents on how these quiet spaces should be designed should these settings be potentially set up. The perspectives of all individuals impacted by these settings would thus have been sought.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- **An opportunity** that might enhance the teaching and learning process is the creation of **quiet areas** (Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; GÖle & Aslan, 2020; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Roberts and Simpson, 2016).
- Educators suggested a **resource room as an opportunity** whereby **learners could retreat** and **carry out work** with educators **in a much calmer environment** (GÖle & Aslan, 2020). This space could have a **sofa, a computer, and adequate lighting** (Leonard and Smyth, 2022).
- Quiet spaces would be **ideally set up in the classroom as students with autism could interpret their time out of class as having free time rather than carrying out work with the LSE. The latter could not be confirmed with empirical research as no evidence of this has been identified.**

Further emerging questions

- What are the **views of parents** of learners with autism on the development of **quiet spaces and their design?**
- What are the views of learners with autism on the development of **quiet spaces and their design?**

Table 42: Summary of Data: Quiet Spaces

Support from external service providers: Educators in this study reported that collaborating with external service providers and following their recommendations and support could provide them with opportunities to further enhance the support

for learners (Cloninger, 2017; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022; Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021; Sulek *et al.*, 2019; Strunk, Leisen and Schubert, 2019; Syriopoulou-Delli *et al.*, 2012). As suggested in previous research (Cloninger, 2017) and as noted in Table 43, respondents in the current research indicated that having support from service providers such as the ASST and Speech Therapists is perceived as an opportunity that could enhance learners' teaching and learning process. As concluded by qualitative studies conducted in Spain and Australia (Simó-Pinatella, Günther-Bel and Mumbardó-Adam, 2021; Sulek *et al.*, 2019; Walton *et al.*, 2022), external professionals can provide advice, and share knowledge and experiences, thus enabling educators to develop more awareness on strategies that would allow them to support their learners further.

However, unlike previous research (Daly *et al.*, 2016; Majoko, 2018; McDougal, Riby and Hanley, 2020), the lack of support provided by psychologists in schools dominated participants' views. Interview participants acknowledged that understaffing is the major issue as such a service focuses more on assessment than school intervention. This situation from the perspectives of educators transpires in schools in Malta despite that Majoko (2018) asserts that the intervention of psychologists in schools has the potential to instil in educators optimistic attitudes and the necessary abilities to be responsive to services and programmes for learners, including those with autism. Having the guidance of external service providers could potentially see educators: i) being more accepting of learners with autism; ii) moving away from a “one size fits all” approach; iii) using approaches in the classroom that foster equity. This inclination towards more favourable attitudes could potentially overcome the threat identified in this study,

which will be discussed in Section 5.2.4 regarding the lack of clarity in terms of the perspectives of inclusive education.

Current findings and their link to previous ones	Further emerging questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educators in this study reported that an opportunity that might enhance the teaching and learning process is the collaboration with external service providers such as autism specialists and speech therapists and following their recommendations could provide them with opportunities to further enhance support to learners (Cloninger, 2017; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022; Sim6-Pinatella, Gunther-Bel and Mumbard6-Adam, 2021; Sulek <i>eta/.</i>, 2019; Strunk, Leisen and Schubert, 2019; Syriopoulou-Delli <i>et al.</i>, 2012; Walton <i>et al.</i>, 2022). • Findings indicated that psychological intervention in schools lacks in terms of support for learners with autism and educators (Daly <i>et al.</i>, 2016; Majoko, 2018; McDougal, Riby and Hanley, 2020). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the views of psychologists in terms of what has been implied by educators in schools in Malta in terms of lack of intervention for learners with autism?

Table 43: Summary of Data: Support from External Service Providers

Considering the above from the Ecology of Inclusive Education lens, it may be concluded that human resource allocation could influence attitudes regarding enhancing quality support (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). As one situated at an exosystem level, this may be interpreted as an external influence that, when penetrated through the mesosystem into the microsystem, will indirectly influence the learner (Dobson and Douglas, 2018). Indeed, as identified in Section 2.1,

despite occurring at an exosystem level, these elements still impact the learners' schooling experience (Onwuegbuzie, Collins and Frels, 2013).

Nevertheless, as noted in Table 43, psychologists' views must be considered to explore what factors lead to school intervention being less frequent. Indeed, given that the voices of psychologists were absent from the current research, future studies could look into the extent of support related to how psychological intervention takes place for students with autism who attend schools in Malta. This inquiry could potentially add credibility to the current data and seek the reasons why (if applicable from their perspective) intervention is not taking place in schools.

5.2.4 Threats to the teaching and learning process

Unclear perspectives about Inclusive Education: When considered from the Ecology of Inclusive Education perspective, the attitudes held towards the construct of Inclusive Education by educators in this study indicate that the impacts within each system influence this. As discussed in Sections 1.2 and 2.1, policies and expectations, the socio-political climate, and student, parent and educators' attitudes impact the inclusion of learners with autism. As indicated in Table 44, the current study revealed that having unclear perspectives about inclusion threatens the teaching and learning process of learners with autism. The current findings align with those of Abed, Jameel and Ahmad (2021), Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis (2019), and Krischler, Powell and Pit-Ten Cate (2019), who concluded that the understanding of inclusion is still unclear for some educators who support learners with autism. This threat might impact the learners' ecological system as an unclear understanding of what inclusion entails, "a one size fits all" approach tends to

dominate the teaching and learning process of learners with autism. Contrary to what the microsystem and exosystem propose regarding what is positioned at these levels impacting learners' participation, achievement and value, unclear views regarding inclusion could imply that students with autism would merely be present in the classroom with no equity in learning content. Hence, in light of this situation, the learners' sense of belonging might decrease (Hodges *et al.*, 2020).

As mentioned in Section 5.2.3, an opportunity that may overcome the threat in terms of the lack of clarity of what inclusion entails is the potential to have more support services from external service providers. Service providers such as the ASST, Speech Therapists and psychologists are perceived as an opportunity that could enhance the guidance that educators may receive regarding the support of learners with autism. This opportunity transpires because if external service providers share their expertise with educators who support learners with autism, their support towards educators may impact the frequency of the implementation of inclusive practice, including EBPs, and the supportive mechanisms enhancing its implementation (Abed, Jameel and Ahmad, 2021; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019). This optimistic impact would instil a better understanding of viewing inclusion as a way of promoting participation rather than as an inadequate placement with no reference to support and practice (Russell, Scriney and Smyth, 2022). Hence, this would lead educators towards a practice that facilitates equality of provision (Felder, 2018).

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- **Having differing perspectives about the notion of inclusion is perceived as a threat to the teaching and learning process** of learners with autism in Malta as this leads to "a one size fits all" approach (Abed, Jameel and Ahmad, 2021; Krischler, Powell and Pit-Ten Cate, 2019; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019).

Further emerging questions

- **What common definition in terms of inclusion** do educators in Malta have?

Table 44: Summary of Data: Unclear Perspectives about Inclusive Education

Lack of knowledge of policy content and implementation: As noted in Table 45, similar to the evolving body of literature (e.g. Abed, Jameel and Ahmad, 2021; Farlin, 2006; Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Xu, 2012), the current research presents an indication that a threat to the teaching and learning process of learners with autism is the lack of knowledge that educators have on existing policies on inclusion. As noted in Table 45, in agreement with the findings of the Lithuanian qualitative study conducted by RaudeliOnaite and Steponeniene (2020) and the U.S. study of Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis (2019), the current research suggests that due to such lack of knowledge in terms of what policies entail, there seems to be a disposition where lack of specificity of the roles and responsibilities of each educator could delay policy translation into practice.

This situation above may lead to two significant consequences related to: i) having more educators being more inclined to maintain the "status quo" (p.59) and hence, not necessarily implementing inclusive practices (Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis,

2019); ii) the potential of harming the school's ability to support learners with autism appropriately. Consequently, this would impact the learners' provision as when an education system fails to implement national and local education policies within the exosystem, the school microsystem's practices, curriculum, teaching strategies, and student evaluation system are affected (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; El Zaatari and Maalouf, 2022). Indeed, Bronfenbrenner (1979) outlined that although the policy context sits at a macrosystems level in the Ecological Systems Theory, it tends to influence educators' practice directly. Therefore, to enhance the effectiveness of support of learners with autism, educators must be given a clear picture of what is expected of them regarding how to implement existing policy in particular since this would impact the quality and levels of participation, achievement and value (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

When considering the findings above, one also needs to appreciate that to date, the policy and framework on Inclusive Education in Malta (MEYR, 2022a; MEYR, 2022b) and the Autism State Plan (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government) are still at an early stage of their implementation in Malta. Indeed, the Inclusion Policy and Framework have been officially launched on the 6th of February 2023, whilst the Autism State Plan has embarked on a strategy which will run between 2021 and 2030. Hence, as time goes by, one may expect that such knowledge regarding content policy and implementation among educators working in schools in Malta would potentially increase. Thus, further research in regards to how the content of the Inclusion Policy and its Framework (MEYR, 2022a; MEYR, 2022b) and the Autism State Plan (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local

Government) are being translated into practice would be able to shed light upon educators understanding of these policies.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A threat to the teaching and learning process of learners with autism is the **lack of knowledge that educators have on existing policies** on inclusion (e.g. Abed, Jameel and Ahmad, 2021; Forlin, 2006; Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Xu, 2012).
- Due to such lack of clarity in terms of what policies entail, there seems to be a disposition where **lack of specificity of the roles and responsibilities** of each educator exists (Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019).

Further emerging questions

- **What knowledge do educators have on the current existing policies on inclusion and autism in Malta?**
- How are **current policies being translated into practice** in schools in Malta so as to enhance the support provided to learners with autism?

Table 45: Summary of Data: Lack of knowledge on policy content and implementation

5.3 Training for Educators

Which are the SWOTs within the training process of educators who support learners with autism in mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Recent literature has shown that further knowledge of autism's characteristics, causes, and management is related to increased awareness and understanding of classroom practices (Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Segall and Campbell, 2014). Such knowledge is critical as teaching students with autism often accentuates concerns regarding social interaction, verbal and non-verbal communication, sensory processing, and restricted and repetitive behaviour

(American Psychiatric Association, 2013; World Health Organization, 2019). Furthermore, at an exo-system ecological level, having educators acquire the necessary abilities to address behaviour could impact the curriculum, pedagogy, and classroom routines (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). However, in reviewing the current literature, no data was found on how training on autism for educators who work in primary mainstream state schools in Malta transpires. Therefore, this study set out to report upon the current SWOTs within the training made available for educators who support learners in primary educational settings in Malta.

5.3.1 Strengths of training

Sharing of good practice: The findings of this study revealed that several training sessions are based on sharing of good practice. The current research identified how such a possibility enables educators to feel more confident whilst conducting their duties. This finding is consistent with the conclusions emerging from the Irish studies of Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella (2017) and Brennan and King (2021) in terms of the fact that when educators are provided with opportunities to share their good practice with colleagues, their confidence to address the needs of learners with autism increases. Therefore, it may be assumed that providing a voice to educators to share their practice and experiences regarding the strategies applied in the class provides prospects for them to improve classroom instruction and to brainstorm interventions to effectively support learners (Ainscow, 2020; Ho, 2022). Indeed, this has been viewed as a solution that allows for better chances of finding solutions to any arising issues (Ainscow, 2020; Ho, 2022). Indeed, when considering this finding from the ecological lens, the sharing of good practice amongst colleagues may be

seen as one which could impact the development and achievement of the learner as through educator-to-educator influences, the provision for learners with autism may be ameliorated. As noted in Table 46, it is critical that since the sharing of good practice is a positive element, educators should be provided with more opportunities to share their practice. This opportunity to share practice is critically necessary since, as will be noted in the following sections, without adequate skills, confidence, knowledge, and positive attitudes towards learners with autism will decline.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- The findings of this study revealed that a strength to the training process is located within educators having the possibility to share **good practice with colleagues** (Ainscow, 2020; Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Brennan and King, 2021; Ho, 2022).

Further emerging questions

- How many **opportunities throughout the scholastic year are educators provided to share their good practice** on how to support learners with autism?

Table 46: Summary of the Data: Sharing of Good Practice

User-friendly strategies: As noted in Table 47, another interesting finding from this study was educators indicating that a strength of the training process is the recommendation of user-friendly approaches by trainers. As the researcher of the current study, to my knowledge, this finding is a new contribution to research. Indeed, the suggestion of user-friendly approaches to educators as a strength in training for educators on autism has never emerged in the current empirical literature. The buddy system was among the strategies mentioned by educators, which was classified as 'less complicated' to implement. Aligned with the findings of

Curtin and Long (2021), the visual schedule was also one of the strategies recommended by trainers, which was also classified as 'being less complicated to implement' by participants of the current research. Both of the indicated strategies classified by current participants as being ones which are easy to implement have been viewed as being beneficial for learners with autism in terms of them: i) being sources which enhance the inclusion of learners with autism (Hersh and Elley, 2019; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014); ii) being strategies which help learners with autism overcome the challenges they encounter related to social communication skills (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; Baczewski and Kasari, 2021; Finnegan and Accardo, 2018; Hebron, 2018; Huxter, 2021; World Health Organization, 2019; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019; Zhou, Zhan and Ma, 2019).

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- **Educators appreciate the provision for user-friendly approaches** when training is provided to them as this facilitates their implementation. This finding is a new contribution to research as a strength in training for educators on autism given that it was not identified in the work reviewed in Chapter 2.
- **Strategies such as the buddy system and the visual schedule which were viewed as being user-friendly to implement.** This finding is a new contribution to research as a strength in training for educators on autism given that it was not identified in the previous empirical literature.

Further emerging questions

- Which **other strategies** have been put forward from training and which educators **perceive as 'user-friendly'**?

Table 47: Summary of Data: User-Friendly Strategies

Taken from the perspective of an ecological lens, when educators feel that they can implement straightforward strategies, they tend to tacit knowledge at the micro, meso and macro levels and hence become more cognisant and confident to facilitate learning for students, including those with autism. This enabling factor in terms of promoting access to students in terms of teaching and learning would lead to an educational environment promoting inclusion, potentially increasing learners' participation, achievement and value (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014).

5.3.2 Weaknesses of training

Theoretical training: Conspicuously present in educators' responses regarding weaknesses within the training process were reports that training sessions tend to focus more on theoretical rather than practical strategies. As noted in Table 48, the findings in the current study substantiate the views of educators in Turkey, Croatia, Poland, and North Macedonia, who also verified that training content on autism is based on theoretical training rather than on practical strategies (Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Lisak Šegota *et al.*, 2022).

Aligned with the perspectives of educators in Turkey, Canada and the U.S. (Corkum *et al.*, 2014; Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Güleç-Aslan, 2020), the current research found that educators feel concerned as they find it difficult to implement what is presented in practice, in particular, when trainers do not demonstrate how strategies should be applied. The latter seems to be persistent across the training provided to educators on autism in various parts of the world, as educators working in schools in Malta have again brought forward the same views of what has been reported

following studies on training in Turkey, Croatia, Poland, and North Macedonia (Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Lisak Šegota *et al.*, 2022).

Echoing the findings of Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella (2017), a further weakness brought forward by this research is that most training sessions, apart from being theoretical, also do not provide further follow-up sessions. A possible implication of the aforementioned is leading educators to implement approaches on a 'trial and error' basis (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Sulek *et al.*, 2019). The above-mentioned seems to consequently place two significant risks upon the provision for learners with autism as: i) training is seen as one which provides no answers; ii) training does not improve educators' self-efficacy when addressing the needs of learners with autism (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Dillenberger *et al.*, 2016; Sharma *et al.*, 2019; Silveira-Zaldivar and Curtis, 2019; Vlcek, Somerton and Rayner, 2020). These risks are somewhat concerning, particularly since educators are regarded as meaningful agents at a microsystem level, as they are the bodies who directly implement the curriculum and educational policies, organise learning experiences and, more notably, address the several needs of learners within the classrooms (Aihie and Uwaoluetan, 2022). Thus, if training is based on a theoretical rather than a practical approach, it will not only possibly demotivate educators as this will not provide any solutions to the challenges they encounter but would significantly reduce the quality of the provision for learners with autism.

The weaknesses identified in terms of the above also raise concerns regarding whether quality assurance strategies concerning the training provided to educators

on autism are put in place by educational authorities. This question is alluded to as, although training is an indirect factor located at a macrosystem level, it is nonetheless an element penetrating the exo, meso, and microsystems (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Such a ripple effect would consequently interfere with the levels of participation, achievement, and value of learners with autism. This issue is worth a future evaluation to establish the level of quality in terms of training content.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A weakness in training has been identified in terms of training sessions being more focused on **theory rather than on practical strategies** (Devi and Ganguly, 2022; GOiec-Asian, 2020; Lisak Segota *et al.*, 2022).
- Training sessions **do not allow for further follow-up sessions.** A possible implication of the aforementioned is leading educators to implement approaches on a 'trial and error' basis (Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Sulek *et al.*, 2019).

Further emerging questions

- How is **quality assurance ensured throughout the training provided** on autism to educators in schools in Malta?

Table 48: Summary of Data: Theoretical Training

To potentially overcome such a weakness, an opportunity identified by current research participants was located within the aspect of having educators identify their training needs. This identification of training needs would potentially enable schools to locate the relevant training that educators require, and hence training would be provided accordingly. This provision of training in terms of relevance may decrease

the instances where training is based on theory and potentially increase practical training. Giving educators a voice in terms of their training needs may also enable schools to continue to enhance the strength of this study in terms of having training based on user-friendly strategies. Therefore, it may be concluded that the latter may potentially contribute to faster strategy adoption and higher implementation quality (Johnson *et al.*, 2014).

Training provided following appointment: An intriguing but concerning finding that emerged from this research has seen teachers and LSEs outlining that training on autism tends to be provided to them following their appointment and not prior to supporting learners in the class. Thus, any training or qualification in inclusive education and/or autism is not required, and a 10-week compulsory training programme is completed after LSEs are appointed. For instance, in Malta, LSEs may be recruited if they have 1 Advanced Level subject at an MQF Level 4, have 4 Ordinary Level subjects, including Maths, English Language and Maltese, and pass a job interview. Motivated by an increase in salary and seniority, most LSEs seek to undergo courses at a certificate, diploma and degree level on inclusive education on a voluntary and self-funded basis. LSEs undergo these courses on their own time. However, although LSEs may be motivated by the financial incentive of an increase in their salary when completing courses at a certificate, diploma and degree level when carrying out such courses, teachers do not benefit from such financial incentives. Thus, it may be argued that the lack of training on autism undergone by teachers may derive from a lack of financial motivation, lack of time and indifference to their seniority.

As noted in Table 49, the fact that this research revealed a situation where educators may be recruited without any prior training on autism and/or inclusive education leads to a situation similar to what transpires in the U.S. and the U.K experience whereby teachers and LSEs carrying out duties in schools in Malta are expected to put “the fire out when it’s already started” (Frantz *et al.*, 2022, p.26) as they are being provided with training “a little too late” (Ravet, 2018, p.717). Unfortunately, similar to the findings of Devi and Ganguly's (2022) Australian study, the current findings indicate that the learning curve for educators on how to support learners with autism has been steep due to a lack of training before being appointed. Consequently, this exposes a paradox whereby increased levels of educator stress and burnout from lack of pre-service training may increase educators' negative attitudes while supporting learners with autism. The abovementioned situation is closely linked to seeing educators losing their confidence whilst supporting learners with autism in the classroom due to increased feelings of doubt and levels of anxiety (Güleç-Aslan, 2020) (Table 48). The latter has various consequences, which could include increased educators' level of stress and burn-out (Güleç-Aslan, 2020) whilst also leading to a “mechanism for recycling existing patterns of thinking and thus reinforcing the status quo” in terms of non-inclusive practice (De La Cruz, 2020; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Saggars *et al.*, 2019; Walton *et al.*, 2022). This reinforcement of the “status quo” may shed concerns on how the practices implemented are increasing learners' participation, achievement and value, as proposed by Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014). Indeed, it may be argued that through training provision on autism, after educators are appointed and not prior to them carrying out duties in the classroom, a situation where the child may be constrained in terms of performing to achieve their learning potential may arise.

Nevertheless, suppose the situation regarding the provision of training after appointment persists. In that case, the opportunities identified by educators themselves in the current research (See 4.2.3) in terms of having training during school hours which specialised trainers provide, must be provided to educators is put in place. It may be argued that, at least, this possibility would potentially fill the current gap within the training process of educators who support learners with autism. However, this may transpire through the support and cooperation of Heads of Schools, with release time to attend training during school hours being a possibility (Suhrheinrich *et al.*, 2021). In fact, one-off training opportunities do not result in the shifts required for sustained, inclusive practice (Walton *et al.*, 2022). Hence, it is understood that there should be a training continuum if the provision for learners with autism is to be enhanced.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- **A weakness of training** on autism has been identified in terms of it being **provided to teachers and LSEs following their appointment** and not prior to them supporting learners in the class (Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Ravet, 2018).
- **Lack of training prior to being appointed has lessens the confidence of teachers and LSEs and increases the levels of anxiety and burn out of educators** (De La Cruz, 2020; GOiec-Asian, 2020; Saggars *et al.*, 2019; Walton *et al.*, 2022).

Further emerging questions

- **Why is training on autism being provided to educators following their appointment** in the classroom rather than before?

Table 49: Summary of Data: Training Following Appointment

Given the implications arising from the shortcomings of the current training process for educators who support learners with autism, a future evaluation must determine why training on autism is provided to educators following their appointment. This evaluation is pertinent since, as already indicated in Section 1.1., due to the increase in the incidence of autism, most educators can rationally expect to have one or more students with autism in their classes each year (Clark *et al.*, 2020).

5.3.3 Opportunities in training

Training Needs: The need for school administrators to gather educators' perspectives on their training needs before organising training sessions emerged strongly in the current study, as the participating educators voiced their views on the opportunities to enhance the training process (Table 50). The current study's findings identified that when educators are asked what training should involve, they tend to be: i) more motivated to attend these sessions; ii) more involved when training content is presented. This delineated opportunity provides an understanding that training should not be uniform in all schools (Bertuccio *et al.*, 2019; Brock *et al.*, 2014) and that gauging what educators' training requirements are would possibly benefit both educators and also learners with autism (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Such an opportunity may also enable schools to overcome the identified weakness in terms of having more practical training, which is practical rather than theoretical (Section 5.3.2), and to continue to enhance the strength of having further training on user-friendly strategies.

This study identified that in the case of Malta, most educators would like to pursue training on challenging behaviour and self-management and on how to support

learners in communication (Figure 35). Further to this data and aligned with what was found in the American and Lithuanian studies of Brock *et al.* (2014) and Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020), this study also saw several participants indicating their interest in undergoing training on how to help students use functional communication means, how to support them in self-management, and how to address behaviour perceived as challenging. The fact that educators want to seek training on addressing communication challenges may justify why reference was not made in terms of instructional adaptations concerning communication skills (See Section 5.2.1). It may be noted that this data, in terms of the areas related to training needs, is closely aligned with the challenges that learners with autism encounter in social communication and restricted and repetitive behaviour patterns (Bertuccio *et al.*, 2019). Such training would possibly help educators to spend less time in class attempting to find solutions to such behaviour (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020), as they would have the necessary knowledge to address these issues promptly. Given this, it may be concluded that the acquisition of relevant knowledge on autism by educators would possibly lead to an endeavour whereby inclusive practice would be provided promptly and hence be fruitful to learners.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- An opportunity that could enhance the training process is for schools to **ask educators about their training needs** (Bertuccio *et al.*, 2019; Brock *et al.*, 2014; Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene, 2020).
- Aligned with what was found in the American and Lithuanian studies of Brock *et al.* (2014) and Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene (2020), which also saw several participants indicating their interest in undergoing **training on how to help students use functional communication means, how to support them in self-management and how to address behaviour perceived as challenging.**

Further emerging questions

- **How often are educators consulted on which training** they would like to pursue?

Table 50: Summary of Data: Training Needs

Training during school hours: Another opportunity that could enhance the training, as identified in the current study, is located within increased opportunities for teachers and LSEs to attend training during school hours. As noted in Table 51, this result may be explained by the fact that increased training during school hours would fulfil educators' training needs (Sobeck and Robertson, 2019; Suhrheinrich *et al.*, 2021; Williams *et al.*, 2021) and potentially overcome voluntary training as a potential threat which decreases the opportunities for educators to receive training on autism (Section 5.3.4). The accomplishment of such training would transpire mainly since this would be ongoing and not only based on one-off sessions (Walton *et al.*, 2022). Indeed, a correlation has been identified between educators receiving

training during school hours and the opportunity to embed prospective mechanisms in the shifts needed for sustained, inclusive practice (Walton *et al.*, 2022).

Further to such findings and similar to previous empirical research, this study also acknowledged the need for all staff, including school administrators, to be trained to acquire knowledge on autism (Sobeck and Robertson, 2019; Williams *et al.*, 2021). One Head of School suggested that more hours allocated to CoPE sessions could be used to train all the school staff members on autism. This suggestion emerging from the voice of a head of school leads to an understanding that school leaders have the prospect of shaping school culture and climate (Williams *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, support from the school's administration in training provision should be perceived as one of the most prominent embedding mechanisms for educators to approach training on autism (Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Williams *et al.*, 2021).

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- An opportunity that could enhance the training for educators on autism is located within the **increased opportunities for teachers and LSEs to attend training during school hours** (Sobeck and Robertson, 2019; Suhrheinrich *et al.*, 2021; Williams *et al.*, 2021).
- A Head of School suggested that the use of **more hours provided within CoPE sessions could be used to provide training to all the members of staff** in schools on the area of autism. This suggestion was not observed as being brought forward in previous available published articles.

Further emerging questions

- **How many hours per scholastic year are SLTs committed to allocate to the provision of training on autism** to educators in schools in Malta?

Table 51: Summary of Data: Training During School Hours

Training by autism specialists: As noted in Table 52, corroborating previous findings from empirical studies which sought the perspectives of educators in Scotland, Australia, and the U.S. (Ballantyne *et al.*, 2022; Hamrick *et al.*, 2021; Walton *et al.*, 2022), educators in this study have also indicated that an opportunity that could enhance their training needs was that of having sessions delivered by autism specialists. The latter might be explained by the relationship verified by previous research that better decision-making in supporting learners with autism tends to be likely determined by training provided by specialists in the field (Hamrick *et al.*, 2021). Given the positive impact of collaboration with external service providers such as autism specialists, the provision for training to educators by specialists in the field needs to be acknowledged and followed up at school, state, and national levels.

Similar to the conclusion that Walton *et al.* (2022) have drawn, an educator in this study argued that if training has to be provided by autism specialists, such training would involve the latest updates in terms of strategies which may be used with learners. Such promptness and updated information are necessary as, when educators are informed of the latest development in research and strategies in the area of autism, this would not only increase the prospect for learners with autism to receive a better quality education (Wilson and Landa, 2019). Indeed, this updated information would also potentially decrease the research-to-practice gap, which educators have lamented within the field of inclusive education (Wilson and Landa, 2019). Further to this, one participant suggested that the training provided by autism specialists should not be limited to educators but should also involve parents. According to this participant, this would enable educators and parents to learn more

about autism. Consequently, this would increase the prospects for educators and parents to benefit from each other's experiences while fostering collaboration.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- Educators in this study have outlined that an opportunity that could enhance their training needs on autism is of **having sessions delivered by autism specialists** (Hamrick *et al.*, 2021).
- Training by autism specialists would **provide updated and timely information** (Walton *et al.*, 2022).
- Training provided by autism specialists **should not be limited to educators but should also involve parents**. According to this participant, this would enable educators and parents to learn more about autism whilst also **benefitting from each other's experience through collaboration**.

Further emerging questions

- **Is training on autism to educators in Malta provided by autism specialists?**

Table 52: Summary of Data: Training by Autism Specialists

It may be noted that if autism specialists had to provide training to educators and parents who support learners with autism in schools, several weaknesses and threats that this research has identified might be mitigated. For instance, training by autism specialists to parents may help overcome the identified weakness of under-involved parents, particularly since parents might not collaborate with schools due to their lack of knowledge about their children's condition. Furthermore, training by autism specialists to educators may help teachers and members of the SLT to

receive more training on autism. Hence this opportunity identified by current research participants in terms of having training by autism specialists may help overcome several weaknesses and threats identified not only in the training process but also within the process of teaching and learning and home-school collaboration.

5.3.4 Threats in training

Teacher preparatory courses lack content on autism: As noted in Table 53, analogously confirming a threat which has been persistently reported internationally during the last decade (Able *et al.*, 2015; Dillenberger *et al.*, 2016; Finch *et al.*, 2013; Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Kossewska *et al.*, 2021; Morrier, Hess and Heflin, 2011; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Ravet, 2018; Tran *et al.*, 2020), the findings of this study indicated that teacher pedagogical courses lack content on how learners with autism may be supported. This situation transpires even though training in the context of the Ecology of Inclusive Education has been identified as the most influential in terms of the extent to which learners are included in the mainstream classroom (Hoskin, Boyle and Anderson, 2015). Verifying educators' views in the study of Hersh and Elley (2019), such lack of training within undergraduate courses may lead to a situation whereby teachers become unable to recognise the needs of learners with autism. Such a lack of pre-service teacher training content on autism could put at risk the quality of support provided to learners, with the possibility of explicitly seeing teachers not applying diverse learning methods according to the specific needs of learners (Saggers *et al.*, 2019). In turn, such a lack of support could lead to lower success rates of inclusive education programs (De la Cruz, 2020) and a situation where teachers cannot cope in class (Teo, Lau and Then, 2022).

Indeed, as discussed in Section 5.2.2., lack of training for teachers impacts the frequency of adaptations provided to learners with autism by teachers and hence would possibly jeopardise the quality of support provided to these learners (Hernández-González *et al.*, 2022). However, it may be argued that, as mentioned in Section 5.2.2., whilst developments within the Ecological Systems Framework are viewed as being under the teacher's control (Hoskin, Boyle and Anderson, 2015), other issues are seen as beyond the control of educators. A case in point would be the current threat of providing training on autism in pre-service teacher courses. Therefore, it may be contended that it is time for such teacher preparatory courses to be vetted for quality in terms of their content, particularly since, as mentioned in previous sections, teachers are very likely to have students with autism in the class due to the increase in the incidence rate. Nevertheless, it is interesting to note that when comparing the data from Figure 31, it may be observed that the level of training educators acquire differs according to the role they are undertaking in schools. For instance, the six participants who answered the questionnaire and carried out duties in schools as Heads of Department who support schools in the area of inclusion seem to be better trained on autism when compared to the training reported by Heads of Schools and Assistant Heads of Schools. The same contradictory views may be seen when comparing the data between KGEs and class teachers, whereby the latter seem to have acquired less training on autism than KGEs.

In order to mitigate the situation in terms of having teacher preparatory courses that lack substantial content that adequately prepares teachers to support learners with autism, participants have identified an opportunity to have more frequent training

provided during school hours. Such content in teacher preparatory courses may provide educators with guidance emerging from their professional experience and expertise to be prepared to meet children's needs consistently and coherently (Predescu, Al-Ghazi and Darjan, 2018).

Current findings and their link to previous ones	Further emerging questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A threat to the training process of educators has been identified in terms of lack of content on how to support students with autism within the content of teacher preparatory courses (Able <i>et al.</i>, 2015; Dillenberger <i>et al.</i>, 2016; Finch <i>et al.</i>, 2013; GOiec-Asian, 2020; Kossewska <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Merrier, Hess and Heflin, 2011; Raudeliunaite and Steponeniene, 2020; Ravet, 2018; Tran <i>et al.</i>, 2020). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How are teacher-preparatory courses vetted for quality in terms of the content (if any) on autism?

Table 53: Summary of Data: Teacher Preparatory Courses

Non-inclusive practice: As noted in Table 54, whilst conceding that teacher preparatory courses lack content on addressing the needs of learners with autism, the findings of this study indicate that this issue leads to non-inclusive practice. Similar to the conclusion drawn by Ferroni-Bast *et al.* (2020), and Huws and Jones (2010), this study has found that a lack of teacher training leads to a context whereby the behaviour of learners with autism is perceived as defiant and disruptive. This perspective could lead teachers to avoid or dislike children with autism (Chung *et al.*, 2015; GOiec-Asian, 2020). Current data has further substantiated previous empirical findings (Boujut *et al.*, 2017; De La Cruz, 2020;

Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Iadarola *et al.*, 2015; Sagers *et al.*, 2019), which indicate that limited teacher training places potential adverse risks on the provision for learners with autism, whereby their needs would possibly not be met inclusively and appropriately (De La Cruz, 2020). Analogous to a previous study, teachers may be less accepting of learners with autism (Leonard and Smyth, 2022). LSEs in this current study reported that when a student throws a tantrum, the teacher might send him out of the classroom. Hence, this leads to an understanding that lack of training and knowledge on autism makes it difficult for teachers to have positive attitudes towards learners with autism (Leonard and Smyth, 2022) and to accept them in their classrooms (Güleç-Aslan, 2020).

Consequently, this would potentially “fuel a culture of exclusion” (Iadarola *et al.*, 2015, p.700), leading to a situation where adapted instruction is not developed according to the needs of learners (Boujout *et al.*, 2019), as students with autism would be perceived as challenging to teach (Ferroni-Bast *et al.*, 2020). The latter confirms that lack of training on autism could threaten the provision for learners on their inclusion, support, and well-being throughout the educational experience. Taken within the Ecology of Inclusive Education context, research to better understand the type of training that promotes attitudinal change towards learners with autism is critical. This inquiry is needed as even though policy development in inclusive education has occurred, attitudes towards implementing this notion may not be happening. Unfortunately, it may be argued that little progress in quality inclusive education would be observed without the knowledge and capacity to shift educators' attitudes.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A threat within the training process in terms of **lack of training for teachers has been perceived as leading to a context whereby the behaviour of learners with autism is perceived as defiant and disruptive** (Ferroni-Bast *et al.*, 2020; Huws and Jones, 2010) and that **teachers become less accepting of learners** with autism (Göle and Aslan, 2020; Leonard and Smyth, 2022).
- Current data has substantiated previous empirical findings (Boujut *et al.*, 2017; De La Cruz, 2020; Göle and Aslan, 2020; Iadarola *et al.*, 2015; Saggars *et al.*, 2019) regarding the issue that **limited teacher training places potential negative risks on the provision for learners with autism whereby their needs would possibly not be met.**

Further emerging questions

- **What type of training** would be effective in **promoting attitudinal change** towards learners with autism?

Table 54: Summary of Data Related: Exclusionary Practice

Training sessions are not mandatory: As noted in Table 55, aligned with the views of previous research (Boujut *et al.*, 2017; Dillenburger *et al.*, 2016; Roberts and Simpson, 2016), the literature indicates that one of the threats located within the training provided to educators on autism is linked to training being non-mandatory for educators. The questionnaire findings and interviewees' views confirmed this, which indicated that training is not accessible during school hours. Hence, any training sought is entirely voluntary (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021; Frantz *et al.*, 2022). Analogous to the findings of Frantz *et al.* (2022), one of the issues leading educators to not participate in training after school hours

is that they are not remunerated for the hours spent in training if they had to seek these after-school hours. In terms of expecting educators to seek training after school hours voluntarily, this situation arises notwithstanding that education and training in autism have been highly prioritised as urgent in school systems (Roberts and Simpson, 2016).

Current findings and their link to previous ones	Further emerging questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A threat to the training process of educators has been identified in terms of lack of content on how to support students with autism within the content of teacher preparatory courses (Able <i>et al.</i>, 2015; Dillenberger <i>et al.</i>, 2016; Finch <i>et al.</i>, 2013; GOiec-Asian, 2020; Kossewska <i>et al.</i>, 2021; Morrier, Hess and Heflin, 2011; Raudeliunaite and Steponeniene, 2020; Ravet, 2018; Tran <i>et al.</i>, 2020). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are teacher-preparatory courses vetted for quality in terms of the content (if any) on autism?

Table 55: Summary of Data: Non-Mandatory Training

On a similar broad point to what Dillenburger *et al.* (2016) and Roberts and Simpson (2016) have previously reported, this study has seen educators arguing that if training is held during school hours, this would become compulsory for all and not sought voluntarily. This finding indicates the need for training for staff induction and CoPE sessions to be held during school hours, particularly since, similar to what happens in Poland, Croatia, North Macedonia, Greece, and Romania, this current study saw participants claiming that courses they underwent on autism were mainly

provided by private entities (Folostina *et al.*, 2022; Lisak Šegota *et al.*, 2022). This finding shows that educators sought training on autism in their own time, on their initiative and by self-financing such courses. If taken from an ecological lens, the fact that training is not mandatory may be seen as stemming from the paradoxical policies sitting at the most indirect child development system (macrosystem), but which may still reinforce the cycle of exclusion given that lack of training will hinder educators from acquiring the necessary skills to support learners with autism. The traits mentioned above make it more difficult for educators to acquire training to support learners with autism, potentially hindering schools from performing at an optimum level regarding the provision for learners with autism. Although, as mentioned earlier, education and training in autism have been highly prioritised as urgent within school systems (Roberts and Simpson, 2016), a gap in how this training transpires during school hours for educators in Malta is identified. This gap calls for further research to establish what hinders schools from creating such training opportunities for potential change.

5.4 The Home-School Collaboration Process

Which are the SWOTs within the home-school collaboration process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Educators' views on the relationship with families of children with IEN, including those with autism, allow for a fruitful discussion (Lalvani, 2015). Collaborative practices enable the proactive involvement of parents of students with autism and help establish effective communication means for families and educators to share strategies and information about the child's progress (Guldborg, 2019).

Bronfenbrenner (1979) and Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014) have delineated the role of parents and their connection with educators within their framework as, according to them, parents directly influence child and learner development at a microsystem level. Thus, the partnership between families and schools should be active and relational, as both parties have a decisive role in establishing what is best for the learner. Considering the points above, this research aimed to identify the SWOTs within the home-school collaboration process of students with autism from educators' perspectives. The following sections shall interpret these views in the context of the previously reviewed literature, the findings of the current studies, and through the lens of the theoretical framework underpinning this research.

5.4.1. Strengths of the home-school collaboration process

Open and frequent communication: The findings of this research indicate that a current strength of the home-school collaboration process is located within schools having frequent and open communication with parents of children with autism. As noted in Table 56, in line with previous research, this study has found that this is beneficial as home-school collaboration enables parents to be kept updated regarding their children's progress (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017).

When elaborating on the rationale of this strength, this study found that open and frequent communication is critical since some children with autism who have limited communication could find it difficult to tell their parents what happened at school. This finding conceives two key benefits regarding schools having open and frequent

communication means with parents of learners with autism. Firstly, similar to international educational contexts, it enables educators in Malta to inform parents about their children's progress (Josilowksi and Morris, 2019; Guldberg, 2019; La Barbera, 2017; Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022). Secondly, through open and frequent communication with parents of children with autism, prompt intervention on any issues that may arise would transpire. Such immediate support would thus avoid a situation where children may “fall through the cracks” (La Barbera, 2017, p. 45) hence confirming the significant beneficial impacts of the home-school collaboration process on the learner’s development and experiences.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A current strength of the collaboration process is located within the ability of having frequent and open communication with parents of children **with autism** as this enables parents to be kept updated regarding their children's progress (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017).
- Similar to what has been reported in other international contexts (Josilowski and Morris, 2019; Guldberg, 2019; La Barbera, 2017; Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022), this current study has also found that the current school strength of having open and frequent communication means with parents not only strengthen home-school partnerships but also enables educators in Malta to **inform parents about the progress their children are making.**
- Current findings have reported that the **most frequently used communication means by educators in Malta is that of communicating with parents through the communication diary and face-to-face meetings** (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017).
- To a **lesser frequency, this study also saw some educators outlining that home-school communication is kept through email, telephone calls and Messenger®** (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019).
- Despite not being able to corroborate this with the findings of previous research, the current study's findings particularly emphasised on **having open and frequent communication with parents since children with autism who have limited communication could find it difficult to tell their parents what happened at school.**
- However, an interesting finding within this study sees **educators admitting to the fact that notwithstanding that the MEYR does not acknowledge Messenger® as part of the official communication means, educators still use it** as, according to them, this serves as a quick method of how to keep collaborative communication with parents.

Further emerging questions

- What are the **parents' preferred modes of communication with the school?**

Table 56: Summary of Data: Open and Frequent Communication

When asked about the means used to communicate with parents, educators in the current study delineated that the most frequently used means were the communication diary and face-to-face meetings. These findings align with existing evidence (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017). Albeit to a lesser frequency than the communication diary and face-to-face meetings, this study has indicated that some educators also use email, telephone calls and Messenger® to maintain contact with parents. Aligned with previous findings (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Azeem, Imran and Khawaja, 2016, Josilowski, 2019; Kurth, Love and Pirtle, 2020), such means were perceived as sources that provide prompt updates to parents on the progress of their children and a way of how two-way collaborative communication is kept.

An interesting finding worth emphasising within this study is how educators 'admit' to using Messenger®, notwithstanding that the MEYR does not acknowledge such source as an official communication means. Nevertheless, given that the voices of parents were missing from this study, future research may consider looking into the preferences of parents in terms of communication means when collaborating with the educators of their children, particularly since this critical interaction at a mesosystem between the home and school (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014) could potentially impact child development and the extent of participation, achievement and values of learners.

Sharing of techniques and resources with parents: As noted in Table 57, The current study has also indicated that another strength within the home-school collaboration process is the possibility of forwarding any approaches used within

the school to parents. This research has seen Maltese participants suggesting that this strength allows them to provide helpful strategies and tips to parents, a view which was also voiced by educators in the U.S., Zambia and China (Busiku and Matafwali, 2022; Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022). A justification emerging from this study related to the need to share strategies with families is linked to the fact that this promotes opportunities for families and schools to work in a synchronised manner on the approaches used and on ways how these may be reinforced (Azad, Marcus and Mandell, 2021; Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016). Such sharing of strategies would enable parents to support the school, particularly in consolidating the material presented in the classroom and within the home environment.

Current findings and their link to previous ones	Further emerging questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A strength of the collaborative process with parents of children with autism in schools in Malta allows educators to forward any approaches used within the school to parents thus allowing for consistency in terms of the implementation of strategies to take place (Azad, Marcus and Mandell, 2021; Busiku and Matafwali, 2022; Hodges <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016, Yan, Hou and Deng, 2022). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the views of parents on the benefits of shared approaches by the school?

Table 57: Summary of Data: Sharing Strategies with Parents

Furthermore, the current study has identified two other focal points on the advantages of sharing strategies with families within the home-school collaboration process. In fact, having school-sharing strategies with parents has been correlated to parents feeling more confident in assisting their children through potentially generalising skills learned at school. The current study has also identified that the sharing of strategies with parents also has a positive effect on educators because this enables educators to feel more self-assured when presenting new material in the classroom since they would have the support of parents in reviewing and practising such skills at home (Josilowski and Morris, 2019). An essential point from the aforementioned is seen arising from the consistency of support across all settings (Hodges *et al.*, 2022), which, as indicated in Section 2.6.2, would therefore make environments more predictable and structured for learners with autism (Clark and Adams, 2020; Lei *et al.*, 2017). However, as already concluded in the previous section, such practical home-school collaboration flourishes if there is good communication between parents and educators, as this would mainly allow parents to actively participate in the decisions taken by the school concerning their children's education (Murray and Mereoiu, 2015).

Parents' provision of information about the child: The current study indicated that educators deem parents as a critical source of information on learners with autism. As noted in Table 58, these findings confirm the existing evidence emerging from the studies of Saggars *et al.* (2019), Schultz *et al.* (2016), Soto-Chodiman, Pooley and Taylor (2012) and may be explained within two key views. Firstly, as indicated in Section 2.6.1., although educators unquestionably have a critical role to play in the placement and education of learners with autism, parents are usually

in a better position than educational professionals to know what is in their own child's interest (Merry, 2020). Secondly, having parents share information with the school about their children will allow educators to instantly be informed about learners' challenges and strengths without wasting time (Schultz *et al.*, 2016). This prompt information will place educators in a better position to provide timely and effective support to the student. This study saw participants highlighting the importance of communication with parents and concluding that parents know their children best (Saggers *et al.*, 2019). Hence, this evidence validated the argument of Merry(2020) in terms of the incontestable role that parents play in the education of their children.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A strength of the collaborative process with parents of children with autism in schools in Malta is **educators seeing parents as a critical source of information about learners with autism** (Saggers *et al.*, 2019; Schultz *et al.*, 2016; Soto-Chodiman, Pooley and Taylor, 2012).
- This study saw participants highlighting the importance of communication with parents and concluding that **parents know their children best** (Saggers *et al.*, 2019).

Further emerging questions

- According to parents, **what are the benefits of sharing information with educators** who support their children?

Table 58: Summary of Data: Parents Sharing Information with Educators

5.4.2 Weaknesses of the home-school collaboration process

Under-involved parents: Aligned to findings conducted in research studies in the U.S., Lithuania, and Australia (Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Schultz *et al.*, 2016), the majority of educator participants in this study perceive that the under-involvement of parents with autism is a weakness of the home-school collaboration process (Table 59). For instance, according to educators' perspectives, some parents did not attend parents' days and did not acknowledge notes written in the communication diary, which hindered home-school collaboration. An explanation as per the perceptions of educators derives from parents perceiving collaboration as an additional responsibility (LaBarbera, 2017) or parents' lack of education regarding children's condition. The implications of this emergent finding may be somewhat unfavourable. Similar to the findings of Josilowski and Morris (2019), the perceptions of the educators in the current study indicate that children's progress tends to be limited when parents do not collaborate with the school since a home-school relationship enhances the reinforcement of resources and approaches (Josilowski, 2019; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Placing this within the Ecology of Inclusive Education context, having parents not collaborating with the school would impact the child's mesosystem, possibly to the detriment of the learner's participation, achievement, and value.

Nevertheless, an opportunity identified by participants in this research has been located in training from specialised trainers outlined in Section 5.3.3., which may mitigate the weakness identified in this section. This training for parents is necessary as there could be situations where parents might not collaborate with

schools due to their lack of knowledge about their children's condition. Indeed, if schools had to organise training for parents by autism specialists may potentially help overcome the identified weakness of under-involved parents.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- The **under-involvement of parents** with autism has been identified as a weakness to the collaborative process between the home and the school (Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017; Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene, 2020; Schultz *et al.*, 2016).
- Examples of under involvement that hinders home-school collaboration within the current study occurred within instances where **parents do not attend parents' days and acknowledging notes written on the communication diary.**
- Educators in the current study saw that **children's progress tends to be limited when parents do not collaborate** with the school since a home-school relationship enhances reinforcement of resources and approaches within the home (Josilowski, 2019; Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene, 2020).

Further emerging questions

- What are the **parents' perspectives in terms of frequency of involvement in the education of their children?**

Table 59: Summary of Data: Under Involved Parents

Parents being in denial: As noted in Table 60, interestingly, this study has unfolded that a weakness within the home-school collaboration process as perceived by

educators is located within the fact that some parents of learners with autism are in denial of their children's condition. Three possible explanations arise from the perceptions of educators who have participated in current and previous studies' findings in terms of denial whereby parents might: i) not recognise their children as being diagnosed with autism (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Tran *et al.*, 2020); ii) choose not to identify their child's condition; (Josilowski, 2019; La Barbera, 2019; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Schultz *et al.*, 2016); iii) not accept the diagnosis (Schultz *et al.*, 2016). Consequently, substantiating the findings from the growing body of literature regarding this issue (Josilowski, 2019; La Barbera, 2019; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Schultz *et al.*, 2016), this research has also reported that children of parents who are in denial tend to experience lower success rates in terms of progress, and may also not receive the support services they need. Unfortunately, this suggests that learners with autism would suffer several consequences in acquiring the support they are entitled to. However, it should be noted that parents may contest these findings since their views on the matter have not been gathered throughout this research study. Hence, future research would need to involve parents for such a weakness to be confirmed or refuted.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A weakness of home-school collaboration has been identified as being located within the fact that **some parents of children with autism are in denial of their children's condition**, possibly leading to lower success rates regarding progress and which would potentially see learners not receiving the support services they need (Josilowski, 2019; La Barbera, 2019; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene, 2020; Schultz *et al.*, 2016).

Further emerging link questions

- **What are the parents' views in terms of what has been implied by educators of them 'being in denial' of their children's diagnosis?**

Table 60: Summary of Data: Denial

5.4.3 Opportunities to the home-school collaboration process

Parent education: Current findings indicate an opportunity to enhance collaboration by providing parents of learners with autism educational/training sessions. Aligned with previous research, having parents knowledgeable on how to support their children has been perceived as an advantage to the school in effectively supporting learners with autism. As noted in Table 61, this may mitigate the identified weaknesses (Section 5.4.2) and the threats (5.4.4) of the home-school collaboration process. Indeed, having parents gain more knowledge in terms of how they may support their children may: i) reduce the stress levels experienced by parents of students with autism; ii) increase the sense of competence of parents in terms of how they may support their children (Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016; Schultz, Schmidt and Stichter, 2011). Given that the parents are placed within the most immediate system (microsystem) within the Ecological Systems

Framework (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979), such reduced stress levels deriving from an increased sense of ability would place parents in a better position to support their children.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- An opportunity that may to enhance home-school collaboration is located of within the provision for **educational/training sessions on autism for parents** (Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016; Schultz, Schmidt and Stichter, 2011).

Further emerging questions

- Which are the **training needs of parents of children with autism?**

Table 61: Summary of Data: Education for Parents

More opportunities to meet with parents: An opportunity identified by current data gathered from this study that may enhance the home-school collaboration process has been located within the creation of opportunities for more frequent meetings between parents and educators. As noted in Table 62, aligned with Azad, Wolk and Mandell's (2018) conclusions, educators in primary schools in Malta believe that creating more opportunities to meet parents would allow them to voice their concerns, bring forward their queries and present their ideas. The latter may be seen as a characteristic that enhances further the home-school collaborative process, mainly since this not only allows educators to 'show off the progress of students to parents but also allows parents to share specific information about their children's strengths and needs (Schultz *et al.*, 2016). Such opportunities in enabling parents to have frequent meetings with the school may also mitigate the weakness of having under-involved parents, as identified by participants in the current

research study. Given that parents' voices were missing from this research, future research may inquire about parental satisfaction related to the frequency of meetings between the home and the school as opportunities to discuss progress or concerns, enhancing their involvement accordingly.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- An opportunity identified by current data gathered from this study was located within the creation of opportunities for **more frequent meetings between parents and educators** (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018).

Further emerging questions

- **How satisfied are parents in terms of the frequency of meetings between the home-school as opportunities to discuss any progress or concerns?**

Table 62: Summary of Data: Frequency of Meetings

Being sensitive to the needs of parents: Being empathic towards the difficulties of parents with autism was brought forward as one of the external opportunities that could enhance the collaborative process between parents and educators. As noted in Table 63, substantiating the point of view of Josilowski (2019), this study acknowledged that when parents are aware that the school is sensitive to their challenges, collaboration tends to be reinforced. Consequently, this would possibly see schools better locating the necessary support for learners with autism (La Barbera, 2017) whilst also helping parents with the identification of any challenges and supporting them even when significant transitions in the life of learners with autism take place (Mereoiu, Abercrombie and Murray, 2016). Following the findings of this research study regarding a threat related to having parents of learners with autism encountering psychological stress and depression, consequently leaving them with less energy to collaborate with schools, the fact that schools are more

sensitive to their needs may mitigate such a threat. Nevertheless, given that parents' voices were missing from this research, future research may inquire about parental satisfaction regarding schools' level of empathy towards them.

Taken from the Ecological Systems perspective (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979), the major transitions in the life of learners with autism may be viewed from a chronosystem level. Indeed, the major transition that learners have to go through when moving from primary to secondary school would see the chronosystem providing prospects for issues that need to change and evolve regarding the support provided to learners with autism. Therefore, inclusive education could be seen as an influential and progressive process.

Current findings and their link to previous ones	Further emerging questions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being emphatic towards the difficulties of parents with autism was brought forward as one of the external opportunities that could enhance the collaborative process between parents and educators (Josilowski, 2019). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the parents' views on the level of satisfaction in terms on how empathy is demonstrated towards them by schools?

Table 63: Summary of Data: Empathy Towards Parents

5.4.4 Threats to the home-school collaboration process

Psychological well-being of parents: As noted in Table 64, a threat brought forward by educator participants in this research further substantiates the significant body of literature on the topic (Bonis, 2016; Cooke, Smith, and Brenner, 2020; Da

Paz, Wallander, and Tiemensma, 2018; Giovagnoli *et al.*, 2015; Lalvani, 2015; LeBlanc *et al.*, 2020; Shepherd *et al.*, 2018; Zaidman-Zait *et al.*, 2017). This threat has been perceived by educators as being located among parents of learners with autism encountering psychological stress and depression, consequently leaving them with less energy to collaborate with schools.

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A threat brought forward by this research further confirms the significant body of literature on the topic is related to **parents of learners with autism encountering psychological stress may leave them with less energy to collaborate with schools** (Bonis, 2016; Cooke, Smith, and Brenner, 2020; Da Paz, Wallander, and Tiemensma, 2018; Giovagnoli *et al.*, 2015; Lalvani, 2015; LeBlanc *et al.*, 2020; Shepherd *et al.*, 2018; Zaidman-Zait *et al.*, 2017).

Further emerging questions

- **Do parents of children with autism feel that their child's condition has impacted their psychological well-being and whether this has impacted the levels of collaboration with schools?**

Table 64: Summary of Data: Psychological Well-Being of Parents

Two critical points have been identified from the educators' perspectives as providing a potential explanation concerning this threat. Firstly, grief and loss will likely manifest in the parents' lives of children with a disability, including those with autism (Lalvani, 2015). Secondly, bringing up a child with a disability, including one with autism, may be "a struggle", may "drain their emotions", and may also "wear them out" (Lalvani, 2015, p.386). An implication of the latter, as indicated by this research, and that is aligned with findings from the previous but relevant studies of

Lalvani (2015) and Azad Wolk and Mandell (2018), is that such stressors impact partnerships and ideal interactions between the home and school, which consequently could, in turn, affect the child's progress. However, as already mentioned in previous sections, given that the voices of parents of children with autism are missing from the current research, future research would need to be conducted for Maltese parents to verify whether or not their child's condition has impacted their psychological well-being.

Education not given priority: As noted in Table 65, a further threat indicated in the current empirical research and which echoed the perspectives of educators in Canada and Lithuania (Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020) saw educators in Malta reporting that some parents may not always prioritise the education of their children. According to the current research, educators have outlined that the lack of prioritisation of their children's education from the parents' end places the collaborative process between the home and the school at risk. This finding may be explained by the fact that a subsequent mixed-method study that involved 102 educators also saw participants outlining that not all parents hold the same views related to levels of priority on education, whereby this may lead parents not to be entirely willing to become involved in their child's education (LaBarbera, 2017). An implication of this threat, as it emerges within current and previous research, sees educators feeling frustrated as no common language between the home and the school is ever established hence, making the educational process for learners with autism "more complicated" (Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė 2020, p. 2017).

Current findings and their link to previous ones

- A threat outlined in this empirical research and which echoed the perspectives of educators in Canada and Lithuania (Lindsay et al., 2013; Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene, 2020) saw educators in Malta reporting that **some parents may not always give the education of learners with autism priority.**
- **Educators feel frustrated** when no common language between the home and the school is ever established (Raudeli0naite and Steponeniene 2020).
- The current research also reported on the fact that even when educators made specific contact with parents to inform them about daily happenings in the classroom, **parents were perceived as not providing sufficient follow-up communication** despite the fact that the purpose was to generate effective partnerships between the home and school (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018).

Further emerging questions

- What are **the views of parents in terms of their levels of collaboration and involvement** within the education process of children?

Table 65: Summary of Data: Education Not a Priority

The current research also reported on the fact that even when educators made specific contact with parents to inform them about daily happenings in the classroom, parents were perceived as not providing sufficient follow-up, even though the purpose was to generate effective partnerships between the home and school (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018). In turn, this tends to further place at risk the provision for learners with autism as the intention of collaboration is to create consistency for learners across both settings (Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018),

mainly due to the challenges faced in the areas of restrictive and repetitive behaviour patterns (American Psychiatric Association, 2013; World Health Organization, 2019). Nevertheless, one should note that the data in this study is linked to educators' perceptions. Thus, this data might not concord with the same views parents might have.

5.5 The Relationship of the Located SWOTs, the Ecological Systems Framework and the Provision for Learners with Autism

Given that the learners' development is impacted by the interconnections between different systems (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014; Bronfenbrenner, 1979), it is critical to appraise the correlations of the SWOTs within the teaching and learning, training for educators and home-school collaboration to the learners' ecological systems. Figure 44 illustrates the position of each located SWOT emerging from the findings of this research study within the Ecological Systems Framework.

Figure 44: The Relationship Between the Located SWOTs, the Ecological Systems Framework and the Provision for Learners with Autism

Several scholars who conducted research on the teaching and learning process of learners with autism (e.g. Bolourian *et al.*, 2022; Clark *et al.*, 2020; Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021; Hersh and Elley, 2019; Leonard and Smyth, 2022; Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponienė, 2020), training for educators (e.g. Curtin and Long, 2021; Siggers *et al.*, 2019; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019) and home-school collaboration (e.g. Azad, Wolk and Mandell, 2018; Josilowski, 2019) have indicated that the inclusion of learners with autism in schools

is dependent on the consistency and adjustments that arise in the setting that the learner is part of. Thus, if appropriate structures are not in place, schools cannot go through the necessary reform leading to changes and modifications in educational content and approaches. The latter will eventually enable learners, including those with autism, to overcome barriers through an equitable and participatory learning experience that best corresponds to their needs and preferences (United Nations, 2016, para. 11). Given this, the following section will present how the SWOTs in each area are positioned in the learners' ecological systems and how the strengths and the opportunities may be used to overcome the weaknesses and the threats.

As discussed in Section 5.2, findings from the current study outline that the availability of adaptations of instructions for learners with autism, which takes the form of visual and tangible content, step-by-step instruction and digitalised learning tools, has been acknowledged as a strength of the provision (e.g. Ayuningtyas *et al.*, 2021; Cooper *et al.*, 2022; Curtin and Long, 2021; Dijkhuis *et al.*, 2020; Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou, 2021; Jimenez and Besaw, 2020; Lindsay *et al.*, 2014; Tynan and Davy, 2021; Van Der Steen *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019). Positioned at the microsystem within the ecological system of the learner with autism, it is presumed that adaptations to the curriculum would positively impact the learners' participation, achievement and value. Nevertheless, as already noted in Section 5.2.2, a weakness in the teaching process has been identified in schools lacking resources (e.g. Lindsay *et al.*, 2013; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Tran *et al.*, 2020; Yazici and McKenzie, 2019). Therefore, despite the attempt to implement strategies to include learners with autism, it may be argued that, if it is the case that some schools lack resources, this

might jeopardise the provision for learners with autism. To mitigate this risk, the support from the SLT may help parents, teachers and LSEs to negotiate access to resources, particularly if these may perhaps be requested to support a few learners with autism (e.g. Lloyd, 2019; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020; Stadnick et al., 2019; Symes and Humphrey, 2011). Positioning these interactions as happening at a mesosystem level, such relationships between educational stakeholders responsible for including learners with autism in mainstream schools would promote an egalitarian process whereby learners would be provided with what they merit regarding their right to access quality education.

Another weakness in the provision is related to LSEs being the ones to create the adaptations of learners with autism in the majority of situations, with teachers perhaps taking a more passive role regarding this (Breyer, Lederer and Gasteiger-Klicpera, 2021; Carter, Stephenson and Webster, 2019; Fisher and Pleasants, 2011; Holmes and Butcher, 2020; Jellinek *et al.*, 2020). Hence despite having adaptations to the curriculum as a strength located at the learners' most immediate system, the classroom culture in terms of who is responsible for such adaptations questions the impact of adaptations in terms of the levels of participation, achievement and value of the learner. It may be argued that LSEs should not shoulder all the responsibility regarding the adaptations as LSEs should facilitate the support process for learners with autism and not be the exclusive source of support (Giangreco, 2013). This is because, at a microsystem level, the teachers' and the LSEs' roles and responsibilities closely involve collaborating throughout the planning, delivery and evaluation of every lesson and supporting inclusion by ensuring that students can access all aspects of learning.

Nevertheless, it may be argued that the emergence of having some teachers not involved in adapting the curriculum for learners with autism could transpire because most teachers are not adequately trained. In this research study, teacher preparatory courses seem to be lacking substantial content on autism and this has been located as a threat located at the macrosystem. However, despite being located at the farthest level of the ecological systems framework, this development is one whereby lack of it would still impact the teaching and learning, thus further influencing the participation, achievement and value of the learner. Indeed, such lack of knowledge on how to address the needs of learners with autism emerging from limited teacher training places potential adverse risks on the provision for learners with autism, whereby their needs would possibly not be met inclusively and appropriately. A weakness of training also located at the macrosystem level has been related to the aspect of it being provided to educators after being recruited in the classroom. This situation tends to leave educators basing their support strategies on trial-and-error approaches, which may not always favour the learners' needs. Therefore, it may be posited that if educators are actively involved in training on how to support learners with autism, this will benefit the learners' educational experience, therefore, enhancing learners' participation, achievement and value.

Nonetheless, although training in terms of support is critical, this research has located that lack of training on policy content and its implementation is placing at risk the provision for learners with autism who attend mainstream schools in Malta. Indeed, despite being located at the macrosystem within the framework of Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler (2014), the political and accountability contexts impact how provision for learners with autism is shaped. Indeed, through knowledge

of policy and its implementation, learners' achievement and the professional performance of educators may be preserved (Anderson, Boyle and Deppeler, 2014). Yet, as discussed in previous sections, it is through training for educators that such knowledge leading to implementation emerges since Darling-Hammond (2020) argues that it is through professional development that quality assurance systems based on high-quality support programmes for learners are established. When educators do not have the skills to implement policy, there is minimal progress in providing inclusive teaching and learning for learners with autism. This leads to a situation where the “status quo” in terms of lack of quality of education continues to dominate the placement of learners (Walton *et al.*, 2022). This, in turn, would impede reform in terms of the provision to take place (e.g., Abed, Jameel, and Ahmad, 2021; Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Xu, 2012), thus consequently seeing learners with autism potentially experiencing high levels of exclusion and academic underachievement (Hebron, 2018; Maciver *et al.*, 2021; Paget *et al.*, 2018). In fact, this situation would potentially also increase the levels of the current threat located within the exosystem in terms of potentially reinforcing the implementation of the non-inclusive practice.

Further to the aforementioned, such lack of knowledge on policy might not only impact teaching and learning designs, but also classroom setups. Similar to what other studies have concluded (Jones, Hanley and Riby, 2020; Nthibeli, Griffiths and Bekker, 2022), this study found that the ‘sensory’ clutter found in classrooms makes it challenging for learners with autism to function in that environment. This being a weakness located at a microsystem might be overcome if training is thus provided before educators are appointed as opposed to what currently occurs both locally

and internationally (e.g. Anglim, Prendeville and Kinsella, 2017; Devi and Ganguly, 2022; Frantz *et al.*, 2022; Sulek *et al.*, 2019). Indeed, over-sensory stimuli in the classroom environment could be avoided if educators were aware of its negative impact on learners, with them potentially being more prepared to modify the classroom environment, thus making it more autism friendly. Given that the classroom physical space is located in the learners' microsystem, the positive impact on the participation and achievement of learners with autism would possibly increase as they would experience fewer sensory overloading episodes.

In view of the aforementioned situation, quiet spaces have been recommended by current research participants as an opportunity located within the microsystem that could enhance the provision, particularly when learners feel the need to retreat when requiring time to calm down or to carry out work in a quiet area. However, it should be noted that careful consideration regarding the use of quiet areas is critical since, whilst some students would need them to escape the overwhelming environment of the classroom, other learners may perceive this as 'free time' to escape tasks that need to be carried out in the classroom. Given this, soliciting the expertise of professionals such as psychologists, autism specialists, and speech therapists as support service providers located at the exosystem level, may help schools design and use these spaces. This is especially necessary since as Dukpa, Carrington and Mavropoulou (2021) argued and as already stated in Section 5.2.3, teaching in self-contained classrooms may lead to micro-exclusion, where students are segregated from their neurotypical peers. The latter is a practice that is inconsistent with inclusive pedagogy. Hence, appropriate consideration of the

design of quiet spaces is critical to avoid a situation that might jeopardise the inclusive provision for learners with autism in mainstream schools.

To bridge some of the aforementioned gaps so as to safeguard the inclusion of learners with autism in mainstream schools, according to the findings of this study, training for educators should: i) be provided during school hours (exosystem); ii) be based on the training needs of educators (exosystem); iii) be less theoretical (macrosystem); iv) present more user-friendly strategies (exosystem); v) allow educators to share their practice with colleagues(exosystem). Such training characteristics might help overcome two threats identified in the current study, which are located in the macrosystem and the exosystem. These threats are related to the fact that participation in training is voluntary and provided after educators are appointed to work in schools.

Nevertheless, the school's culture, values and ideologies may also potentially enhance the home-school collaboration process. Indeed, located at an exosystem level, an emphatic approach towards the needs of parents would potentially see educators being more sensitive to their needs. The latter has been located as an opportunity to the home-school collaboration process within this study, whereby its impact favours both parents and learners. Indeed, LaBarbera (2017) argues that when schools understand the challenges and frustrations that their students' families encounter, this encourages parents and families to be more involved in the home-school collaborative process. Such an empathic approach being an opportunity located at the exosystem would potentially mitigate the threat located at

the microsystem in terms of having parents of learners with autism encountering psychological stress and depression, consequently leaving them with less energy to collaborate with schools. This might explain why some parents might not give education priority and may be under-involved as the latter and the former may be repercussions emerging from the experiences they may encounter. Hence, schools need to increase their empathy levels towards parents with autism since research has consistently reported that families of children with autism may experience greater stress levels than those of children with any other developmental disability (e.g., Bonis, 2016; Cooke, Smith, and Brenner, 2020; Da Paz, Wallander and Tiemensma, 2018; Giovagnoli *et al.*, 2015; LeBlanc *et al.*, 2020; Shepherd *et al.*, 2018; Zaidman-Zait *et al.*, 2017).

Furthermore, as discussed in Section 5.4.2, a weakness that emerged was that educators perceive that some parents may be in denial of their child's condition. This identified weakness located in the microsystem adds to the need for educators to be more sensitive to parents' needs. This is because, denial in terms of accepting a diagnosis of autism has several implications impacting the participation, value and achievement of learners with autism, with these being evident when parents delay seeking advice from professionals to get the necessary diagnosis and support and when parents display a lack of interest in partnering with the school (Josilowksi, 2019; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). These situations tend to see learners with autism not getting timely support, thus resulting in lower success rates and a lack of services to which learners are entitled to (Josilowksi, 2019; Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė, 2020). Hence compassion as an opportunity in the home-school collaboration process would see: i) educators being more sensitive

towards the difficulties of parents with autism; ii) collaboration potentially being reinforced; iii) potentially seeing an amelioration in the quality of the teaching and learning process; iv) an increase in the progress made by learners with autism.

Given that a current school strength located at the mesosystem level in terms of home-school collaboration seems to emerge from schools having open communication channels with parents mainly based on the communication book, meetings, emails and telephone calls, these means may be perceived as something which would allow educators to reach out to parents who may need support. Furthermore, the open communication channels would continue to support the current strengths of home-school collaboration as educators and parents can continue to share strategies and techniques of support for skills to be reinforced at school and home. As discussed in Section 5.4.1, the latter is critical as when educators share strategies with parents, this optimises individualised educational service provision whilst also enabling learners with autism to feel more confident with the new material presented in class since parents review and practise such skills at home (Azad, Marcus and Mandell, 2021; Josilowksi and Morris, 2019). All the aforementioned are connected through the mesosystem whereby the collaborative of parents and educators influence the school microsystem positively impacting the levels of participation, achievement and values of the learner on the spectrum. Hence, as suggested through the current research findings, creating further opportunities to meet with parents would potentially enhance the home-school collaboration process whereby all key stakeholders, including the learners, would benefit from this positive partnership.

Positive partnerships between the home and the school would also potentially enhance peer support. Peer support is a critical part of the provision as it is located in the school microsystem. In view of this, a healthy home-school collaboration must be kept, especially to bring parents who may assent to PPPs on board. In fact, given that some parents might hesitate to consent to the implementation of PPP, a good and trusting collaborative relationship would potentially see the school explaining to them the process of such a programme, its benefits and its positive impact on learners with autism. Given this, the current strength in terms of learners with autism receiving support from their neurotypical peers would potentially see them overcome the challenges they might encounter in the social communication domain.

This chapter has focused on a discussion of the findings derived from the questionnaires and interviews of participants. This discussion occurred in view of the literature reviewed in Chapter 2 and in light of the Ecological System Theories. This section acknowledged that the presented data derives from educators' perceptions and that parents may contest these results. Nevertheless, this discussion enabled me as the researcher to interpret the data collected following questionnaires and interviews with educators. The following chapter shall provide conclusions, recommendations to policymakers and practitioners and suggestions for further research. It will also discuss the strengths and limitations of the current study.

Chapter 6: Conclusions and Recommendations

This study set out to respond to several research questions related to the provision for learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta. Through the implementation of a sequential explanatory research design, the SWOTs located within the process of teaching and learning, the process of training for educators, and the process of home-school collaboration were explored. This chapter concludes by foregrounding several limitations, the implications for policy and practice, and recommendations for practitioners, policymakers, and future research.

6.1 The SWOTs and the Provision for Learners with Autism

The combination of the findings on the existing SWOTs supports the conceptual premise that schools may lack adequate support from the exosystem, which threatens their provision for learners with autism. This research has concluded that the inclusive attitude educators are expected to have is not always existent, with inclusion being misunderstood by many. An implication of this is the possibility that learners with autism would be merely placed in mainstream schools. Hence, a 'one-size-fits-all' would persist, thus leaving many learners with autism to experience high levels of exclusion and academic underachievement (Hebron, 2018; Maciver *et al.*, 2021; Paget *et al.*, 2018).

A further justification of the aforementioned has emerged from the finding that educators lack clarity on existing policies on inclusion and this may lead to such pit-

falls within the provision (e.g. Abed, Jameel and Ahmad, 2021; Forlin, 2006; Lessner Listiakova and Preece, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019; Xu, 2012). This study concluded that at the school microsystem level, there appears to be a disposition where there is a lack of specificity in the roles and responsibilities of educators due to such ambiguity in terms of what policies entail (Raudelinait and Steponnien, 2020; Silveira-Zaldivara and Curtis, 2019). This tendency was evident when this study revealed that LSEs mainly develop the adaptations of students with autism, and when students with autism need the help of teachers, they are directed to address the LSE. This weakness in the provision transpires despite the promising scenario established by the current research in terms of having the aspect of adaptations to the curriculum being classified as a strength located in the microsystem with these being based on step-by-step instruction, visual support, tangibles, and the use of technology. At the macrosystem level, this study found that teachers are undertrained to support learners with autism due to a lack of content on autism in teacher preparation courses. This has led to a situation where LSEs tend to develop adaptations rather than teachers. Another implication in terms of the threat located in terms of lack of content on autism in teacher preparatory courses is linked to feelings of unpreparedness on how to support learners with autism, which consequently impacts the morale of educators, leads to high levels of burn-out, and sees educators becoming increasingly anxious and stressed. The latter may also potentially lead to a context in which learners with autism are perceived as defiant and disruptive (Ferroni-Bast *et al.*, 2020; Huws and Jones, 2010) and teachers become less accepting of learners with autism (Güleç-Aslan, 2020; Leonard and Smyth, 2022). Thus, future evaluations of how teachers and LSEs collaborate in the design and development of instruction for learners with

autism may shed some light on this issue to provide relevant and valid recommendations for this situation to possibly ameliorate itself. Furthermore, while having the SLT's support as a strength in the microsystem, school administration members may also monitor whether and how collaboration between the teacher and the LSE is taking place in terms of the development of support for learners with autism.

Further to the aforementioned and despite it being located at the macrosystem, level, this study established that an identified development placing at risk the provision has seen this study concluding that training is provided after educators are recruited, with many educators perceiving this as relatively late. Furthermore, this study concluded that this training is voluntary if not offered during school hours. Evidence emerging from this research has seen the location of hours provided for CoPE sessions, and the training provided by external service providers, as effective ways of how schools may increase training opportunities for all staff members. Yet, as further concluded by this study, it is critical that training content is less theoretical, is based on user-friendly strategies, continues to allow educators to share strategies, focuses on policy content and implementation and is provided according to the educators' training needs. This type of training will potentially lessen the instances where educators implement approaches on a 'trial and error' basis. Further training, which includes the characteristics above, might also provide scope whereby the threat located at the exosystem level in terms of having unclear perspectives on inclusion is minimised.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that the implementation of the Autism State Plan (Cap. 557, Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government) and the Inclusive Education Policy and its Framework (MEYR, 2022a; MEYR, 2022b) are still in their early stages of implementation. Indeed, the targets set are being gradually implemented as of this scholastic year (2022-2023). Therefore, the findings concerning the lack of clarity of policies and their lack of translation into practice require more solid future evaluations. A further pertinent question relates to whether quality assurance strategies concerning the training provided on autism are put in place by educational authorities. This issue is worth a future evaluation to establish the level of quality in terms of training. Such quality evaluation would possibly shed light on the length of training, its mode of delivery, and content to identify the existing gaps and make the necessary modifications to such programmes.

The training characteristics at an exosystem level outlined above may also help mitigate the weaknesses located in the microsystem of what this study has concluded in terms of educators perceiving that the mainstream primary classroom settings in Malta are inadequately set up for learners with autism. Such inadequacy in their physical environment could hinder the provision for learners with autism, particularly since some may experience sensory overload. This study concluded that educators in Malta are calling for establishing quiet and multisensory spaces to address sensory overload issues, which could improve the provision. Nevertheless, how these spaces should be established is still unclear, as this study saw mixed perspectives on whether these areas should be developed in or outside the classroom. This study revealed that some educators feel that learners with autism may perceive this time out of the class as 'free time'. Therefore, when creating such

spaces, schools should consider the specific needs of children with autism, as whilst some would prefer to retreat for some quiet time outside of the classroom, others may feel overwhelmed by the transition of moving from one area to another. Thus, every school needs to conduct its evaluation regarding the creation of quiet spaces, as it would enable them to establish the way forward regarding setting up these areas. It would be a good idea that when conducting such evaluations, the views of external support providers, parents and learners with autism are included, as this would provide the school with a clear picture of what is considered an 'autism-friendly' space.

Addressing the research questions of the present study on the SWOTs within the process of home-school collaboration, this study was able to conclude that at the mesosystem level, open and frequent communication is a strength of home-school collaboration, in particular since this enables educators and parents to share pertinent information about their children and also share resources and techniques across all contexts. According to educators in this study, such communication occurs through the use of means such as the communication diary, meetings, e-mails, telephone calls and social media.

An interesting finding emerging from this study worth commenting upon as it contributes to current knowledge was the indication that some educators use Messenger[®] to communicate with parents, even though this is not an official communication channel of the MEYR. Yet, it may be argued that educators use such means as they would use whatever is convenient for parents to establish home-school collaboration. However, this conclusion needs to be cautiously

considered, mainly since following the COVID-19 pandemic, LSEs have been given further directions by MEYR to solely resort to the use of the communication diary as the official means of communication with parents of children with a statement of needs, including those with autism. Still, although this finding cannot be extrapolated to all educators, this is critical. However, more research needs to identify whether this mode has increased remarkably since the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic or whether chat functions have become the current digitalised communication trend. Further research could also look into the parents' most preferred means of communication, potentially filling this gap since parental involvement was lacking within this research study.

Notwithstanding the emergence of the strengths that positively impact the relationship between educators and parents within this research, particularly since both stakeholders are part of the microsystem, the sequential explanatory design applied in this study involving educators' views concluded that some parents do not perceive their children's education as a priority and are under-involved in the home-school collaboration process. According to educator participants in this study, the significant implication of the aforementioned is that parents may not follow through with the support recommended by the school within the home environment (Schultz *et al.*, 2016). However, this data must be interpreted with caution since the ability to collaborate with schools differs from parent to parent. While some educators have delineated that parents may deny their child's condition, impacting the microsystem, others could be going through psychological stress. Hence, educators must be empathic and sensitive to the parents' needs and backgrounds, as this family-

centred practice tends to increase collaboration between home and school (Josilowski, 2019; LaBarbera, 2017).

Nevertheless, the above finding cannot be generalised to the entire parent population since parents were not part of this research. Thus, their views cannot be compared to those of educators. Therefore, this information must be considered, deliberated vigilantly, and treated with caution, as the parents' views may considerably contradict those of educators. Making parental participation feasible to gain their perspectives on home-school collaboration is necessary, enabling this area to be appraised. Nonetheless, opportunities located at an exosystem level brought forward, and which schools can implement to enhance the home-school collaboration process, are the provision for more meetings with parents and the development of training opportunities for parents. Asking the parents what their needs are regarding knowledge and skills on autism would possibly facilitate the process for schools to organise training sessions relevant to parents of children with autism.

The current research further established that educators view peers as a means of support and classified this as a strength located at the microsystem. This study identified two key strategies implemented in terms of peer support: the 'buddy system' and the PPP. According to this study, their benefits are two-fold: these are not only strategies for facilitating peer support for learners with autism but also enable neurotypical developing learners to become more accepting towards others and to develop empathy and tolerance. Despite this optimistic conclusion, this study has seen educators commenting on two key points schools must consider before

implementing these two strategies. According to the educators participating in this study, it would be 'unfair' if the same children were repeatedly assigned to support learners with autism. Indeed, the 'buddy' supporting the student with autism needs to be designated on a rotation basis. Due to this area being under-researched, it would also be interesting to gather the views of peers of learners with autism to be able to gather their perspectives regarding the implementation of buddy systems.

When debating PPPs, educators argued that for it to be implemented, consent from the parents of children with a statement of needs, including those with autism, is required. Indeed, without parental consent, educators cannot implement the PPP. This study concluded that whereas parents sometimes approach the school to implement PPP, other parents do not consent for these to occur. Given these findings, it is recommended that further research on the latter is conducted to provide a clearer picture of how lack of parental consent leading to the inability to implement PPPs impacts schools, educators, peers, and learners with autism. It would also be interesting to gather parents' views on what leads them to consent or not to implement PPPs in schools since this is an under-researched area.

When this research inquired about the availability of resources, this study revealed mixed perspectives. The quantitative findings placed the lack of resources as one significant weakness located at the microsystem hindering schools from reaching their planned goals for learners with autism. Nevertheless, when qualitative data was gathered, members of the Schools' administration delineated that ample resources are available within schools. However, an LSE participant contested this view and reported that parents might be asked to purchase resources themselves,

particularly if specific resources benefit only one student. However, this finding must be considered cautiously since parents' views were absent from this research study. Hence, further research could delve deeper into the structure of Maltese schools on budgeting and investment for learners with autism and the parent's perspective in this regard. Gathering such data would better determine whether schools lack resources to support learners with autism whilst also identifying its impact within the provision for learners with autism.

As suggested in previous research (Daly *et al.*, 2016; Cloninger, 2017; Mercieca and Mercieca, 2022), this study concluded that supporting external services such as autism specialists, psychologists, and speech therapists would provide an opportunity at an exosystem level that enhances the teaching and learning process of learners with autism. This perspective emerges as educators not only view such support as benefitting learners but also as one which benefits them in receiving recommendations of how they may support learners in providing further recommendations. However, given that, as per the conclusion of the current research, psychological intervention in schools is lacking due to factors such as understaffing, further studies could look into the extent of the characteristics of such service provision. The appraisal of this service is critical as through their assessments and intervention, psychologists would be able to identify the children's needs and recommend how these may be met (Mercieca and Mercieca, 2022).

The conclusions reported here shed new light on the current characteristics within the provision for learners with autism in schools in Malta and the rationale behind these SWOTs. The SWOT analysis method to outline the provisions' strengths,

weaknesses, opportunities, and threats may be applied to other settings that support learners with autism worldwide. These conclusions make a valid contribution to the educational community to understand and ponder upon the SWOTs within the provision and their rationale. Given that this is the first study seeking the existing SWOTs from a cohort of educators working in primary schools in Malta, this research also makes an important contribution to the current literature and research community.

6.2 The Limitations of the Current Study

Limitations are constraints beyond the researcher's control which could affect the study's outcome (Simon and Goes, 2013; Theofanidis and Fountouki, 2019). Some researchers argue that limitations in research are closely associated with the choice of methodology and the research design (Theofanidis and Fountouki, 2019). However, other scholars argue that limitations are not only limited to the latter. Simon and Goes (2013) assert that studies may also encounter restrictions related to contacting and approaching certain individuals within an organisation to access certain documents and specific data. However, through reflexivity, I, as the researcher, have engaged in critical self-reflection to recognise these limitations to monitor, control and possibly overcome them throughout the research.

Despite the abovementioned limitations, these still provide an in-depth perspective on autism. Given that the area is considerably understudied, with no research on SWOTs and the provision for learners with autism locally or internationally, a key strength of this research is that it fills a considerable number of gaps and makes a

valid contribution to the current knowledge. This is the first study that explored the provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta through a SWOT analysis framework. Furthermore, this is also the first study that has used a sequential explanatory research design to not only explore characteristics within the provision and their SWOTs, but also to seek in-depth justifications for the identified findings from the voices of educators. This design enabled the research study to fulfil all its aims successfully, address the research questions, and contribute to current knowledge, literature, and awareness of autism.

6.2.1 Lack of locally published research

This research has encountered limitations related to what is outlined by Simon and Goes (2013) and Theofanidis and Fountouki (2019) and directly related to certain documents and data. Indeed, whilst looking into published literature concerning the educational provision for learners with autism in schools in Malta, I, as the researcher, found only one study on the topic. The only published study on scholarly databases that researched one facet of the provision for learners with autism in Malta was a study that looked into implementing EBPs for learners with autism (Sciberras, 2018). Although appraisal towards the only study about the provision for learners with autism in Malta was made, comparison to other international studies dominated this research. Shipman (2014) argues that all human beings, including professionals, form part of different groups that share different beliefs, belong to different disciplines, and specialise in different areas. Hence, generalisation concerning this research may be limited because it was compared only to the

available international research, which may have included samples that belong to educational systems differing from the ones in the current research study.

6.2.2 Limitations related to sample size

Despite adopting a mixed-methods approach based on self-administered questionnaires and interviews with self-selected participants, this research has also seen several limitations related to the sample size. The distribution of the questionnaire and requests for voluntary participation in a semi-structured interview were made following a national lockdown by the Maltese authorities due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. This lockdown required schools in Malta to physically close down and resulted in educators working from home, mainly using online teaching methods. Consequently, educators were spending significant time on their computers. Hence, having 'digitally fatigued' educators could have contributed to the low response rate. Distinctly, this phenomenon related to digital fatigue has been acknowledged by Oducado (2021), who, following research on the experience of teachers following remote learning, termed this phenomenon 'Zoom Fatigue'. Other researchers who, like Oducado (2021), looked into educators' perspectives on remote teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic, termed such fatigue as 'technostress' (e.g. Estrada-Muñoz *et al.*, 2021; Nang, Maat and Mahmud, 2022). Furthermore, another limitation that could have impacted the sample size of this research was communication by one of the teachers' unions in Malta (MUT). Communication by this Union was disseminated to all its members as it received complaints that state primary schools were receiving an overwhelming number of requests for their staff to participate in research studies (Appendix 10).

Despite that purposive sampling was employed with the research selection criteria, thus involving educators working in a state mainstream primary school setting in Malta and also educators who have in some way or another supported learners with autism in mainstream primary schools, this research still gathered data which is relevant and valid in answering its research questions. Through purposive sampling, the study could stipulate the necessary characteristics of the population of interest and, hence, gather data from the individuals with those pre-established characteristics (Johnson and Christensen, 2013). As the researcher, this sampling procedure enabled me to increase the prospects of generalising the findings gathered from educators to the wider population (Johnson and Christensen, 2013). However, limitations in the sample size persisted not only because the data emerging from this study involved a limited sample of 53 questionnaire respondents and five interview participants but also because my initial intentions as the researcher to involve parents yielded unsatisfactory findings. Hence this research had to take a different turn. Indeed, although parents of students with autism were approached through a series of attempts, including social media and associations for parents of children with autism, this resulted in a nil response. Such lack of participation could have transpired due to the unprecedented school lockdown following a substantial rise in the cases of COVID-19 in Malta. This lockdown made it difficult for me to approach parents of students with autism, particularly by gaining access from schools. Despite trying to reach out through other communication methods, such as email and social media, no parents contacted me to participate in this study.

Supporting the above-mentioned issues concerning the limited sample in this research, both regarding educator and parent participants, are the reports of a study which involved the views of other researchers in the field who were also conducting research on autism during the COVID-19 pandemic period (Harrop *et al.*, 2021). This study which surveyed respondents who had been actively involved in research projects related to autism or neurodevelopmental disorders when the pandemic started, saw over 80% of the respondents stating that recruitment of human subjects paused or was significantly reduced by two-thirds during the COVID-19 pandemic (Harrop *et al.*, 2021). This research concluded that COVID-19 thus disrupted conventional research processes, which, most probably, under 'normal' circumstances, researchers would not have experienced (Harrop *et al.*, 2021). Thus, this study concluded that if early autism research had been carried out in a non-pandemic situation, the study would have probably taken a different course (Harrop *et al.*, 2021).

Similar to what Harrop *et al.* (2021) reported, the current research study also experienced reduced recruitment of participants, which impacted the sample size. Corroborating views to the findings of Harrop *et al.* (2021) derive from a study conducted by the journal 'Nature' on the lessons learnt by researchers in China, the U.S., Canada, the U.K., Italy, Spain, India, Australia and Brazil ($n = 3209$) following the COVID-19 pandemic situation. This research saw the majority of respondents (57%) reporting that the pandemic had impaired their ability to collect data (Woolston, 2021), potentially impacting the study sample size. This study concluded that early researchers were especially vulnerable to this issue, reporting that the pandemic had hampered their prospects during their planned research (Woolston,

2021). Thus, the current study's initial intended route planned for in 2017 took a different path because of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, with the research projecting a larger sample, the involvement of parents, the opportunity to physically access schools, and the opportunity to interview participants face-to-face. Interviews with participants in the current study were held through TEAMS because social distancing and lockdown measures were imposed on the country from which this study originates, i.e. Malta. The latter was also reported by Levine and Rathmell (2020), who revealed that the COVID-19 pandemic primarily and intermittently forced many countries worldwide to implement immediate and multiple lockdowns. As a result, face-to-face research ended unexpectedly, resumed, and ended again, and continues to be somewhat unstable (Levine and Rathmell, 2020). Commenting on the experiences of student and trainee autism researchers during the COVID-19 pandemic, Kaku *et al.* (2021) reported that such unprecedented situations have led researchers to postpone, redesign, and/or modify existing methods to complete projects, including doctoral research. In the case of the current research study, I, as the researcher, decided to be flexible regarding the data collection approach and adapted to the new system of conducting online interviews with participants who voluntarily wanted to form part of this research study. Postponing the data collection period was not an option primarily because I, as the researcher (like the rest of the world), did not know when lockdown restrictions would be lifted.

A further justification for the non-participatory issue of parents in the current study was delineated by several studies that reported upon the several challenges that parents of children with autism faced during this unprecedented time and confirmed why participation in research was of secondary importance (e.g. Degli Espinosa *et*

al., 2020; Tokatly Latzer, Leitner and Karnieli-Miller, 2021). A study concluded that shutting down educational settings due to the COVID-19 pandemic meant parents of children with autism lost a vital support network and had to be the sole full-time caregivers (Tokatly Latzer, Leitner and Karnieli-Miller, 2021). Research shows that during this period, parents of children with autism faced challenges stemming from routine changes, lack of education services, limited physical space, and food- and sleep-related issues (Tokatly Latzer, Leitner and Karnieli-Miller, 2021). Further literature has delineated that parents faced a situation whereby their children with autism demanded high levels of undivided attention and were becoming more difficult to direct to independent activities (Degli Espinosa *et al.*, 2020). All the evidence above shows that participation in research studies by parents was of secondary importance, as the main priority during the school lockdown period was the well-being of their children and themselves. Small samples involving parents of children with autism in research had already been located in research studies prior to the pandemic period (e.g. Hodges *et al.*, 2020; Musetti *et al.*, 2021) with this research arguing that this might have further impacted sample sizes of researches held during the pandemic due to the circumstances mentioned earlier (Degli Espinosa *et al.*, 2020; Tokatly Latzer, Leitner and Karnieli-Miller, 2021).

6.3 The Strengths of this Research Study

Even though the findings of this study need to be considered in view of its limitations, this research still gathered some insightful perspectives from the voices of educators who work with students with autism, making the research valid and reliable. In fact, despite all the limitations encountered with ones explicitly arising

from the unprecedented experience of a worldwide pandemic, this study still provides insightful data on the SWOTs within the provision for learners with autism who attend primary mainstream schools in Malta. Indeed, it is salient to point out that this has not been the sole study that has looked into the home-school collaboration process whereby only the educators' voices were present. Scholars in the field, such as Linsday *et al.* (2013), Schultz *et al.* (2016), Josilowski (2019), Josilowski and Morris (2019) and Raudeliūnaitė and Steponėnienė (2020) have also conducted studies which only involved educators, and whereby characteristics related to home-school collaboration were nonetheless discussed, examined and reviewed. Studies similar to the current one, thus, have still provided an in-depth view of the potential facilitators and impediments to home-school collaboration.

In the case of the current study, data triangulation arising from the qualitative and the quantitative findings also adds to the credibility of this research study. In fact, through the data gathered in the first phase of data collection through questionnaires and the data gathered throughout the interviews, this research was repeatedly able to establish identifiable patterns (Stahl and King, 2020). Furthermore, given that this research has focused on using the SWOT analysis framework, this study may be replicated in other contexts, including educational ones, to possibly report on learners' provision. Therefore, other educational settings may learn and be inspired by the current study's framework and fit them into their environment to create new knowledge. According to Stahl and King (2020), it is with such an intention that external validity and generalisability are ensured in quantitative and qualitative research designs, whilst in the latter, qualitative inquiry seeks to expand understanding by transferring findings from one context to another,

the former may be used for productivity purposes. Therefore, this analogy makes this study trustworthy, plausible, and thus transferable, as the richness of the data gathered makes it possible for those who wish to compare it with their context (Stahl and King, 2020).

6.4 Recommendations for Further Research Work

Notwithstanding the valid contribution made by this study on the provision for learners with autism who attend primary schools in Malta, several questions remain to be answered. Future research may gather parents' perspectives of students with autism in Malta on the provision in primary school. This potential research could allow this study to make the necessary comparisons regarding how parents and educators perceive such provisions. Such further research would give parents a 'right of reply' since their voices were not included in the current research study.

Another natural progression of this work could be to analyse the provision from the voices of learners with autism. Children are at the centre of Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, so their voices must be heard. Outlining the SWOTs from learners' perspectives would be an original and valid contribution to existing research, mainly due to its limited nature. Building on the current findings, future research could look into the SWOTs within the provision for learners attending secondary mainstream school settings in Malta. Given that the secondary school setting somehow differs from the primary, looking into the SWOTs within this educational environment could contribute to existing knowledge.

Despite the fact that this study has somehow managed to bridge the gap in research, more information on budgeting and investment in schools for learners with autism would help establish a greater degree of information on the matter. Perhaps looking into the allocated budgets for resources, creating autism friendly schools, and increasing educators' training would be interesting areas that future research studies may pursue.

6.5 Implications and Recommendations for Practice

Following the findings and conclusions of this study, mixed perspectives have been brought forward in using the available resources in schools to support learners with autism. A recommendation in terms of good practice would perhaps be for SLT members in schools to share an inventory of the available resources with all their educational staff. Hence, having an inventory of resources complemented by a brief description of their function may be distributed to teachers and LSEs.

A second recommendation is that collaboration between teachers and LSEs to develop adaptations is necessary. This would allow for continuation also by the teacher in the absence of the LSE and vice-versa. Facilitating the aforementioned is the provision of sessions to further support what the notion of inclusion entails, given that this study has concluded that, at times, a 'one-size-fits-all' attitude persists within the provision for learners. Therefore, members of the SLT should organise such sessions and make them available to all staff members in their school.

One of the conclusions of this research was that open communication is critical in maintaining a positive relationship with parents and that this must be established as soon as the school meets the parents. This will ensure that collaboration regarding the sharing strategies, resources, reinforcement of skills, and documentation of the child's progress is in place. Regular meetings facilitate the process and help the school and parents build meaningful relationships. Regular communication with parents would also help entice several parents to prioritise their children's education and hence, potentially follow through with support recommended by the school within the home environment.

Since this study has concluded that the primary school could be an overwhelming environment for students with autism, it is recommended that quiet spaces in and outside the classroom may be created. Although it is appreciated that not every class is large and thus space may be limited, quiet areas may not necessarily be roomy. In-class areas would possibly allow learners with autism to retreat to them when they need to, without leaving the classroom. A calming down kit that includes fidgets such as stress balls, a feelings pinwheel, a bubble bottle, and a small station available in the class could significantly benefit children with autism.

6.6 Implications and Recommendations for Policymakers

More significant efforts are needed to ensure that the resources available in schools are sufficient and that the educational authorities do their best to support schools financially. Such endeavours would ensure that the provision for learners with autism is of good quality and that educators are not limited in the support they

provide to them. Furthermore, given that the current school environment is perceived as overwhelming and inadequate for learners with autism who attend primary schools, schools need to become more autism friendly. Hence, the State should assist by creating quiet rooms in all schools. Adding to this, modifying the current school environment regarding sound and lighting is critical, as this could lessen sensory processing difficulties experienced by learners with autism, thus making the school environment more conducive to learning.

Furthermore, ensuring appropriate systems, services, and support in having autism specialists and psychologists carrying out intervention with learners with autism should be a priority for the concerned educational authorities in charge of such services. These services are particularly necessary as educators need support when addressing the social, communication, and behavioural patterns of learners with autism. Such support would also benefit parents, as the recommendations of autism specialists and psychologists would also support them whilst providing support to their children.

Given the conclusions of this research, training on autism needs to be consistent in its content and provision. A key priority should therefore be to plan for long-term training opportunities involving all the stakeholders who support learners with autism. This plan should primarily start with undergraduate teacher preparatory courses that focus on how teachers should address the needs of learners with autism, particularly since teachers feel they are expected to support students with autism in the classroom without adequate training. Training that focuses on practical

strategies rather than theory is critical, as this would possibly ensure that autism is given the priority that it warrants within teacher preparatory courses.

This study has also concluded that training content held in schools tends to only involve LSEs, participation is voluntary, is mainly held outside school hours and training sessions do not include follow-ups. A reasonable approach to tackle this issue could be for educational authorities to create a common training programme for all educators to ensure consistency in its content. Such training should be held during school hours and involve all educators, including teachers, LSEs, and members of the SLT. This training programme should involve follow-up sessions allowing educators to share feedback on the implemented strategies and be consistent, relevant, and possibly effective for learners and educators. Furthermore, asking educators about what training should involve could also lead to increased participation regarding training on autism.

Quality assurance is critical as it would help educators receive quality training and potentially translate it into practice, possibly benefiting learners with autism. The standards and procedures set for a quality assurance programme in terms of training would potentially help prevent the weaknesses and threats related to training as per the evidence gathered in Chapter 4. Quality assurance benchmarks may also be set by educational authorities to provide training which meets the needs, expectations, and requirements of educators who support learners with autism in schools in Malta.

An extension to the recommendation mentioned above is a suggestion to policymakers to provide parents with similar training that involves follow-up sessions. This recommendation is particularly necessary since one of the conclusions brought forward in this research has seen educators concluding that some parents do not collaborate with schools as they lack knowledge on how to support their children. A recommendation of how these sessions may be organised would first see what parents are interested in pursuing regarding the support they need to assist their children. Secondly, training content would be based on the parents' suggestions as this would ensure that what is being presented is relevant to their needs and the needs of their children. Thirdly, follow-up sessions to gather parents' feedback would ensure issues are addressed accordingly. These sessions would also allow parents to discuss their challenges and facilitators with other fellow parents of learners with autism. Hence, this would create a community of families built on optimism where knowledge and skills are shared from parent to parent.

6.7 Final Thoughts

This study was designed to understand better the provision for learners with autism in schools in Malta following a sequential explanatory research design based on a mixed methods approach. The quantitative phase provided data on the existing SWOT and further characteristics impacting the provision for learners with autism. Following its analysis, the qualitative data delved into the justifications of the indicated SWOTs. The findings of this study have delineated important SWOTs within the provision in view of home-school collaboration, teaching and learning strategies, and the extent of training for educators in the area of autism.

The outcomes of this study in examining the SWOTs of the provision for learners with autism who attend primary schools in Malta are intended to provide valuable information to educators, policymakers, and academics on how provision takes place in schools in Malta, and what needs to be modified for it to be ameliorated. Being a pragmatic researcher by incorporating functional decisions based on 'what will work best' has enabled me as the researcher of the current study to conduct research innovatively and dynamically by using the SWOT analysis framework to report upon the provision for learners with autism. As a pragmatic scholar, this has allowed me to answer the research questions and fill in most of the existing gaps within research and literature. Furthermore, this research study has undoubtedly impacted my practice. It has helped me as the researcher to identify autism friendly practices and those that need improvement. As a Head of Department promoting inclusive education in schools, I have already given staff some recommendations to reduce weaknesses and threats and to boost strengths and opportunities for learners with autism. It is also intended that following the conclusion of this research study, academic content will be published to make valid contributions to the social sciences field and inspire scholars and educators working in the field. Promoting this work in the academic field will potentially maximise beneficence, which is the duty of researchers to advance knowledge in the area of expertise that will help potentially help individuals and society. Therefore, this research process has enabled me as the researcher of the current study to grow and develop into a better educator and academic within the field of inclusive education and autism.

References

- Abed, S., Jameel, K. and Ahmad, A. (2021) 'Inclusion of students with autism spectrum disorder in the Jordanian regular classrooms: Teachers' perspectives', *Specijalna Edukacija I Rehabilitacija*, 20(2), pp.79-91. doi:10.5937/specedreh20-30875.
- Able, H., Sreckovic, M., Schultz, T., Garwood, J. and Sherman, J. (2015) 'Views from the trenches', *Teacher Education And Special Education: The Journal of the Teacher Education Division of the Council for Exceptional Children*, 38(1), pp. 44-57. doi:10.1177/0888406414558096.
- Adewumi, T. M. and Mosito, C. (2019) 'Experiences of teachers in implementing inclusion of learners with special education needs in selected Fort Beaufort District primary schools, South Africa', *Cogent Education*, 6(1), pp. 1-20. doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2019.1703446.
- Adler, B., Minshawi, N., and Erickson, C. (2014) 'Evolution of Autism: From Kanner to the DSM-V', in Tarbox J., Dixon D., Sturmey P., Matson J. (eds) *Handbook of Early Intervention for Autism Spectrum Disorders. Autism and Child Psychopathology Series*. Springer, New York, NY, pp. 3-19.
- Aihie, O. N., and Uwaoluetan, O. (2022) 'Primary school teachers' knowledge of autism spectrum disorders and their attitudes towards inclusive education', *Journal of Teaching and Teacher Education*, 10(1), pp. 31-38. doi:http:dx.doi.org/10.12785/jtte/100104.
- Ainscow, M. (2005). Developing inclusive education systems: What are the levers for change? *Journal of Educational Change*, 6(2), pp. 109–124. doi.org/10.1007/s10833-005-1298-4
- Ainscow, M. (2020) 'Promoting inclusion and equity in education: Lessons from international experiences', *The Nordic Journal of Studies on Educational Policy*, 6(1), pp. 7–16. doi.org/10.1080/20020317.2020.1729587.
- Ainscow, M., T. Booth, A. Dyson, P. Farrell, J. Frankham, F. Gallannaugh, A. Howes, and R. Smith. (2006) *Improving Schools, Developing Inclusion*. London and New York: Routledge.
- Albright, K., Gechter, K., and Kempe, A. (2013) 'Importance of mixed methods in pragmatic trials and dissemination and implementation research', *Academic Pediatrics*, 13(5), pp. 400-407. doi.org/10.1016/j.acap.2013.06.010.
- Alexaki, N., Foulidi, X., and Papakitsos, E.C. (2022) 'The three dimensions of inclusive education in the attempt for educational change: cultures, policies and practices', *Journal of Research Initiatives*, 6(1). Available at: digitalcommons.uncfsu.edu/jri/vol6/iss1/5 (Accessed: 27 September 2022).

Alkinj, I., Pereira, A. and Santos, P.C.(2022) 'The effects of an educational program based on modeling and social stories on improvements in the social skills of students with autism', *Heliyon*, 8(5), pp. 1-8. doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09289.

Almeida, F. (2018) 'Strategies to perform a mixed methods study', *European Journal of Educational Research*, 5(1), pp. 1-10. doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v0i0.1902.

Al-Shammari, Z. and Hornby, G. (2020) 'Special education teachers' knowledge and experience of IEPs in the education of students with special educational needs', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 67(2), pp. 167-181. doi:10.1080/1034912x.2019.1620182.

Alsaedi, R., Carrington, S., and Watters, J. (2020) 'Behavioral and neuropsychological evaluation of executive functions in children with autism spectrum disorder in the Gulf region', *Brain Sciences*, 10(2), pp. 1-21. doi.org/10.3390/brainsci10020120.

Alves, I., Barrett, L., Cantali, D., Barnett, H., Catlin, J., Darling-McQuistan, K., Dey, D., Essex, J., Florian, L., Foley, Y., Graham, A., Jaap, A., Jones, S., Watson, K. L., McAuliffe, L., McGill, C., Mercieca, D., Munro, A., ...Wang, Y. (2022) *National Framework for Inclusion* (3rd ed.) Scottish Universities Inclusion Group. Available at: <https://www.gtcs.org.uk/professional-standards/national-framework-for-inclusion/> (Accessed: 13 April 2023)

American Psychiatric Association (2013) *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th Edition, Text Revision (DSM-V)*, Washington, D.C: APA

Anderson, L. (2020) 'Schooling for pupils with autism spectrum disorder: parents' perspectives', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 50, pp. 4356–4366. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-020-04496-2.

Anderson, J., Boyle, C. and Deppeler, J. (2014) 'The ecology of inclusive education', *Equality in Education*, pp. 23-34. Available at: doi:10.1007/978-94-6209-692-9_3.

Anglim, J., Prendeville, P. and Kinsella, W. (2017) 'The self-efficacy of primary teachers in supporting the inclusion of children with autism spectrum disorder', *Educational Psychology in Practice*, 34(1), pp. 73-88. doi.org/10.1080/02667363.2017.1391750.

Anokhin, A., Golosheykin, S. and Heath, A. (2010) Heritability of individual differences in cortical processing of facial affect, *Behavior Genetics*, 40(2), pp. 178-185. doi: 10.1007/s10519-010-9337-1

Ansell, C. (2011) *Pragmatist Democracy: Evolutionary Learning as Public Philosophy*. Oxford University Press.

Anthony, N., and Campbell, E. (2020) 'Promoting collaboration among special educators, social workers, and families impacted by autism spectrum

disorders', *Advances in Neurodevelopmental Disorders*, 4(3), pp. 319-324. doi:10.1007/s41252-020-00171-w.

Armstrong, D., Armstrong, A., and Spandagou, I. (2011) 'Inclusion: By choice or by chance?'. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 15(1), pp. 29-39. doi: 10.1080/13603116.2010.496192

Artiles, A.J. and Kozleski, E. B. (2016) 'Inclusive education's promises and trajectories: Critical notes about future research on a venerable idea', *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 24(43), pp. 1-30. doi.org/10.14507/epaa.24.1919

Ashbaker, B. and Morgan, J. (2012) 'Team players and team managers: Special educators working with paraeducators to support inclusive classroom', *Creative Education*, 3(3), pp. 322-327. doi: 10.4236/ce.2012.33051

Ashburner, J., Ziviani, J. and Rodger, S. (2010) 'Surviving in the mainstream: Capacity of children with autism spectrum disorders to perform academically and regulate their emotions and behavior at school', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 4(1), pp. 18-27. doi: 10.1016/j.rasd.2009.07.002

Asperger, H. (1944) Die "Autistischen Psychopathen" im Kindesalter. *Archiv fur Psychiatrie und Nervenkrankheiten*, 177, pp. 76–136. Available at: shorturl.at/dJS47 (Accessed: 10 February 2019).

Attard, N. and Booth, N. (2023) 'Autism and mainstream education: The parental perspective', *International Journal of Educational Research*, 121, p. 102234. doi:10.1016/j.ijer.2023.102234.

Au, T.C. and Lau, N.S. (2021) 'Private music teachers' knowledge of and attitudes toward students with autism spectrum disorder', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 51, pp. 4551–4559. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-020-04809-5.

Ayuningtyas, F., Venus, A., Suryana, A., and Yustikasari, Y. (2021) 'Using e-social story to improve the social behavior of children with autism during the COVID-19 pandemic at Rumah Autis Depok, Indonesia', *Library Philosophy and Practice*, pp. 1-16. Available at: digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/4898 (Accessed on: 3 January 2022).

Azad, G. F., Kim, M., Marcus, S. C., Mandell, D. S., and Sheridan, S. M. (2016) 'Parent-teacher communication about children with autism spectrum disorder: An examination of collaborative problem-solving', *Psychology in the Schools*, 53(10), pp. 1071–1084. doi.org/10.1002/pits.21976

Azad, G., Wolk, C. B., and Mandell, D. S. (2018) 'Ideal Interactions: Perspectives of parents and teachers of children with autism spectrum disorder', *School Community Journal*, 28(2), pp. 63–84. Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1201931 (Accessed 18 February 2021)

Azad, G. F., Marcus, S. C., Sheridan, S. M., and Mandell, D. S. (2018) 'Partners in

school: An innovative parent teacher consultation model for children with autism spectrum disorder', *Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation*, 28(4), pp. 460–486. doi:10.1080/10474412.2018.1431550.

Azad, G. F., Marcus, S. C., and Mandell, D. S. (2021) 'Partners in school: Optimizing communication between parents and teachers of children with autism spectrum disorder', *Journal of Educational and Psychological Consultation*, 31(4), pp. 438-462. doi.org/10.1080/10474412.2020.1830100.

Azad, G. F., Williams, B. J., Minton, K. E., Sheridan, S. M., and Mandell, D. S. (2020) 'Partners in school: An example of care coordination to ensure consistency of evidence-based practices across home and school for youth with autism spectrum disorder (ASD)', in McClain, M.B, Shahidullah, J.D. and Mezher, K.R. *Inter-professional Care Coordination for Paediatric Autism Spectrum Disorder*. Springer: New York. pp. 153–167.

Azeem, M. W., Imran, N., and Khawaja, I. S. (2016) 'Autism spectrum disorder: An update', *Psychiatric Annals*, 46(1), pp. 58–62. doi. org/10.3928/00485713-20151202-01

Azzopardi, A., Azzopardi Lane, C. and Bezzina, L. (2019) *Systematic Review Legislation, Policies, Strategies and Guidelines Relating to Disability in Malta*, Poulton's Ltd - Printers-Offset: Zejtun.

Babbie, E. (2017) *The Basics of Social Research*. Canada: Cengage Learning.

Baczewski, L., and Kasari, C. (2021) 'Loneliness and associated mental health sequelae in individuals with autism spectrum disorder', in Coplan, R.J., Bowker, J.C., and Nelson, L.J. *The Handbook of Solitude*, John Wiley and Sons: New Jersey, pp.351-363.

Baghdadli, A., Pry, R., Michelon, C., and Rattaz, C. (2014) 'Impact of autism in adolescents on parental quality of life', *Quality of Life Research*, 23(6), pp. 1859-1868. doi:10.1007/s11136-014-0635-6.

Baglama, B., Yikmis, A. and Demirok, M.S. (2017) 'Special education teachers' views on using technology in teaching mathematics', *European Journal of Special Education Research* 2(5), pp. 120–134. doi:10.5281/zenodo.839032.

Baio, J., Wiggins, L., Christensen, D. L., Maenner, M. J., Daniels, J., Warren, Z., Kurzius-Spencer, M., Zahorodny, W., Robinson Rosenberg, C., White, T., Durkin, M. S., Imm, P., Nikolaou, L., Yeargin-Allsopp, M., Lee, L. C., Harrington, R., Ballantyne, C., Gillespie-Smith, K. and Wilson, C (2021) 'A comparison of knowledge and experience of autism spectrum disorder among teachers in the United Kingdom and China', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 68(2), pp. 160-171. doi:10.1080/1034912X.2019.1674254.

Ballantyne, C., Wilson, C., Toye, M. K., and Gillespie-Smith, K. (2022) 'Knowledge and barriers to inclusion of ASC pupils in Scottish mainstream schools: A mixed

methods approach', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, pp. 1-20. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2022.2036829.

Bambara, L. M., Cole, C. L., Chovanes, J., Telesford, A., Thomas, A., Tsai, S. C., ... and Bilgili, I. (2018) 'Improving the assertive conversational skills of adolescents with autism spectrum disorder in a natural context', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 48, pp. 1-16. doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2018.01.002

Baron-Cohen, S. (2001) 'Theory of mind in normal development and autism', *Prisme*, 34, pp. 174-183. Available at: shorturl.at/cFV06 (Accessed, 15 January 2019).

Baron-Cohen, S., Leslie, A. and Frith, U. (1985) 'Does the autistic child have a "theory of mind"?', *Cognition*, 21(1), pp. 37-46. doi:10.1016/0010-0277(85)90022-8.

Baron-Cohen, S. and Lombardo, M.V. (2017) 'Autism and talent: the cognitive and neural basis of systemizing', *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, 19(4), pp. 345-353. doi:10.31887/DCNS.2017.19.4/sbaroncohen.

Bartlett, F.C. (1932) *Remembering: A Study in Experimental and Social Psychology*. London: Cambridge University Press.

Bartolo, P. (2010) 'The process of teacher education for inclusion: The Maltese experience', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 10(1), pp. 139-148. doi:10.1111/j.1471-3802.2010.01163.x.

Bassette, L., Bouck, E., Shurr, J., Park, J. and Cremeans, M. (2019) 'Comparison of concrete and app-based manipulatives to teach subtraction skills to elementary students with autism', *Education and Training in Autism and Developmental Disabilities*, 54(4), pp. 391-405. Available at: shorturl.at/fhjU5 (Accessed: 20 June 2021)

Bauminger, N., and Kasari, C. (2000) 'Loneliness and friendship in high-functioning children with autism', *Child Development*, 71(2), pp. 447-456. doi:10.1111/1467-8624.00156.

Beckerson, M.E., May, K. and Kana, R. (2022) 'Social, cognitive, perceptual, and other models of autism spectrum disorder', *The Neuroscience of Autism*, pp. 65-85. doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-816393-1.00005-1.

Benallie, K., McClain, M., Bakner, K., Roanhorse, T. and Ha, J. (2021) 'Executive functioning in children with ASD + ADHD and ASD + ID: A systematic review', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 86, pp. 1-21. doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2021.101807

Benedetto, L., Cucinotta, F., Maggio, R., Germanò, E., De Raco, R., Alquino, A., Impallomeni, C., et al. (2021) 'One-year follow-up diagnostic stability of autism spectrum disorder diagnosis in a clinical sample of children and toddlers', *Brain Sciences*, 11(1), pp. 37. doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11010037

Bengtsson, M. (2016) 'How to plan and perform a qualitative study using content analysis', *Nursing Plus Open*, 2, pp.8-14. doi.org/10.1016/j.npls.2016.01.001

Benzaghta, M. A., Elwalda, A., Mousa, M. M., Erkan, I., and Rahman, M. (2021) 'SWOT analysis applications: An integrative literature review', *Journal of Global Business Insights*, 6(1), pp. 55-73. doi.org/10.5038/2640-6489.6.1.1148

Berelson, B.L. (1952) *Content Analysis in Communications Research*. New York: Free Press.

Berger, R. (2015). Now I see it, now I don't: researcher's position and reflexivity in qualitative research. *Qualitative Research*, 15(2), pp. 219–234. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794112468475>

Bernhardt, V., and Geise, B. (2016) *From Questions to Actions Using Questionnaire Data for Continuous School Improvement*. London: Routledge.

Bertuccio, R., Runion, M., Culler, E., Moeller, J. and Hall, C. (2019) 'A comparison of autism-specific training outcomes for teachers and paraeducators', *Teacher Education and Special Education: The Journal of the Teacher Education Division of The Council for Exceptional Children*, 42(4), pp. 338-354. doi.org/10.1177/0888406419839771

Biedenbach, T. and Jacobsson, M. (2016) 'The open secret of values: The roles of values and axiology in project research', *Project Management Journal*, 47(3), pp. 139-155. doi.org/10.1177/875697281604700312.

Biddle, C. and Schafft, K. (2014) 'Axiology and anomaly in the practice of mixed methods work', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 9(4), pp. 320-334. doi.org/10.1177/1558689814533157.

Biesta, G. (2010) 'Pragmatism and the philosophical foundations of mixed methods research', in Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C. *SAGE Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research*. USA: SAGE, pp. 1-27

binti Ghazali, R., Sakip, S. R. M., Samsuddin, I., and Samra, H. (2021) 'The relationship of sensory design towards the physical learning environment for autism classroom', *Environment-Behaviour Proceedings Journal*, 6(18), pp. 85-90. doi.org/10.21834/ebpj.v6i18.3070.

Black, M. H., McGarry, S., Churchill, L., D'Arcy, E., Dalgleish, J., Nash, I., Jones, A., Tse, T. Y., Gibson, J., Bölte, S., and Girdler, S. (2022) 'Considerations of the built environment for autistic individuals: A review of the literature', *Autism*. 26(8), pp. 1904–1915. doi.org/10.1177/13623613221102753.

Blatchford, P., Russell, A. and Webster, R. (2012) *Reassessing the Impact of Teaching Assistants*. London: Routledge.

Bolourian, Y., Losh, A., Hamsho, N., Eisenhower, A. and Blacher, J. (2022) 'General education teachers' perceptions of autism, inclusive practices, and relationship building strategies', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 52, pp. 3977-3990. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-021-05266-4.

Bond, C., and Hebron, J. (2016) 'Developing mainstream resource provision for pupils with autism spectrum disorder: Staff perceptions and satisfaction', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 31(2), pp. 250-263. doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2016.1141543.

Bonis S. (2016) 'Stress and parents of children with autism: A review of literature', *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*, 37(3), pp. 153–163. doi.org/10.3109/01612840.2015.1116030

Boujut, E., Popa-Roch, M., Palomares, E., Dean, A. and Cappe, E. (2017) 'Self-efficacy and burnout in teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 36, pp. 8-20. doi:10.1016/j.rasd.2017.01.002.

Boyle, C., and Anderson, J. (2020) 'Inclusive education and the progressive inclusionists', in U. Sharma and S. Salend (Eds.) *The Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Education*. Oxford University Press. pp. 1-23

Boyle, C., Anderson, J. and Allen, K-A. (2020) The importance of teacher attitudes to inclusive education: in C. Boyle, C., Anderson, J., Page and S. Mavropoulou (Eds.), *Inclusive education: Global issues and Controversies*, pp. 127-146 .Brill.http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/9789004431171_008

Brask, B. H. (1972) 'A prevalence investigation of childhood psychoses' in *Nordic Symposium on the Comprehensive Care of the Psychotic Children* Oslo: Barnepsykiatrist Forening, pp. 145–153

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2). pp. 77-101. Doi:10.1191/1478088706qp063oa

Brennan, A. and King, F. (2022) 'Teachers' experiences of transformative professional learning to narrow the values practice gap related to inclusive practice', *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 52(2), pp.175-193. doi:10.1080/0305764X.2021.1965092

Breyer, C., Lederer, J. and Gasteiger-Klicpera, B. (2021) 'Learning and support assistants in inclusive education: A transnational analysis of assistance services in Europe', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 36(3), pp. 344-357. doi:10.1080/08856257.2020.1754546

British Educational Research Association (BERA) (2018) *Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research: 4th Edition*. BERA: London

Brock, M. E., Huber, H. B., Carter, E. W., Juarez, A. P. and Warren, Z. E. (2014) 'Statewide assessment of professional development needs related to educating students with autism spectrum disorder', *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 29(2), pp. 67–79. doi.org/10.1177/1088357614522290

Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979) *The Ecology of Human Development Experiments by Nature and Design*. Harvard University Press: Cambridge

Bronfenbrenner, U. (1994) 'Ecological models of human development', in *International Encyclopedia of Education*, Husen, T. and Postlethwaite, N. (Eds) Elsevier: Oxford, UK. pp. 1643-1647.

Bronfenbrenner, U. (2005) *Making Human Beings Human*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Bronfenbrenner, U. and Morris, P. A. (1998) 'The ecology of developmental processes', in W. Damon and R. M. Lerner (Eds.), *Handbook of Child Psychology: Theoretical Models of Human Development*, John Wiley and Sons Inc. pp. 993–1028.

Brookman-Frazee L., Vismara L., Drahota A., Stahmer A. and Openden D. (2009) 'Parent training interventions for children with autism spectrum disorders', in Matson J. (eds) *Applied Behavior Analysis for Children with Autism Spectrum Disorders*. Springer, New York, NY. pp.237-257

Brown, J., McLennan, C., Mercieca, D., Mercieca, D. P., Robertson, D. P., and Valentine, E. (2021) 'Technology as thirdspace: Teachers in Scottish schools engaging with and being challenged by digital technology in first COVID-19 lockdown', *Education Sciences*, 11(3), 136. doi.org/10.3390/educsci11030136.

Busiku, C. and Matafwali, B. (2022) 'Management strategies for children with autism spectrum disorders in mainstream classrooms: evidence from selected special units in Lusaka Province of Zambia', *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*. 3(2), pp. 135–141. doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2022.3.2.288.

Butera, C., Ring, P., Sideris, J., Jayashankar, A., Kilroy, E., and Harrison, L. *et al.* (2020) 'Impact of sensory processing on school performance outcomes in high functioning individuals with autism spectrum disorder', *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 14(3), pp. 243-254. doi.org/10.1111/mbe.12242.

Burnham Riosa, P., Chan, V., Maughan, A., Stables, V., Albaum, C., and Weiss, J. A. (2017) 'Remediating deficits or increasing strengths in autism spectrum disorder research: A content analysis', *Advances in Neurodevelopmental Disorders*, 1, pp. 113-121. doi.org/10.1007/s41252-017-0027-3

Butt, R. (2016) 'Teacher assistant support and deployment in mainstream schools', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 20(9), pp. 995–1007. doi:10.1080/13603116.2016.1145260

Byrne, B. (2022) 'How inclusive is the right to inclusive education? An assessment of the UN convention on the rights of persons with disabilities' concluding observations', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 26(3), pp. 301-318. doi:10.1080/13603116.2019.1651411

Calleja, C., Callus, A. M., Gauci, M. V., and Mercieca, D. (Eds.). (2017) 'Inclusive education: listening to disabled students' voices', *Malta Review of Educational Research, Special Issue*, 11(2), pp. 161-275. Available at: <http://www.mreronline.org/issues/issue-2-december-2017/> (Accessed: 3 May 2022)

Camargo, S., Rispoli, M., Ganz, J., Hong, E., Davis, H. and Mason, R. (2014) 'A review of the quality of behaviorally-based intervention research to improve social interaction skills of children with ASD in inclusive settings', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 44(9), pp. 2096-2116. doi:10.1007/s10803-014-2060-7

Cameron, R. (2011) 'Mixed methods research: The five Ps framework electronic', *Journal of Business Research Methods*, 9(2), pp. 96-108. shorturl.at/rwxMW

Camilleri, L. J. (2022) Exploring the lived experiences of fathers of children on the autism spectrum: A Narrative Inquiry. *SAGE Open*, 12(2), pp. 1-13. doi.org/10.1177/21582440221089927

Camilleri, M. and Camilleri, A. (2017) 'Digital learning resources and ubiquitous technologies in education', *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 22(1), pp. 65-82. doi:10.1007/s10758-016-9287-7.

Campbell, J. (2002) 'A critical appraisal of participatory methods in development research', *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 5(1), pp. 19-29. doi.org/10.1080/13645570110098046

Cappe, E., Bolduc, M., Poirier, N., Popa-Roch, M. and Boujut, E. (2017) 'Teaching students with autism spectrum disorder across various educational settings: The factors involved in burnout', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 67, pp.498-508. doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2017.07.014

Cappe, E., Poirier, N., Engelberg, A. and Boujut, E. (2021) 'Comparison of teachers in France and in Quebec working with autistic students: Self-efficacy, stress, social support, coping, and burnout', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 98, pp.1-12. doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103244

Carbonneau, K. J., Marley, S. C., and Selig, J. P. (2013) 'A meta-analysis of the efficacy of teaching mathematics with concrete manipulatives', *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 105(2), pp. 380 – 400. doi:10.1037/a0031084.

Carruthers, S., Pickles, A., Slonims, V., Howlin, P., and Charman, T. (2020) 'Beyond intervention into daily life: A systematic review of generalisation following social communication interventions for young children with autism', *Autism Research*, 13(4), pp. 506-522. doi.org/10.1002/aur.2264.

Carter, E. W., Gustafson, J. R., Sreckovic, M. A., Dykstra Steinbrenner, J. R., Pierce, N. P., Bord, A., . . . Mullins, T. (2017) 'Efficacy of peer support interventions in general education classrooms for high school students with autism spectrum disorder', *Remedial and Special Education*, 38(4), pp. 207–221. doi.org/10.1177/0741932516672067.

Carter, E., O'Rourke, L., Sisco, G.L. and Pelsue, D. (2009) 'Knowledge, responsibilities, and training needs of paraprofessionals in elementary and secondary schools', *Remedial and Special Education*, 30(6), pp. 344–359. doi:10.1177/0741932508324399.

Carter, M., Stephenson, J. and Webster, A., (2019) 'A survey of professional tasks and training needs of teaching assistants in New South Wales mainstream public schools', *Journal of Intellectual and Developmental Disability*, 44(4), pp.447-456. doi.org/10.3109/13668250.2018.1462638.

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, (CDC) (2022) *What is Autism Spectrum Disorder?* Available at: www.cdc.gov/ncbddd/autism/index.html (Accessed 3 February 2022).

Chamberlain, B., Kasari, C., and Rotheram-Fuller, E. (2007) 'Involvement or isolation? The social networks of children with autism in regular classrooms', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 37(2), pp. 230–242. doi:10.1007/s10803-006-0164-4.

Chammas, G. (2020) 'The insider-researcher status: A challenge for social work practice research', *The Qualitative Report*, 25(2), pp. 537-552. doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2020.3928

Chapman R. (2020) 'Defining neurodiversity for research and practice', in Bertilsdotter-Rosqvist, H., Chown, N. and Stenning, A. (eds.), *Neurodiversity Studies. A New Critical Paradigm*. Abingdon: Routledge. pp. 218–220.

Che Ahmad, C. N., and Amirul, N. J. (2017) 'The effect of the physical learning environment on students' health, enjoyment and learning', *Jurnal Pendidikan Sains Dan Matematik Malaysia*, 7(1), pp. 47–55. doi.org/10.37134.

Chen, L., Abrams, D. A., Rosenberg-Lee, M., Luculano, T., Wakeman, H. N., Prathap, S., Chen, T., and Menon, V. (2019) 'Quantitative analysis of heterogeneity in academic achievement of children with autism', *Clinical Psychological Science*, 7(2), pp. 362–380. Available at: doi.org/10.1177/2167702618809353.

Cheung, C. S. and Pomerantz, E. M. (2012) 'Why does parents' involvement enhance children's achievement? The role of parent-oriented motivation', *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(3), pp. 820-832. doi.org/10.1037/a0027183.

Christ, T.W. (2010) 'Teaching mixed methods and action research: Pedagogical, practical, and evaluative considerations', in Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C. (Eds.) in *SAGE Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research* . USA: SAGE, pp. 643-676.

Christ, S. E., Stichter, J. P., O'Connor, K. V., Bodner, K., Moffitt, A. J., and Herzog, M. J. (2017) Social skills intervention participation and associated improvements in executive function performance. *Autism Research and Treatment*, 2017, pp.1-13, doi.org/10.1155/2017/5843851

Chung, W., Chung, S., Edgar-Smith, S., Palmer, R. B., DeLambo, D. and Huang, W. (2015) 'An examination of in-service teacher attitudes toward students with Autism Spectrum Disorder: Implications for professional practice', *Current Issues in Education*, 18(2), pp. 1–12. Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1064970 (Accessed 20 April 2020).

Clark, M., Adams, D., Roberts, J. and Westerveld, M. (2020) 'How do teachers support their students with autism in Australian primary schools?', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 20(1), pp.38-50. doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12464.

Clark, M., and Adams, D. (2020) 'Parent perspectives of what helps and hinders their child with autism to manage their anxiety', *Clinical Psychologist*, 24(3), pp. 315–328. doi.org/10.1111/cp.12223.

Cloninger, C.J. (2017) 'Designing collaborative educational services', In Orelove, F. P., Sobsey, D., and Gilles, D. L. (Eds.), *Educating Students with Severe and Multiple Disabilities: A Collaborative Approach* (5th ed.). Baltimore, MD: Brookes Publishing, pp. 10-44

Coates, M., Lamb, J., Bartlett, B. and Datta, P. (2017) 'Autism Spectrum Disorder coursework for teachers and teacher-aides: An investigation of courses offered in Queensland, Australia', *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 42(11), pp. 1-17. doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2017v42n11.5

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2018) *Research Methods in Education*. London and New York: Routledge.

Collier, M., Keefe, E. B., and Hirrel, L. A. (2015) Preparing special education teachers to collaborate with families, *School Community Journal*, 25(1), pp. 117–136. Available at: files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1066210.pdf (Accessed: 1 July 2021).

Colville, T., Hulme, S., Kerr, C., Mercieca, D., and Mercieca, D. P. (2021) 'Teaching and Learning in COVID-19 Lockdown in Scotland: Teachers' engaged pedagogy', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 733633. doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.733633

Cook, A. and Ogden, J. (2022) 'Challenges, strategies and self-efficacy of teachers supporting autistic pupils in contrasting school settings: A qualitative study', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 37(3), pp. 371-385. doi:10.1080/08856257.2021.1878659

Cooke, E., Smith, V. and Brenner, M. (2020) 'Parents' experiences of accessing respite care for children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) at the acute and primary care interface: A systematic review', *BMC Pediatrics*, 20(1). doi:10.1186/s12887-020-02045-5

Cooper, K., Russell, A., Calley, S., Chen, H., Kramer, J. and Verplanken, B. (2022) 'Cognitive processes in autism: Repetitive thinking in autistic versus non-autistic adults', *Autism*, 26(4), pp. 849–858. doi.org/10.1177/13623613211034380

Corkum, P., Bryson, S., Smith, I., Giffin, C., Hume, K., and Power, A. (2014) 'Professional development needs for educators working with children with autism spectrum disorders in inclusive school environments', *Exceptionality Education International*, 24(1), pp. 33-47. doi:10.5206/eei.v24i1.7709

Creswell, J. W. (Ed.). (2003) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc

Creswell, J. W. (Ed.). (2009) *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc

Creswell, J. (2014) *A Concise Introduction to Mixed Methods Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc

Creswell, J. and Miller, G. (1997) Research methodologies and the doctoral process. *New Directions for Higher Education*, 1997(99), pp. 33-46. doi:10.1002/he.9903

Creswell, J. W., and Plano Clark, V.L. (2011) *Designing and Conducting Mixed Methods Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.

Cresswell, L., Hinch, R., and Cage, E. (2019) 'The experiences of peer relationships amongst autistic adolescents: A systematic review of the qualitative evidence', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 61, pp. 45–60. doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2019.01.003

Crompton, C. J., Hallett, S., Axbey, H., McAuliffe, C., and Cebula, K. (2022) 'Someone like-minded in a big place': Autistic young adults' attitudes towards autistic peer support in mainstream education, *Autism*. pp.1-16 doi.org/10.1177/13623613221081189

Crossley, M. and Vulliamy, G. (1997) *Qualitative Educational Research in Developing Countries*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis.

Cunningham, M. (2022) 'This school is 100% not autistic friendly!' Listening to the voices of primary-aged autistic children to understand what an autistic-friendly primary school should be like, *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 26(12), pp.1211-1225, doi: 10.1080/13603116.2020.1789767

Curtin, A. and Long, S. (2021) 'Using visual schedules to support children with autism spectrum disorder', *Learn: Journal of the Irish Learning Support Association*, 42, pp. 61-70. Available at: shorturl.at/lqCJ9. (Accessed 14 July 2022).

D'Agostino, S.R. and Douglas, S.N. (2021) Early childhood educators' perceptions of inclusion for children with autism spectrum disorder, *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 49, pp. 725–737. doi.org/10.1007/s10643-020-01108-7.

Dahary, H., Rimmer, C., Kaedbey, M. *et al.* (2022) 'A systematic review of shared social activities for children with autism and their peers', *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*. pp. 1-22. doi.org/10.1007/s40489-022-00322-w.

Da Paz, N., Wallander, J. and Tiemensma, J. (2018) 'Effects of written disclosure on psychophysiological stress among parents of children with autism: A randomized controlled pilot study', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 53, pp. 7-17. doi:10.1016/j.rasd.2018.05.007.

Daly, P., Ring, E., Egan, M., Fitzgerald, J., Griffin, C., Long, S., McCarthy, E., Moloney, M., O'Brien, T., O'Byrne, A., O'Sullivan, S., Ryan, M., Wall, E., Madden, R. and Gibbons, S. (2016) *An Evaluation of Education Provision for Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder in Ireland*. Trim: NCSE

Damianidou, E. and Phtiaka, H. (2017) 'Implementing inclusion in disabling settings: the role of teachers' attitudes and practices', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 22(10), pp. 1078-1092. doi:10.1080/13603116.2017.1415381.

Daniel, G. R. (2016) 'Parents' experiences of teacher outreach in the early years of schooling', *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 36(4), pp. 559-569. doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2015.1005051.

Danker, J., Strnadová, I. and Cumming, T.M. (2019) "They don't have a good life if we keep thinking that they're doing it on purpose!", Teachers' perspectives on the well-being of students with autism', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 49, pp. 2923–2934. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-019-04025-w.

Dargue, N., Adams, D. and Simpson, K. (2021) 'Can characteristics of the physical environment impact engagement in learning activities in children with autism? A Systematic Review', *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, pp. 1-17. doi:10.1007/s40489-021-00248-9.

Darling-Hammond, L. (2020) 'Accountability in teacher education', *Action in Teacher Education*, 42(1), pp.60-71. doi.org/10.1080/01626620.2019.1704464.

Darwin Holmes, A.G. (2020) 'Researcher positionality - a consideration of its influence and place in qualitative research - a new researcher guide', *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 8(4), pp. 1–10. doi:10.34293/education.v8i4.3232.

Das, D., Nath, K., Barman, V. and Hazarika, B. (2020) 'Pragmatism: The interpretations of C.S. Peirce, Hasiam James and John Dewey', *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(3), pp. 1684-1691. doi:10.31838/jcr.07.03.247.

Data Protection Act 2018. (2019) [Online]. Legislation.gov.uk. Available: <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2018/12/contents/enacted> [Accessed 17 Dec 2020].

Davies, B. and Ellison, L. (2005) *Strategic Direction and Development of the School: Key Frameworks for School Improvement Planning*. London: Routledge.

Dawadi, S., Shrestha, S., and Giri, R. A. (2021) 'Mixed-Methods Research: A discussion on its types, challenges, and criticisms', *Journal of Practical Studies in Education*, 2(2), pp. 25-36. doi.org/10.46809/jpse.v2i2.20.

De Jager, P.S, and Condy, J. (2020) 'Weak central coherence is a syndrome of autism spectrum disorder during teacher–learner task instructions', *South African Journal of Childhood Education*, 10(1), pp. 1-11. doi.org/10.4102/sajce.v10i1.785.

De La Cruz, R.V (2020) 'Exploring the real-life experiences of regular teachers handling children with autism in inclusive setting', *The Educational Review*, 4(7), pp. 135-149. doi:10.26855/er.2020.07.001.

de Marchena, A. B., Eigsti, I.-M. and Yerys, B. E. (2015) 'Brief report: Generalization weaknesses of verbally fluent children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 45(10), pp. 3370– 3376. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-015-2478-6.

de Vries, M. and Geurts, H. (2014) 'Beyond individual differences: are working memory and inhibition informative specifiers within ASD?', *Journal of Neural Transmission*, 121(9), pp.1183-1198. doi:10.1007/s00702-014-1225-z.

Degli Espinosa, F., Metko, A., Raimondi, M., Impenna, M., and Scognamiglio, E. (2020) 'A model of support for families of children with autism living in the COVID-19 lockdown: Lessons from Italy', *Behavior Analysis in Practice*, 13(3), pp. 550-558. doi.org/10.1177/1362361320984317.

Demetriou, E., DeMayo, M., and Guastella, A. (2019) 'Executive function in autism spectrum disorder: History, theoretical models, empirical findings, and potential as an endophenotype', *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10, pp. 1-17. doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00753.

Department for Education and Skills (2006) *Departmental Report 2006*, Norwich:Crown.

Department of Education. (2001) *White Paper on Special Needs Education: Building an Inclusive Education and Training System*. Pretoria: Government.

Depastas, C. and Kalaitzaki, A.(2022) 'The epidemiology of autism spectrum disorder and factors contributing to the increase in its prevalence', *Arheia Ellenikes Iatrikes*, 39(3), pp. 308-312. Available at: shorturl.at/BHI35 (Accessed: 9 December 2022).

Devecchi, C., Dettori, F., Doveston, M., Sedgwick, P. and Jament, J. (2012) Inclusive classrooms in Italy and England: The role of support teachers and teaching assistants. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 27(2), pp. 171-184. doi: 10.1080/08856257.2011.645587

Devi, A., and Ganguly, R. (2022) 'Pre-service teachers' and recent teacher graduates' perceptions of self-efficacy in teaching students with Autism Spectrum

Disorder—An exploratory case study', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, pp. 1-17. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2022.2088869

Dewey, J. (1931) George Herbert Mead, *The Journal of Philosophy*, 28(12), pp. 309-314. doi.org/10.2307/2012910

Dewey, J. (1938) *Experience and Education*. New York: Simon and Schuster

Dewey, J. (2008) *Democracy and Education*. South Carolina: BiblioBazaar

Díaz-Gibson, J., Daly, A., Miller-Balslev, G., and Zaragoza, M. C. (2021) 'The SchoolWeavers tool: supporting school leaders to weave learning ecosystems', *School Leadership & Management*, 41(4-5), 429-446. doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2020.1770210

Di Tore, P., Giuseppe, T. and Corona, F. (2017) 'Autism spectrum as an empathy disorder', *Autism-Open Access*, 7(1), pp. 1-3. doi:10.4172/2165-7890.1000198.

Dijkhuis, R., de Sonnevile, L., Ziermans, T., Staal, W. and Swaab, H. (2020) 'Autism symptoms, executive functioning and academic progress in higher education students', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 50(4), pp. 1353-1363. doi:10.1007/s10803-019-04267-8.

Dillenburger, K., McKerr, L. and Jordan, J. (2014) 'Lost in translation: Public policies, evidence-based practice, and autism spectrum disorder', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 61(2), pp. 134-151. doi:10.1080/1034912x.2014.905059.

Dillenburger, K., McKerr, L., Jordan, J. and Keenan, M. (2016) 'Staff training in autism: The one-eyed wo/man', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 13(7), pp. 1-17. doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13070716.

Dobson, G.J. and Douglas, G. (2020) 'Who would do that role? Understanding why teachers become SENCos through an ecological systems theory', *Educational Review*, 72(3), pp. 298-318. doi:10.1080/00131911.2018.1556206.

Dörnyei, Z. (2007) *Research Methods in Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Draper, A. R. (2022) 'Music education for students with autism spectrum disorder in a full-inclusion context', *Journal of Research in Music Education*, 70(2), pp. 132–155. doi.org/10.1177/00224294211042833.

Ducarre, L. M. (2023) 'Informing conceptual issues related to autistic children's right to education through a literature review of their lived experience', *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, pp. 1-17.

Dukpa, D., Carrington, S. and Mavropoulou, S. (2021) 'Exploring Bhutanese teachers' knowledge and use of strategies for the inclusion of students with autism', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, pp. 1-25. doi:10.1080/13603116.2021.1973124.

Duncan, A., Risley, S., Combs, A., Lacey, H. M., Hamik, E., Fershtman, C., Kneeskern, E., Patel, M., Crosby, L., Hood, A. M., Zoromski, A. K., and Tamm, L. (2022) 'School challenges and services related to executive functioning for fully included middle schoolers with autism', *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*. doi.org/10.1177/10883576221110167.

Dyer, R. (2022) 'Successful inclusion of students with autism spectrum disorder', *International Journal of Technology and Inclusive Education*, 11(1), pp. 1712-1716. doi.org/10.20533/ijtie.2047.0533.2022.0211

Education (Scotland) Act 2016 (2021) Retrieved 7 May 2021, from www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2016/8/contents/enacted

Eguiguren Istuany, O. and Wood, R (2020) 'Perspectives on educational inclusion from a small sample of autistic pupils in Santiago, Chile', *Scandinavian Journal of Disability Research*, 22(1), pp. 210–220. doi.org/10.16993/sjdr.724

El Zaatari, W. and Maalouf, I. (2022) 'How the Bronfenbrenner bio-ecological system theory explains the development of students' sense of belonging to school?', *SAGE Open*, 12(4). doi.org/10.1177/21582440221134089

Engelbrecht, P., Nel, M., Smit, S. and Van Deventer, M. (2016) 'The idealism of education policies and the realities in schools: The implementation of inclusive education in South Africa', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 20(5), pp. 520–535.

Estrada-Muñoz, C., Vega-Muñoz, A., Castillo, D., Müller-Pérez, S., and Boada-Grau, J. (2021) 'Technostress of Chilean teachers in the context of the covid-19 pandemic and teleworking', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(10), pp.54-58. doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18105458

European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (2012) *Special Needs Education Country Data*. Odense: European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education

European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (2014) *Education for All: Special Needs and Inclusive Education in Malta, External Audit Report*. Denmark: European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education.

Ewy, R. (2009) *Stakeholder-driven Strategic Planning in Education: A Practical Guide for Developing and Deploying Successful Long-range Plans*. Wisconsin: ASQ Quality Press

Evans, J.R. and Mathur, A. (2005) 'The value of online surveys', *Internet Research*, 15(2), pp. 195-219. doi.org/10.1108/10662240510590360

Farjoun, M., Ansell, C. and Boin, A. (2015) 'PERSPECTIVE—Pragmatism in organization studies: Meeting the challenges of a dynamic and complex world', *Organization Science*, 26(6), pp. 1787-1804. doi:10.1287/orsc.2015.1016

Farrugia, J.M. (2013) 'The use or misuse of biomedical treatment approaches to autism', *Malta Medical Journal*, 25(1), p. 8-14, Available at: www.um.edu.mt/library/oar/handle/123456789/1189 (Accessed 21 September 2021)

Fatima, S. (2019) 'Executive Dysfunctions in Autism Spectrum Disorders' in Ardila, A., Fatima, S., Rosselli, M. (eds) *Dysexecutive Syndromes*. Springer, Cham. pp. 61-82

Feilzer, Y. M. (2010) 'Doing mixed methods research pragmatically: Implications for the rediscovery of pragmatism as a research paradigm', *Journal Of Mixed Methods Research*, 4(1), pp. 6-16. doi.org/10.1177/1558689809349691

Felder, F. (2018) 'The value of inclusion', *Journal of Philosophy of Education*, 52(1), pp. 54–70. doi.org/10.1111/1467-9752.12280

Ferguson, P., McKenzie, M., Mercieca, D., Mercieca, D. P., and Sutherland, L. (2021) 'Primary head teachers' construction and re-negotiation of care in COVID-19 lockdown in Scotland', *Frontiers in Education* (6) p. 617869. doi.org/10.3389/educ.2021.617869

Ferraioli, S. and Harris, S., (2011) 'Teaching joint attention to children with autism through a sibling-mediated behavioral intervention', *Behavioral Interventions*, 26(4), pp.261-281. doi.org/10.1002/bin.336

Ferroni Bast, D., Lyons, C., Stewart, I., Connor, T., Kelly, M. and Goyos, C. (2020) 'The effect of educational messages on implicit and explicit attitudes towards individuals with autism versus normally developing individuals', *The Psychological Record*, 70(1), pp. 123-145. doi.org/10.1007/s40732-019-00363-4

Filippello P., Caterina, B., Sebastiano, C. and Sorrenti, L. (2019) 'School refusal and absenteeism: Perception of teacher behaviors, psychological basic needs, and academic achievement', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, pp. 1-9. doi =10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01471

Finch, K., Watson, R., MacGregor, C. and Precise, N. (2013) 'Teacher needs for educating children with Autism Spectrum Disorders in the general education classroom', *The Journal of Special Education Apprenticeship*, 2(2), pp. 1-26, Available at: scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/josea/vol2/iss2/6 (Accessed 13 January 2022).

Finkelman, S. (2017) 'The evolution of autism', *The Touro Teacher*, 1(1), Available: touro scholar.touro.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1002&context=touroteacher, (Accessed 13 January 2022)

Finnegan, E., and Accardo, A. (2018) 'Understanding character perspective: Strategies to support students with autism spectrum disorder', *The Reading Teacher*, 72(1), pp. 71-80. doi.org/10.1002/trtr.1682

Fisher, M. and Pleasants, S. (2011) 'Roles, responsibilities, and concerns of paraeducators', *Remedial and Special Education*, 33(5), pp. 287-297. doi:10.1177/0741932510397762.

Fletcher-Watson, S. and Happé, F. (2019) *Autism: A New Introduction to Psychological Theory and Current Debate*. Oxon: Routledge.

Folostina, R., Dumitru, C., Iacob, C., and Syriopoulou-Delli, C. (2022) 'Mapping knowledge and training needs in teachers working with students with autism spectrum disorder: A comparative cross-sectional investigation', *Sustainability*, 14(5), pp. 1-13. doi.org/10.3390/su14052986

Forlin, C. (2006) 'Inclusive education in Australia ten years after Salamanca', *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 21(3), pp. 265-277. doi:10.1007/BF03173415

Fox, R. A., Leif, E. S., Moore, D. W., Furlonger, B., Anderson, A. and Sharma, U. (2021) 'A systematic review of the facilitators and barriers to the sustained implementation of school-wide positive behavioral interventions and supports', *Education and Treatment of Children*, 45(1), pp. 1–22. doi:10.1007/s43494-021-00056-0

Frantz, R., Douglas, S., Meadan, H., Sands, M., Bhana, N., and D'Agostino, S. (2022) 'Exploring the professional development needs of early childhood paraeducators and supervising teachers', *Topics in Early Childhood Special Education*, 42(1), pp. 20–32. doi.org/10.1177/0271121420921237

Frega, R. (2011) *Pragmatist Epistemologies*. Lexington Books.

Frith U. (1989) Autism and Theory of Mind in Gillberg, C. (eds) *Diagnosis and Treatment of Autism*. Springer, Boston, MA, pp. 33-52

Frith, U. (1998) 'What autism teaches us about communication', *Logopedics Phoniatrics Vocology*, 23(2), pp.51-58. doi.org/10.1080/140154398434194

Frith, U. and Happé, F. (1994) 'Autism: beyond "theory of mind"', *Cognition*, 50(1-3), pp. 115-132. doi:10.1016/0010-0277(94)90024-8

Galkiene, A. and Puskorienė, G. (2020) 'Development of adaptation tools for pupils with autism in microsystems', *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 5(2), pp. 1-21. doi.org/10.46303/ressat.05.02.1

Garcia-Melgar, A., Hyett, N., Bagley, K., McKinstry, C., Spong, J. and Iacono, T. (2022) 'Collaborative team approaches to supporting inclusion of children with disability in mainstream schools: A co-design study', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 126, pp. 1-11. doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2022.104233

Garrad, T. A., Rayner, C., and Pedersen, S. (2019) 'Attitudes of Australian primary school teachers towards the inclusion of students with autism spectrum

disorders', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 19(1), 58-67. doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12424

Gentil-Gutiérrez, A., Cuesta-Gómez, J.L., Rodríguez-Fernández, P. and González-Bernal, J.J. (2021) 'Implication of the sensory environment in children with autism spectrum disorder: Perspectives from school', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(14), p.7670. doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18147670.

Gentil-Gutiérrez, A., Santamaría-Peláez, M., Mínguez-Mínguez, L., González-Santos, J., Fernández-Solana, J., and González-Bernal, J. (2022) 'Executive functions in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorder, grade 1 and 2, vs. neurotypical development: A school view', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13), pp. 79-87. doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137987

Ghanouni, P., Jarus, T., Zwicker, J.G. Lucyshyn, J. Chauhan, S. and Moir, C. (2019) 'Perceived barriers and existing challenges in participation of children with autism spectrum disorders: "He did not understand and no one else seemed to understand him"', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 49, pp. 3136–3145. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-019-04036-7

Ghazali, R., Sakip, S. R. M., Samsuddin, I., and Samra, H. (2021) 'Determinant Factors of Sensory in Creating Autism Learning Environment' *Environment-Behaviour Proceedings Journal*, 6(16), pp. 113-118. Available at: ebpj.eiph.co.uk/index.php/EBProceedings/article/view/2696/1449 (Accessed 22 April 2022)

Giangreco, M. (2013) 'Teacher assistant supports in inclusive schools: Research, practices and alternatives', *Australasian Journal of Special Education*, 37(2), pp. 93-106. doi:10.1017/jse.2013.1.

Giangreco, M. F., Doyle, M.B. and Suter, J.C (2014) 'Teacher Assistants in Inclusive Classrooms', in Florian, L. *The SAGE Handbook of Special Education*, 2nd. Vol. 2. London: Sage Publications, pp. 691–702.

Gillberg, C. and Wing, L. (1999) 'Autism: not an extremely rare disorder', *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 99(6), pp. 399-406. doi:10.1111/j.1600-0447.1999.tb00984.x

Giovagnoli, G., Postorino, V., Fatta, L., Sanges, V., De Peppo, L. and Vassena, L. *et al.* (2015) 'Behavioral and emotional profile and parental stress in preschool children with autism spectrum disorder', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 45-46, pp. 411-421. doi:10.1016/j.ridd.2015.08.006

Glogowska, M. (2011) 'Paradigms, pragmatism and possibilities: mixed-methods research in speech and language therapy', *International Journal of Language and Communication Disorders*, 46(3), pp. 251–260. doi:10.3109/13682822.2010.507614

Goldkuhl, G. (2008) *Practical Inquiry as Action Research and Beyond*, in Proceedings of the 16th European Conference on Information Systems, Galway

Goldkuhl, G. (2011) 'The research practice of practice research: theorizing and situational inquiry', *Systems, Signs and Actions: An International Journal on Communication, Information Technology and Work*, 5(1), pp. 7–29. Available at: <http://www.sysiac.org/uploads/SySiAc2011-Editorial.pdf> (Accessed 20 March 2020).

Goldkuhl, G. (2012) 'Pragmatism vs interpretivism in qualitative information systems research', *European Journal of Information Systems*, 21(2), pp. 135-146. doi.org/10.1057/ejis.2011.54

Gómez-Marí, I., Sanz-Cervera, P. and Tárraga-Mínguez, R. (2022) 'Teachers' attitudes toward autism spectrum disorder: A systematic review', *Education Sciences*, 12(2), 138. doi.org/10.3390/educsci12020138

Goñi-Cervera, J., Cañadas, M.C. and Polo-Blanco, I. (2022) 'Generalisation in students with autism spectrum disorder: an exploratory study of strategies', *ZDM Mathematics Education* 54, pp. 1333–1347. doi.org/10.1007/s11858-022-01415-w

Gonzales, M. (2020) 'The Bronfenbrenner micro-and meso-systems', In *Systems Thinking for Supporting Students with Special Needs and Disabilities*, Springer, Singapore, pp. 81-92.

Goodall, C. (2018) 'Inclusion is a feeling, not a place: A qualitative study exploring autistic young people's conceptualisations of inclusion', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*. 24(12), pp. 1285-1310. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1523475

Goodley, D. (2016) *Disability Studies: An Interdisciplinary Introduction*. London: Sage.

Goodman, G. and Williams, C. (2007) Interventions for increasing the academic engagement of students with autism spectrum disorders in inclusive classrooms, *Teaching Exceptional Children*, 39(6), pp. 53-61. doi:10.1177/004005990703900608

Goodson, I., Loveless, A.M. and Stephens, D. (2013) *Explorations in Narrative Research*. The Netherlands: Sense Publishers

Goussé, V., Plumet, M., Chabane, N., Mouren-Siméoni, M., Ferradian, N. and Leboyer, M. (2002) Fringe phenotypes in autism: A review of clinical, biochemical and cognitive studies. *European Psychiatry*, 17(3), pp. 120-128. doi:10.1016/S0924-9338(02)00640-5

Grandin, T. (1995) *Thinking in Pictures and Other Reports from My Life with Autism*. Vintage Press: New York

Gray, D. (2017) *Doing Research in the Real World*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc

Greene, J.C. and Hall, J.N. (2010) 'Dialectics and pragmatism: Being of consequence', in Tashakkori, A and Teddlie, C. (Eds.) In *SAGE Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research*. USA: SAGE

Grinker, R.R (2020), 'Autism, "stigma," disability: A shifting historical terrain', *Current Anthropology*, 61(21), pp.S55-S67. doi:10.1086/705748

Guba, E. G. and Lincoln, Y. S. (1994) 'Competing paradigms in qualitative research', in N. K. Denzin and Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of Qualitative Research* Sage Publications, Inc. pp. 105–117.

Guldberg, K. (2019) Making a difference in the education of autistic children and young people: the Autism Education Trust (AET) good autism practice guidance, 2019, *Good Autism Practice (GAP)*, 20(2), pp. 77-87, Available at: web.a.ebscohost.com/ehost/detail/detail?vid=0&sid=98706357-d5ab-40a4-9191-b406c308e3b3%40sdc-v-sessmgr01&bdata=JnNpdGU9ZWWhvc3QtbGl2ZQ%3d%3d#AN=140501228&db=eue (Accessed 22 June 2021)

Guldberg, K., Bradley, R., Wittemeyer, K., Briscoe, J., Phillips, C. and Jones, G. (2020) *Good Autism Practice (GAP): Full Report*. London: Autism Education Trust

Güleç-Aslan, Y. (2020) 'Experiences of Turkish preschool teachers for including children with autism spectrum disorders: Challenges faced and methods used', *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 7(2), pp.37-49. doi:10.17220/ijpes.2020.02.004

Gulveren, A. C., Yucesoy Ozkan, S., and Oncul, N. (2022) 'The examination of special education teachers' views on teaching play skills to children with autism spectrum disorders', *Journal of Qualitative Research in Education*, 29, pp. 56-77. doi:10.14689/enad.29.3

Gunning, C., Holloway, J., Fee, B., Breathnach, O., Bergin, C.M., Greene, I and Ní Bheoláin, R. (2019) 'A systematic review of generalization and maintenance outcomes of social skills intervention for preschool children with autism spectrum disorder', *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 6, pp. 172–199. doi.org/10.1007/s40489-019-00162-1

Gürel, E. and Tat, M. (2017) 'SWOT analysis: A theoretical review', *Journal of International Social Research*, 10(51), pp. 994-1006. doi.org/10.17719/jjsr.2017.1832

Hall, J. (2013) 'Pragmatism, evidence, and mixed methods evaluation (Special Issue: Mixed methods and credibility of evidence in evaluation)', *New Directions for Evaluation*, 138, pp. 15-26. doi:10.1002/ev.20054

Hall, L. J. (2015) 'Sustaining evidence-based practices by graduated special educators of students with ASD', *Teacher Education and Special Education: The Journal of the Teacher Education Division of the Council for Exceptional Children*, 38(1), pp. 28-43. doi.org/10.1177/0888406414558883

Hamrick, J., Cerda, M., O'Toole, C. and Hagen-Collins, K., (2021) 'Educator knowledge and preparedness for educating students with autism in public schools', *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 36(4), pp.213-224. doi.org/10.1177/1088357621989310

Hancock, B., Ockleford, E. and Windridge, K. (2009) *An Introduction to Qualitative Research*. East Midlands and Yorkshire: NIHR.

Happé, F. (1991) *Theory of Mind and Communication in Autism*. Doctoral thesis (Ph.D), University of London

Happé, F. (1994) *Autism: An Introduction to Psychological Theory*, Harvard University Press: Cambridge

Happé, F. (1997) 'Central coherence and theory of mind in autism: Reading homographs in context', *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 15(1), pp. 1-12. doi:10.1111/j.2044-835x.1997.tb00721.x

Happé, F. (1999) 'Autism: cognitive deficit or cognitive style?', *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 3(6), pp. 216-222. doi:10.1016/s1364-6613(99)01318-2

Happé, F. and Frith, U. (2006) 'The weak coherence account: Detail-focused cognitive style in autism spectrum disorders', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 36, pp. 5–25. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-005-0039-0

Harrop, C., Bal, V., Carpenter, K., and Halladay, A. (2021) 'A lost generation? The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on early career ASD researchers', *Autism Research*, 14(6), pp. 1078-1087. doi.org/10.1002/aur.2503

Hathcoat, J. D. and Meixner, C. (2017) 'Pragmatism, factor analysis, and the conditional incompatibility thesis in mixed methods research', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 11(4), pp. 433–449. doi.org/10.1177/1558689815622114

Hayes, N., O'Toole, L. and Halpenny, A. (2023) *Introducing Bronfenbrenner: A Guide for Practitioners and Students in Early Years Education*. Routledge: New York.

Hebron, J. S. (2018) 'School connectedness and the primary to secondary school transition for young people with autism spectrum conditions', *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 88(3), pp. 396–409. doi:10.1111/bjep.12190.

Hernández-González, O., Spencer-Contreras, R., Sanz-Cervera, P., and Tárraga-Mínguez, R. (2022) 'Analysis of the autism spectrum disorder (ASD) knowledge of Cuban teachers in primary schools and preschools', *Education Sciences*, 12(4), pp. 1-13. doi.org/10.3390/educsci12040284

Hernes, T. (2014) *A Process Theory of Organization*. Oxford: Oxford University Press

Hersh, M. and Elley, S. (2019) 'Barriers and enablers of inclusion for young autistic learners: Lessons from the Polish experiences of teachers and related professionals', *Advances in Autism*, 5(2), pp. 117-130. doi:10.1108/aia-06-2018-0021.

Hesse-Biber, S. (2012) 'Feminist approaches to triangulation', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 6(2), pp. 137-146. doi.org/10.1177/1558689812437184

Hill, E. (2004) Executive dysfunction in autism, *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 8(1), pp. 26-32. doi: 10.1016/j.tics.2003.11.003

Hill, E. and Frith, U. (2003) Understanding autism: insights from mind and brain, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences*, 358(1430), pp. 281-289. doi: 10.1098/rstb.2002.1209

Hodges, A., Joosten, A., Bourke-Taylor, H. and Cordier, R. (2020) 'School participation: The shared perspectives of parents and educators of primary school students with autism', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 97, pp.1-12. doi:10.1016/j.ridd.2019.103550

Holcombe, W. and Plunkett, M. (2023) 'Bridges and barriers: Building an innovative model of support for teachers of students with ASD', In Weuffen, S., Burke, J., Plunkett, M., Goriss-Hunter, A. and Emmet, S. (eds) *Inclusion, Equity, Diversity, and Social Justice in Education: A Critical Exploration of the Sustainable Development Goals* Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, pp. 217-232.

Holmes, S. and Butcher, J. (2020) 'Educational leaders can lead the way for increased academic achievement for students with autism', *School Leadership*, 15(20), pp. 1-20. Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1283230 (Accessed: 13 May 2022)

Hong, M., Lee, S. M., Park, S., Yoon, S.-J., Kim, Y.-E., and Oh, I.-H. (2020) 'Prevalence and economic burden of autism spectrum disorder in South Korea using National Health Insurance Data from 2008 to 2015', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 50(1), pp. 333– 339. doi:10.1007/s10803-019-04255-y

Hoskin, J., Boyle, C. and Anderson, J., (2015) 'Inclusive education in pre-schools: Predictors of pre-service teacher attitudes in Australia', *Teachers and Teaching*, 21(8), pp.974-989. doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2015.1005867

Hothersall, S. (2018) 'Epistemology and social work: Enhancing the integration of theory, practice and research through philosophical pragmatism', *European Journal of Social Work*, 22(5), pp. 860-870. Available at: doi.org/10.1080/13691457.2018.1499613

Howe, F. and Stagg, S. (2016) 'How sensory experiences affect adolescents with an autistic spectrum condition within the classroom', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 46(5), pp. 1656-1668. doi:10.1007/s10803-015-2693-1

Howlin, P. and Magiati, I. (2017) 'Autism spectrum disorder: Outcomes in adulthood', *Current Opinion in Psychiatry*, 30(2), pp. 69–76. Doi:10.1097/YCO.0000000000000308

Hu, X. (2019) 'Educational placement of children with autism spectrum disorder in China', in Hu, X., and Kärnä, E. *Educating Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder in China and Finland*. Springer, Singapore. pp. 54-62.

Hummerstone, H. and Parsons, S. (2020) 'What makes a good teacher? Comparing the perspectives of students with autism and staff', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 36(4), pp. 610-624. doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2020.1783800

Humphrey, N. (2008) 'Including pupils with autistic spectrum disorders in mainstream schools', *Support for Learning*, 23(1), pp. 41-47. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9604.2007.00367.x

Humphrey, N. and Hebron, J. (2015) 'Bullying of children and adolescents with autism spectrum conditions: A 'state of the field' review', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 19(8), pp. 845-862, DOI: 10.1080/13603116.2014.981602

Humphrey, N. and Symes, W. (2013) 'Inclusive education for pupils with autistic spectrum disorders in secondary mainstream schools: Teacher attitudes, experience and knowledge', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 17(1), pp. 32-46. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2011.580462

Hung, L. (2022) 'Professional development for teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder in Taiwan', in Ho, F., Lam, C.S. and Arthur-Kelly, M., *Promoting Collaborative Learning Cultures to Help Teachers Support Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder*. Springer: Singapore, pp. 31-44.

Huws, J. and Jones, R. (2010) 'They just seem to live their lives in their own little world': lay perceptions of autism', *Disability and Society*, 25(3), pp.331-344. doi.org/10.1080/09687591003701231

Huxter, M.E (2021) 'Exploring bullying in autism through a content analysis of autobiographies', *Good Autism Practice (GAP)*, 22(2), pp. 5-11, Available at: www.ingentaconnect.com/content/bild/gap/2021/00000022/00000002/art00002. (Accessed 2 June 2022)

Iadarola, S., Hetherington, S., Clinton, C., Dean, M., Reisinger, E. and Huynh, L. *et al.* (2015) 'Services for children with autism spectrum disorder in three, large urban school districts: Perspectives of parents and educators', *Autism*, 19(6), pp.694-703. doi:10.1177/1362361314548078.

Idris, A.B., Abdulrahim, R., Al-Mamari, W., Shih, A and Kantaris, M (2022) A SWOT analysis of parent-mediated intervention for children with autism spectrum disorder: *Oman as a regional model*, *International Journal of Developmental Disabilities*, 68(9), pp. 773 780. doi:10.1080/20473869.2021.1895700

Ivankova, N. V. (2014) 'Implementing quality criteria in designing and conducting a sequential quan → qual mixed methods study of student engagement with learning applied research methods online', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 8(1), pp. 25–51. doi.org/10.1177/1558689813487945

Ivankova, N., Creswell, J. and Stick, S. (2006) 'Using mixed-methods sequential explanatory design: From theory to practice', *Field Methods*. 18(1), pp.3-20. doi.org/10.1177/1525822X0528226

Jaarsma, P. and Welin, S. (2012) 'Autism as a natural human variation: reflections on the claims of the neurodiversity movement', *Health Care Anal*, 20(1), pp. 20–30, doi: 10.1007/s10728-011-0169-9

Jackman, A. and Zwaigenbaum, L. (2023) 'The history of autism spectrum disorder', in Eisenstat, D.D., Goldowitz, D., Oberlander, T.F., Yager, J.Y. (eds) *Neurodevelopmental Pediatrics*. Springer: Cham, pp. 215-226.

James, W. (1948) *Essays in Pragmatism*. New York: Hafner. (Original work published 1907)

Jellinek, E., Keller-Margulis, M., Mire, S., and Fan, W. (2022) 'Pre-service teachers' perspectives on transition to kindergarten practices for autistic children', *Early Childhood Education Journal*. doi.org/10.1007/s10643-022-01367-6

Jimenez, B. A. and Besaw, J. (2020) 'Building early numeracy through virtual manipulatives for students with intellectual disability and autism', *Education and Training in Autism and Developmental Disabilities*, 55(1), pp. 28-44. Available at ife.idm.oclc.org/login. (Accessed: 1 June 2022)

Jimenez, B. and Stanger, C. (2017) 'Math manipulatives for students with severe intellectual disability: A survey of special education teachers', *Physical Disabilities: Education and Related Services*, 36(1), pp. 1-12. doi:10.14434/pders.v36i1.22172.

Johnson, R.B and Christensen, L. (2013) *Educational Research: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Approaches*. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications

Johnson, R.B. and Onwuegbuzie, A.J. (2004) 'Mixed methods research: A research paradigm whose time has come', *Educational Researcher*, 33(7), pp. 14-26. doi.org/10.3102/0013189X033007014

Johnson, R., Onwuegbuzie, A. and Turner, L. (2007) 'Toward a definition of mixed methods research', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(2), pp. 112-133. doi.org/10.1177/1558689806298224

Johnson, L. D., Wehby, J. H., Symons, F. J., Moore, T. C., Maggin, D. M. and Sutherland, K. S. (2014) 'An analysis of preference relative to teacher implementation of intervention', *The Journal of Special Education*, 48(3), pp. 214-224. doi:10.1177/0022466913475872

Jones, G. (2019) Professional development for those working in education with students with autism, in Jordan, R., Hume, K., and Roberts, J. (eds) *The SAGE Handbook of Autism and Education*, London: Sage, pp. 70-88

Jones, C. and Kennedy, G. (2011) 'Stepping beyond the paradigm wars: pluralist methods for research in learning technology', *Research in Learning Technology*, 19(1), pp. 18-28. doi:10.3402/rlt.v19s1/7798

Jones, W. and Klin, A. (2009) 'Heterogeneity and homogeneity across the autism spectrum: The role of development', *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 48(5), pp. 471-473. doi:10.1097/chi.0b013e31819f6c0d

Jones, E., Hanley, M. and Riby, D. (2020) 'Distraction, distress and diversity: Exploring the impact of sensory processing differences on learning and school life for pupils with autism spectrum disorders', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 72, pp. 1-12. doi:10.1016/j.rasd.2020.101515

Jones, M. H., Symonds, J. E., Downey, S., Sloan, S., Devine, D. and Kinsella, W. (2023) 'The social acceptance of neurodiverse children in Irish primary schools', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, pp. 1-17. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2023.2195861

Jordan, R., Roberts, J.M. and Hume, K. (2019) *The Sage Handbook of Autism and Education*. London: Sage.

Jorquera-Cabrera, S., Romero-Ayuso, D., Rodriguez-Gil, G., and Triviño-Juárez, J. M. (2017) 'Assessment of sensory processing characteristics in children between 3 and 11 years old: A systematic review', *Frontiers in Pediatrics*, 5(57), pp. 1-18. doi.org/10.3389/fped.2017.00057

Josilowski, C. S. (2019) 'Teachers' perceptions of the home-school collaboration: Enhancing learning for children with autism', *The Qualitative Report*, 24(12), pp. 3008-3021. doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2019.3408

Josilowski, C. S. and Morris, W. (2019) 'A qualitative exploration of teachers' experiences with students with autism spectrum disorder transitioning and adjusting to inclusion: Impacts of the home and school collaboration', *The Qualitative Report*, 24(6), pp. 1275-1286. doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2019.3757

Jury, M., Perrin, A., Desombre, C., and Rohmer, O. (2021) 'Teachers' attitudes toward the inclusion of students with autism spectrum disorder: Impact of students' difficulties', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 83, pp. 101746. doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2021.i01746

Kaku, S.M., McVey, A.J., Gerber, A.H., Pretzsch, C.M., Jones, D.R., Kodakkadan, F.M., Lei, J., Singer, L., Chitehwe, L., Poulsen, R.E. and Coffman, M. (2022) 'Experiences of student and trainee autism researchers during the COVID-19 pandemic', *Autism Research*, 15(3), pp.413-420. doi:10.1002/aur.2662

Kaland, N., Callesen, K., Møller-Nielsen, A. and Smith, L. (2008) Performance of children and adolescents with asperger syndrome or high-functioning autism on advanced theory of mind tasks, *J Autism Dev Disord* 38, pp. 1112–1123 (2008). doi.org/10.1007/s10803-007-0496-

Kanner, L. (1943) 'Autistic disturbances of affective contact', *Nervous Child*, 2, pp. 217–250.

Kanner, L. (1944) 'Early infantile autism', *The Journal of Pediatrics*, 25, pp. 211–217. doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476(44)80156-1

Kapp, S. K., Gillespie-Lynch, K., Sherman, L. E., and Hutman, T. (2013), 'Deficit, difference, or both? Autism and neurodiversity', *Developmental Psychology*, 49(1), pp. 59–71. doi.org/10.1037/a0028353

Kasari, C. and Rotheram-Fuller, E. (2007) 'Peer relationships of children with autism: Challenges and interventions', in E.Hollander and E. Anagnostou (Eds.), *Clinical Manual for the Treatment of Autism* Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Publishing, Inc, pp. 235–257.

Karadağ Yılmaz, R. and Yeganeh, E. (2021) 'Who and how do I include? A case study on teachers' inclusive education practices', *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 17(2), pp. 406-429. doi.org/10.29329/ijpe.2021.332.25

Kasari, C., Locke, J., Gulsrud, A., and Rotheram-Fuller, E. (2011) 'Social networks and friendships at school: Comparing children with and without autism', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 41, pp. 533–544. doi:10.1007/s10803-010-1076-x

Kaushik, V. and Walsh, C. (2019) 'Pragmatism as a research paradigm and its implications for social work research', *Social Sciences*, 8(9), pp. 255. doi.org/10.3390/socsci8090255

Keen, D., Webster, A. and Ridley, G. (2015) 'How well are children with autism spectrum disorder doing academically at school? An overview of the literature' *Autism*, 20(3), pp. 276-294. doi: 10.1177/1362361315580962

Kelly, L. and Cordeiro, M. (2020) 'Three principles of pragmatism for research on organizational processes', *Methodological Innovations*, 13(2), pp. 1-10. doi.org/10.1177/2059799120937242

Kenny, L., Hattersley, C., Molins, B., Buckley, C., Povey, C. and Pellicano, E. (2016) 'Which terms should be used to describe autism? Perspectives from the UK autism community', *Autism*, 20(4), pp.442-462. doi.org/10.1177/1362361315588200

Khaldi, K. (2017) 'Quantitative, qualitative or mixed research: Which research paradigm to use?' *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 7(2), pp. 15-24, doi:10.5901/jesr.2017.v7n2p15

King, A. M., Brady, K. W., and Voreis, G. (2017) 'It's a blessing and a curse: Perspectives on tablet use in children with autism spectrum disorder', *Autism and Developmental Language Impairments*, 2, pp. 1-12. doi.org/10.1177/2396941516683183

Kisbu-Sakarya, Y. and Doenyas, C. (2021) 'Can school teachers' willingness to teach ASD-inclusion classes be increased via special education training? Uncovering mediating mechanisms', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 113, pp. 1-9. doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2021.103941

Kivunja, C. and Kuyini, A. (2017) 'Understanding and applying research paradigms in educational contexts', *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), pp. 26-41. doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v6n5p

Kossewska, J., Preece, D., Lisak, N., Bombińska-Domżał, A., Cierpiałowska, T., Lessner Listiakova, I., ... and Troshanska, J. (2020) 'Training needs in the field of autism of contemporary Polish teachers in the context of the international ASD-EAST project', *Social Welfare: Interdisciplinary Approach*, 1(9), pp. 82-92. doi:10.21277/sw.v1i9.441

Krampač-Grljušić, A., Ralić, A. Ž., and Akšamović, D. (2021) 'Cooperation in inclusive education from the perspective of parents of students with autism spectrum disorder-case study', *Intercultural Education*, pp. 227-239. Available at: files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED611743.pdf#page=227 (Accessed 19 September 2022)

Krippendorff, K. (2018) *Content Analysis: An Introduction to Its Methodology*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.

Krischler, M., Powell, J.J. and Pit-Ten Cate, I.M. (2019) 'What is meant by inclusion? On the effects of different definitions on attitudes toward inclusive education', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 34(5), pp.632-648. doi:10.1080/08856257.2019.158083.

Kurth, J., Morningstar, M. E. and Kozleski, E. B. (2014) 'The persistence of highly restrictive special education placements for students with low-incidence disabilities', *Research and Practice for Persons with Severe Disabilities*, 39, pp. 227-239. doi:10.1177/1540796914555580.

Kurth, J. A., Love, H., and Pirtle, J. (2020) 'Parent perspectives of their involvement in IEP development for children with autism', *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 35(1), pp. 36–46. doi.org/10.1177/1088357619842858

LaBarbera, R. (2017) 'A comparison of teacher and caregiver perspectives of collaboration in the education of students with autism spectrum disorders', *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 44(3), pp. 35-56. Available at: www.jstor.org/stable/90010902. (Accessed 22 May 2022).

Lalvani, P. (2015) 'Disability, stigma and otherness: Perspectives of parents and teachers', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 62(4), pp.379-393. doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2015.1029877.

Lam, C. S. C. (2022) 'Collaborative problem-based approach in training teachers to use positive behaviour support to help students with autism spectrum disorder', in Ho, F., Lam, C.S. and Arthur-Kelly, M., *Promoting Collaborative Learning Cultures to Help Teachers Support Students with Autism Spectrum Disorder*. Springer: Singapore, pp. 197-210.

Langley, A and Tsoukas, H. (2012) *Constructing Identity in and Around Organizations*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Lefever, S., Dal, M. and Matthíasdóttir, Á. (2007) 'Online data collection in academic research: advantages and limitations', *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 38(4), pp. 574-582. Available at: doi:10.1111/j.1467-8535.2006.00638.x

LeBlanc, L.A., Lazo-Pearson, J.F., Pollard, J.S and Unumb, L.S. (2020) 'The role of compassion and ethics in decision making regarding access to Applied Behavior Analysis Services during the COVID-19 crisis: A response to Cox, Plavnick, and Brodhea', *Behav Analysis Practice* 13, pp. 604–608.doi.org/10.1007/s40617-020-00446-7.

Lei, J., Sukhodolsky, D. G., Abdullahi, S. M., Braconnier, M. L., and Ventola, P. (2017) 'Reduced anxiety following pivotal response treatment in young children with autism spectrum disorder', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 43, pp. 1–7. doi:10.1016/j.rasd.2017.09.002.

Leiber, T. (2017) 'Computational social science and big data: A quick SWOT analysis'. in Wernecke J., Pietsch,W. and Ott, M. *Berechenbarkeit der Welt? Philosophie und Wissenschaft im Zeitalter von Big Data [Computability of the World? Philosophy and Science in the Age of Big Data]*, edited by, Berlin: Springer, pp. 287–301.

Leiber, T., Stensaker, B. and Harvey, L.C. (2018) 'Bridging theory and practice of impact evaluation of quality management in higher education institutions: a SWOT analysis', *European Journal of Higher Education*, 8(3), pp. 351-365. doi :10.1080/21568235.2018.1474782.

Leifler, E., Carpelan, G., Zakrevska, A., Bölte, S. and Jonsson, U. (2021) 'Does the learning environment 'make the grade'? A systematic review of accommodations for children with autism in mainstream school', *Scandinavian Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 28(8), pp.582-597. doi.org/10.1080/11038128.2020.1832145.

Lemay, R. A. (2009) 'Deinstitutionalization of people with developmental disabilities: A review of the literature', *Canadian Journal of Community Mental Health*, 28(1), pp. 181-194. doi.org/10.7870/cjcmh-2009-0014.

Leonard, N. and Smyth, S. (2022) 'Does training matter? Exploring teachers' attitudes towards the inclusion of children with autism spectrum disorder in mainstream education in Ireland', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, pp. 1-15. doi:10.1080/13603116.2020.1718221.

Lessner Listiakova, I. and Preece, D. (2020) 'In-service education and training for teachers regarding autism spectrum disorder: A review of the literature', *Annales Universitatis Paedagogicae Cracoviensis: Studia Psychologica*, 12, pp. 177-199. doi.org/10.24917/20845596.12.9.

Levine, R. L., and Rathmell, W. K. (2020) 'COVID-19 impact on early career investigators: A call for action', *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 20(7), pp. 357–358. doi.org/10.1038/s41568-020-0279-5.

Lewin, N. and Akhtar, N. (2020) 'Neurodiversity and deficit perspectives in The Washington Post's coverage of autism', *Disability & Society*, 36(5), pp. 812-833. doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2020.1751073

Lincoln, Y. and Denzin, N. (2003) *Turning Points in Qualitative Research: Tying Knots in a Handkerchief*. Walnut Creek: Altamira Press.

Lincoln, Y.S., Lyman, S.A. and Guba, E.G. (2011) 'Paradigmatic Controversies, Contradictions, and Emerging Confluences, Revisited' in Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. *The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research*, SAGE: London, pp.97-128.

Lindsay, S., Proulx, M., Thomson, N. and Scott, H. (2013) 'Educators' challenges of including children with Autism Spectrum Disorder in mainstream classrooms', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 60(4), pp.347-362. doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2013.846470.

Lindsay, S., Proulx, M., Scott, H. and Thomson, N. (2014) 'Exploring teachers' strategies for including children with autism spectrum disorder in mainstream classrooms', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 2, pp. 101-122. doi:10.1080/13603116.2012.758320.

Lindsay, G., Wedell, K. and Dockrell, J., (2020) 'Warnock 40 years on: The development of special educational needs since the Warnock Report and implications for the future', *Frontiers in Education*, 4, pp. 164- 184. doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2019.00164.

Lisak Šegota, N., Lištiaková, I., Stošić, J., Kossewska, J., Troshanska, J., and Nikolovska, A. *et al.* (2022) 'Teacher education and confidence regarding autism of specialist primary school teachers', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 37(1), pp. 14-27. doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2020.1829865

Lloyd, E. (2019) 'Creating 'Autism Friendly' education in an inclusive mainstream primary school', *Good Autism Practice (GAP)*, 20(2), pp. 13-26. Available at: web.a.ebscohost.com/ehost/detail/detail?vid=0&sid=a375bf7c-714c-4e21-a53ce48f80fb82b2%40sessionmgr4008&dbdata=JnNpdGU9ZWWhvc3QtGIZZQ%3d%3d#AN=140501222&db=eue. (Accessed 21 May 2021)

Lohse, S. (2017) 'Pragmatism, ontology, and philosophy of the social sciences in practice', *Philosophy of the Social Sciences*, 47(1), pp. 3-27. doi.org/10.1177/0048393116654869

Lollini, A. (2018) 'Brain equality: Legal implications of neurodiversity in a comparative perspective', *NYUJ Int'l L. & Pol.*, 51, pp. 69.

Lopez, M., Fitzgerald, R. T., Hewitt, A., Pettygrove, S., ... Dowling, N. F. (2018) 'Prevalence of Autism Spectrum Disorder among children aged 8 Years - Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network, 11 Sites, United States, 2014', *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report. Surveillance Summaries*, 67(6), pp. 1–23. doi.org/10.15585/mmwr.ss6706a1

Lord, C. (2011) How common is autism?. *Nature*, 474(7350), pp. 166-167. doi:167.10.1038/474166a

Lord C., Petkova E., Hus V., *et al.* (2012) 'A multisite study of the clinical diagnosis of different autism spectrum disorders', *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 69(3), pp. 306–313. doi:10.1001/archgenpsychiatry.2011.148

Lotter, V. (1966) Epidemiology of autistic conditions in young children, *Soc Psychiatry* 1, pp. 124–135. doi.org/10.1007/BF00584048

Lüddeckens, J., Anderson, L. and Östlund, D. (2022) 'Principals' perspectives of inclusive education involving students with autism spectrum conditions – A Swedish case study,' *Journal of Educational Administration*, 60(20), pp. 207-221. doi.org/10.1108/JEA-02-2021-0022

Ludicke, P. and Kortman, W. (2012) 'Tensions in home–school partnerships: The different perspectives of teachers and parents of students with learning barriers', *Australasian Journal of Special Education*, 36(2), pp. 155-171. doi:10.1017/jse.2012.13

Lundy, L. (2007) 'Voice' is not enough: conceptualising Article 12 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child', *British Educational Research Journal*, 33(6), pp. 927-942. doi:10.1080/01411920701657033

Lyall, K., Croen, L., Daniels, J., Fallin, M., Ladd-Acosta, C., and Lee, B. *et al.* (2017) 'The changing epidemiology of autism spectrum disorders', *Annual Review of Public Health*, 38(1), pp. 81-102. doi:10.1146/annurev-publhealth-031816-044318

Maarouf, H. (2019) 'Pragmatism as a supportive paradigm for the mixed research approach: Conceptualizing the ontological, epistemological, and axiological stances of pragmatism', *International Business Research*, 12(9), pp. 1-12. doi:10.5539/ibr.v12n9p1

Maciver, D., Rutherford, M., Arakelyan, S., Kramer, J. M., Richmond, J., Todorova, L., Romero-Ayuso, D., NakamuraThomas, H., Ten Velden, M., Finlayson, I., O'Hare, A., and Forsyth, K. (2021) 'Participation of children with disabilities in school: A realist systematic review of psychosocial and environmental factors', *PLOS ONE*, 14(1), doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0210511

Mackenzie, N. and Knipe, S. (2006) 'Research dilemmas: Paradigms, methods and methodology', *Issues in Educational Research*, 16, pp. 193-205. Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ806133 (Accessed 14 May 2021)

Majoko, T. (2018) 'Inclusion of children with autism spectrum disorders: Listening and hearing to voices from the grassroots', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 46(4), pp.1429-1440. doi:10.1007/s10803-015-2685-1.

Mamas, C., Daly, A., Cohen, S. and Jones, G., (2021) 'Social participation of students with autism spectrum disorder in general education settings', *Learning, Culture and Social Interaction*, 28, pp.1-14. doi.org/10.1016/j.lcsi.2020.100467

Mandy, W., Murin, M., Baykaner, O., Staunton, S., Hellriegel, J., Anderson, S. and Skuse, D. (2016) 'The transition from primary to secondary school in mainstream education for children with autism spectrum disorder', *Autism*, 20(1), pp. 5-13. doi.org/10.1177/1362361314562616

Mariage, T. V., Englert, C. S., and Plavnick, J. B. (2021) 'Teaching early learners with autism to follow written directions: Making text mediate action to promote independence', *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*, 36(1), pp. 36–46. doi.org/10.1177/1088357620943501

Marley, S. C., and Carbonneau, K. J. (2014) 'Future directions for theory and research with instructional manipulatives: Commentary on the special issue papers', *Educational Psychology Review*, 26, pp. 91–100. doi:10.1007/s10648-014-9259-1

Martin, W. and Bridgmon, K. (2012) *Quantitative and Statistical Research Methods: From Hypothesis to Findings*. New Jersey, USA: Jossey-Bass.

Materechera, E. (2018) 'Inclusive education: why it poses a dilemma to some teachers', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 24(7), pp. 771-786. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1492640

Maxcy, Spencer J. (2003) 'Pragmatic threads in mixed methods research in the social sciences: The search for multiple modes of inquiry and the end of the philosophy of formalism', in *Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research*. Edited by Abbas Tashakkori and Charles Teddlie. Thousand Oaks: Sage, pp. 51–89.

May, T., Brignell, A., and Williams, K. (2020) Autism spectrum disorder prevalence in children aged 12–13 years from the longitudinal study of Australian children. *Autism Research*, 13, pp. 821– 827. doi:10.1002/aur.2286.

Mazon, C., Etchegoyhen, K., Saint-Supery, I., Amestoy, A., Bouvard, M., Consel, C., and Sauzéon, H. (2021) 'Fostering parents-professional collaboration for facilitating the school inclusion of students with ASD: design of the "ToGather" web-based prototype', *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 70(1), pp. 231-262. doi.org/10.1007/s11423-021-10073-w.

McDougal, E., Riby, D., and Hanley, M. (2020) 'Teacher insights into the barriers and facilitators of learning in autism', *Research In Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 79, 101674. doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2020.101674.

McGrath, C., Palmgren, P. and Liljedahl, M. (2019) 'Twelve tips for conducting qualitative research interviews', *Medical Teacher*, 41(9), pp.1002-1006. doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2018.1497149.

McKinlay, J., Wilson, C., Hendry, G., and Ballantyne, C. (2022) "It feels like sending your children into the lions' den"—'A qualitative investigation into parental attitudes towards ASD inclusion, and the impact of mainstream education on their child', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 120, pp. 104-128. doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2021.104128.

McLaren, S.J. (2013) 'Is inclusive education right for every child? An account by the parent of a child with high and complex needs due to autism spectrum', *KAIRARANGA*, 14(2), pp. 26-34, <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1025671>

McLinden, M., Lynch, P., Soni, A. *et al.* (2018) 'Supporting children with disabilities in low- and middle-income countries: Promoting inclusive practice within community-based childcare centres in Malawi through a bioecological systems perspective', *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 50, pp.159–174. doi.org/10.1007/s13158-018-0223-y.

McLinden, M. and McCracken, W. (2016) 'Review of the visiting teachers service for children with hearing and visual impairment in supporting inclusive educational practice in Ireland: Examining stakeholder feedback through an ecological systems theory', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 31(4), pp. 472-488. doi:10.1080/08856257.2016.1194570

McNeal, R. B., Jr. (2014) 'Parent involvement, academic achievement and the role of student attitudes and behaviors as mediators', *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 2(8), pp. 564-576. Available at: ERIC database. (EJ1053945) (Accessed 17 June 2021)

Mead, G. H. (1938) *The Philosophy of the Act*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Meilleur, A., Jelenic, P. and Mottron, L. (2015) 'Prevalence of clinically and empirically defined talents and Strengths of autism', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 45(5), pp. 1354-1367. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-014-2296-2

Melgarejo, M., Lind, T., Stadnick, N. A., Helm, J. L., and Locke, J. (2020) 'Strengthening capacity for implementation of evidence-based practices for autism in schools: The roles of implementation climate, school leadership, and fidelity', *American Psychologist*, 75(8), pp. 1105–1115. doi.org/10.1037/amp0000649.

Mercieca, D., and Mercieca, D. P. (2022) 'Educational psychologists as 'dissenting voices': Thinking again about educational psychologists and social justice', *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 171. doi.org/10.3390/educsci12030171.

Mereoiu, M., Abercrombie, S. and Murray, M., (2016) 'Structured intervention as a tool to shift views of parent–professional partnerships: Impact on attitudes toward the IEP', *Exceptionality Education International*, 26(1), pp.36-52. doi:10.5206/eei.v26i1.7734.

Merriam, S. B. and Tisdell, E. J. (2016) *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation* (4th ed.). San Francisco, CA: Jossey Bass.

Merry, M. (2020) 'Do inclusion policies deliver educational justice for children with autism? An ethical analysis', *Journal of School Choice*, 14(1), pp. 9-25. Available at: doi:10.1080/15582159.2019.1644126.

Mertens, D.M. (2005) *Research Methods in Education and Psychology: Integrating Diversity with Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. (2nd ed.) Thousand Oaks: Sage

Miles, M., and Huberman, A. (1994) *Qualitative Data Analysis*. Thousand Oaks: SAGE Publications

Milton, D. and Sims, T. (2016) 'How is a sense of wellbeing and belonging constructed in the accounts of autistic adults?', *Disability and Society*, 31(4), pp. 520–534, doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2016.1186529

Minke, K., Sheridan, S., Kim, E., Ryoo, J. and Koziol, N. (2014) 'Congruence in parent-teacher relationships', *The Elementary School Journal*, 114(4), pp. 527-546. doi:10.1086/675637

Ministerial Committee on Inclusive Education (MCIE) (2000) *Inclusive Education Policy Regarding Students with a Disability*, Floriana: Ministry of Education

Ministero dell'Istruzione (2020) *Inclusione e nuovo PEI*. Italia: Ministero dell'Istruzione.

Ministry for Education and Employment (2012) *National Curriculum Framework for All*. Floriana: Ministry for Education and Employment

Ministry for Education and Employment (2014) *Respect for All Framework*. Floriana: Ministry for Education and Employment

Ministry for Education, Sport, Youth, Research and Innovation (MEYR) (2022a), *A Policy on Inclusive Education in Schools: Route to Quality Inclusion*. Floriana:

Ministry for Education, Sport, Youth, Research and Innovation (MEYR) (2022b), *A National Inclusive Education Framework*, Floriana: Ministry for Education, Sport, Youth, Research and Innovation (MEYR)

Ministry for Education, Sport, Youth, Research and Innovation (MEYR) (2023) *Lenti Project*. Available at: education.gov.mt/en/NSSS/Pages/Lenti-Project.aspx (Accessed: January 13, 2023).

Ministry for Inclusion and Social WellBeing (2021) *RESPECTING DIVERSITY SAFEGUARDING EQUALITY; Malta's 2021 – 2030 National Autism Strategy*. Government of Malta

Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government, *Persons Within the Autism Spectrum (Empowerment) Act* (Act XXVI of 2016) (Cap. 557): Malta.

Ministry of Education, (1999) *National Minimum Curriculum (NMC)*, Floriana: Ministry of Education

Ministry of Education and Employment (2012) *A National Curriculum Framework for All*. Floriana: Ministry of Education and Employment

Ministry of Education, Youth and Employment (2005) *For All Children to Succeed*, Floriana: Ministry of Education, Youth and Employment

Ministry of Education, Culture, Youth and Sport (2009) *Special Schools Reform*. Malta: Department of Student Services

Mirzakhani, N., and Shahriarpour, S. (2021) 'Sensory processing disorder and its effect on children's skills and development in autism disorders, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder and learning disabilities: A review article', *Journal of Clinical Physiotherapy Research*, 6(1), pp. 26. doi.org/10.22037/jcpr.v4i2.30978

Mitchell, D. (2014) *What Really Works in Special and Inclusive Education: Using Evidence-Based Teaching Strategies*. Second Edition. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.

Molina-Azorin, J. F. (2016) 'Mixed methods research: An opportunity to improve our studies and our research skill', *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 25, pp. 37-38. doi.org/10.1016/j.redeen.2016.05.001

Monteiro, E.M. (2021) 'An ecologically valid understanding of executive functioning', *Psychology in the Schools*, 59(7), pp.1390-1401. doi.org/10.1002/pits.22627

Moosa, D. (2013) 'Challenges to anonymity and representation in educational qualitative research in a small community: a reflection on my research journey', *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 43(4), pp. 483-495. doi.org/10.1080/03057925.2013.797733

Morgan, D. (2007) 'Paradigms lost and pragmatism regained', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 1(1), pp. 48-76. doi.org/10.1177/2345678906292462

Morgan, D.L. (2014) 'Pragmatism as a paradigm for social research', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 20(8), pp. 1045-1053. doi.org/10.1177/1077800413513733

Morgan, B., Maybery, M. and Durkin, K. (2003) 'Weak central coherence, poor joint attention, and low verbal ability: Independent deficits in early autism', *Developmental Psychology*, 39(4), pp. 646–656.: doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.39.4.646

Morrier, M., Hess, K. and Heflin, L. (2011) 'Teacher training for implementation of teaching strategies for students with autism spectrum disorders', *Teacher Education and Special Education: The Journal of the Teacher Education Division of the Council for Exceptional Children*, 34(2), pp. 119-132. doi:10.1177/0888406410376660

Morrison, K. (2006) 'Sensitive educational research in small states and territories: the case of Macau', *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 36(2), pp.249-264. doi.org/10.1080/03057920600741297

Morrison, K. E., Pinkham, A. E., Kelsven, S., Ludwig, K., Penn, D. L and Sasson, N. J. (2019) 'Psychometric evaluation of social cognitive measures for adults with autism', *Autism Research : Official Journal of the International Society for Autism Research*, 12(5), pp. 766–778. doi.org/10.1002/aur.2084

Morton, J. F. and Campbell, J. M. (2008) 'Information source affects peers' initial attitudes toward autism', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 29, pp. 189-201. doi:10.1016/j.ridd.2007.02.006

Msangi, B. (2012) 'The relevancy of Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems Theory in early childhood education', *Journal of Issues and Practices in Education*, 4(1), pp. 1-12, Available at: <http://repository.out.ac.tz/2347/> (Accessed 21 June 2022)

Mucharreira, P. R., Cabrito, B. G., and Capucha, L. (2019) 'Net costs of class-size reduction: The Portuguese case', *Cadernos de Pesquisa*, 49, pp. 164-181. doi:10.1590/198053146878

Murray, M. and Mereoiu, M., (2015) 'Teacher–parent partnership: an authentic teacher education model to improve student outcomes', *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 40(2), pp.276-292. doi:10.1080/0309877X.2014.971108

Murray, E., McFarland-Piazza, L., and Harrison, L. J. (2015) 'Changing patterns of parent–teacher communication and parent involvement from preschool to school', *Early Child Development and Care*, 185(7), pp. 1031-1052. doi:10.1080/03004430.2014.975223

Musetti, A., Manari, T., Dioni, B., Raffin, C., Bravo, G., Mariani, R., ... and Corsano, P. (2021) 'Parental quality of life and involvement in intervention for children or adolescents with autism spectrum disorders: A systematic review', *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 11(9), pp.894. doi:10.3390/jpm11090894.

Nah, Y.H. and Tan, J.W.L. (2021) 'The effect of diagnostic labels on teachers' perceptions of behaviours of students with autism spectrum disorder', *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 91(1), pp.315-327. doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12368

Namugenyi, C., Nimmagadda, S. L., and Reiners, T. (2019) 'Design of a SWOT analysis model and its evaluation in diverse digital business ecosystem contexts', *Procedia Computer Science*, 159, pp. 1145-1154. doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.283

Nang, A. F. M., Maat, S. M., and Mahmud, M. S. (2022) 'Teacher technostress and coping mechanisms during Covid-19 pandemic: A systematic review', *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, 12(2), pp. 200-212. Available at: orcid.org/0000-0002-5507-9081 (Accessed: 30 October 2022)

Negeri, S.D., Kristiawan, M., and Puspita, A. (2020) 'SWOT analysis of instruction at state elementary school south Indralaya', *Electronic Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 2(2), pp. 136-150. Available at: ISSN: 2706 – 8242 (Accessed 20 March 2021).

Neuendorf, K. (2002) *The Content Analysis Guidebook*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications Inc.

Ní Bhroin, O. and King, F. (2020) 'Teacher education for inclusive education: A framework for developing collaboration for the inclusion of students with support plans', *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(1), pp.38–63. doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2019.1691993

Norris, N. (2022) 'How does my student learn? Neurodiversity and the nature of learning in autism', *International Journal of Christianity and Education*, pp. 1-23. doi.org/10.1177/20569971221084350

Nthibeli, M., Griffiths, D. and Bekker, T. (2022) 'Teaching learners with autism in the South African inclusive classroom: Pedagogic strategies and possibilities', *African Journal of Disability*, 11, pp.979. doi. org/10.4102/ajod.v11i0.979

Nyein, K., Caylor, J., Duong, N., Fry, T. and Wildman, J. (2020) 'Beyond positivism: Toward a pluralistic approach to studying “real” teams', *Organizational Psychology Review*, 10(2), pp. 87-112. doi.org/10.1177/2041386620915593

Ochs, E., Kremer-Sadlik, T., Solomon, O., and Sirota, K. G. (2001) 'Inclusion as social practice: Views of children with autism', *Social Development*, 10(3), pp. 399–419. doi.org/10.1111/1467-9507.00172

Odom, S.L. (2019) 'Peer-based interventions for children and youth with autism spectrum disorder: History and effects', *School Psychology Review*, 48(2), pp. 170-176. doi:10.17105/SPR-2019-0019.V48-2

Oducado, R.M. (2021) 'A cross-sectional exploration of zoom fatigue among Filipino university teachers', *Social Science Research Network*, doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3972518

O'Donoghue, T. (2007) *Planning Your Qualitative Research Project: An Introduction to Interpretivist Research in Education*. London: Routledge

O'Rourke, J. (2015) Inclusive schooling: if it's so good – why is it so hard to sell?. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 19(5), pp. 530-546. doi: 10.1080/13603116.2014.954641

Onwuegbuzie, A.J. and Combs, J.P. (2010) 'Emergent data analysis techniques in mixed methods research: A synthesis', in Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C. (Eds.), *Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioral Research* (2nd ed.), Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. pp. 397-430.

Onwuegbuzie, A., Collins, K. and Frels, R. (2013) 'Foreword' *International Journal of Multiple Research Approaches*, 7(1), pp. 2-8. doi:10.5172/mra.2013.7.1.2

Onwuegbuzie, A. J., and Johnson, R. B. (2006) 'The validity issue in mixed research', *Research in the Schools*, 13, pp. 48-63. Available at: www.proquest.com/openview/2e0bfef20ec8fbb0fc5f8057460a8d1c/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=10235. (Accessed 13 September 2021).

Óskarsdóttir, E., Donnelly, V., Turner-Cmuchal, M. and Florian, L., (2020) 'Inclusive school leaders—their role in raising the achievement of all learners', *Journal of Educational Administration*, 58(5), pp.521-537. doi.org/10.1108/JEA-10-2019-0190

Ousley, O., and Cermak, T. (2014) 'Autism spectrum disorder: Defining dimensions and subgroups', *Curr Dev Disord Rep* 1, pp. 20–28, Available at: doi.org/10.1007/s40474-013-0003-1

Ozel, E., Sau Cheng Loh, D., and Mahmoud Danaee, D. (2022) 'What is the effect of general education teachers' attitudes on knowledge and experience on the education of ASD students?', *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, pp. 1869-1887. Available at: journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/3384/2207. (Accessed 1 September 2022)

Ozonoff, S., Young, G. S., Brian, J., Charman, T., Shephard, E., Solish, A., and Zwaigenbaum, L. (2018) 'Diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder after age 5 in children evaluated longitudinally since infancy', *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 57(11), pp. 849–857. /doi.org/10.1016/j.jaac.2018.06.022

Ozonoff, S., Young, G. S., Landa, R. J., Brian, J., Bryson, S., Charman, T., ... Iosif, A. M. (2015) 'Diagnostic stability in young children at risk for autism spectrum disorder: A baby siblings research consortium study', *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 56(9), pp. 988-998. doi.org/10.1111/jcpp.12421

Paget, A., Parker, C., Heron, J., Logan, S., Henley, W., Emond, A., and Ford, T. (2018) 'Findings from a large British birth cohort study', *Child Care, Health and Development*, 44(2), pp. 285–296. doi:10.1111/cch.12525.

Pannucci, C. J. and Wilkins, E. G. (2010) Identifying and avoiding bias in research. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 126(2), pp.619–625. <https://doi.org/10.1097/PRS.0b013e3181de24bc>

Park, M. and Chitiyo, M. (2010) 'An examination of teacher attitudes towards children with autism', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 11(1), pp. 70-78. doi:10.1111/j.1471-3802.2010.01181.x

Pasco, G. (2018) 'The value of early intervention for children with autism', *Paediatrics and Child Health*, 28(8), pp. 364-367. doi:10.1016/j.paed.2018.06.001

Patton, M. (2005) 'Qualitative research', *Encyclopedia of Statistics in Behavioral Science*. Available at: doi.org/10.1002/0470013192.bsa514

Pastor-Cerezuela, G., Fernández-Andrés, M., Sanz-Cervera, P. and Marín-Suelves, D. (2020) 'The impact of sensory processing on executive and cognitive functions in children with autism spectrum disorder in the school context', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 96, pp.1-10. doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2019.103540

Pearson, J. N., Traficante, A. L., Denny, L. M., Malone, K., and Codd, E. (2020) 'Meeting FACES: Preliminary findings from a community workshop for minority parents of children with autism in Central North Carolina', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 50(1), pp. 1-11. doi:10.1007/s10803-019-04295-4.

Perrault E.K. and Keating D.M (2018) 'Seeking ways to inform the uninformed: Improving the informed consent process in online social science research', *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, 13(1), pp. 50-60. doi:10.1177/1556264617738846

Pierce K, Gazestani VH, Bacon E, Courchesne, E. (2019) 'Evaluation of the diagnostic stability of the early autism spectrum disorder phenotype in the general population starting at 12 months', *JAMA Pediatrics*, 173(6), pp. 578–587. doi:10.1001/jamapediatrics.2019.0624

Posada, M., Garcia Primo, P., Ferrari, M.J. and Martín-Arribas, M.C. (2007) *European Autism Information System (Eais) Report on The 'Autism Spectrum Disorders Prevalence Data And Accessibility To Services' Questionnaire (Q-Eais)*, Research Institute for Rare Diseases, Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Madrid

Poth, C. and Munce, S. E. P. (2020) 'Commentary—Preparing today's researchers for a yet unknown tomorrow: Promising practices for a synergistic and sustainable mentoring approach to mixed methods research learning', *International Journal of Multiple Research Approaches*, 12(1), pp. 56-64. doi:10.29034/ijmra.v12n1commentary

Pound, L. (2011) *Influencing Early Childhood Education. Key Figures, Philosophies and Ideas*. Maidenhead: Open University Press.

Powell, T. (2001) 'Competitive advantage: logical and philosophical considerations', *Strategic Management Journal*, 22(9), pp. 875-888. doi.org/10.1002/smj.173

Pratt, S. F. (2016) 'Pragmatism as ontology, not (just) epistemology: Exploring the full horizon of pragmatism as an approach to IR theory', *International Studies*

Review, 18(3), pp. 508-527. Available at: www.jstor.org/stable/26407952 (Accessed: 1 May 2020)

Prizant, B. and Fields-Meyer, T. (2015) *Uniquely Human: A Different Way of Seeing Autism*. New York: Simon and Schuster.

Proff, I., Williams, G. L., Quadt, L., and Garfinkel, S. N. (2022) 'Sensory processing in autism across exteroceptive and interoceptive domains', *Psychology and Neuroscience*, 15(2), pp. 105–130. doi.org/10.1037/pne0000262

Predescu, M., Al Ghazi, L. and Darjan, I. (2018) 'An ecological approach of autism spectrum disorders', *Journal of Educational Sciences*, XIX, 2(38), pp. 31-43. doi:10.35923/JES.2018.2.03

Premack, D. and Woodruff, G. (1978) 'Does the chimpanzee have a theory of mind?' *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 1(4), pp. 515-526. doi:10.1017/S0140525X00076512

Putnam, L.L. (1994) 'Productive conflict: Negotiation as implicit coordination', *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 5(3), pp. 284-298. doi.org/10.1108/eb022748

Queirós, A., Faria, D. and Almeida, F. (2017) 'Strengths and limitation of qualitative and quantitative research methods', *European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(9), pp. 369-387. doi:10.5281/zenodo.887089

Rajendran, G. and Mitchell, P. (2007) Cognitive theories of autism, *Developmental Review*, 27(2), pp. 224-260. doi: 10.1016/j.dr.2007.02.001

Rajotte, É., Grandisson, M., Hamel, C., Couture, M.M., Desmarais, C., Gravel, M. and Chrétien-Vincent, M. (2022) 'Inclusion of autistic students: Promising modalities for supporting a school team', *Disability and Rehabilitation*, pp.1-11. doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2022.2057598

Rakap, S., Balikci, S. and Kalkan, S. (2018) 'Teachers' knowledge about autism spectrum disorder: The case of Turkey', *Turkish Journal of Education*, 7(4), pp. 169-185. doi:10.19128/turje.388398.

Raudeliūnaitė, R. and Steponėnienė, E. (2020) 'Challenges for primary school teachers in ensuring inclusive education for children with autism spectrum disorders', *Pedagogika*, 138(2), pp. 209-225. doi.org/10.15823/p.2020.138.12

Ravet, J. (2018) 'But how do I teach them?': Autism and Initial Teacher Education (ITE). *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 22(7), pp. 714-733. doi:10.1080/13603116.2017.1412505

Razali, N.M., Toran, H., Kamaralzaman, S., Salleh, N.M., and Yasin, M.H. (2013) 'Teachers' perceptions of including children with autism in a preschool', *Asian Social Science*, 9, pp.261-267. doi:10.5539/ass.v9n12p261

Redding, S. (2013) 'Through the student's eyes: A perspective on personalized learning and practice guide for teachers', *Center on Innovations in Learning*, pp. 1-38. Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=ED558042 (Accessed 23 June 2022)

Reja, U., Manfreda, K.L., Hlebec, V. and Vehovar, V. (2003) Open-ended vs. close-ended questions in web questionnaires. *Metodološki Zvezki*, 19, pp. 159–177. Available at: shorturl.at/acjKX (Accessed 22 June 2020)

Reupert, A., Deppeler, J. and Sharma, U. (2015) 'Enablers for inclusion: The perspectives of parents of children with autism spectrum disorder', *Australasian Journal of Special Education*, 39(1), pp. 85-96. doi:10.1017/jse.2014.17

Rissanen, I., Kuusisto, E., Tuominen, M. and Tirri, K. (2019) 'In search of a growth mindset pedagogy: A case study of one teacher's classroom practices in a Finnish elementary school', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 77, pp. 204-213. doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2018.10.002

Roberts, J. and Simpson, K. (2016) 'A review of research into stakeholder perspectives on inclusion of students with autism in mainstream schools', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*. 20(10), pp.1084-1096. doi:10.1080/13603116.2016.1145267

Roberts, J. and Webster, A. (2022) 'Including students with autism in schools: a whole school approach to improve outcomes for students with autism', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 26(7), pp. 701-718. doi:10.1080/13603116.2020.1712622

Robins, D. L., Fein, D., Barton, M. L., and Green, J. A. (2001) 'The Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers: an initial study investigating the early detection of autism and pervasive developmental disorders', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 31(2), pp. 131–144. doi.org/10.1023/a:1010738829569

Robson, C. (2011) *Real World Research: A Resource for Users of Social Research Methods in Applied Settings*. Wiley: Chichester

Rodden, B., Prendeville, P., Burke, S., and Kinsella, W. (2019) 'Framing secondary teachers' perspectives on the inclusion of students with autism spectrum disorder using critical discourse analysis', *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 49(2), pp. 235-253. doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2018.1506018

Roleska, M., Roman-Urrestarazu, A., Griffiths, S., Ruigrok, A., Holt, R., van Kessel, R., McColl, K., Sherlaw, W., Brayne, C. and Czabanowska, K. (2018) 'Autism and the right to education in the EU: Policy mapping and scoping review of the United Kingdom, France, Poland and Spain', *PLOS ONE*, 13(8), pp. 1-17, doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0202336

Romero-Gutierrez, M., Jimenez-Liso, M. and Martinez-Chico, M. (2016) 'SWOT analysis to evaluate the programme of a joint online/onsite Master's degree in environmental education through the students' perceptions', *Evaluation and Program Planning*. 54, pp.41-49. doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2015.10.001

- Rorty, R. (1980) *Philosophy and the Mirror of Nature*. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Rorty, R. (1991) *Essays on Heidegger and Others*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Rorty, R. (1998) *Truth and Progress*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Rose, R. and Shevlin, M. (2019) 'Support provision for students with special educational needs in Irish primary schools', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 20(1), pp. 51-63. doi:10.1111/1471-3802.12465
- Rosello, B., Berenguer, C., Baixauli, I., García, R., and Miranda, A. (2020) 'Theory of mind profiles in children with autism spectrum disorder: Adaptive/social skills and pragmatic competence', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, pp.1-14. doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.567401
- Rowe, W.E. (2014) 'Positionality', *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Action Research* doi:10.4135/9781446294406.n277.
- Runswick-Cole, K., Timimi, S. and Mallett, R. (2016) *Re-thinking Autism: Diagnosis, Identity and Equality*. London: Jessica Kingsley
- Russell, G., Kapp, S. K., Elliott, D., Elphick, C., Gwernan-Jones, R., and Owens, C. (2019) 'Mapping the autistic advantage from the accounts of adults diagnosed with autism: A qualitative study', *Autism in Adulthood*, 1(2), pp. 124–133. doi:10.1089/aut.2018.0035.
- Russell, A., Scriney, A., and Smyth, S. (2022) 'Educator attitudes towards the inclusion of students with autism spectrum disorders in mainstream education: A Systematic Review', *Review Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*. doi.org/10.1007/s40489-022-00303-z
- Russell, G., Stapley, S., Newlove-Delgado, T., Salmon, A., White, R., Warren, F., Pearson, A. and Ford, T. (2022) 'Time trends in autism diagnosis over 20 years: a UK population-based cohort study', *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 63(6), pp.674-682. doi:10.1111/jcpp.13505
- Rutherford, M., Baxter, J., Grayson, Z., Johnston, L. and O'Hare, A. (2020) 'Visual supports at home and in the community for individuals with autism spectrum disorders: A scoping review', *Autism*, 24(2), pp. 447-469. doi:10.1177/1362361319871756.
- Sabayleh, O. A. and Alramamneh, A. K. S. (2020) 'Obstacles of implementing educational techniques in special education centres from autism teachers' perspective', *Cypriot Journal of Educational Science*. 15(2), pp. 171-183. doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v15i2.4485
- Saggers, B., Klug, D., Harper-Hill, K., Ashburner, J., Costley, D., Clark, T., Bruck, S., Trembath, D., Webster, A., and Carrington, S. (2016) *Australian Autism Educational Needs Analysis - What are the Needs of Schools, Parents and Students*

with autism? (Full Report). Cooperative Research Centre for Living with Autism (Autism CRC), Australia.

Saggers, B., Tones, M., Dunne, J., Trembath, D., Bruck, S. and Webster, A. *et al.* (2019) 'Promoting a collective voice from parents, educators and allied health professionals on the educational needs of students with autism', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 49(9), pp. 3845-3865. doi:10.1007/s10803-019-04097-8

Santos, M.I., Breda, A. and Almeida, A.M. (2017) 'Design approach of Mathematics learning activities in a digital environment for children with autism spectrum disorders', *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 61, pp. 1305–1323, doi.org/10.1007/s11423-017-9525-2

Sarantakos, S. (2013) *Social Research*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Sarsby, A. (2016) *SWOT Analysis: A Guide to SWOT for Business Study Students*. U.K: Leadership Library

Sasson, I., Yehuda, I. and Miedijensky, S. (2021) 'Innovative learning spaces: class management and universal design for learning', *Learning Environments Research*, pp. 1-15. doi.org/10.1007/s10984-021-09393-8

Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., (2009), *Research Onion. Research Methods for Business Students*. Essex: Pearson Education

Savin-Baden, M. and Major, C. (2013) *Qualitative Research: The Essential Guide to Theory and Practice*. Routledge, London.

Schopler, E., Van Bourgondien, M. E., Wellman, G. J. and Love, S. R. (2010) *Childhood Autism Rating Scale (CARS)* (2nd ed.). Los Angeles, CA, USA: Western Psychological Service

Schultz, T., Schmidt, C. and Stichter, J. (2011) 'A review of parent education programs for parents of children with Autism Spectrum Disorders', *Focus on Autism And Other Developmental Disabilities*, 26(2), pp. 96-104. doi:10.1177/1088357610397346

Schultz, T., Able, H., Sreckovic, M. and White, T. (2016) 'Parent-teacher collaboration: Teacher perceptions of what is needed to support students with ASD in the inclusive classroom', *Education and Training in Autism and Developmental Disabilities*, 51(4), pp. 344-354. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26173862> (Accessed 12 May 2021)

Scanlon, G., Radeva, S., Pitsia, V., Maguire, C., and Nikolaeva, S. (2022) 'Attitudes of teachers in Bulgarian kindergartens towards inclusive education', *Teaching And Teacher Education*, 112, 103650. doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2022.103650

Sciberras, C. (2018) 'Moving towards an evidence-based practice approach? Exploring the strategies used as part of the support programmes of students with

autism in primary mainstream, state-funded schools in Malta', *Malta Review of Educational Research*, 12(2), pp. 220-237. Available at : www.um.edu.mt/library/oar/handle/123456789/38813 (Accessed 21 September 2020)

Sciberras, C. (2019) 'Applying a SWOT analysis to inform educational provision for learners with autism', *Advances in Autism*, 5(4), pp. 226-230. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AIA-03-2018-0011>

Segall, M. J., and Campbell, J. M. (2012) 'Factors relating to education professionals' classroom practices for the inclusion of students with autism spectrum disorders'. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 6, 1156–1167. doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2012.02.007

Segall, M. and Campbell, J. (2014) 'Factors influencing the educational placement of students with autism spectrum disorders', *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 8(1), pp. 31-43. doi.org/10.1016/j.rasd.2013.10.006

Shaari, M. F. and Ahmad, S. S. (2016) 'Physical learning environment: impact on children school readiness in Malaysian preschools', *Procedia -Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 222, pp. 9–18. Available at: doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.164

Shah, A. and Frith, U. (1983) An islet of ability in autistic children: A research note, *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 24(4), pp. 613-620. [doi: 10.1111/j.1469-7610.1983.tb00137.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.1983.tb00137.x)

Shah, A. and Frith, U. (1993) Why do autistic individuals show superior performance on the block design task?, *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 34(8), pp. 1351-1364. [doi: 10.1111/j.1469-7610.1993.tb02095.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.1993.tb02095.x)

Shah, P., Boilson, M., Rutherford, M., Prior, S., Johnston, L., Maciver, D., and Forsyth, K. (2022), 'Neurodevelopmental disorders and neurodiversity: Definition of terms from Scotland's National Autism Implementation Team', *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 221(3), pp. 577-579. [doi:10.1192/bjp.2022.43](https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.2022.43)

Shannon-Baker, P. (2016) 'Making paradigms meaningful in mixed methods research', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 10(4), pp. 319-334. doi.org/10.1177/1558689815575861

Sharma, S., Devi, R. and Kumari, J. (2018) 'Pragmatism in education', *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 5(1), pp. 1549-1554, ISSN 2394 – 3386

Sharma, U., A. C. Armstrong, L. Merumeru, J. Simi, and H. Yared. (2019), 'Addressing barriers to implementing inclusive education in the Pacific', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 23, pp. 65–78. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1514751

Sharp, J., Mobley, C., Hammond, C., Withington, C., Drew, S., Stringfield, S. and Stipanovic, N. (2012) 'A mixed methods sampling methodology for a multisite case

study', *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 6(1), pp. 34-54. doi.org/10.1177/1558689811417133

Sheldrick, R.C., Carter, A.S., Eisenhower, A., Mackie, T.I., Cole, M.B., Hoch, N., Brunt, S. and Pedraza, F.M. (2022) 'Effectiveness of screening in early intervention settings to improve diagnosis of autism and reduce health disparities', *JAMA Pediatrics*, 176(3), pp.262-269. doi:10.1001/jamapediatrics.2021.5380

Shepherd, D., Landon, J., Taylor, S. and Goedeke, S. (2018) 'Coping and care-related stress in parents of a child with autism spectrum disorder', *Anxiety, Stress, and Coping*, 31(3), pp. 277-290. doi:10.1080/10615806.2018.144261

Sheridan, S. M., Smith, T. E., Moorman Kim, E., Beretvas, S. N. and Park, S. (2019). 'A meta-analysis of family-school interventions and children's social-emotional functioning: Moderators and components of efficacy', *Review of Educational Research*, 89(2), pp. 296–332. doi.org/10.3102/0034654318825437

Shipman, M. (2014) *The Limitations of Social Research*. Hoboken: Taylor and Francis.

Shusterman, R. (1994) Dewey on experience: foundation or reconstruction? *Philosophical Forum*, XXVI: pp. 127–148.

Siller, M., Morgan, L., Wedderburn, Q., Fuhrmeister, S. and Rudrabhatla, A. (2021) 'Inclusive early childhood education for children with and without autism: Progress, barriers, and future directions', *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 12, 754648. doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2021.754648

Silveira-Zaldivar, T. and Curtis, H. (2019) "I m Not Trained for This " and other barriers to evidence-based social skills interventions for elementary students with high functioning autism in inclusion', *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 12(1), pp.53-66. Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1232739 (Accessed 17 August 2021).

Silverman, C. (2008) 'Fieldwork on another planet: Social science perspectives on the autism spectrum' *BioSocieties*, 3(3), pp. 325-341. doi:10.1017/S1745855208006236

Simó-Pinatella, D., Günther-Bel, C., and Mumbardó-Adam, C. (2021) 'Addressing challenging behaviours in children with autism: A qualitative analysis of teachers' experiences', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*. doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2020.187066

Simon, M.K. and Goes, J. (2013) 'Scope, limitations, and delimitations', *Dissertation and Scholarly Research: Recipes for Success*. Seattle, WA: Dissertation Success LLC

Simons, L. and Lathlean, J. (2010) 'Mixed methods' in Gerrish, K. and Lacey, A. (Eds.) *The Research Process in Nursing*. 6th ed. London, Wiley-Blackwell. Pp. 350-375

Simpson, B. (2009) 'Pragmatism, Mead and the practice turn.', *Organization Studies*, 30(12), pp. 1329-1347. doi.org/10.1177/0170840609349861

Singer, J. (2017) *NeuroDiversity. The Birth of an Idea*. Singer: Australia

Skowroński, K.P. (2019) 'Naturalistic axiology and normativity in Rorty', In Auxier, R., Kramer, E. and Skowroński, K.P. *Rorty and Beyond*. Lexington Books: London, pp. 61-76

Smith, C. and Mercieca, D. (2021) 'Teachers working in special education in Scotland: Perceptions regarding emotional awareness and regulation amongst pupils within the Autism Spectrum', *Scottish Educational Review* 53(1), pp. 42-63, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1163/27730840-05301004>

Smith, B.O., Meux, M., Coombs, J., Nuthall, G. and Precians, R. (1967) *A Study of the Strategies of Teaching*. Office of Education: Washington.

Smogorzewska, J., Szumski, G. and Grygiel, P. (2020) 'Theory of mind goes to school: Does educational environment influence the development of theory of mind in middle childhood?', *PLOS ONE*, 15(8), pp. 1-14. doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0237524

Sobeck, A.A. and Robertson, R. (2019) 'Perspectives on current practices and barriers to training for paraeducators of students with autism in inclusive settings', *Journal of the American Academy of Special Education Professionals*, pp.131-151 Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1254304 (Accessed 22 October 2021)

Sonido, M., Arnold, S., Higgins, J., and Hwang, Y.J. (2020) 'Autism in later life: What Is known and what is needed?', *Current Developmental Disorders Report*, 7, pp. 69–77. doi.org/10.1007/s40474-020-00192-z

Soto-Chodiman, R., J. Pooley, J. and M. Taylor (2012) 'Students with ASD in mainstream primary education settings: Teachers' experiences in Western Australian classrooms', *Australasian Journal of Special Education* 36, pp. 97–111. doi:10.1017/jse.2012.10.

Spooner, F., Root, J. R., Saunders, A. F. and Browder, D. M. (2019) 'An updated evidence-based practice review on teaching mathematics to students with moderate and severe developmental disabilities' *Remedial and Special Education*, 40(3), pp. 150–165. doi.org/10.1177/0741932517751055

Stadnick NA, Brookman-Frazee L, Mandell DS, Kuelbs CL, Coleman KJ, Sahms T, Aarons G.A. (2019) 'Mixed methods study to adapt and implement integrated mental healthcare for children with autism spectrum disorder', *Pilot Feasibility Stud.* 28(5), pp. 51. doi:10.1186/s40814-019-0434-5.

Stahl, N.A. and King, J.R. (2020) 'Expanding approaches for research: Understanding and using trustworthiness in qualitative research', *Journal of Developmental Education*, 44(1), pp.26-28. Available at: eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1320570 (Accessed 15 October 2020)

Stahmer, A., Rieth, S., Lee, E., Reisinger, E., Mandell, D. and Connell, J. (2015) 'Training teachers to use evidence-based practices for autism: Examining procedural implementation fidelity', *Psychology in the Schools*, 52(2), pp. 181-195. doi:10.1002/pits.21815

Stenhoff, D. M., Pennington, R. C., and Tapp, M. C. (2020) 'Distance education support for students with autism spectrum disorder and complex needs during covid-19 and school closures', *Rural Special Education Quarterly*, 39(4), pp. 211–219. doi.org/10.1177/8756870520959658

Stephenson, J. and Adams, C. (2016) 'The social communication experience of children with autism in mainstream school', *Good Autism Practice (GAP)*, 17(2) pp.43-54. Available at: shorturl.at/cquU3 (Accessed 7 December 2021).

Stokes, M., Thomson, M., Macmillan, C., Pecora, L., Dymond, S. and Donaldson, E. (2017) 'Principals' and teachers' reports of successful teaching strategies with children with high-functioning autism spectrum disorder', *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 32(3-4), pp.192-208. doi.org/10.1177/0829573516672969

Stroetinga, M., Leeman, Y., and Veugelers, W. (2019) 'Primary school teachers' collaboration with parents on upbringing: A review of the empirical literature', *Educational Review*, 71(5), pp. 650–667. doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2018.1459478

Strunk, J., Leisen, M. and Schubert, C. (2017) 'Using a multidisciplinary approach with children diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder', *Journal of Interprofessional Education and Practice*, 8, pp. 60-68. doi:10.1016/j.xjep.2017.03.009

Styslinger, M. (2012) 'Making Meaning Strategies for Literacy Learning', *Phi Delta Kappan*, 94(4), pp. 40-45. doi:10.1177/003172171209400411.

Subedi, D. (2016) Explanatory sequential mixed method design as the third research: Community of knowledge claim. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4, pp. 570–577. doi:10.12691/education-4-7-10

Sukbunpant, S., Arthur-Kelly, M. and Dempsey, I., (2013) 'Thai preschool teachers' views about inclusive education for young children with disabilities', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 17(10), pp.1106-1118. doi:10.1080/13603116.2012.741146

Suhrheinrich, J., Melgarejo, M., Root, B., Aarons, G. and Brookman-Frazee, L., (2021) 'Implementation of school-based services for students with autism: Barriers and facilitators across urban and rural districts and phases of implementation', *Autism*, 25(8), pp. 2291-2304. doi.org/10.1177/13623613211016729

Sulek, R., Trembath, D., Paynter, J. and Keen, D. (2019) 'Empirically supported treatments for students with autism: General education teacher knowledge, use, and social validity ratings', *Developmental Neurorehabilitation*, 22(6) pp. 380-389, doi:10.1080/17518423.2018.1526224.

Sun, X., Allison, C., Auyeung, B., Baron-Cohen, S. and Brayne, C. (2013) 'A review of healthcare service and education provision for Autism Spectrum Condition in mainland China', *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 34(1), pp.469-479. doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2012.08.013

Syeda, N., and Bruck, S. (2022) 'We are on the same page! Strengthening parent-teacher partnerships through autism-focused training workshops', *School Community Journal*, 32(1), pp. 225-244, Available at: <http://www.schoolcommunitynetwork.org/SCJ.aspx> (Accessed 10 September 2022)

Symes, W. and Humphrey, N. (2011) 'School factors that facilitate or hinder the ability of teaching assistants to effectively support pupils with autism spectrum disorders (ASDs) in mainstream secondary schools', *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 11(3), pp. 153-161. doi:10.1111/j.1471-3802.2011.01196.x

Syriopoulou-Delli, C., Cassimos, D., Tripsianis, G. and Polychronopoulou, S. (2012) 'Teachers' perceptions regarding the management of children with autism spectrum disorders', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 42(5), pp. 755-768. doi:10.1007/s10803-011-1309-7.

Syriopoulou Delli, C., Varveris, A. and Geronta, A. (2017) Application of the theory of mind, theory of executive functions and weak central coherence theory to individuals with ASD, *Journal of Educational and Developmental Psychology*, 7(1), pp. 102-122. doi: 10.5539/jedp.v7n1p102

Takayanagi, M., Kawasaki, Y., Shinomiya, M., Hiroshi, H., Okada, S., and Ino, T. *et al.* (2021) 'Review of cognitive characteristics of autism spectrum disorder using performance on six subtests on four versions of the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 52(1), pp. 240-253. Available at: doi.org/10.1007/s10803-021-04932-x

Taguchi, N. (2018) 'Description and explanation of pragmatic development: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research', *System*, 75, pp. 23-32. doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2018.03.010

Tanti Burlo', E. (2016) in Ministry for Justice, Culture and Local Government *Persons Within the Autism Spectrum (Empowerment) Act (Act XXVI of 2016) (Cap. 557)*: Malta

Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C. (2003) 'The past and future of mixed methods research: From data triangulation to mixed model designs' in Tashakkori, A. and Teddlie, C., *Handbook of Mixed Methods in Social and Behavioural Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publication.

Teddlie, C. and Tashakkori, A. (2009) *Foundations of Mixed Methods Research: Integrating Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches in Social And Behavioral Sciences*. California: Sage Publication.

Teddlie, C. and Tashakkori, A. (2011) 'Mixed-methods research: Contemporary issues in an emerging field' in Denzin, N.K and Lincoln, Y.S. (2011) *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research*, London: Sage Publication, pp. 285-300

Teo, J., Lau, B., and Then, P. (2022) 'Autism spectrum disorders in Sarawak: An overview and analysis of educator awareness, training, development opportunities, and challenges', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 69(2), pp.623-639. doi.org/10.1080/1034912x.2020.1731433

Test, D. W., Smith, L. E., and Carter, E. W. (2014) 'Equipping youth with autism spectrum disorders for adulthood: Promoting rigor, relevance, and relationships', *Remedial and Special Education*, 35(2), pp. 80–90. doi:10.1177/074193251351485710.1177

Thamrin, H. and Pamungkas, E.W. (2017) 'A rule based SWOT analysis application: a case study for Indonesian higher education institution', *Proc Comput Sci*, 116, pp. 144–150, Available at: doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2017.10.056

The Scottish Government (2018) *The Scottish Strategy for Autism*. Crown; Edinburgh

Theofanidis, D. and Fountouki, A. (2019) 'Limitations and delimitations in the research process', *Perioperative Nursing (GORNA)*, 7(3), pp.155–162, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.2552022

Thomson, P. Lingard, B. and Wrigley, T. (2012) 'Ideas for changing educational systems, educational policy and schools', *Critical Studies in Education*, 53(1), pp. 1-7. doi:10.1080/17508487.2011.636451

Todd, T., Beamer, J. and Goodreau, J. (2014) 'Bridging the gap: Teacher-parent partnerships for students with Autism Spectrum Disorder', *Learning Landscapes*, 8(1), pp. 287-304. doi:10.36510/learnland.v8i1.686

Tokatly Latzer, I., Leitner, Y., and Karnieli-Miller, O. (2021) 'Core experiences of parents of children with autism during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown', *Autism*, 25(4), pp. 1047-1059. doi:10.1177/1362361320984317

Tola, G., Talu, V., Congiu, T., Bain, P. and Lindert, J. (2021) 'Built environment design and people with autism spectrum disorder (ASD): A scoping review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(6), pp. 3203. doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18063203

Torres, E. B., Caballero, C., and Mistry, S. (2020) 'Aging with autism departs greatly from typical aging', *Sensors*, 20(2), pp. 572. doi.org/10.3390/s20020572

Totsika, V., Hastings, R. P., Dutton, Y., Worsley, A., Melvin, G., Gray, K., Tonge, B., and Heyne, D. (2020) 'Types and correlates of school non-attendance in students with autism spectrum disorders', *Autism*, 24(7), pp. 1639–1649.

Tran, L., Patton, J. and Brohammer, M. (2018) 'Preparing educators for developing culturally and linguistically responsive IEPs', *Teacher Education and Special Education: The Journal of the Teacher Education Division of the Council for Exceptional Children*, 41(3), pp. 229-242. doi:10.1177/0888406418772079

Tran, C., Pham, M., Mai, P., Le, T. and Nguyen, D. (2020) 'Inclusive education for students with autism spectrum disorder in elementary schools in Vietnam: The current situation and solutions', *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 12(3), pp.265-273, doi: 10.26822/iejee.2020358220

Tutt, R., Powell, S. and Thornton, M. (2006) Educational approaches in autism: What we know about what we do, *Educational Psychology in Practice* 22(1), pp. 69-81. 10.1080/02667360500512452

Tynan, F., and Davy, K. (2021) 'An exploration of teachers' perceptions of how the classroom environment can support pupils with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) in the mainstream primary school', *REACH: Journal of Inclusive Education in Ireland*, 34(1). Available at: reachjournal.ie/index.php/reach/article/view/314 (Accessed 5 January 2022)

Unal, Z. and Unal, A. (2014) 'Perspectives of pre-service and in-service teachers on their preparation to work with parents in elementary classrooms', *The Educational Forum*, 78, pp. 112–126. Available at: doi:10.1080/00131725.2013.87842

UNESCO (1994) *The Salamanca Statement*. Madrid, Spain: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

UNESCO (1996) *The International Commission on Education for the Twenty-first Century Learning: The Treasure Within*. Spain: UNESCO.

UNESCO (2005) *Guidelines for Inclusion: Ensuring Access to Education for All*, Paris, France: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.

United Nations (UN) (2016) *Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities.html

University of the West of Scotland (2020) *University Ethics Committee: Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship*. Scotland: UWS

Urbanowicz, A., Nicolaidis, C., Houting, J. D., Shore, S. M., Gaudion, K., Girdler, and Savarese, R. J. (2019) 'An expert discussion on strengths-based approaches in autism', *Autism in Adulthood*, 1(2), pp. 82-89. doi.org/10.1089/aut.2019.29002.aju

Ustabulut, M. (2021) 'SWOT analysis for the distance education process of lecturers teaching turkish as a foreign language', *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 16(1), pp. 139-152. doi.org/10.29329/epasr.2020.334.8

van Bakel, M. M. E., Delobel-Ayoub, M., Cans, C., Assouline, B., Jouk, P.-S., Raynaud, J.-P., and Arnaud, C. (2015) 'Low but increasing prevalence of autism spectrum disorders in a French area from register-based data', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 45(10), pp. 3255–3261. doi:10.1007/s10803-015-2486-6.

Van Der Steen, S., Geveke, C., Steenbakkens, A. and Steenbeek, H. (2020) 'Teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorders: What are the needs of educational professionals?', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 90, pp. 103 -136. doi:10.1016/j.tate.2020.103036.

van Kessel, R.V., Cassidy, S., Baron-Cohen, S., Roman-Urrestarazu, A. and Czabanowska, K. (2021) 'Inclusive education in the European Union: A fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis of education policy for autism', *Research Square*, pp.1-22. doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-36514/v1

Van Mieghem, A., Verschueren, K., Petry, K., and Struyf, E. (2020) 'An analysis of research on inclusive education: A systematic search and meta review', *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 24(6), pp. 675–689. doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2018.1482012

Vincent, J., and Ralston, K. (2020) 'Trainee teachers' knowledge of autism: implications for understanding and inclusive practice', *Oxford Review of Education* 46(2), pp. 202–221. doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2019.1645651

Vivanti, G. (2020) 'Autism and autism treatment: Evolution of concepts and practices from Kanner to contemporary approaches', in Vivanti, G., Bottema-Beutel, K., Turner-Brown, L. (eds) *Clinical Guide to Early Interventions for Children with Autism. Best Practices in Child and Adolescent Behavioral Health Care*. Springer, Cham. pp. 1-24

Vlcek, S., Somerton, M., and Rayner, C. (2020) 'Collaborative teams: Teachers, parents, and allied health professionals supporting students with autism spectrum disorder in mainstream Australian schools', *Australasian Journal of Special and Inclusive Education*, 44(2), pp. 102-115. doi:10.1017/jsi.2020.11

Volkmar, F. and McPartland, J. (2014) 'From Kanner to DSM-5: Autism as an evolving diagnostic concept', *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 10(1), pp. 193-212. doi:10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-032813-153710

Vorlíček, R. (2022) 'Inclusion of a pupil with autism spectrum disorder in mainstream education in the Czech Republic', *European Journal Of Special Needs Education*, 1-10. Available at: doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2022.2076479

Wahyuni, D. (2012) 'The research design maze: Understanding paradigms, cases, methods and methodologies', *Journal of Applied Management Accounting Research*, 10(1), pp. 69-80. Available at: www.proquest.com/docview/1034602171 (Accessed 4 February 2022)

Walton, E., Carrington, S., Siggers, B., Edwards, C. and Kimani, W. (2022) 'What matters in learning communities for inclusive education: A cross-case analysis', *Professional Development in Education*, 48(1), pp.134-148. doi:10.1080/19415257.2019.1689525

Walton, E., McIntyre, J., Awidi, S., De Wet-Billings, N., Dixon, K., Madziva, R., Monk, D., Nyoni, C., Thondhlana, J. and Wedekind, V. (2020) 'Compounded exclusion: Education for disabled refugees in sub-Saharan Africa', *Frontiers in Education*, 5(47), pp. 1-14. doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2020.00047

Warnock, M. (1978) *Special Educational Needs: Report of the Committee of Enquiry into the Education of Handicapped Children and Young People*. London: Her Majesty's Stationery Office.

Warnock, B. (2005) Special schools or not?. *Education Review*, 19(1). pp. 13-17.

Warhurst, C., Nickson, D., Commander, J. and Gilbert, K. (2013) 'Role stretch': Assessing the blurring of teaching and non-teaching in the classroom assistant role in Scotland', *British Educational Research Journal*, 40(1), pp. 170-186. doi: 10.1002/berj.3036

Waterhouse, L. (2013) *Rethinking Autism. Variation and Complexity*. London, Waltham, MA.

Watkins, L.V. and Angus-Leppan, H. (2022) 'Increasing incidence of autism spectrum disorder: are we over-diagnosing?', *Advances in Autism*. doi.org/10.1108/AIA-10-2021-0041

Watkins, L., Ledbetter-Cho, K., O'Reilly, M., Barnard-Brak, L., Garcia-Grau, P. (2019) 'Interventions for students with autism in inclusive settings: A best-evidence synthesis and meta-analysis', *Psychological Bulletin*, 145, pp. 490–507. doi:10.1037/bul0000190.

Webster, R., Blatchford, P., Bassett, P., Brown, P., Martin, C and Russell, A. (2010), 'Double standards and first principles: Framing teaching assistant support for pupils with special educational needs', *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 25(4), pp. 319–336. doi:10.1080/08856257.2010.513533

Weaver, J.A. (2018) *Science, Democracy, and Curriculum Studies* Switzerland: Springer.

Wei, L. and Lin, H. (2017) Not a one-size-fits-all methodology: A survey of mixed methods, *Journal of Advances in Education Research*, 2(2), pp. 97-102. doi.org/10.22606/jaer.2017.22005

White, J., McGarry, S., Falkmer, M., Scott, M., Williams, P. J., and Black, M. H. (2023) Creating inclusive schools for autistic students: A scoping review on elements contributing to strengths-based approaches. *Education Sciences*, 13(7), pp. 1-25. doi.org/10.3390/educsci13070709

Williams, N., Frederick, L., Ching, A., Mandell, D., Kang-Yi, C. and Locke, J. (2021) 'Embedding school cultures and climates that promote evidence-based practice implementation for youth with autism: A qualitative study', *Autism*, 25(4), pp. 982-994. doi:10.1177/1362361320974509

Wilmshurst, L., and Brue. A. (2010) *The Complete Guide to Special Education*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

Wilson K.P. and Landa R. J. (2019) 'Barriers to educator implementation of a classroom-based intervention for preschoolers with autism spectrum disorder', *Frontiers in Education*, 4(27), pp. 1-10. doi =10.3389/feduc.2019.00027

Wing, L. and Gould, J. (1979) 'Severe impairments of social interaction and associated abnormalities in children: Epidemiology and classification', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 9, pp. 11–29 doi.org/10.1007/BF01531288

Witkin, H. A., Oltman, P. K., Ruskin, R. K. and Karp, S. A. (1971) *The Embedded Figures Test*, Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologist Press

Woolston, C. (2021) 'Scientists count the career costs of COVID', *Nature*, 599, pp. 331-334, Available at: www.nature.com/articles/d41586-021-03040-1 (Accessed 23 February 2022)

World Health Organization (WHO) (2019) *International Classification of Diseases: 11th Revision (ICD-11)*. Geneva: United Nations Economic and Social Council.

Xu, J. (2012) 'Development of learning in regular class and measure of teacher education in China', in Forlin, C. (Ed) *Future Directions for Inclusive Teacher Education: An International Perspective*, London: Routledge, pp. 33-41.

Xuereb, K. and Lawson, W. (2019) 'Reframing autism in a mainstream classroom via the constructs of inclusion and stigma', *Journal of Intellectual Disability - Diagnosis and Treatment*, 7(3), pp. 57-67. doi:10.6000/2292-2598.2019.07.03.1.

Yazici, M. and McKenzie, B. (2019) 'Strategies used to develop socio-communicative skills among children with autism in a Turkish special education school and implications for development of practice', *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 67(5), pp. 515-535. doi:10.1080/1034912x.2019.1614152.

Yan, T., Hou, Y., and Deng, M. (2022) 'Direct, indirect, and buffering effect of social support on parental involvement among Chinese parents of children with autism spectrum disorders', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 52(7), pp. 2911-2923. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-021-05170-x

Yong, Y.H. and Block, E. (2020) 'A multidisciplinary approach in diagnosing children with autistic traits and multiple behavioural issues: A case report', *Australian Medical Student Journal*, pp. 1-14. Available at: <http://www.amsj.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/A-multidisciplinary-approach-in-diagnosing-children-with-autistic-traits-and-multiple-behavioural-issues-a-case-report.pdf>

Zaidman-Zait, A., Mirenda, P., Duku, E., Vaillancourt, T., Smith, I., Szatmari, P., Bryson, S., Fombonne, E., Volden, J., Waddell, C., Zwaigenbaum, L., Georgiades, S, Bennett, T. Elsabaggh, M. and Thompson, A. (2017) 'Impact of personal and social resources on parenting stress in mothers of children with autism spectrum disorder', *Autism*, 21(2), pp. 155-166. doi:10.1177/1362361316633033

Zelazo, P. (2020) 'Executive function and psychopathology: A neurodevelopmental perspective', *Annual Review Of Clinical Psychology*, 16(1), pp. 431-454. doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-072319-024242

Zhou, P., Zhan, L., and Ma, H. (2019) 'Understanding others' minds: social inference in preschool children with autism spectrum disorder', *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 49(11), pp. 4523–4534. doi.org/10.1007/s10803-019-04167-x

Appendix 1: Permission from the Ministry for Education, Sport, Youth, Research and Innovation (MEYR)

DIPARTIMENT GJ=fALL-KURRIKULU, TAGJ=fLIM
_TUL IL-J=fAJJA U IMPJEGABILITA'
FLORIANA FRN 1810

DEPARTMENT FOR THE CURRICULUM, LIFELONG
LEARNING AND EMPLOYABILITY (DCLE)
FLORIANA FRN 1810

Directorate for Research, Lifelong Learning and Employability

Tel: 25982743

PERMISSION TO CONDUCT RESEARCH STUDY

Date: 19th January 2020

Ref: R02-2020 132

To: Head of School
From: Director

THE EDUCATIONAL PROVISION FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM IN PRIMARY MAINSTREAM STATE SCHOOLS IN MALTA: REVEALING THE EDUCATORS' PERSPECTIVES ON THE SWOTS

The Directorate for Research, Lifelong Learning and Employability would like to inform that approval is granted to **Claire Sciberras** to conduct the research in State Schools according to the official rules and regulations, subject to approval from the Ethics Committee of the respective Higher Educational Institution.

The researcher is committed to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and will ensure that these requirements are followed in the conduct of this research. The researcher will be sending letters with clear information about the research, as well as consent forms to all data subjects and their parents/guardians when minors are involved. Consent forms should be signed in all cases particularly for the participation of minors in research.

For further details about our policy for research in schools, kindly visit www.research.gov.mt.

Thank you for your attention and cooperation.

Claire Mamo
MA Ed (Open)
Research Support Teacher
Directorate for Research, Lifelong Learning and Employability

/s/ Alex Farrugia
Director
Directorate for Research, Lifelong Learning and Employability
Great Siege Road | Floriana | VLT 2000

MINISTRY FOR EDUCATION AND EMPLOYMENT

Appendix 2: Ethical Approval from the University of the West of Scotland

27/02/2020

Dear Claire Sciberras,

Your application 9659: The Educational Provision for Learners on the Autism Spectrum in Primary Mainstream Schools in Malta: Revealing the SWOTs, submission 9091, has been approved by the Education and Social Sciences SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Appendix 3: Correspondence to the Heads of College Networks

Dear College Principal,

I hope that this correspondence finds you well.

I am Claire Sciberras, a PhD Researcher at the University of the West of Scotland. I am currently researching to explore the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOTs) in the support provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta. This research is needed as, although a significant rise in the number of learners diagnosed with autism attending mainstream primary settings in Malta was reported by the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (2014), limited research is available about the educational provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta.

Given this, a research study focusing on the current educational provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta could be useful. The data collection process will involve educators responding to an anonymous online questionnaire. Educators interested in participating in an interview can provide their contact details via a link to an online form; the link will be provided at the end of the online questionnaire. The form is independent of the questionnaire, so it will not be possible to link the contact details of those who express interest in participating in the interview to their responses in the online questionnaire. Any educator who wishes to be involved further can participate in an interview with me at a time and date that is convenient for them.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. As already mentioned, the questionnaire is anonymous: at no point during the questionnaire will the respondents be asked for personal details, and there is no way to trace any responses back to individual respondents. The identity of the interviewees will be known to me. However, I will treat this information in strict confidence and will not include in the PhD thesis or any reports or publications arising from this research any details that can lead to the identification of the interviewees.

All data collected during this study will be used solely for my PhD thesis and in reports and publications associated with my PhD.

My research is being fully funded by the Endeavour Scholarship Scheme (Malta). The Directorate has granted permission to conduct this research for Quality and Standards in Education and by the Education and Social Sciences Research Committee at the UWS. The approval the Director of Research and Development granted is attached to this correspondence. If you have any questions about this research and wish to discuss them with me, please contact me using the details below. If you wish to discuss this research with my supervisory team, please use the contact details provided at the end of this letter.

If you approve of me approaching the primary schools within your College, please let me know via [REDACTED] will then disseminate an invitation via electronic mail to the Heads of Schools within your network.

Thank you for considering my request.
Kind Regards
Claire Sciberras

Researcher Contacts:
Claire Sciberras (M.Ed Inclusive Education)
PhD Candidate (UWS)
[REDACTED]

Supervisory Team:
Dr Lisa McAuliffe
Senior Lecturer
Director of Studies
Programme Leader: MSc Education | MEd Inclusive Education
UWS, School of Education and Social Sciences, AYR
[REDACTED]

Dr Carole Bignell
Lecturer
UWS, School of Education and Social Sciences, AYR
[REDACTED]

Appendix 4: Correspondence to Heads of Schools of the Primary Schools

Dear Head of School,

I hope that this correspondence finds you well.

I am Claire Sciberras, a PhD Researcher at the University of the West of Scotland. I am researching the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOTs) in the support provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta. This research is needed as, although a significant rise in the number of learners diagnosed with autism attending mainstream primary settings in Malta was reported by the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (2014), limited research is available about the educational provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta.

Given this, a research study focusing on the current educational provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta could be useful. The data collection process will involve educators responding to an anonymous online questionnaire. Any educator who wishes to be involved further can participate in an interview with me at a date and time convenient for the participant. Educators interested in participating in an interview can provide their contact details via a link to an online form; the link will be provided at the end of the online questionnaire. The form is independent of the questionnaire, so it will not be possible to link the contact details of those who express interest in participating in the interview to their responses in the online questionnaire. The questionnaire and interview schedule are included in the appendix to this letter for your information.

Participation in this study is entirely voluntary. As already mentioned, the questionnaire is anonymous: at no point during the questionnaire will the respondents be asked for personal details, and there is no way to trace any responses back to individual respondents. The identity of the interviewees will be known to me. However, I will treat this information in strict confidence. I will not include in the PhD thesis or in any reports or publications arising from this research any details that can lead to the identification of the interviewees.

All data collected during this study will be used solely for my PhD thesis and in reports and publications associated with my PhD.

My research is being fully funded by the Endeavour Scholarship Scheme (Malta). Permission to conduct this research has been granted by the Directorate for Quality and Standards in Education, the UWS Ethics Committee, and the College Principal. The approval the Director of Research and Development and College Principle granted are attached to this correspondence. If you have any questions about this research and wish to discuss them with me, please contact me using the details below. If you wish to discuss this research with my supervisory team, please use the contact details provided at the end of this letter.

Should you be willing to give your approval to the educators in your school to participate in this study, and in turn, should they wish to do so, please forward the participant information sheet for educators to them via the school's email system.

Interested educators from your school can then complete the online questionnaire and provide their contact details via the form linked at the end of the questionnaire, should they be willing to be interviewed. The research is open to all educators working in primary schools in Malta, so I hope you will also consider participating.

Thank you for considering my request.

Kind Regards
Claire Sciberras

Researcher Contacts:

Claire Sciberras (M.Ed Inclusive Education)
PhD Candidate (UWS)

[REDACTED]

Supervisory Team:

Dr Lisa McAuliffe
Senior Lecturer
Director of Studies
Programme Leader: MSc Education | MEd Inclusive Education
UWS, School of Education and Social Sciences, AYR

[REDACTED]

Dr Carole Bignell
Lecturer
UWS, School of Education and Social Sciences, AYR

[REDACTED]

1. Research Project Title

THE EDUCATIONAL PROVISION FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM IN PRIMARY MAINSTREAM STATE SCHOOLS IN MALTA: REVEALING THE EDUCATORS' PERSPECTIVE ON THE SWOTS

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to participate, you must understand the aims of this study and its expectations. Please take your time to read and consider the following information carefully. If you wish, you may also discuss this information with others. Please feel free to forward your queries should you require further clarification about the purpose of the research. Please take your time to make your decision about whether or not you wish to participate.

3. What is the purpose of this research?

Following a reform where special schools in Malta were transformed into resource centres (Ministry of Education, Culture, Youth and Sport, 2009), these centres cater for a small number of students with complex difficulties full-time. Given this restructuring, the absolute majority of students with autism in Malta are receiving their education within mainstream educational settings (European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education, 2014).

The shift of placing learners with autism in mainstream settings rather than resource centres warrants research on the provision for students with autism in mainstream classrooms in Malta. Hence, this study will comprise of an empirical account on the provision for students with autism. The intention is to explain such provision in terms of the elements which lead to the inclusion of learners with autism. An inquiry on this topic would shed light on the areas which might already evidence good practice on the philosophies underpinning the notion of inclusive education and which areas need to be improved. This would allow

recommendations to be brought forward with the intention that policy and pedagogy in this field is enhanced and/or modified.

Given the core motives which have influenced this research, this study will aim to address the following research question:

The overall aim of the study is:

To explore the SWOTs in the provision for students with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta.

The objectives of this study are:

- ***To identify the SWOTs which exist within the three areas mentioned above and beyond;***
- ***To develop recommendations that reinforce current strengths within the provision, which provide specific suggestions for mainstream educational settings to effectively support students with autism who attend mainstream school settings in Malta and beyond.***

This study intends to answer the following questions:

Research Question 1: Which are the SWOTs within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Research Question 2: Which are the SWOTs within training for educators who support learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Research Question 3: Which are the SWOTs within the home-school collaboration process of learners with autism who attend mainstream primary schools in Malta?

Reference:

European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education (2014) *Education for All: Special Needs and Inclusive Education in Malta, External Audit Report*. Denmark: European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education.

Ministry of Education, Culture, Youth and Sport (2009). *Special Schools Reform*. Malta: Department of Student Services.

4. Why have I been chosen?

I have chosen you as a prospective participant for this research as this study will focus on exploring the provision for learners with autism with the intention that the SWOTs within such provision are identified. Thus, since you are an educator within the primary sector, your knowledge and perspectives regarding the situation of support for learners with autism within your school would be beneficial towards gathering data so as to fulfil the purpose of this study.

5. Do I have to take part?

Your participation throughout this research is entirely voluntary.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part in this research, you will be asked to complete a web-based questionnaire ([link to the questionnaire](#)). It is estimated that it will take you 25 minutes to complete. After completing the questionnaire, you may also wish to participate in an interview which will be held at a place and a time convenient for yourself. If you decide to participate in the interviews, please follow the link at the end of the questionnaire and enter your email address. The link is independent to the questionnaire. Hence, questionnaire anonymity will not be compromised because of this.

If you decide to contribute towards this research, you can withdraw at any time and without specifying the reasons for your withdrawal until the data analysis process has commenced.

7. What do I have to do?

If you decide to take part, you must answer all the questions in the questionnaire. After completing the questionnaire, you may also wish to participate in an interview which will be held at a place and a time convenient for yourself. If you decide to participate in the interviews, please follow the link at the end of the questionnaire and enter your email address. The link is independent to the questionnaire. Hence, questionnaire anonymity will not be compromised because of this.

If you decide to contribute towards this research, you can withdraw at any time and without specifying your reasons until the data analysis process has commenced.

8. Which are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Participating in this study is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort.

9. Which are the possible benefits of taking part?

It is hoped that the findings of this study could contribute to increased knowledge and understanding of this topic in terms of the SWOTs within the provision. It will also provide useful recommendations that can lead to improved practice especially within the field of autism in Malta to ensure that the provision for learners with autism in the classroom is beneficial.

10. What happens if the research study stops earlier than expected?

Should the research have to stop at an earlier stage than what has been originally envisioned for any reason, you will be informed and an explanation regarding this will be provided.

11. What if something goes wrong?

If you feel the need to forward a complaint throughout this research, you may contact my supervisors.

12. Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All the information that will be gathered throughout the course of the research study will be kept strictly confidential. You as a questionnaire participant will not be requested to provide any information which might disclose your identity. Moreover, the interviews will not disclose your identity, or your organisation's identity in any subsequent reports or publications. It is envisioned that the data collected will be shared anonymously to allow third parties to reuse it as necessary. Thus, if any of your responses are quoted in the final report of this research, pseudonyms will be used as this would guarantee that the readers of the findings will not be able to establish your identity. Any data collected within the online questionnaire will be securely stored through passwords and encrypted means as permitted by current available technological software.

13. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

Only the answers you will digitally input will be recorded if you decide to participate in the questionnaire. However, the interviews that will be carried out are intended to be audio recorded. Before participating in the interview, you will be required to sign a consent form indicating that you have understood the purposes of this research and agree for the interviews to be audio recorded. Although the interviews will be audio recorded and transcribed after the recording process, your identity will never be revealed during this study. This procedure will be followed to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Thus, when any quotations will be added in the final report, pseudonyms will be used as this would guarantee that the readers of the findings will not be able to establish the identity of the participating schools and/or participants.

14. What type of information will be sought from me and why is collecting this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

The questionnaire will inquire about your opinions on the provision for learners with autism within your school. Your views and experience in this regard is what this research study is interested in exploring.

15. What will happen to the findings of the research project?

The findings of the research will be published in a final report which will be submitted to the University of the West of Scotland as part of my Doctoral thesis, to the Endeavour Scholarship Board (Malta), the entity who is funding my doctoral studies, and also to the Directorate for Quality and Standards in Education (Malta), the entity who provides approval related to research which might be carried out in state-funded primary schools. Your identity will not be disclosed in any report or publication as pseudonyms will be assigned. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please send me your email address so I can forward you a copy of the findings of this research.

16. Who is organising and funding the research?

This research study partially fulfils the Doctoral Award by the University of the West of Scotland. This research study is being fully funded by the Endeavour Scholarship Scheme – Group B, National Funds (Malta)

17. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

The study has been ethically approved by the Educational and Social Sciences Research Committee at the University of the West of Scotland and the Research and Development Department in charge of research carried out in State Schools within the Directorate for Quality and Standards in Education (Malta).

18. Contacts for further information

Researcher Contacts:

Claire Sciberras (M.Ed Inclusive Education)
PhD Candidate (UWS)

██

Supervisory Team:

Dr Lisa McAuliffe
Senior Lecturer

Programme Leader: MSc Education | MEd Inclusive Education
UWS, School of Education and Social Sciences, AYR

Dr Carole Bignell
Lecturer
UWS, School of Education and Social Sciences, AYR

Thank you for considering taking part in this research

**THE EDUCATIONAL PROVISION FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM IN
PRIMARY MAINSTREAM STATE SCHOOLS IN MALTA: REVEALING THE
EDUCATORS' PERSPECTIVE ON THE SWOTS**

I am Claire Sciberras, a PhD researcher at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). I am conducting a research study to further explore the provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta.

You are invited to participate in a questionnaire which will reveal the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats (SWOTs) through your perspectives regarding the educational provision for learners with autism in primary schools in Malta. Given this, you are invited to outline the existing SWOTs within the teaching and learning process, the training process, and the collaboration process. The following is what SWOTs stand for:

Strengths refer to the current assets and capabilities that have an advantage for the school to reach its goals in terms of the provision for learners with autism.

Weaknesses refer to the current limitations that impede schools from achieving their goals when supporting learners with autism.

Opportunities refer to the ideas that could support change and produce more quality provisions for learners with autism.

Threats refer to the potential risks that could eventually negatively impact the provision for learners with autism in schools.

If you decide to participate in this research by responding to the questionnaire, kindly accept the terms and conditions within the below consent form and you may proceed to complete this questionnaire accordingly. The questionnaire will take approximately 25 minutes to complete and you may also wish to provide your email at the end of the questionnaire to participate in a follow-up interview. Thank you in advance for considering participating in this research.

Research Project Title

**THE EDUCATIONAL PROVISION FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM IN
PRIMARY MAINSTREAM STATE SCHOOLS IN MALTA: REVEALING THE
EDUCATORS' PERSPECTIVE ON THE SWOTS**

1. I have read and understood all the information provided in the information sheet for the above mentioned research study, and have been allowed to ask any questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that the survey is anonymous – at no point during the questionnaire will I be asked for any

personal details and there is no way to trace any responses back to individual respondents.

3. I understand that the responses in this questionnaire will be used in the researcher's PhD thesis and reports and publications associated with the researcher's PhD.
4. I understand that, because the questionnaire is anonymous, if, after I submit my responses, I change my mind and wish to withdraw them, it will not be possible to distinguish my responses from those of other participants and because of this it will not be possible to withdraw them.

I agree that my responses are used in the research

1. What is your role within the education system?
2. How long have you been carrying out your current role?
3. Which strategies do you use to support learners with autism in primary schools in Malta?
4. Which are the strengths within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism in primary schools in Malta?
5. Which are the weaknesses within the teaching and learning process of learners with autism in primary schools in Malta?
6. Which are the opportunities of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism in primary schools in Malta?
7. Which are the threats of the teaching and learning process of learners with autism in primary schools in Malta?
8. Did you receive training on how to support learners with autism?
9. If you have indicated 'yes' in question 8, kindly specify what training has involved.
10. If you had the opportunity to undergo training on autism, which areas would you consider?
11. Which are the strengths within the training process?
12. Which are the weaknesses within the training process?
13. Which are the opportunities to the training process?

14. Which are the threats to the training process?
15. Which means do you use to collaborate with parents of children with autism who attend primary schools in Malta?
16. Which are the strengths within the collaboration process with parents of children with autism who attend primary schools in Malta?
17. Which are the weaknesses within the collaboration process with parents of children with autism who attend primary schools in Malta?
18. What are the collaboration process opportunities with parents of children with autism who attend primary schools in Malta?
19. Which are the threats of collaboration with parents of children with autism who attend primary schools in Malta?
20. Do you wish to add any other comments? If so, you may use the space below to type in your comments?
21. Do you wish to participate in a follow-up interview that will allow you to elaborate further on your responses?
22. If you have responded with a 'yes' to question 21, kindly provide your email address by clicking on the link hereunder and the researcher will get back to you with more information regarding the participation process. Kindly note that the link is independent of the responses to the questionnaire. Therefore, any data you have provided here will remain anonymous.

Thank you for participating in this research

Appendix 7: The Interview Schedule

1. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **strengths** that schools may have concerning *Teaching and Learning*:

- Adaptations of instruction
- Support from the SLT
- Support from Peers

What are your views regarding these?

2. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **weaknesses** that schools may have concerning *Teaching and Learning*:

- Inadequate physical school environment
- Adaptations done by the LSE
- Lack of funding to purchase resources

What are your views regarding these?

3. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **opportunities** that schools could have concerning *Teaching and Learning*:

- Support from external service providers
- Quiet areas

What are your views regarding these?

4. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **threats** that schools could have concerning *Teaching and Learning*:

- Unclear perspectives about inclusive education
- Lack of knowledge on policy content and implementation

What are your views regarding these?

5. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **strengths** that schools may have concerning *Home-School Collaboration*:

- Sharing of Techniques and Resources with Parents
- Open and frequent Communication Channels Between the School and Parents

- Parents sharing of information about the child with the school

What are your views regarding these?

6. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **weaknesses** that schools may have concerning *Home-School Collaboration*:

- Parents being in denial of the child's condition
- Underinvolved parents

What are your views regarding these?

7. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **opportunities** that schools could have concerning *Home-School Collaboration*:

- Opportunities for Frequent Meetings
- Being sensitive to parents' needs
- Parent education sessions

What are your views regarding these?

8. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **threats** that schools could have concerning *Home-School Collaboration*:

- Parents' psychological wellbeing
- Education not being a priority for parents

What are your views regarding these?

9. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **strengths** that schools may have concerning *Training for Educators*:

- Training involving time to share good practices
- Strategies shared were user-friendly

What are your views regarding these?

10. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **weaknesses** that schools may have concerning *Training for Educators*:

- Training sessions are generally based on theory rather than practical strategies

- Training is provided following appointment.

What are your views regarding these?

11. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **opportunities** that schools could have concerning *Training for Educators*:

- Asking educators what training should entail
- Providing more opportunities to training to all educational stakeholders during school hours
- Training provided by specialised trainers

What are your views regarding these?

12. Following the questionnaire which was forwarded to participants in Phase 1 it was found that the following are the most common **threats** that schools could have concerning *Training for Educators*:

- Teachers and members of the SLT are undertrained.
- Lack of training could lead to the implementation of non-inclusive practices.
- Participation in training is voluntary, not mandatory.

What are your views regarding these?

Research Project Title

**THE EDUCATIONAL PROVISION FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM IN
PRIMARY MAINSTREAM STATE SCHOOLS IN MALTA: REVEALING THE
EDUCATORS' PERSPECTIVE ON THE SWOTS**

1. I have read and understood all the information provided in the information sheet for the above-mentioned research study and have been given the opportunity to ask any questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that the questionnaire is anonymous – at no point during the questionnaire will I be asked for any personal details and there is no way to trace any responses back to individual respondents.
3. I understand that the responses provided in this questionnaire will be used in the researcher's PhD thesis and in reports and publications associated with the researcher's PhD.
4. I understand that, because the questionnaire is anonymous, if, after I submit my responses, I change my mind and wish to withdraw them, it will not be possible to distinguish my responses from those of other participants and because of this it will not be possible to withdraw them.

I agree for my responses to be used in the research

Research Project Title

**THE EDUCATIONAL PROVISION FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM IN
PRIMARY MAINSTREAM STATE SCHOOLS IN MALTA: REVEALING THE
EDUCATORS' PERSPECTIVE ON THE SWOTS**

- I confirm that I have read and understood all the information provided in the information sheet for the above-mentioned research study and have been given the opportunity to ask any questions.
- I have been informed that my interview with the researcher will be audio recorded and I agree to this.
- I have been informed that the responses I will provide during the interview will be used in the researcher's PhD thesis and in reports and publications associated with the researcher's PhD. I agree to this under the condition that neither my name nor any other details that can lead to my identification will be included in the PhD thesis or in any reports or publications, including drafts.
- I will be given the opportunity to look into the transcription of my interview.
- I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any point until the submission of the PhD thesis, at which point it will not be possible to remove the responses from the analysis and findings.

Name of the Participant: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Name of the Researcher: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Appendix 10: Communication by the Malta Union of Teachers (MUT)

Personal details withheld.